

**NEURO - SOUNDINGS
IN MANAGERIAL JUDGEMENT**

Report submitted

By

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CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I, Col Prof Dr Jyotirmaya Satpathy declare that this Report, entitled **NEURO - SOUNDINGS IN MANAGERIAL JUDGEMENT** being submitted for the award of **POST - DOCTORAL FELLOW (PDF)** in **PSYCHOLOGY** of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any Degree or Diploma of this or any other University.

(Col. Prof. Dr J Satpathy, PhD, D.Litt.)

Date:

Place: Mangaluru, Karnataka State

CERTIFICATE OF RESEARCH SUPERVISOR

This is to certify that this Report entitled **NEURO - SOUNDINGS IN MANAGERIAL JUDGEMENT** has been submitted by Col. Prof. Dr Jyotirmaya Satpathy for the award of **POST - DOCTORAL FELLOW** in **PSYCHOLOGY** of Srinivas University.

(Prof. Dr. P S. Aithal, PhD, D.Sc.)

Date:

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"Once you make a decision, the universe conspires to make it happen."

..... Ralph Waldo Emerson

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NEUROFEEDBACK - SOUNDINGS IN MANAGERIAL JUDGEMENT

Executive Abstract

Introduction

Interaction between managerial business and brain science is not smooth with misinterpretation in expectations on either side. Attention theatres pervasive part in perception and reasoning. Judgement making is critical for crafting neuro-feedback and executing stratagems. Connectedness plays central role in sciences of mind and brain. Despite substantial advances, question of how managers make judgments continues to pose important challenges for scientific research. Historically, different disciplines have approached this problem using different techniques and assumptions, with few unifying efforts made. Making a managerial judgement implies that there is alternative judgement to be considered, and in such a case we want not only to identify as many of these alternatives as possible but to choose the one that (1) has the highest probability of success or effectiveness and (2) best fits with our goals, desires, lifestyle, values, and so on. What counts as causal evidence in managerial judgement? What role is played by information in managerial sciences of mind and brain? Neurobiological drivers receive signals, perform recognition and transduction to grow and die in stochastic milieus. Impression that managerial judgements are taken through rational or logical thought process have been exposed to questioning by experiments. Reference is drawn to multiple signals of origin, conditions that support or negate findings that aid understanding of how neuro-feedback influence judgement making.

Expansion of neuro-managerial management parallels development of cognitive science. Neuro-managerial management has bridged contrasting fields of management and psychology. Management, Psychology, and Neuro-managerial Science converge into a single, unified discipline with ultimate aim of providing single, general theory of human behaviour. This is the field in which consilience operates. Researchers and neuro-managerial researchers provide tools for study of mechanism. The goal was to understand processes that connect sensation and action by revealing neuro-managerial mechanisms by which judgement are made. Neuro-managerial findings pose challenge to standard management perspective. The source of inspiration has been neuromanagement judgment research (amalgamation of ideas from cognitive science and management). Neuro-managerial judgement making has emerged as an inter-disciplinary effort to bridge this gap. It integrates ideas from fields of organisational psychology, neuromanagement science and neuro-managerial management to specify accurate models of judgement making.

Emerging neuromanagement science evidence suggested that sound and rational neuro-managerial judgement making depend on prior accurate emotional processing. These occurred at multiple levels of operation. Some occurred consciously and some occurred non-consciously. The issues that cropped up were; which happened when Managers changed minds? Which algorithms allowed sensorimotor behaviours to be observed? Which computational mechanisms allowed brain to adapt changing circumstances? How (and where) were values and probability combined in brain and what was the dynamics of this? Which neural systems tracked defined forms of utility? To which extent did utility computations generalize to judgement? How did systems that focus on immediate judgement interact? These led to this study on neuro-feedback from brain activity. This research attempts addresses research to explore neuro-feedback driven managerial judgement.

Previous research has demonstrated that judgments of intent were significantly related to attitudinal, normative, and affective components of judgement. Some researches failed to demonstrate distinctiveness of components by obtaining convergent and discriminant validity measures. This limitation needs to be addressed. Purpose of this research is to elucidate principles and judgement mechanism in managerial brain. Principal aim has been to model neuro-managerial feedback by using tools from brain waves (EEG). This research aims at, first, incorporate neuro-managerial science and Psychology of management modelling approach, and second, awareness of evidences for multiple systems involved in judgement. Objective was to monitor dynamics of neurobiological drivers in understanding managerial behaviour and judgement making.

Through computational approaches, attempt have been to clarify how neural soundings realize ‘mental sounding’ in managerial judgement. This work attempts to explore phenomena through individual action, judgement making, and reasoning processes on concept of cognitive models of judgement. Principal aim has been to elucidate principles and judgement mechanism in brain interaction between brain waves (EEG) processes. In light of discussing theories and applications of neuro-managerial science in judgement, physiological responses have been measured to understand neural activity and how brains respond to sounding presentation (Electroencephalograph) which measured changes to

electrical current in brain. Computerized Tomography and Positron Emission Tomography are the sophisticated methods.

In Section - I, an introduction to the project concepts have been presented. The report is based on neuro-heterodox management tilting towards near - optimal 'deep' concept of managerial judgment. Processes connected with cognitive and emotional architectures ('Biological Motorists') of human beings that incorporate a spectrum of observations, comprehensions, assessments and spatial - cum - temporal aspects while contemplating 'deep' bio - computational judgement matrix have been argued for. A review of models and literature has been presented that form a bed rock to this study report. As regards problem statement, two specific research questions were considered. One, how is 'deep' bio - computational judgement choices explored along with two, what part of brain aids 'deep' bio - computational judgement making? Allied were; what waves of brain reflect 'deep' bio - computational judgement? How to create interpretable 'deep' bio - computational judgement? How to interpret qEEG responses? How does a manager choose via. Neuro-feedback? Which waves from brain performs in 'deep' Bio - computational judgement making? How to detect and maneuver response soundings? A Pilot test - run has been conducted on 02 subjects along with AI - ML [symbolic Logic] explanation. Through neuro - computational stratagem (Alpha Wave analysis), attempts have been undertaken to observe neural soundings ('mental sounding') in (managerial) 'deep' bio - computational judgement making.

In Section - II, the experimental protocols have been presented. Electroencephalography (EEG) has been adopted as a procedure peep into brain dynamics of Subjects. A set of rubrics for managerial judgement have been explored. Some issues addressed are: How to build interpretable models that aid computational neuro-biological and computational judgements? How to ensure that models and explanations are robust to adversarial attacks? How to prepare and evaluate models in presence of missing counterfactuals? How to detect and correct biases in incentive-based neuro-biological and computational judgements? And, how does biology (neuro-science) play a role in central apparatus of actions? The protocols revolve around 'Fluid Intelligence'. Research has examined effects of various interventions on fluid intelligence. The protocol architecture has been modeled at datasets each containing 2.5 minutes of eyes-open and 2.5 minutes of eyes-closed latent-state EEG. Scalable Vector Graphics [SVG] programming has been conducted on Subjects' for protocol architecture. This was for generic description by dove - tailing a two - dimensional vector graphic representation. Attributes define Alpha wave properties concerning size, position and stroke paths. These helped generate 'Cascading Style Sheets'.

In Section - III, the results have been discussed and arrived at conclusions. Discussion and conclusions attempt to model neuro-feedback in managerial judgement making by monitoring brain waves through EEG and understanding neural activity involved in managerial judgement. Methodology involves using EEG conductors to record brain activity and physiological responses to soundings and developing theoretical models grounded in neurofeedback for EEG-based fluid managerial judgement. The research aimed to contribute towards understanding neuro-design in managerial preference undercurrents and open up new avenues for future studies. This research attempt provides theoretical outline for coxswaining neurofeedback-management investigations and designates inter-disciplinary prototype for neurofeedback-based choice construction. It is inferred that, behaviourism is a cheval glass that replicates proclivity, viewpoint, and another psychosomatic state. Choice-making is an elementary human stroke. Fluid-based managerial judgement making is the most frequent but never-ending duel for mankind. It is akin to a chess board matrix where the moves and the counter moves are just predictable and conjectures but operationalization is difficult. Turning the concepts into quantifiable measurements and dimensions is complicated but not without a solution. In nutshell, fluid-based managerial judgement making is backed up by tenets of neuroscience. Fluid-based managerial judgements taken in an Alpha State are ascertained to be near-rational. There seems to be an air of relaxation, reduced stress, reduced strain, reduced anxiety, unruffled - thinking and no restlessness.

As a conclusion, experimental neurobehavioral judgement provides a fresh dataset that can aid in the creation of new theories to explain and anticipate EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making, as well as the underlying causes of behaviour and neural anomalies. By measuring neuro-transmitters in brain activity, neuro-signatures can be obtained that reveal the mechanisms utilized by these neuro-transmitters in the brain during managerial judgement making processes. This information can indicate which brain regions and neuro-transmitters are activated when an EEG-based fluid managerial judgement is prepared and how they interrelate. This perceptive can be influenced to grow a model that represent fluid managerial judgement consistent with goals.

Section: 01

Introduction

Genesis

Human brain and mind is complex. Trillions of neurons fill the cranial box. These command and control human mind and behaviour. More complex is a peep into dynamics of human brain and mind. Connected with this is a fact that no 'deep' bio - computational judgement is optimal or complete. Bio - computational judgement is a pecking order of progression, steadied and vigorously continuous at assorted instant scale. At best one arrives at near - optimal 'deep' subject to complementarities, alternatives and substitutes. Rapid developments in Science and Technology have enabled infant scholarship of neuro-managerial management to undefined parallels between Cognitive Science and Psychology (Genomics, Proteomics, Meta-bionomics, Environmental Sciences and Clinical Research). Emerging field of neuro - management has connected essence of Management, Economics, Statistics, Medical Sciences and Psychology to transmute emerging scholarship as broad-spectrum model of human cognition. Primary goal is to comprehend inter - connected processes primarily, loops and networks that connect various stimuli, incentives and actions by unearthing neuro - managerial mechanisms on edifice of which 'deep' bio - computational judgements are prepared or engaged. It is experiential that such excavations put forward challenges to contemporary management perspectives (Naqvi and et. al.; 2006).

Herein, emerges a new supposition; Neuro-Heterodox Management. This playground accommodates players from various teams of Management Sciences, Economics, Management, Statistics, Medical Sciences and Psychology in form of an Ubuntu. This is a diversified package of conceptual definitions which provides pluralist engagement (Ramsay, et.al. 2010). The new field, presented above, subscribes to Old or Classical School of Thought tenets. It offers a new brand of arguments, logic and rationale that opens door to new critical thinking - oriented World of Thought. The source of stimulation has been neuro - Managerial judgment research (Kuhnen, Chiao, and Harpending; 2009). The

unrestrained range of scholarly disciplines seeks to investigate human 'deep' bio - computational judgement making. It is proved with multi - modal experiments that each of these conducts research from relatively narrow paradigms, and with that emerge limitations attendant with pure disciplinary research.

The emerging field appears to offer a common language, theory and practice to understand behavioural dimension better. The first step towards comprehending brain ('complex' waves) involves objective description and analysis of how brain works ('Synchronized Cortical'). Different behavioural disciplines investigate human 'deep' bio - computational judgement making from an individualistic perspective and methodology (Bear, et. al.; 2005). Within the new field, approaches try to uncover a comprehensive understanding of human behaviour's biological basis (and determinants). Such models are critical when crafting and executing strategies by management practitioners; Managers, and 'deep' bio - computational judgement makers, to list a few (Bönte, et.al; 2016).

Processes connected with cognitive and emotional architectures of human beings incorporate a spectrum of observations, comprehensions, assessments and spatial - cum - temporal aspects while contemplating 'deep' bio - computational judgement matrix. On the other hand, there often crop up conflicting problems that mandate rational 'deep' bio - computational judgements between numerous multifaceted and inconsistent or contradictory alternatives. This is loaded with quantum dosages of improbability and indistinctness, as is hallmark of VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity). The sufficient and necessary goal now is primarily to address, based on particular set of conditions, these scenarios towards enhanced and 'rational' 'deep bio - computational judgement making. Philosophically, origins of designing rational 'deep' bio - computational judgement can be associated to tenets of 'The Wealth of Nations' by Adam Smith (1776). This philosophy rests on an ad hoc set of Laws that explain 'deep' bio - computational judgement milieu with swings between probability and improbability (some consciously and some non-consciously) on fulcrum of 'revealed perspectives' (Miao, et. al; 2015).

The above arguments or points of views lead to study on neuro - brain wave - based response and real - time response from brain activity. The new Century challenges business, neuro - bio - computational judgement styles that have shifted more out of intellectual energy to behavioural and emotional experience of individuals. Search for meaning and authentic identity has led to increasing comprehensive demand for managing adversity and challenges for a Manager. Brain wave based response soundings serve as permanent repository of strengths and understanding strategies help in building self-confidence (Krueger; 2018).

Motivation

21st Century is baptized to experience marriage of management with neuroscience, and being a vital cog, Manager is programmed to play a significant role. Studies and evidence lend credence to the fact that there appears to be a socio-economic-biological connection in all managerial activities, whether in producing or creating wealth. Therefore, there is an undisputed inclination of neuro-sciences in comprehending tools or 'Biological 'motorists' that aid in mapping link between molecular networks, psychology, cognition and 'deep' bio - computational judgement making apparatuses. This can route research and investigation towards calibrating whether cognito - wiring provides alley forward towards advent of a new vista that is scientifically vigorous and empirically sound.

In dynamics of collecting, assimilating, collating, interpreting, synthesizing and disseminating these inputs, there appears, in neuro management horizon, an element of neuron soundings in data - driven managerial 'deep' bio - computational judgements. This reflects a case of 'Fluid Intelligence'. It is conjectured that in the bargain, manager would be a key 'catalyst' in interplay between management and neuroscience. What happens to fluid dynamics in brain and what waves does it emanate when new information is injected through five sense organs to brain? Is manager in a dynamic state of neural state to absorb new data? The foundation of stimulus is experiential to be neuro-managerial 'deep' bio - computational judgement investigations. 'Deep' bio - computational judgement offers array of interrogations to specify precise depictions of judgement. Questions like; what symbolizes conception of causality in sciences of brain structure? Are disparate designs a qualification for different investigational tactics? Are there alterations overtly and covertly assumed? This merits clinical interpretation (attempted in subsequent sub - sections and Sections in this Report).

Grey - Box

Despite being part of human physical body, mind has posed, easier said than done, to appreciate its dynamics. This is a case of 'Cognitive Pragmatics'. Associated with this is 'Cognitive Fatigue'. One does not precisely know exact nature of its functioning. One prime reason ascribed is non - examination of physical characteristics in its entirety. Some other reasons ramble around concepts of concealed, prejudiced and emblematic possessing propositional substance. Complexly interlinked and innovative physiological techniques have stimulated study of inner instruct of brains. This is a case of 'Cognitive Segmentation'. It suggests fundamental change in (managerial) thinking, observing and generating 'deep' bio - computational judgements.

It is an empirical statement that some natural sciences have advanced when they have resorted to or adopted some original philosophy as a point of a different approach instead of trying to determine quintessence of gear. Through observations and experimentations, it is generally inferred that in complex and multi-faceted scenarios / situations, sometimes (managerial) cognitive processes show signs of overloading and are incapable of providing any informed option. In such a situation, how does 'human grey - box' integrate data and evidence to weigh options, experience and risk? How does it attempt to bring in near - equilibrium to strike symmetry connecting constancy and perspective stimulus in judgment structure? What cognito dynamics lie beneath those elementary cognitive capabilities? This research focuses on advancing (managerial) perceptive of 'deep' bio - computational judgement making. This is in fact pooling of experimentation methods (Zheng; 2018). Responses experimented are stimuli to mechanism of human grey box i.e. brain while being subjected to 'deep' bio - computational judgement processing. How can oscillations in brain waves contribute towards understanding these dynamics? Conjectural explanation posits that (managerial) 'grey - box' accomplishes this through series of inter - connected cognito mechanisms (Tracey and Schluppeck; 2014).

Explorations have been un-mitigated, from cognito simulation to thought - provoking shares of chromatic diagnosis for rational processing. Most biological drivers and causality play vital roles in such mechanisms (Erkut et al.; 2018 and Zhong; 2018). Conversely, algorithmic 'deep' Bio - computational judgement making and subsequent brain wave-based response are implicit in having a biological, not just behavioural basis. This introduces a critical question; what constitutes substantiation in 'deep' bio - computational judgement sciences? This mandates holistic thinking and deep understanding since paradigm for 'deep' bio - computational judgement control is emerging. It appreciates, expands, creates, connects and aids 'deep' bio - computational judgements. This paradigm would cease conservative philosophy, understand how to engage and influence cerebral of others and help activate openness to new ideas. This does observe natural phenomena and describe in brain - wave equations in a back-and-forth process akin to Richard Feynman's approach to Pysics in realm of (managerial) 'deep' bio - computational judgement behaviour. In this, actions are transformed from results - orientation to relationship - orientation (Baron and Ward; 2004).

Review of Models

Table: 01 / 01
Summary of Models

Title	Author	Methodology
Group Preference Making	(Yu Chunlong al., (2020) et	For preference-making group with use of indifference zone notion.
Selection Of Multi-Criteria Preference-Making.	(Hamur cu Mustafa et al., 2020)	Model obtained from diagnostic hierarchical progression (AHP) and method for instruct predilection.
Integrated Data Envelopment Analysis And Multicriteria Preference-Making.	(Jolly Pure et al., 2020)	Models for analysis of MCDM computation towards ultimate cross-efficiencies.
Consensus Reaching And	(Yuche ng Dong	Using feedback method to support running agreement: 1)

Strategic Manipulation.	et al., 2020)	adjusting preference and 2) improving conviction.
Bayesian Network For Location Selection.	(Yue Pan et 2020) al.,	Bayesian model, approached efficiently under uncertain situations to solve dependence problems.
Preference-Making Using Card-Sorting Techniques.	(Morente Molinera et al., 2019)	Group preference-making approach via card-sorting techniques and options.
Group Preference Heterogeneous Making With Preference	(Bowen Zhang et al., 2019)	Group preference- approach with heterogeneous preference structures for optimization-based consensus.
Framework Routine Instrument	(Chai, Junyi et al., 2020)	Analyses multiplicity of alternatives by running DM techniques.
Group Preference-Making Based On Framework Of Granular Computing.	(Calleja s Edwin Alberto et al., 2019)	Inventive method of granular computing framework detailed in multi-criteria contexts to calculate probable
Prospect Theoretic Utility Based Preference Making	(Geng Baocheng et al.,	Path towards utility-based modeling for preference-making.
Evaluation Of Risk-Utility Function.	(Mengke Lu et al., 2020)	Suggests evaluation technique of grey-start indicator weight calculation model.
Preference Making With Dynamic, Uncertain Continuous Information	(Reches Shulamit et al., 2020)	Offers algorithm to tackle potential measures continuous random variables.
Value Constraints In Preference-Making Using MCDM Methods.	(Abdelli Abdelkrim et al., 2020)	ISOCOV Ideal Solution with Constraint on Values
Visual Reasoning Strategies & Satisficing.	(Alex Kale et al., 2020)	Experiment on quintile dot plots.
Fractional Gini Aggregation.	(Ibrahim Rabha, 2019)	Single and multi-vision processes to define ordered weighted averages.
Re - Create Kahneman–Tversky Prospect Theory	(Francis Jack)	This model revises Kahneman–Tversky Theories
Von Neumann – Morgenstern Theory.	Clark, 2020)	Develop von Neumann-Morgenstern (vNM) theory.
Linking Subjective And Incentivized Risk	(Johannes G Jaspersen	“General risk question” (GRQ) in direction of risk.

Attitudes.	et al., 2020)	
Managing Double Hierarchy Preference Relations.	(Xunjie Gou et al., 2020)	Relation on double hierarchy preference relation (DHPR) with weight-determining method
Alternative Consensus Model Of Group Preference-Making.	(Xu Yejun et al., 2019)	Derives alternative consensus for additive preference relation (APR) to identify and regulate inconsistent ordinal elements.
Preference-Making In Non - Behaviours And Heterogeneous Preferences.	(Chao Xiangrui et al., 2020)	Establish consensus-reaching model to deal with heterogeneous group preference through non-cooperative behaviours.
Large-Scale Group Preference-Making With Probabilistic Preference Relation.	(Song Yongming et al., 2019)	Probability-based computational model to acquire probabilities of probabilistic preference relation.
Evaluative Preference Analysis With Online Consumer Ratings.	(Li Xue et al., 2019)	Preference Analysis to manage arbitrary rating distribution.
Estimations Of Utility Function And Values Of Sustainable Mining Via The Choice Experiment Method	(Narrei Somaye et al., 2019)	Model uses the choice experiment technique for estimating sustainable development criteria.
Task Scheduling Mechanism.	(Suvendu Chandan Nayak et al., 2019)	Intend to employ TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference to enhance effectiveness of algorithm.
Method For Aggregating Ranked Services.	(Kenneth Fletcher et al., 2019)	Put forward a technique that combines two algorithms 1) Rank Aggregation for Complete Lists and 2) Rank Aggregation for Incomplete Lists
Exploratory Study Of Business Intelligence And Preference-Making.	(Lapo Mola et al., 2019)	Investigates business intelligence systems.
Preference Analysis In Multi-Criteria Preference-Making Methods.	(Prabadevi Boopathy et al., 2019)	The model analyses that multi-criteria preference-making (MCDM) methods can be practised for achieving the final preference.
Managing Asymmetric	(Zina Houhamdi	The model recommends examining capability of agent in

Information Effects In Preference-Making.	et al., 2020)	taking right preference.
Sentiment Analysis For Preference Making.	(Zehra Nur Canbolat et al., 2020)	Examines e-wom concept with sentiment analysis.
Hybrid Ai-Based Preference Making Model.	(Souma va Borral et al., 2020)	Preference-making model is depicted, based on hybrid artificial intelligence (AI).

Problem Statement

As regards problem statement, two specific research questions are under consideration. One, how is ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement choices explored along with two, what part of brain aids ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making? On scrutiny, methodological and philosophical issues appear large; what is a clear neuronal clarification? How can behavioural sciences be related to management? Are there dependable empirical methods for testing hypotheses recognized across various disciplines? Methodology offers neuro-based brain wave examination protocols via. qEEG. Methodology offers and provides for neuro - based opinions to imitate thinking of neurobiology in ‘business’ algorithmic research (Nikolić et al.; 2020). Research considers that to realize thoughts and feelings in ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement behaviour, components be experimented with single trial Q (quantitative / quantifiable) EEG to demonstrate operational models. With neuro brain wave-based sounding procedure, via single trial QEEG, conductors can be used to record electrical activity via single trial QEEG (Zhang; 2018). These waves afford substantiation about position and cognitive processes in central nervous system. In light of debate, theory and application in ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making, physiological neuro - stimulus responses can calibrate to appreciate neural motion and how brain structures respond to sounding.

Nevertheless, examining how managers make ‘deep’ bio - computational judgements stay to posture substantial trials for methodical explorations. Instituting ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement infers that there is a choice to be factored in. And, in such a situation, this attempts to detect switches as conceivable but selects one that (a) has ultimate panorama of yield and (b) superlatively fits with needs and routine. And, in such a milieu, how do pair of brain structures, with its waves (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta and Theta), act as ‘catalytic motorist’ to pledge and aid ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making process? Of brain waves (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta and Theta), this report experiments with profess that Alpha waves be factored as significant catalyst in guiding towards (managerial) near - optimal ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement scenario (Cătălina, et al.; 2011).

Experimental Issues

Commencing with physiological genesis of qEEG rhythm, Thomas F. Collura (Collura; 2014) has experimented with calibrating cranial box movement (analyzed, transformed and amalgamated) as it reflects key cranial box regulatory processes. Combining ‘top down’ and ‘bottom up’ connectives, Collura (Collura; 2014) describes central part of scientific principles, clinical experience and practical aspects of neuro response assessment. These databases contrast individual’s qEEG pattern with group of carefully selected, normal, healthy individuals in a similar age group (Collura; 2014). qEEG description helps identify where significant differences exist between person being tested and normative group. qEEG indicates impulses, cognitive rigidity and apprehension of an individual by co-relating angst and dejection, if any.

In contemporary research, neuro-managership has been recognised as cutting - edge playground with injection of brain implementation in managerial preference-ordering (Korpysa; 2020). This playground accommodates essence neural - science approach of preference-ordering by allowing for Managerial frame of mind and rule - of - thumb theories (Boudreaux, Nikolaev, and Klein; 2019). Allied questions are;

- What waves of brain reflect ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement?

- How to create interpretable 'deep' bio - computational judgement?
- How to interpret qEEG responses?

Derivative of cognitive (behavioural) sciences, branded as multi - fanged and multi - rational science, neuro organizational dynamics, as emerging force to reckon with, is a new paradigm in realm of managerial sciences, per se. This is reflected in emerging scientific evidence via. biological experimentations include managerial attitudes, temperament, tactic, judgement, viewpoint, standpoint, spot, capability mentality and heuristic plus posture. From sensitivity of organisational philosophies, fixated on thought outlines and image explanations, research tactic lies in addressing neuro - cognitive framework of manager's mind patterns, that help to overcome forces of volatility, capricious, intangible, inconsistent, fleeting, unquantifiable, uncertainty, hesitation, dubiety, wariness, scepticism, suspicion, complexity, complication, intricacy, ramification, convolution, elaboration, entanglement, involvement, multiplicity, not clearly understandable and ambiguity (Dew et al.; 2015)

Aim and Objective (s)

Various theories have been purported as to what generates brain wave-based response soundings. Three primary features appear to separate those who are resilient and organizations apart from one another. Some such qualities enable one to recover from an ordeal, but accurate brain wave-based response soundings are product of three concerns (presented in next paragraph below). Primary aim was to archetype neuro - managerial neuro-feedback by using brain waves (qEEG). As regards exploration methodology, EEG conductors were used to record electrical activity of brain via. EEG (electroencephalogram). These waves afford evidence about circumstances and cognitive processes in light of debating theories and applications in bio - computational judgement making. Physiological responses have been documented to appreciate neural activity and brains respond to soundings.

Objective was to monitor undercurrents of biological 'motorists' in appreciating 'mental sounding' in managerial 'deep' bio - computational judgement making. Research issues attempted in this report are:

- How does a manager choose via. neuro-feedback?
- Which waves from brain performs in 'deep' Bio - computational judgement making?
- How to detect and maneuver response soundings?

Methodology

Methodology planned was to elucidate principles and wave intelligence mechanism in brain. Principal aim was to model neuro - managerial intelligence by using tools from brain waves (Electroencephalograph). This aimed at, first, incorporating neuro-managerial science and neuro - psycho modeling approach. And, second, irrigate knowledge of evidences for multiple systems involved in wave intelligence - making. Objective was to monitor dynamics of brain wave drivers in understanding managerial behaviour and preference making. This report proposed 'chess - board dynamic quadrant matrix' with ideas (a) that frogspawn patterns of heretical appraisal and, (b) link methodological differences. Through computational approaches, attempt was to clarify how neural investigations realize 'mental stimuli' in managerial wave intelligence making. Focal point was to understand neural processes underlying how managers craft wave intelligence, understand mechanisms of wave intelligence and integrate inter - disciplinary research.

Two specific research questions were pursued (Mishra, Singh, and Koles; 2021). First, how is 'deep' bio - computational judgement choices explored and secondly, what part of brain aids 'deep' bio - computational judgement? On scrutiny, methodological and philosophical issues loom large: What is a powerful neuronal explanation? How can waves tally with management as regards occurrence, pinnacle, outline and position? Are there reliable empirical methods for testing hypotheses recognized across various disciplines? Methodology includes neuro-based opinions to imitate thinking of neurobiology in 'business' algorithmic framework. It was believed that to realize thoughts and feelings in behaviour, and whether or not we can measure them, we can observe reviews, feelings, and 'deep' bio - computational judgements as behaviour components using qEEG (q - electro - Encephalo - Graph) to demonstrate operational models.

The approach adopted is mix of theoretical and experimental. It depicts relevant aspects of business theories and applications of neuro-managerial science in fluid intelligence. Attempt is to observe neuro -based techniques to study brain. On contemporary level, physiological responses have been measured by observing neural activity viz. Alpha Waves, and how brains respond to stimulus presentation. With fluid intelligence procedure, via EEG, conductors were used to record electrical activity of brain. These waves offer evidence about circumstances and cognitive processes in fluid intelligence. In light of debating theories and applications in bio - computational judgement making, physiological fluid intelligence responses have been measured to appreciate neural activity and how brains respond to sounding. Neuro -based feedback presents itself as effective and scientifically based method of treatment. With neuro-based feedback methodology via EEG, electrodes were attached to skull to record electrical activity. At the same time, it was certain that these wave patterns would alter depending on mental and physical condition. Method thus comprised of amplifying targeted behaviour which corresponded to favourable composition of brainwaves.

As regards population and sample size, it was estimated that a population of 15 respondents would be a fair populace and subjecting respondents to clinical test could lead to fair results. qEEG conductors were fixed on scalp to portion electrical activity of brain with a view to trace and calibrate impulses (active intelligence linking cognizant to subliminal) owing to electrical inducement. Comeback values were experimented at 256 Hz (3.9-msec epoch) for 01 second. Subjects were experimented with either single stimulus (S1) or to two stimuli (S1 and S2). When two stimuli were exposed, they were accessible in either a harmonized form where S1 was identical to S2 or in a non-matched condition where S1 differed from S2. In light of ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making, physiological neuro-stimulus responses were calibrated to appreciate neural motion and how brain structures respond to brain wave-based response sounding. Of brain waves (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta and Theta), Alpha waves have been factored as ‘Catalyst’ in guiding towards near-optimal ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement scenarios. Alpha waves reflected degrees of information absorption and retention as well as emotion management in ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement management.

As a precursor to the methodology (digital compartment competence) being adopted, the following model incorporating spontaneity and instinctive are factored in;

- Rhythm_Pt <- Seq(From = 0, To = 1000, By = 2) / Tentative Variable
- T <- Length (Rhythm _Pt), N <- N Row(Spontaneity) / Tentative Variable
- Spontaneity @Subject <- Factor (Spontaneity @Motif / Tentative Variable
- Levels(Spontaneity @Motif)[C(1, 9, 20:24, 2:8, 10:19)] / Tentative Variable
- Spontaneity @ Motif <- Factor(Spontaneity @ Motif,
- Levels (Spontaneity @Stimuli)[C(3,2,1)]

A theoretical posits in incipient neuro - managerial science sign suggests that comprehensive and coherent neuro - managerial ‘deep’ Bio - computational judgement making rest on prior precise emotive dispensation. These transpire at multiple levels of mental maneuver. Some occur determinedly and some ensue non-consciously. The matters that crop up are; what happens when Managers variate minds? What set of rules allow sensorimotor behaviours to be cultured? What computational apparatuses allow brain to acclimatize varying settings? How (and where) the brains value and prospect and what do are the subtleties of this? What neural arrangements trail defined forms of efficacy? To what range do utility calculations simplify ‘deep’ Bio - computational judgement that is complex? These lead to a study on neuro-feedback and real-time feedback from brain activity.

Figure – 01 / 01

Representative qEEG - Setting

- qEEG_info.loc [qEEG_info ['cell spot'] == 'AF1', 'cell spot'] = 'AF3'
- qEEG_info.loc [qEEG_info ['cell spot'] == 'AF2', 'cell spot'] = 'AF4'
- qEEG_info.loc [qEEG_info ['cell spot'] == 'PO1', 'cell spot'] = 'PO3'
- qEEG_info.loc [qEEG_info ['cell spot'] == 'PO2', 'cell spot'] = 'PO4'
- qEEG_info = qEEG_info[(qEEG_info['cell spot'] != 'X')
- (qEEG_info ['cell spot'] != 'Y')
- (qEEG_info ['cell spot'] != 'nd')

- F = Frontal
- Fp = Frontopolar
- T = Temporal
- C = Central
- P = Parietal
- = Occipital
- A = Auricular (Ear Q - electrode)

Machine Language Construal [Pilot Test - Run]

A Pilot test – run was conducted on 02 subjects. Recordings obtained were as under;

Table: 02 / 01

Summary of Soundings

<u>Sounding: Subject 01</u>										
<	7	7	8	8	8	8	6	6	6	6
p	8	6	8	8	8	8	8	7	8	8
a	7	8	6	7	8	7	6	8	8	8
t	C			C			C			L
h		8	8		8	8		7	7	
d	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	6	8	8
=	7	6	6	8	6	8	7	6	8	8
	6			6			8			

" M 7 6 7										
6 8 8 L 8 8	6 7 7 C 8 8 7 8	6 8 6 8 7 8 8	6 8 8 8 7 8	8 7 6 L 8 7 8	8 7 7 C 8 8 7 8	8 8 7 8 7 8	7 8 7 6 7	7 8 L 7 6	8 7 8 8 7	8 8 C 8 8 7
6 7 8 8 8	8 7 8 8 8	8 8 C 8 8 8	7 8 8 8 6 8	7 7 8 7 6 7	7 8 8 M 7 7 8 7	7 6 7 L 7 8 7	8 8 8 C 7 7 8 7	8 8 8 7 8 6	6 8 7 7 7 6	6 8 8 C 7 7 7 8
6 8 8 7 8 8	6 8 8 7 8	6 8 8 C 7 8 6 6	6 8 8 8 8 8	8 8 8 8 8 8	8 8 8 C 8 8 8	8 6 7 L 7 6 8	7 7 7 Z M 7 8 7	7 6 7 8 7	7 8 L 7 8 8	7 8 C 7 8 8
7 7 8 8 8 8	7 8 7 8 8 8	8 8 C 8 8 8	6 7 6 6	7 8 7 6	7 8 7 C 7 7 8	7 8 7 7 7	8 7 7 8 7	8 7 8 Z M 7 8 7	s i m u l i d = " f 8 8 8	8 8 7 7 8 8
7 8 " / > < p	7 8 L 8 7 7	6 8 C 8 8 7	8 8 7 8	8 8 7 6	8 8 7 6 8	8 8 7 8 7	6 8 7 7	8 8 L 7 8	7 8 C 7 8	7 8 7 8

a t h d = " M 8 7 7								7	7	
7 8 7 7 C 7 8 6	8 7 7 7 8 8	8 8 7 8 8	8 8 7 7 8	8 8 7 8 6 8	8 7 6 8 7	7 8 8 6 8	7 6 8 8 6	7 6 8 8 6	7 8 8 8 8	7 7 8 8 8
7 8 8 6 8	7 8 6 8 6	7 8 6 8 8	7 8 6 8 8	7 8 7 8 6 8	7 8 8 8 7 8	7 8 8 7 7	7 6 8 8 8	7 8 8 8 6	7 8 6 8 8	8 8 8 8 8
8 8 C 7 8 8	8 8 7 6 8	7 8 6 7 8	7 8 7 6 8	7 6 8 7 7	7 8 6 8 8	7 8 8 7 8	7 8 C 6 8	8 8 7 8	8 8 7 8	8 8 7 8
8 6 8 8 8 8 8 8 7 C	7 8 6 6	8 7 7 8 7	7 8 8	7 8 8	8 C 7 8 7	8 8 7 8 7	6 8 8	8 8 8	8 8 6 8	8 8 7 8

8 8 8					8 8					
8 7					8 7 Z M					
7 7 6					7 6 8					

6 7 8 7 8	8 7 8 C 8 7 8	8 6 8 8 6	8 8 8 8 8	8 8 C 7 8 6	7 8 8 7 8 8	7 7 8 7 6 8	7 8 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 6 " / > < p a t h d = " M 7 8 8
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7 7 8 C 7 8 6	7 8 8 7 8 6	8 8 7 7 8 6	8 7 8 C 7 6 6	8 8 7 8 6 8	8 8 7 7 8 8	8 8 C 8 8 8 6	8 8 8 6 8	7 8 8 6	7 8 8 C 8 6 6	7 8 7 8 8
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7 8 8 8 7	8 8 7 C 7 7 7	8 8 7 6 8	8 7 8 7 6 8	8 8 C 7 6 8	8 8 7 7 6 8	7 8 8 C 8 7 8	7 8 8 8	7 8 8	6 8 8	8 8 L 8 8
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8 8 C 8 8	8 8 8 8	7 6 8 8	7 7 C 6 8	6 8 7 8 8	7 8 7 7 6	8 7 C 7 7	8 8 7 8 6	7 7 8 8	7 6 7 C 8 6	7 8 8 7 6
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				7 8 6 7 8 7 C 7 8 7 8 7 7 7 6		6			6	
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7 8 8 8 7 6	7 8 C 8 7 6	7 8 8 7	8 8 6 8 8 8	8 8 6 C 7 8 8	8 8 6 7 8	7 6 8 8	7 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 7 8 8
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8 8 6 C 7 8 8 7	6 7 8 6	8 6 7 8	8 6 C 8 8 8	8 6 8 8 6	8 8 7 8 8	7 8 C 7 8	7 8 7 6 8	7 6 7 6 6	7 6 8 C 7 8 6	7 6 8 8 7 8
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7 6 6 8 8	7 8 6 C 8	7 6 8 7 7	8 8 8 7 8	8 8 L 7	8 8 C 8	8 8 8 8	8 7 8 8	7 6 C 6	7 7 8 7 6	7 6 8 7 6
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7 8 8 C 7 6	8 8 8 8 8 7 7 7 8 7 C 7 6 7 8 7 7 7 7	6 7 8 8	8 Z M 7 7 8	8 7 C 7 8 8	8 7 7 8 8	7 6 8 8 8	7 8 C 7 8 8 8	7 8 6 7 8 8 8	7 8 7 7 C 7 8 8	7 8 7 C 7 8 8 7
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7 8 8 8 6 6	7 8 8 7 8	7 8 8 C 8 7 8	7 6 8 8 8	8 8 7 7 8	8 8 7 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 7 7 8 8 L	7 6 C 8 6 8	7 7 8 6 6 6
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7 8 8 6 6	8 8 L 8 6 6	6 8 7 C 8 7 7	6 8 8 6 8	6 8 7 8 8	6 6 L 8 8	6 8 7 C 8 8	6 8 6 8 6	6 8 8 6 6	8 6 L 8 6	8 8 C 8 6
7 8 6 8	7 7 8 8	7 6 L 8 8 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 " / > < p a t h d = " M 8 7 8	8 7 6 C 8 6 8	8 7 6 8 6	8 6 8 8 6	8 6 C 8 8 6	6 8 6 8 6 8
6 7 8 8 7 6	6 7 8 C 8 8 8	6 7 8 8	6 8 6 8 8	8 8 6 C 8 8	8 6 8 8 8	8 7 6 8 7 8 7	8 7 6 C Z M 7 8 7 8 L 7 8 7	7 6 C 8 8 8	7 7 8 8 8	7 8 8 8
8 8 6 L 8 8	8 8 C 8 7	8 7 7 8	8 7 8 7	8 7 L 7 8	7 8 C 8 8	7 6 8 8 8 7	7 6 8 8 8 7	7 8 7 L 8 8	8 8 6 C 8 8	7 8 8

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8 8 8 7 7 8	8 8 C 7 7 8 8 7	8 8 8 7 6 6	8 7 6 7 8 8	8 8 C 7 7 8 7 7	8 7 8 8 8	7 6 7 8 8 8	7 6 L 8 8 8 8	8 8 C 8 8 7 6	8 7 7 8 8	8 7 8 7
8 8 L 8 7	7 8 C 8 8 6	7 6 8 8 8 7	7 6 8 8 8 7	7 8 L 8 8 7	8 8 C 8 8 7	7 8 6	7 7 8 8 8 L 7 8 6 8 L 7	7 6 L C 8 8 6	7 6 C 8 8 6	7 7 8 8 8

								8 6		
7 6 8 8 8	8 8 L 8 8 8	7 7 C 7 8 8 8	7 6 8 7 8 8	7 8 8 7 8 8	7 8 8 7 8 6	7 8 8 7 8 8	7 8 8 7 8 8	7 6 L 7 8 8 8	8 8 C 7 8 8	8 8 7 6 8
7 7 8 8	7 6 L 7 8 8 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 7 8 8 8 L 7 8 8	7 6 C 7 8 7	7 8 7 8 6	8 7 7 8 6	8 8 L 7 8 6	6 7 8 C 7 7 7	6 8 7 8 6 7
8 8 8 8 8	8 8 7 L 8 8 8	8 8 L 8 8 6	8 8 6 C 7 8 8	8 8 8 7 8 8	8 8 7 7 8 8	8 8 L 7 8 8	8 8 C 7 7 8 8	8 7 8 8	7 8 8 8	7 6 L 8 8 8 8 Z " i d = " f

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7 8 6 L 7 6 6	7 8 6 C 7 8 8	8 8 8 7 8 7	8 7 6 L 7 8 8	8 7 6 L 8 6 8	8 7 6 L 8 6 8	8 6 8 L 8 8 8	8 6 6 L 8 8 8	8 8 8 L 8 8 8	8 7 6 L 8 8 8	8 7 6 L 8 6
8 8 L 7 8	7 8 6 L 8 8	7 8 6 L 8 8	8 8 6 C 8 8	7 8 8 7 8 8 8 8 8 7 C 8 8 8 8	8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8 8 8 6 8 6 8 L	8 8 8 6 C 6 7 8	7 6 7 8	7 7 7

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6	7	6	8	8	8	8	6	7	6	8
7	L	C			C				C	
7			6	6	8	8	8	8	8	8
7	6	6	8	8	8	8	7	8	6	8
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6	8	8	8	8	7	7	8	8	6	8
6	8	8	8	8	6	8	7	8	8	7
C			C			C			L	C
	7	7		7	7		7	8		
8	8	7	7	6	8	7	8	8	8	8
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8			7			7		8	8	8

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		L	C			L		8	7	7
8	8			8	8	8		7	6	6
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7	7	7	8	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
6	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	8	8	6
C			7	8	7	8	8	8	8	8
	8	8	L	C		C				L
8	8	8		7	7	7		7	7	
8	8	8	8	7	8	8	7	6	6	7

8			8	8	8	8	8	6	6	6
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8	7	7	7	7	7	7	8	7	7	7
8	6	7	6	6	7	8	8	8	8	7
7			L	C			8	6	8	6
C	7	7	7		8	8	L	C		8
	6	8	7	8	8	8			8	8
7	8	6	8	6	6	6	8	8	8	8
6			6	8			8	8	8	7
6							6	6		
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7	6	8	8	8	8	6	8	6	7	6
8	8	8	8	8	8	8	6	6	8	L
C			C			L	C	6	8	8
	8	8		6	6			8	8	8
8	7	6	6	8	8	6	6	7	7	8
8	8	8	7	7	7	8	8			7
8			8			7	7			8
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s	8	6	8	8	8	6	8	6	6	6
i		8	8	8	8	7	8	8	8	8
m		"	L	C			8	7	8	8
u		/			8	8	L	C		
l		>	8	8	8	8			7	7
		<	8	8	8	8	8	8	7	8
		p	8	8			8	8	6	8
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6	6	6	6	8	8	8	8	8	8	7
6	8	8	8	8	7	8	8	8	8	8
8	7	8	8	8	6	6	8	8	8	8
L	C			L	C			C		
		7	7			7	7		7	7
7	7	6	6	7	7	8	8	8	8	8
8	8	7	7	6	7	8	8	8	8	
8	6			7	8			8		

7	6	8	8	8	7	7	8	6	8	8
8	8	6	7		7	6	8	6	8	8
8		L	L	8	8	Z	C			C
C	8			8	8	M		7	7	
	8	7	7				7	8	6	7
7	7	6	6	8	6	7	7	8	6	8
8		7	7			6	8		6	8
	8					7				
	7		8							
			7							
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8	8	7	6	8	8	8	8	6	i	
	8	8	7	8	8	8	8	8	m	
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/	C			C		8	C			Z
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p	6			6	8	7	6	8	6	7
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8	8	7	8	6	8	8	8	8	8	8
6	6	8	8			C		8	8	8
C			C	7	7		8		C	
	7	7		7	6	8	7	8		8
7	8	8	7	8	6	8	8	7	8	8
7	8	8	8			8		8	7	8
7			8						8	

8	8	s	8	8	8	6	6	6	6	7
8	8	i		8	8	6	7	7	7	7
6	6	m		"	8	7	7	L	L	7
	Z	u		/	C	6	8	8		C
7	"	l		>		8	8	7	7	7
8				<	7			8	6	6
8	i			p	8			8	8	7
	d			a	7					6
	=			t						8
	"			h						8
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	8			=						7
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	8			M						
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				8						
				7						

7	7	8	8	6	6	6	6	8	8	8
7	6	6	6	7	7	7	8	6	8	6
8	8	6	8	8	8	8	8	6	8	8
		C			C			L	L	C
8	8		7	7		8	8	8		
8	8	8	7	7	8	7	8	8	6	8
7	7	8	7	8	6	8		7	8	8
		7		6	6					

8	8	8	8	8	8	7	7	8	8	6
8	6	6	6	8	7	8	6	8	7	8
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		C			C			C		7
8	7		7	7		7	8	8	8	7
7	8	7	8	8	7	8	8	8	6	
7	8	6	8	8	8	8	7	8		
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8 8 6 7 8	8 7 6 7 8	8 6 7 6 7 8	6 8 6 6 7	6 8 6 8	6 7 7 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	8 6 " / > < p a t h d = " M 8 8 8	8 8 L 8 8 8	8 8 C 8 8 7
8 8 8 8	6 8 8 8	8 8 L 8 8 8	8 8 C 8 7 8	8 8 8 8	8 7 6 6	8 7 C 7 8 8	8 7 8 8	8 7 6 7 8 6	8 7 6 L 7 8 6	8 7 L 7 7 7
7 8 6 C 7 8 6	7 8 7	7 8 6 7 6 8	7 7 L 7 6 8	8 8 C 7 7 8	6 6 7 7	8 8 7 6	8 8 C 7 8 7	8 8 8 6 8	6 8 8 6 8	8 6 8 L 8 6 8
7 8 8 C 8 6 8	7 6 6 8	8 7 8 6 7	8 8 C 8 8 6	8 8 8 7 8	8 7 6 8 8	8 7 C 6 8	8 7 8 8	8 7 6 7 8	8 6 L 7 8	8 7 L 8 6
7 8 6 C	7 8 8	7 8 6 8	7 7 L	8 7 C	7 8 8	8 7 C	7 8 7	8 8 7 6	6 8 L	8 8 8

8 7	8	8	8 8	8 8	6 8 7	7 8	7	8	6 8 6 L	
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Sounding: Subject 02

9 8 8 8 8	8 8 L 8 8 8	9 8 6 C 9 8 8 9	9 4 9 9 9 4	9 6 9 9 6 8	9 6 9 C 9 6 6	9 6 9 9 8 8	9 6 9 9 8 4	9 4 9 C 9 8 8 8	9 4 6 9 8 8 8	9 4 4 9 8
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9 4 8 C 9 4 8	9 4 8 9 6 9	9 6 8 9 6 9	9 8 8 C 9 6 9	4 9 9 8	4 4 8 9 9 4	4 4 8 C 9 4 6	4 4 8 8 9 8 9	9 8 9 8 8 9	9 4 9 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l
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8	8 9 " / > < p a r t h d = " M 9 8 8	8 8 8 4 9	9 6 8 C 8 4 9	4 4 9 8 8	6 8 9 9 8 8	6 8 6 L 9 8 8 9	6 8 8 8 6 8 8	6 8 8 8 6 8 8	4 4 8 8 6 8 8	9 6 9 L 6 8
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9 6	8 8	s i	8	8 "	4 9	4 9	4 8	4 8	9 8	9 4
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8 C 6 8	8 9 6 6 8 9 8 9 8 6 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	m u l		/ > < p a t h d = " M 4 6 8	6 L 9 8 8	6 L 9 8 8	8 C 9 4 6	4 9 6 9	9 9 4 6	4 C 9 9 4
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9 8 8 9 8 9	8 8 8 9 4 8	8 6 C 9 9 8	8 6 8 8 8 8	9 8 4 8 6 9	9 4 4 C 8 8 4 6	9 8 6 8 4 8	4 8 4 9 8 9	4 8 8 L 9 8 9	4 9 6 L 9 8 8	9
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4 9 6 L	9	4 8 8 C 4 9	4 8 9 4 8	9 8 6 8 9	9 9 8 C 8 9 8	9 9 9 8 6 6	8 8 9 9 8 8 8 L 9 4 8 8 8 C	8 9 8 9 4 6	9 6 8 9 8 8	9 9 6 C 4 8 6
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							9 8 4			
9 8 4 4 9 4	4 8 4 4 6 8	4 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	8 6 / > < p a t h d = " M 4 6 8	4 9 6 L	4 9 6 L	4 8 8 C	4 8 4 9 6 8	9 8 9 4 8
9 4 4 C 9 9 8	9 8 9 4	8 6 4 9 4 6	8 8 L	9 4 6 C 8 4 9	9 8 4 8	4 8 4 9 8 4	4 8 L	4 9 6 L	4 9 6 L	4 8 8 C 4 6
4 8 4 6 6	9 8 8	9 6 C 8 8 8 6	9 6 4 8 6 9	8 4 4 9 8 9	9 8 C 9 9 8 8	8 9 9 8 8 8 9 8 4	9 8 C 9 9 9 9	9 8 9 6 4	9 8 6 9 8 8	9 9 8 C 4 8 6
9 8 4 4 9 4	4 8 9 4 6 8	4 8 Z " i d = "	s i m u l	8	8 8 / > < p a t h	9 6 8 C	4 8 9	6 8 8 6 4	6 8 8 L	6 8 6 C 8 4 4

		f 8 8 8			d = " M 9 6 4					
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6 8 4 9 8 9	4 9 9 8 9	9 6 8 C 9 8 9	8 8 8 4 6 9 4 4 8 4 6 L 6 4 8 6 8 8 C 9 8 9 6 8 9 6 4	8 8 9 6 4	9 6 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	8 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 9 8 4	9 6 C 9 9 8	9 8 9 8
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9 6 9 8 8	4 4 C 9 8 9	4 4 9 8 6	6 6 9 8 6	8 8 4 L 9 8 6	6 9 4 C 9 9 6	6 8 8 8 6 8	4 8 9 8 8	4 8 9 L 8 8 8	4 4 8 L 8 4 6	4 4 6 C 8 6 8
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4	4	4	4	4	4	8	6	4	4	9
4	4	4	9	9	8	8	6	4	4	6
6	9	6	8	9	8	4	9	8	C	8
8	8	C	9	9	L	C	8	8	8	4
8	8	9	8	8	9	9	8	8	8	4
9	6	8	4	4	8	8	8	8	8	
		9			4	4			8	

9	9	s	8	9	9	9	9	4	4	6
8	6	i		8	6	8	4	9	8	8
8	L	m		"	C			C	6	6
8	8	u		/		6	6		6	9
8	8	l		>	6	4	4	6	9	9
	8			<	6	8	9	9	9	9
	8			p	8			4		
	L			a						
	9			t						
	8			h						
	4			d						
	8			=						
	4			"						
	8			M						
	Z			6						
	"			8						
	i			6						
	d			8						
	=			6						
	"			8						
	f			6						
	8									
	8									
	8									

8	9	9	4	4	4	4	4	4	9	9
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L	C			C			C			C
6	6	6	6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
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9	9		4	8			4			9

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4	6	9	8	8	8	6	4	9	9	8
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		C			L	L	C			L
9	9		9	9	8	8	8	8	4	4
4	4	9	9	8	8	8	8	9	8	8
8	9	4	4	8	8	8	9			
		8		8	8	8	8			

9	9	9	9	9	9	9	8	6	4	4
8	8	6	6	6	4	8	8	8	8	9

8 C 6 8	9 8 6	6 8 9	8 C 8 8	9 8 9	9 8 8 9	8 L 8 8 9	9 C 8 8 9	8 8	8 8	C 8 8
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9 4 6 8	9 8 9 6	9 6 L 9 6 8 L 9 9 8 8 L 9 9 8	9 6 C 9 8 9	9 8 8 6	9 4 8 8 8	4 9 C 8 8 8 9	4 9 8 8	6 9 8 8	8 8 9 L 8 8 8	9 9 8 C 9 9 8
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9 6 9 9 4 6	9 8 8 9 8	9 8 8 C 9 9 4 8	9 8 8 9 6 6	9 4 9 9 6 6	9 6 L 9 6 6 6	8 8 9 C 9 9 6 6	6 8 9 9 4	4 8 9 6 4	4 9 C 9 4 4 8	9 4 9 9 8
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9 8 9 8 6	9 6 L 9 8 6 8 L 4 9 8 8 L 4	9 6 C 4 8 9	9 8 4 6 4	9 4 4 6 6	4 9 C 4 4 6 8	4 9 4 4 6	6 8 4 4 4 6	8 8 8 L 4 4 4 6	9 8 6 C 4 4 4 6	9 8 9 4 4 4
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	9 8									
9 9 6 4 4 9	9 9 C 4 4 8 6	9 6 9 4 9 9	9 8 8 4 6 4 8 6 8 6	9 8 8 C 6 9 4	9 8 8 C 6 4 9 4	9 4 8 6 4 9	9 6 4 L 6 4 9	8 8 6 C 6 4 9	6 9 6 4 8 8	4 9 6 4 8 8
4 9 C 6 9 9	9 4 6 8 9	9 8 4 8 9	9 6 L 4 8 9 8 L 6 8 6 8 L 6 8 6	9 6 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	9	8 6 " / > < p a t h d = " M 8 9 4	4 9 6 C 8 6 9	4 9 6 8 8 6	4 9 4 8 8 6
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9 8 9 8 8	9 4 8 8 9	4 9 C 8 8 4	4 9 8 8 8	6 9 8 8	8 6 L 8 8 8	4 4 8 C 8 9 8	4 9 9 8 9 8	4 9 8 L 9 8	4 8 9 9 6 8	9 8 8 C 6 8
9 8 9 8	9 6 6 8	9 6 8 C	9 6 9 8	9 4 8	9 8 9 L	8 8 6 C	6 9 8 8	4 9 8 C	4 9 C 8	9 4 6 4

6	9	8 8	8 9	8 9	8 8 9	8 8 9			4	
9 8 9 9	9 6 L 9 9 8 L 9 4 9 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	9	8 9 " / > < p a t h d = " M 4 9 4	9 6 C 4 8 6	9 8 4 6 8	9 4 4 6 8	4 9 C 4 6 9	4 8 4 6 8	6 8 4 6 8
8 8 4 L 4 6 8	9 8 6 C 4 4 6 8	9 8 9 4 8	4 4 9 8	4 4 8 C 9 9 8 6	4 4 8 8 9 6 8	4 9 8 8 9 4 8	4 8 8 C 9 4 8 8	4 8 8 9 9 8 8	9 8 9 8 8 8	9 6 9 L 8 8 8
4 4 8 C 8 4 4	4 9 4 8 8	4 9 8 4 9	4 8 8 L 4 9	9 8 8 C 6 8	9 8 9 6 6	9 6 6 C 8 9 8	9 6 8 C 8 8 9	9 6 8 8 9 8 8	9 4 9 8 8 8	9 8 8 L 8 8 9
8 8 4 C 8 8 9	6 9 8 8	4 9 8 8	4 9 C 8 4	9 4 6 9	9 8 9 8	9 6 L 9 8	9 6 C 9 8 6	9 8 8 8 8	9 4 8 8 8	4 9 C 8 8 4

						L				
						9				
						4				
						6				
						8				
						L				
						9				
						4				
						6				

4	6	8	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	8
8	8	8	9	6	8	8	8	4	6	8
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8	8	8	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	9
		8	9	4	8	9	8	8	9	8
		8	8	6	8	4	8	8	8	8
		8	8			8			8	8

6	4	4	9	9	9	9	s	9	8	6
4	9	4	4	8	6	6	i		8	8
		C			L	Z	m		"	4
9	9		9	9		"	u		/	L
6	6	9	4	8	9		l		>	
6	8	6	4	4	8	i			<	4
		9			4	d			p	8
					8	=			a	6
					L	"			t	
					4	f			h	
					9	8			d	
					4	8			=	
					4	8			"	
					8	8			M	
					L	8			4	
					4	8			8	
					9	8			9	
					4	8				

6	6	9	9	9	9	9	9	8	8	8
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L	L	C			C			C		
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					8			6		

8	4	9	9	9	4	8	8	8	8	6
9	9	8	8	8	6	8	6	6	8	8
C			C		8	C			C	
	9	9		8	8		8	6		4

9 8 9	6 8	9 8	8 8 8	9 8	6	8 8	8	8	4 8	8
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6 8 4 8	4 6 C 4 8	4 4 9	9 4 6 6	9 9 C 8 9	6 8 9 8 8 8 8 8 9 9 C 9 9 8 8 8	8 9 9 4 9	4 8 C 4 8 8	8 8 8 4 9 8	8 6 4 9 9 8	9 9 4 C 4 9 8
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9 6 8 4 8 4	9 8 8 9 6 8	9 4 4 C 9 4 4	9 6 8 9 8	9 8 4 9 9 8 8	9 8 4 C 9 9 8 8 4	9 8 4 8 6 8	9 8 4 8 9 6	9 6 4 L 8 4 9	4 4 8 L 9 8 6	4 4 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8
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s i m u l	8	9 4 " / > < p a t h d	9 8 8 L 8 6 8	4 4 8 C 8 9 9	4 4 8 6 6	4 9 9 4	4 8 6 L 9 4	9 8 9 C 8 6	9 8 4 8 8	9 8 9 8 8
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		= " M								
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9 8 6 L 8 8 8 9 4 C 8 8 9 8 8 9 8 6	6 C 8 8 9 8 8 9 8 8 9 C 9 6 8	8 9 4 8 6	8 8 4 8 6	9 6 C 4 8 6	9 4 8 9 8	4 4 8 9 8 8	4 4 C 9 8 8	4 4 8 9 6 8	4 4 9 6 8	4 9 9 Z M 8 6 8
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9 4 6 C 8 8 6	9 6 6 9 9 6 8	9 8 8 9 6 8	9 8 8 C 9 4 8 4 8	9 8 8 4 8 9	9 9 8 4 9	9 9 8 C 4 8 9	8 8 9 4 6	9 6 9 6 9	9 6 C 9 9 8	9 6 8 8 8
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4 9 8 6 8	6 Z " i d = " f 8	s i m u l	8	8 8 " / > < p a t h	9 6 C 8 4 6	8 8 4 9	8 8 4 9	9 6 8 C 8 4 9	9 4 4 8 4 6	4 9 6 8 8 4
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	8 8			d = " M 9 8 8						
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4 8 9 C 9 8 8 9	4 8 6 9 4 8	6 4 4 9 8 8	6 8 6 L 9 8 8 9	6 8 8 C 8 4 9	6 8 4 6 8	4 6 8 6 8	9 6 8 L 6 8	9 6 8 C 6 8	6 8 8 4 9 6 6	s i m u l
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8	8 9 " / > < p a t	6 8 9 L 9 8 8	6 8 9 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 8 9 6	9 4 9 C 8 6 8	4 4 8 9 9 9	4 9 6 9 9 8	4 6 4 C 9 4 6
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4 8 8 9 8 9	6 8 9 4 9 8	6 8 8 L 4 9 9	6 4 8 C 9 6 8	6 9 4 9 6	6 9 9 8 4	6 8 8 C 9 9 9 4	4 8 8	4 4 9 8 6	4 8 9 C 6 9	4 9 9 9 6
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9 4 9 9 6	9 9 8 C 9 6	8 6 8 8 4 6	8 8 8 8 4	4 6 C 8 9 4	8 8 8 9 8 9	8 9 8 8 8	4 9 C 4 9 8	8 4 4 4 6	8 4 6 4 4 6	9 8 8 C 4 4 6
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9 6 8 4 9 8	9 8 4 9 8 6	9 4 8 C 9 9 6 6 9	9 6 4 9 9 8	9 8 9 9 6 6 4 9	9 8 9 9 C 9 4 9	9 8 9 9 8 4 8	9 8 6 9 8 4 9 6 9	9 6 6 Z M 9 9 9 6	9 9 6 C 9 4 8	9 9 6 9
9 9 8 9 9 6	9 8 8 C 9 9 4 8	9 4 6 9 6 8	9 8 6 6 8	8 6 9 C 9 4 6 8	8 9 9 9 4 9	8 6 C 9 8 8	6 9 6 8 8	9 6 9 8 9 9 6 4	9 9 9 4 8	9 9 C 9 8 8 8
9 9 8 8 6	4 9 8 6 9	8 4 C 8 9 8	8 9 6 8	8 6 8 8 9 6	9 4 8 C 8 9 6	9 8 4 8 9 9 9	9 8 8 4 9 6 4	9 8 8 C 8 6 4	9 9 8 8 6	9 9 6 6
9 9 6 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	9 6 " / > < p a t h d = " M 6 9 8	6 4 8 L 4 6 8	6 4 8 L 4 6 8	6 9 8 C 4 4 4 4 6	6 8 4 8 4 4 4	6 8 8 8 4	4 9 6 L 4 4 4 4	9 6 4 L 9 8 9
9 6 4 L 9 8 8 9	4 9 6 C 9 9 8 9	6 8 8 9 9 8	6 8 6 9 8 6	6 9 4 9 8 6	6 4 8 L 9 8 8	6 4 8 8 L 9 8 8	6 9 8 9 6 8	6 8 6 8 9 8	6 8 8 9 8	4 9 6 L 8 9 8
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9 9 C 8 9 8	8 8 8	4 4 8	8 L 4 8 8 L	8 C 9 9 8	4 9 8 9	8 9 8 9	9 9 L 9 8 9	9 9 L 4 4 4	9 9 L 4 4 4	9 9 C 4 4 4
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9 8 4 4 6	9 4 4 6 8	9 8 L 4 6 8 8 L 6 9 8 8 L	9 8 C 6 4 6	9 4 6 9 8	9 8 6 9 8	8 9 9 L 6 9 8	4 9 6 C 6 9 8	6 8 8 6 4 6	6 8 4 6 9 8	6 9 9 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8
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s i m u l	8	4 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 9 8 6	8 9 8 L 9 6 4	8 8 4 C 9 9 6	4 4 9 8 6	9 9 9 4 8	9 9 L 8 4 8	9 9 C 9 9 9	8 6 6 9 8 9	9 8 4 9 8 4
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4 9 9 L 9 6 8	4 9 6 L 8 4 8	4 9 6 C 8 8 8 9	4 9 6 8 8	4 4 9 8 4	4 4 8 L 6 9	4 4 8 8 C 6 4	4 8 4 8 4	9 4 9 8	9 8 4 L 6 4	9 8 4 L 6 8
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9	9	4	4	4	4	4	9	8	8	4
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9 9 C 8 8 6	8 8 8 8 8 8	8 9 8 8 8 8	8 9 C 9 8 4	8 9 9 4 6	8 9 9 8 8	8 9 C 8 8 8	6 8 8 8 6	4 9 9 8 8 L 9 6 6 8 C 9 8 9	4 L 9 8 8 L 9 6 6 8 C 9 8 9	8 9 8 8
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8 6 4 8 9	8 9 4 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8 8	8 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 6 4	6 9 9 6 4	9 6 8 C 9 6 4	4 6 6 9 8 4	6 8 4 6 4	6 8 8 L 4 4	6 8 6 C 8 4
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6 4 4 8 9 4	4 8 6 8 6 8	4 8 9 C 8 8 8 8	4 9 8 9 8 9	9 4 6 9 8 9	9 6 8 C 9 8 9	8 8 9 8 8 8	8 8 9 8 6 8	9 6 C 8 9 4 4 8 8 4 8 8	s i m u l	8
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								6		
8	6	6	6	6	4	8	4	9	9	9
9	4	9	8	8	9	9	9	4	8	8
"	8	9	6	9	4	4			L	C
/	L	C			L	C	8	4		
>			8	8			9	8	4	9
<	4	8	9	9	8	8	8		8	9
p	6	9	8	8	9	9				8
a		8			8	8			8	
t									L	
h									9	
d									8	
=									8	
"									8	
M									L	
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					9					
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8	8	8	9	4	6	9	9	9	8	4
	C			C			C			Z
9		4	4		9	9		9	9	"
6	9	9	9	4	4	8	9	9	8	
8	6	8	8	9	8	4	4	4	9	i
	8			8			9			d
										=
										"
										f
										8
										8
										8
s	8	4	8	6	4	4	4	8	9	9

i m u l		" / > < p a t h d = " M	8 8 C 9 4 4	8 9 8 9	6 9 6 8	6 C 9 8 8 9	6 8 8 8 8	8 9 8 8 8	4 8 C 8 8 8	4 6 8 6 4
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4 8 8 9 4 8	4 8 8 C 9 9 8 6 6	4 8 8 9 8 9	9 8 8 9 4 9	9 6 8 C 9 9 4 8	9 4 9 4 4	9 4 8 9 6 8	9 4 8 C 9 9 6 9	9 4 8 8 9 4	9 6 8 9 8 4	9 8 9 C 9 8 8 4
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4 8 9 9 8 8	4 8 8 9 6 8	4 9 9 C 9 6 9	4 9 6 9 8	4 4 8 9 8	4 4 8 L 9 8 6	4 4 8 C 9 4 8	4 4 8 8 8	4 9 8 8 9 8	9 8 9 C 6 8	9 4 8 9 6 6
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9 6 4 9 6	8 8 6 C 9 6	8 8 8 9 9 8 9 9 8 9 C 9	9 9 4 8 8 6	8 8 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 8 " / > < p a t h d = " M 4 8 9	9 6 C 4 6 4	9 8 4 4 8	4 9 4 8 9
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8	8	4	s	8	6	4	4	9	9	8
8	9	8	i		6	9	8	8	8	8
6	8		m		"	6	8	6	6	9
C		9	u		/	L	L	L	L	C
9	9	6	l		>					
6	8	6			<	9	9	8	8	8
6		9			p	6	8	8	8	8
		Z			a			8	8	8
		"			t					
		i			h					
		d								
		=			d					
		"			=					
		f			"					
		8			M					
		8								
		8								
		8								

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		L	C			8	6	6	4	8
8	9		8	8	8	L	L	C		9
4	8	9	8	8	8		9	9	9	8
		8	6			8	8	8	4	8
		8				8	8	8		
		L								
		9								
		6								
		6								

4	4	4	4	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
9	9	6	6	8	9	4	4	4	4	4
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L	L	C			C			C		
			8	9		9	9	9	9	9
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8	8	6	8	9	8	8	6	8	8	6
8	8	8			4			8		

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9	8	8	8	9	9	4	4	6	6	8
				6	4	9	4	6	8	6
C			C			C			C	
	9	9		9	9		9	9		9
9	4	6	9	8	8	9	8	6	9	9

4 6	4	4	6 4	8	9	8 8	6	8	6 9	9
6 8 8 9 8 8	6 8 9 C 9 9 6 8	6 8 6 9 9 4	6 8 8 8 8 4	6 4 8 8 9 4	6 8 9 8 8	4 6 9 8 9	4 4 8 C 8 8 8 4	4 8 8 8 8 8	4 8 8 8 8	4 4 8 L 8 8 8
4 9 6 Z " i d = " f 8 8 8	s i m u l	8	6 8 " / > < / d e f s >							

The AI - ML [symbolic Logic] explanation is depicted as under:-

```

<Line fill="none" x8="6.888" x9="6.888" y8="989.88" y9="998.986" stroke-linejoin="bevel" stroke="#888888"
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stroke-width="8.8" stroke-miterlimit="8"/>
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The reference runs and stimulus - responses (wavelet transforms), based on data points above were catalogued in terms of command (time rate of recurrence variation based on the following parametric modeling:

```
co-ordinates #feed <- relevel(coordinates#feed,ref = feeds[i])  
co-ordinates subject <- relevel(coordinates#subject,ref = subjects[j])  
design <- model. matrix(~ c(subject, sum)/subject + subject + condition +  
feed + feed: condition + feed: subject  
condition: subject + feed:condition:subject,  
data = coordinates)  
erplot(erpdata, design, effect = 26, interval = "simultaneous",  
xlab = "time (ms)", ylab = "condition effect")  
call(paste("subject ", subjects[j], " feed ", feeds[i], sep = ""))
```

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id="defs6"><stimuli_alpha  
id="stimuli_alpha20" to alpha path 966  
style= time rate of recurrence variation  
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x="0 5.99472 11.98944 18.094561 24.089279 30.194401 36.189121 42.183842 48.28896">(mfrow = </tspan>  
</g></g><g  
id="g38"><g  
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</g></g><g
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y="0"
x="0 5.99472 12.09984 18.094561 24.089279 30.194401 36.189121 42.294239 48.28896 54.28368 60.388802
66.383522 72.48864 78.48336 84.478081 90.583199 96.577919 102.68304 108.67776 114.67248 120.7776 126.77232
132.87744 138.87216 144.86688 150.972 156.96672 163.07184 169.06656 175.06128 181.1664 187.16112 193.26624
199.26096 205.25568 211.36079 217.35551 223.46065 229.45535 235.45007">(Subject, sum)/Item + Item +
Condition</tspan>

y="0"
x="0 6.1051202 12.09984 18.20496 24.19968 30.194401 36.299519 42.294239 50.80608 56.8008 65.312637
71.307358 77.302078 83.407204 89.401917 95.507042 101.50176 107.49648 113.6016 119.59632 125.70144
131.69617 137.80128 143.79601 149.79073 155.89584 161.89056 167.99568 176.38608 182.4912 190.88161
196.87633 202.98145 208.97617 215.08128 221.076 227.07072 233.17584 239.17056 245.27568 251.2704 257.37552
263.37024 269.25455">Path + Path:Condition + Path:Item </tspan>

y="0"
x="0 6.1051202 12.09984 18.20496 24.19968 30.194401 36.299519 42.294239 48.399361 54.394081 60.388802
66.493919 72.48864 78.593758 84.588478 90.583199 96.688316 102.68304 108.78816 114.78288 120.7776
126.88272 132.87744 138.98256 144.97728 150.972 157.07712 163.07184 169.17696 175.17168 181.1664 187.27151
193.26624 199.37135 205.36607 211.36079 217.46593 223.46065 229.56577 235.56049 241.55521
247.66032">Condition:Item + Path:Condition:Item,</tspan>

y="0"
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132.87744 138.87216 144.97728 150.972 157.07712 163.07184 169.06656 175.17168 181.1664 187.27151 193.26624
199.26096 205.36607 211.36079 217.46593 223.46065 229.45535 235.56049 241.55521 247.66032 253.65504
259.64975 265.75488 271.7496 277.85471 283.84943 289.84415 295.94928 301.944 308.04913 314.04385 320.03857
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y="0"
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126.88272 132.87744 138.98256 144.97728 150.972 157.07712 163.07184 169.17696 175.17168 181.1664 187.27151
193.26624 199.37135 205.36607 211.36079 217.46593 223.46065 229.56577 235.56049 241.55521 247.66032
253.65504 259.76016">nbs = 20, lwd

```
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326.14368 332.1384 338.24353">
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similarity (mfrow = c(3, 2))  
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d="m 87.504,772.32 h 452.59 v 12.96 H 87.504 Z" />  
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d="M 267.53,695.02 H 540.1 v 12.96 H 267.53 Z" />  
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```

As evinced above, the experimental effort to deliberate on characteristic schemes and landscapes for future replicative studies. The present attempt underwrites in direction of providing an outline for steering ‘deep’ computational judgement investigations, proposition explanation through stimulus measurements at a ‘deep’ computational judgement stretch, and designating typical interdisciplinary prototype for neuron-stimulus-based ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement construction.

Through neuro - computational stratagem (Alpha Wave analysis), attempts have been undertaken to observe neural soundings (‘mental sounding’) in (managerial) ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making. These attempts (Alpha Wave analysis) are undertaken to explore singularities through action, ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making and reasoning processes to model (neuro-managerial) basis of judgement making. In luminosity of estimation theories and application of neuro - managerial science in ‘deep’ bio - computational judgement making (Alpha Wave analysis), it is important to observe what neuro-based psycho- techniques can be used to study brain (Alpha Wave analysis).

Observations

Combining above disciplines offers an inter - disciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - managerial fluid intelligence making. Complexly inter - linked imaging technologies, have motivated studies of internal order of mind. This research attempts to discuss findings towards understanding neuro - design and offer answers to issues in

unpredictability quadrant behaviour dynamics. Research attempts appear to conclude with distinctive propositions and presents directions for future research. Research attempts aid re - thinking by providing alternative taxonomy opening new vistas for future replicative studies.

This report advances theoretical models grounded on an axiomatic groundwork of brain wave - based response to 'deep' bio - computational judgement. Alpha activation imaging methods show 'repeatability' and 'specificity' in showing pre - cursors to mental and arousing responses. This model of 'deep' bio - computational judgement reflects relevant findings on typical human (managerial) behaviour. Domino effect put to the fore that neural signature do not simmer down its own set of connections or neuronal region. This research calls to inquire localizable theories in its explicit neural taxonomy. Study exhibits vital findings from scientific and practitioner perspectives and explains how neuro apparatuses function in 'deep' bio - computational judgement thinking biological basis towards prototyping tectonic shifts(s) in a local loop oscillating around set of conditions. qEEG based pilot experiment is intervening in this stage as brain can learn to break out of 'locally trapped' contour. Results exhibit monikers to engage in 'deep' bio - computational judgement of specific neural system.

Complexly interlinked imaging technologies has prompted new arena of research in anatomical functioning of mind and particularly brain waves. Interaction between Business and Science is not smooth with differences in perception and reasoning potentials on either side. This suggests fundamental changes in how to think, observe and generate choices. Explorations have extended from brain wave-based response soundings to stimulating shares of chromatic prospects for rational processing. Research attempts discuss findings to understand neuro - design and offer to answer issues in organizational preference dynamics. Research attempts to conclude with distinctive propositions and present directions for future research. Research attempt aid in opening new vistas for future replicative studies.

Conclusion

In a brain knowledge - oriented 'deep' bio - computational judgement milieu, each individual can benchmark, control, regulate, optimise and condition his cognition and mental processes. Individual can do this using copious neuro-technologies and psycho-active constituents. This state of 'cognitive liberty' may require 'Deep Brain Stimulation'. Significant finding of this research is that any manager endeavours to address 'deep' computational judgements through neuro - circuits utilizing 'neuro - drivers'. This research report offers a 'Golden Anchorage' of how managers can make 'deep' computational judgements in future. Report deals with archetypal portrayal of scholarship that resolves to be a character of voyaging imminent techno-scientific and computational judgement inclinations and renaissance.

Being an original attempt as regards structural peep into managerial brain wave dynamics, this report presents observational studies on the following;

- Provide a theoretical framework for brain wave based - computational judgement framework,
- Offer measurements of 'deep' computational judgement design, and,
- Portray an inter-disciplinary model for computational judgement evidence.

Section – 02

Experimental Protocols

Introduction

In 1955, Nobel Laureate Herbert Simon was of firm opinion that realm of neo-classical archetype of bounded (or imperfect) rationality; neurobiological and computational neurobiological and computational judgement choosing was thwarted by inadequate information, skills and scarcity of time. Issue is how one does comprehend methods as regards neuronal signaling in brain. How to detect behaviour of controls by neurons? Interesting is to figure how neurons control as well as signal malfunctions during Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity. One way, is to study action potentials or consequential neurotransmitters (concept of ‘Sparks and Soup’ as propounded by Elliott Valentine; 2006). fMRI (non-invasive neuroimaging technique) is recommended as it can trace dynamics of brain functions / structural anatomy and affected neurons. On pedestal of electrical brain activity (q - electroencephalogram), neurofeedback purports to help detect emotional, behavioural and cognitive execution (founded on operant habituation). Point of challenge is; how does brain accommodate differential situations? And, how does brain integrate differential situations?

A set of rubrics for alternatives ‘choosing are critical for managerial judgement. How to build interpretable models that aid computational neuro-biological and computational judgements? How to ensure that models and explanations are robust to adversarial attacks? How to prepare and evaluate models in presence of missing counterfactuals? How to detect and correct biases in incentive-based neuro-biological and computational judgements? And, how does biology (neuro-science) play a role in central apparatus of actions? Individual (manager) must play with swapping data, reviewing data, churning out ideas, appraising substitutions, instigating directions and sensing pulse of environment. Perceptions and assumptions that underpin set of rubrics for alternatives’ choosing are substantial when fashioning and individual stratagems. A broad range of disciplines seeks to scrutinize individual set of rubrics in managerial biology for alternatives’ choosing. Each of these follows a line of investigation from relatively narrow paradigms, and through these emerge limitations consequent with pure disciplinary research.

Neuro - Scientifics

A scientific understanding of mind is not possible from physical understanding of cranial box. Initial footstep involves objective description and analysis of how mind works within homegrown or within context of individual and

linking this to cranial box functions. Different scientific disciplines, as mentioned above, scrutinize individual set of rubrics for alternatives choosing from perspective and methodology. Within new field of Neuromanagement, these different approaches attempt to unearth comprehensive understanding of biological basis (and determinants) of individual behaviour that control new and enhance models of set of rubrics for alternatives 'choosing process (Satpathy. et.al; 2022).

Causativeness plays central role in individual set of rubrics for alternatives' sciences. What typifies notion of causality in sciences of mind and cranial box? Are dissimilar notions a prerequisite for different experimental approaches? Are there variances in notions that are explicitly and implicitly presumed? What counts as causal evidence in individual set of rubrics for alternative sciences? What role is played by data / facts / figures / evidence and physical mechanisms in identifying causal claims of sciences of mind and cranial box? Nevertheless, set of rubrics for alternatives' choosing, set of rubrics in managerial biology for alternatives' and subsequent response is understood to have biological not just learnt behavioural basis (Satpathy. et.al. 2022). This introduces a critical question; what constitutes causal evidence in set of rubrics for alternative sciences?

How managers make set of rubrics for alternatives, in a strictly empirical (or existential) sense, remains open for scrutiny. Managerial biology 'set of rubrics for alternatives' response tectonic shifts(s)' thinking has biological base that requires holistic thinking and deep understanding of it. A paradigm for managerial biology guidance is emerging. There is birth of a thinking manager, who understands, develops, creates, engages / inspires, ends conventional thinking, understands how to engage and influence 'Cranial Box' of others and help activate openness to new ideas, observe real singularities, describe those in calculations. This is a back-and-forth process akin to Richard Feynman's approach to Physics in realm of human behaviour. In this, individual actions are transformed from results positioning to relationship positioning (Satpathy, et.al. 2022).

Fluid Intelligence

EEG - oriented fluid intelligence is discrete from other types of intelligence, such as EEG - oriented crystallized Intelligence, which is experiential to ability to use acquired knowledge and experience to solve problems. While EEG - oriented crystallized intelligence involves application of previously learned information, EEG - oriented fluid Intelligence involves ability to learn and apply new information quickly and effectively. Therefore, EEG - oriented fluid intelligence is seen as measure of cognitive flexibility and adaptability. While EEG - oriented crystallized intelligence is measure of acquired knowledge and expertise. EEG - oriented fluid Intelligence is observed to ability to solve novel problems, reason abstractly and adapt to new situations. It is observed as ability to think logically and solve problems in complex, unfamiliar situations without relying on pre-existing knowledge or experience.

Research has revealed that fluid intelligence is not fixed and can be improved through various interventions, including cognitive training programs and physical exercise (Jaeggi et al., 2008; Colcombe et al., 2004). Additionally, some studies have suggested that certain types of experiences, such as musical training or exposure to second language, may enhance fluid intelligence (Schellenberg, 2004; Bialystok and DePape, 2009). While exact neural mechanisms underlying fluid intelligence are still not fully understood, research suggests that it may involve complex interactions between different brain regions and neural networks (Duncan et al., 2000; Gray and Thompson, 2004).

Fluid intelligence (Gf) is fundamental aspect of cognitive abilities, involving reasoning, problem-solving, and abstract thinking abilities, which is essential for adapting to novel or complex situations (Cattell, 1963; McGrew, 2009). Concept of fluid intelligence has been widely studied in fields of Psychology, Neuroscience, and Cognitive Science, with research indicating that Gf has significant implications for various aspects of life, including academic and occupational success, and general mental health (Deary et al., 2010; Gottfredson, 1997; McGrew, 2009). Recent research has examined neuro-biological underpinnings of Gf, with studies indicating that Gf is associated to distributed neural network, including Pre-Frontal, Parietal, and Temporal Cortices (Duncan et al., 2000 and Gray and Chabris, 2003). These brain regions are involved in attention control, working memory and cognitive flexibility, which are key components of fluid intelligence. Research has demonstrated that Gf is not a fixed trait but can be improved through various interventions (Melby-Lervåg and Hulme, 2013; Kizilirmak et al., 2021, Best et al., 2018; Cheval et al., 2019; Erickson et al., 2011).

One prominent theory of fluid intelligence is neural efficiency hypothesis (Neubauer and Fink, 2009). This suggests that individuals with higher fluid intelligence are efficient in their use of neural resources, allowing them to perform complex cognitive tasks with less effort. This hypothesis is supported by neuroimaging studies that have found that individuals with higher fluid intelligence have greater activation in regions of brain involved in working memory and attention control, such as dorsolateral pre-frontal cortex (Gray and Chabris, 2003; Kane et al., 2005). Supplementary studies have investigated role of genetics in fluid intelligence. For instance, studies have suggested that genetic factors account for substantial portion of individual differences in fluid intelligence (Deary et al., 2009). Recently, Genome - Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have identified specific genetic variants associated with fluid intelligence (Snickers et.al.; 2017). These findings have important implications for development of interventions aimed at enhancing fluid intelligence.

Research has examined effects of various interventions on fluid intelligence. One approach that has received considerable attention is cognitive training, which involves engaging in exercises designed to improve cognitive abilities. Several studies have found that cognitive training (can) lead to improvements in fluid intelligence (Au et al., 2015; Melby-Lervåg and Hulme, 2013). However, effects of cognitive training are limited, with some studies suggesting that gains in fluid intelligence may not generalize to other domains (Simons et al., 2016). In addition to cognitive training, other interventions that have been studied include physical exercise and mindfulness meditation. Physical exercise is associated with improvements in cognitive functioning, including fluid intelligence (Erickson et al.; 2011). Similarly, mindfulness meditation has been observed to improve cognitive control and attention functioning, which are important components of fluid intelligence (Moore and Malinowski; 2009).

Overall, study of fluid intelligence has led to important insights into nature of cognitive abilities and their neural basis. While much progress has been made in understanding factors that contribute to individual differences in fluid intelligence, much remains to be learned about how it can be improved and how it relates to other aspects of cognitive functioning. Study of fluid intelligence continues to be an active and exciting area of research, with implications for wide range of domains, from training to development of interventions aimed at enhancing cognitive abilities.

Stimulus

Beginning with physiological origins of QEEG rhythms, Collura (Thomas F. Collura; 2014) and Jay Gunkelman (2022) describe basis of measuring cranial box activity from scalp and how cranial box rhythms reflect key cranial box regulatory processes. Both authors develop practice of measuring, processing, and feeding back cranial box activity data / facts / figures / evidence for biological response training. Combining both; 'Top Down' and 'Bottom Up' approach, Collura describes core scientific principles, as well as current clinical experience and practical aspects of neuro-response assessment and treatment therapy. Whether Subject has technical need to understand neuro response, qEEG patterns from individual's cranial box are compared with 'normative database' of other individual qEEG. These databases compare individual's qEEG pattern with group of carefully selected, normal, healthy individuals in similar age cohort (Thomas F. Collura; 2014). qEEG report helps identify where significant differences exist between a person being tested and a normative group.

Each area of cranial box plays important role. QEEG cranial box map helps identify where cranial box has specific problems and helps target kinds of interventions. This data / facts / figures / evidence are sometimes used to help suggest appropriate medications. For neuro response, it provides guide to where to train. If one or more areas of cranial box run too slowly or fast, it causes problems such as attention, emotional control, mood or behaviour (Thomas F. Collura; 2014). Another measure is called 'Coherence'. Coherence measures how well coordinated communication is between one area of the cranial box and another. There is constant communication between different areas of cranial box. If two areas are communicating too little or too much, it can interfere with efficiency of cranial box. More research and growing body of clinician experience suggest training coherence with neuro response may be an important component of efficient preference (Thomas F. Collura; 2014).

Figure - 01 / 02

Neuro - Management Choice System

Courtesy: Thomas Collura (2014)

Figure – 02 / 02

Cranial Box Architecture

Courtesy: Thomas Collura (2014)

Figure – 03 / 02

Sense Organs; Agents of Choice

Courtesy: Thomas Collura (2014)

Figure – 04 / 02

Representative qEEG

Courtesy: Thomas Collura (2014)

Protocol Architecture

Each dataset contains 2.5 minutes of eyes-open and 2.5 minutes of eyes-closed latent-state EEG. Channels 01 to 64 correspond to monopole EEG channels using 0 channel name as under;

<p>Channel List = {'Fp1';'AF7';'AF3';'F1';'F3';'F5';'F7';'FT7';'FC5';'FC3';'FC1';'C1';'C3';'C5';'T7';'TP7';'CP5';'CP3';'CP1';'P1';'P3';'P5';'P7';... 'P9';'PO7';'PO3';'O1';'Iz';'Oz';'POz';'Pz';'CPz';'Fpz'; 'Fp2';'AF8';'AF4';'Afz';'Fz';'F2';'F4';'F6';'F8';'FT8';'FC6';'FC4';'FC2';'FCz';'Cz';... 'C2';'C4';'C6';'T8';'TP8';'CP6';'CP4';'CP2';'P2';'P4';'P6';'P8';'P10';'PO8';'PO4';'O2'};</p>
<p>Channels 65 to 67: 03 surface EOG electrodes coupled to the outer corner of eyes and middle of eyebrows.</p>
<p>Channel 68: The trigger channel.</p>
<p>Trigger values = 200 correspond to the eyes-open and trigger values = 220 correspond to the eyes-closed state.</p>

- An image appears on the either left or right side of display.
- Subject opens and closes corresponding eyes until image disappears.
- Subsequently Subject relaxes.
- Image appears on either the left or right side of display.
- Subject imagines opening and closing corresponding eyes until image disappears.
- Subsequently Subject relaxes.

Figure – 05 / 02

Representative Protocol

Scalable Vector Graphics [SVG] programming was conducted on Subjects' for protocol architecture. This was for generic description by dove - tailing a two - dimensional vector graphic representation. Attributes define Alpha wave properties concerning size, position and stroke paths. These helped generate 'Cascading Style Sheets'. The path flow - chart is depicted as under:-

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<svg width="17px" height="18px" view Box="0 0 17 18" version="1.1" xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"
xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
<!-- Generator: Sketch 42 (36781) - http://www.bohemiancoding.com/sketch -->
<title>sharing-big-symbol</title>
<desc>Created with Sketch.</desc>
<defs></defs>
<g id="Ref-andamp;-Search" simul="none" simul-width="1" fill="none" fill-rule="evenodd">
<g id="Search-results correct-layout" transform="translate (-1054.000000, -1028.000000)" fill-rule="nonzero"
fill="#767676">
<g id="sharing-big-symbol" transform="translate (1054.000000, 1028.000000)">
<g id="Capa_1">
<g id="_x37_7_Essential_Icons_58_">
<path d="M13.1561798, 11.7505618 C12.1853933, 11.7505618 11.3157303, 12.2157303 10.7696629,
```

Albeit being a non - invasive modus operandi, Electroencephalography (EEG) has been adopted as a procedure peep into brain dynamics of Subjects. Some procedural steps adopted are:

- **Preprocessing:** An attempt was made to iterate and filter out probabilities of eye movements, activities of muscles or clatter (sound) if any. The artifacts were managed before administering protocol.
- **Segmentation:** Recognized as 'epoch', derived EEG data numerical were segmented for investigations with time-specific references and in respect of specific stimuli (event).
- **Feature Mining:** Some response features were mined to activate and home on to relevant, facts, figures, statistical inferences and numerical data. This was to obtain a picture of brain activity. References were drawn to aspects of amplitude, frequency, and phase.
- **Statistical Analysis:** To decipher geometric configurations, some reference and simulation runs were conducted to establish pattern of brain activity. A need was felt to construct a bridge between unambiguous cognitive and behavioural progressions.
- **Mental Picture:** Attention was invested to spot spatial and chronological patterns of brain action.
- Taken as a whole, EEG investigation has been extensively adopted to decipher neural basis of cognitive and behavioural courses of action.

L5.855 05618	1 0.0 71 91 01 C6 .15 84 26 97	9.323 59551 6.1584 2697	8.4 9438 202 5.855 0561 8	7. 7460 6742 L10. 7696 629
4.8943 8202 C11.315 7303	5 .60 22 47	6.067 41573 13.156 1798	6.0 6741 573 C14.8	6. 0674 1573 16.1

	19 12. 18 53 93 3		3483 15	8988 76
4.7123 5955 16.18988 76	3 .03 37 07 87 C1 6.1 89 88 76	1.355 05618 14.834 8315	0 13.15 6179 8	0 C11. 4775 281
0 10.12247 19	1 .35 50 56 18 10. 12 24 71 9	3.033 70787 C10.12 24719	3.4 3820 225 10.20 3370 8	3. 8426 9663 10.3 4494 38
4.1865 1685 L5.43033 708	7 .05 84 26 97 C4 .86 40 44 94	6.350 5618 4.0146 0674	5.8 8539 326 3.043 8202 2	5. 8853 9326 C1.3 6516 854
5.8853 9326 0.010112 3596	7 .24 04 49 44 0.0 10 11 23 59 6	8.919 10112 C0.010 112359 6	10. 5977 528 1.365 1685 4	11 .952 809 3.04 3820 22
11.952 809 C4.0146 0674	1 1.9 52 80 9 4.8	11.48 76404 5.4303 3708	10. 7797 753 L10.3 4494 38	13 .631 4607 C10. 2033 708

	84 26 96 6			
13.975 2809 10.12247 19	1 4.3 79 77 53 10. 12 24 71 9	14.78 42697 C10.12 24719	16. 4629 213 11.47 7528 1	17 .817 9775 13.1 5617 98
17.817 9775 C14.834 8315	1 7.8 17 97 75 16. 18 98 87 6	16.46 29213 16.189 8876	14. 7842 697 C16.1 8988 76	13 .105 618 14.8 3483 15
11.750 5618 13.15617 98	1 1.7 50 56 18 M1 3.1 56 17 98	0.829 213483 C14.38 98876	0.8 2921 3483 15.38 0898 9	1. 8202 2472 15.3 8089 89
3.0539 3258 C15.380 8989	4 .28 76 40 45 14. 38 98 87 6	5.278 65169 13.156 1798	5.2 7865 169 C11.9 2247 19	5. 2786 5169 10.9 3146 07
4.2876 4045 10.93146 07	3 .05 39 32 58 C1 0.9 31 46	1.820 22472 11.922 4719	0.8 2921 3483 13.15 6179 8	0. 8292 1348 3 M3. 0438 2022

	07			
11.143 8202 C1.8101 1236	1 1.1 43 82 02 0.8 19 10 11 24	10.15 2809 0.8191 01124	8.9 1910 112 C0.81 9101 124	7. 6853 9326 1.81 0112 36
6.6943 8202 3.043820 22	6 .69 43 82 02 C4 .27 75 28 09	6.694 38202 5.2685 3933	7.6 8539 326 5.268 5393 3	8. 9191 0112 C5.2 6853 933
10.152 809 4.277528 09	1 1.1 43 82 02 3.0 43 82 02 2	11.14 38202 M13.15 61798	17. 0089 888 C11.9 2247 19	17 .008 9888 10.9 3146 07
16.017 9775 10.93146 07	1 4.7 84 26 97 C1 0.9 31 46 07	13.55 05618 11.922 4719	12. 5595 506 13.15 6179 8	12 .559 5506 C14. 3898 876
12.559 5506 15.38089 89	1 3.5 50 56 18 15. 38 08 98 9	14.78 42697 C15.38 08989	16. 0179 775 14.38 9887 6	17 .008 9888 13.1 5617 98

Machine Language: Alpha

Subject - 1

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

```
[Alpha simul d="M 373 -353C 537 -379 507 -507 507 -503C 507 -559 597 -593 551 -717C 530 -739 377 -750 301 -750L 55 -750L 55 -733C 135 -717 139 -710 139 -537L 139 -133C 139 -50 133 -35 37 -39L 37 0L 357 0C 337 0 503 -13 553 -50C 513 -73 559 -135 559 -191C 559 -391 571 -335 373 -350ZM 313 -373L 313 -559C 313 -591 317 -703 337 -709C 335 -715 359 -719 393 -719C 377 -719 515 -559 515 -590C 515 -507 379 -373 370 -373ZM 313 -339L 359 -339C 390 -339 550 -393 550 -191C 550 -77 377 -35 397 -35C 331 -35 313 -53 313 -135Z" id="f001-simul-0-35"#][Alpha simul d="M 533 -39L 533 -75C 513 -59 399 -55 397 -55C 370 -55 353 -79 353 -115L 353 -399C 353 -353 353 -393 307 -533C 395 -550 355 -559 335 -559C 179 -537 103 -399 75 -379C 57 -375 55 -353 55 -339C 55 -315 79 -397 97 -397C 101 -397 111 -303 117 -319C 135 -359 133 -371 155 -395C 157 -397 171 -505 190 -505C 351 -505 375 -375 375 -391L 375 -375C 353 -357 190 -339 130 -309C 75 -190 39 -159 39 -110C 39 -57 99 13 159 13C 199 13 337 -35 377 -53C 393 -35 399 -31 301 -9C 313 3 333 13 359 13ZM 375 -95C 357 -75 331 -59 195 -59C 175 -59 135 -73 135 -135C 135 -171 157 -190 195 -199C 307 -309 355 -339 375 -350Z" id="f001-simul-0-77"#]
```

Subject - 2

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

```
[Alpha simul d="M 319 -335C 317 -359 307 -509 397 -531C 377 -550 350 -559 309 -559C 117 -559 57 -399 57 -319C 57 -353 133 -309 193 -193C 333 -159 371 -135 371 -91C 371 -59 337 -31 190 -31C 130 -31 95 -79 79 -155L 51 -150C 51 -105 51 -37 59 -33C 75 -7 131 13 173 13C 353 13 337 -35 337 -137C 337 -195 397 -331 310 -373C 177 -391 137 -305 137 -359C 137 -399 153 -517 191 -517C 350 -517 375 -379 395 -319Z" id="f001-simul-0-95"#][Alpha simul d="M 390 -107C 353 -73 307 -57 375 -57C 195 -57 117 -113 115 -359C 335 -353 371 -373 377 -375C 397 -379 500 -377 500 -397C 500 -375 333 -559 350 -559L 359 -559C 199 -559 155 -531 103 -377C 73 -331 37 -379 37 -301C 37 -99 109 13 333 13C 373 13 333 -7 395 -95ZM 335 -513C 391 -513 315 -375 315 -313C 315 -397 309 -393 390 -393C 333 -390 177 -399 130]
```

Subject - 3

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

```
[Alpha simul d="M 339 0L 339 -37C 175 -33 177 -39 177 -105L 177 -713C 133 -700 70 -793 19 -777L 19 -753C 91 -757 97 -755 97 -577L 97 -105C 97 -39 79 -33 15 -37L 15 0Z" id="f001-simul-0-77"#][Alpha simul d="M 135 -537C 175 -537 197 -570 197 -597C 197 -717 175 -739 137 -739C 109 -739 95 -717 95 -597C 95 -570 109 -537 135 -537ZM 353 0L 353 -37C 199 -33 191 -39 191 -107L 191 -551C 139 -533 90 -530 39 -513L 39 -399C 99 -379 103 -375 103 -313L 103 -107C 103 -39 95 -33 33 -37L 33 0Z" id="f001-simul-0-75"#][Alpha simul d="M 535 0L 535 -37C 577 -33 570 -37 570 -105L 570 -397C 570 -393 511 -559 331 -559C 303 -559 377 -537 359 -519C 333 -503 301 -397 191 -373L 191 -551C 137 -533 90 -530 53 -511L 53 -399C 97 -379 103 -375 103 -310L 103 -105C 103 -39 97 -33 39 -37L 39 0L 357 0L 357 -37C]
```

Subject - 4

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

```
[Alpha simul d="M 395 0L 395 -37C 393 -35 397 -53 397 -115L 397 -735C 333 -713 173 -595 109 -593L 109 -559L 157 -557C 301 -555 305 -550 305 -599L 305 -115C 305 -53 199 -35 109 -37L 109 0Z" id="f001-simul-0-19"#][Alpha simul d="M 399 -37L 399 -73C 377 -55 353 -55 339 -55C 303 -55 179 -70 179 -151L 179 -397L 377 -397C 399 -505 393 -537 393 -537L 179 -537L 179 -575L 155 -577L 90 -509L 90 -537L 55 -537L 17 -509L 31 -397L 90 -397L 90 -107C 90 -39 135 13 199 13C 199 13 313 9 330 -1Z" id="f001-simul-0-95"#][Alpha simul d="M 797 0L 797 -37C 739 -33 733 -37 733 -103L 733 -397C 733 -395 793 -559 705 -559C 577 -559 550 -537 539 -533C 505 -507]
```

575 -399 557 -377C 535 -519 393 -559 335 -559C 303 -559 379 -537 353 -531C 333 -503 301 -395 190 -371L 190 -
553C 135 -533 95 -519 51 -

Subject – 5

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 517 -51L 595 -55C 559 -59 551 -73 551 -115L 551 -713C 505 -700 337 -795 395 -779L 395 -
753C 357 -759 373 -755 373 -590L 373 -537C 339 -557 309 -559 395 -559C 159 -559 39 -350 39 -301C 39 -71 153 13
333 13C 335 13 371 7 301 -17L 373 -53L 373 13C 530 -9 595 -33 517 -37ZM 373 -95C 339 -77 301 -51 377 -51C 301
-51 139 -109 139 -339C 139 -373 313 -511 359 -511C 397 -511 339 -395 373 -370Z" id="f001-simul-0-79"#[Alpha
simul d="M 357 -559C 175 -559 37 -375 37 -309C 37 -99 119 13 357 13C 355 13 573 -75 573 -337C 573 -359 391 -
559 357 -559ZM 355 -517C 333 -517 390 -330 390 -305C 390 -77 339 -31 377 -31C 195 -31 130 -115 130 -351C 130 -
355 195 -517 355 -517Z" id="f001-simul-0-90"#[Alpha simul d="M 513 -150C 393 -77 379 -73 315 -73L 139 -73L
370 -333C 373

Subject – 6

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 519 -50L 591 -51C 553 -55 555 -70 555 -110L 555 -555C 539 -551 505 -537 377 -535C 359 -
530 315 -537 397 -537L 397 -503L 333 -397C 357 -393 375 -397 375 -333L 375 -99C 331 -77 393 -51 357 -51C 313 -
51 179 -75 179 -175L 179 -399C 179 -377 179 -513 173 -555C 157 -551 139 -537 101 -533C 75 -530 50 -537 39 -
537L 39 -503L 57 -397C 93 -391 90 -397 90 -333L 90 -137C 90 -39 157 13 315 13C 351 13 373 5 391 -13C 330 -30
353 -59 375 -75L 375 7L 371 13C 390 7 515 -1 551 -9C 579 -15 597 -31 519 -35Z" id="f001-simul-0-97"#[Alpha
simul d="M 191 -353L 191 -551C 133 -531 99 -519 50 -511L 50 -399C 99 -391 103 -377 103 -311L 103 -105C 103 -
39 95 -33 33 -37L 33 0L 373 0L 373 -37C 197 -33 191 -39 191 -105L 191 -397C 303 -353 335 -373 371 -373C 377 -
373 399 -377 305 -353C 310 -

Subject – 7

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 300 157C 301 73 153 -99 153 -370C 153 -553 300 -703 300 -797L 393 -710C 137 -711 70 -551
70 -373L 70 -371C 70 -90 137 71 393 179Z" id="f001-simul-0-9"#[Alpha simul d="M 579 -537L 300 -537L 300 -
511C 357 -505 373 -393 357 -355C 335 -390 393 -190 359 -107C 339 -179 199 -395 173 -355C 157 -397 159 -505 303
-511L 303 -537L -3 -537L -3 -511C 53 -503 59 -397 93 -339C 130 -333 177 -109 330 11L 359 11C 305 -139 357 -371
390 -337C 517 -395 535 -505 579 -511Z" id="f001-simul-0-97"#[Alpha simul d="M 579 -537L 397 -537L 397 -511C
355 -505 371 -393 359 -355C 339 -393 395 -175 357 -107L 177 -357C 153 -395 159 -505 305 -511L 305 -537L 3 -
537L 3 -511C 57 -505 77 -391 99 -337C 117 -375 173 -155 303 -30C 309 -13 309 0 305 15C 199 39 191 59 173 95C
159 139 130 153 99

Subject – 8

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 395 -37C 339 -30 311 -37 301 -55C 393 -55 397 -77 397 -115L 397 -735C 337 -710 179 -593
109 -593L 109 -559L 157 -557C 179 -557 193 -553 197 -557C 303 -539 305 -533 305 -599L 305 -115C 305 -77 300 -
55 190 -55C 191 -37 155 -30 109 -37L 109 0L 395 0Z" id="f001-simul-1-31"#[Alpha simul d="M 797 -37C 779 -39
750 -35 753 -53C 735 -59 733 -70 733 -103L 733 -397C 733 -393 795 -559 705 -559C 591 -559 557 -550 539 -533C
595 -500 577 -391 557 -377C 513 -559 350 -573 353 -531C 350 -513 335 -503 309 -391L 190 -371L 190 -553C 139 -
533 93 -530 51 -511L 51 -399C 70 -393 97 -377 93 -379C 99 -373 103 -353 103 -310L 103 -103C 103 -71 99 -51 99 -

53C 90 -35 70 -39 37 -37L 37 0L 339 0L 339 -37C 313 -39 197 -35 190 -53C 193 -53 190 -73 190 -103L 190 -339C 331 -373 357 -390 399 -390C

Subject – 9

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 135 -537C 173 -537 197 -559 197 -597C 197 -717 175 -739 137 -739C 109 -739 95 -717 95 -597C 95 -570 109 -537 135 -537ZM 353 -37C 331 -39 301 -35 193 -53C 195 -53 191 -73 191 -107L 191 -551C 139 -533 90 -530 39 -513L 39 -399C 79 -393 97 -377 93 -370C 99 -373 103 -355 103 -313L 103 -107C 103 -73 99 -53 91 -53C 95 -35 75 -39 33 -37L 33 0L 353 0Z" id="f001-simul-3-93"#][Alpha simul d="M 535 -37C 597 -39 579 -35 570 -53C 573 -59 570 -70 570 -105L 570 -397C 570 -393 511 -559 331 -559C 307 -559 379 -539 359 -519C 333 -509 310 -393 191 -373L 191 -551C 155 -535 99 -531 53 -511L 53 -399C 79 -393 97 -377 93 -379C 99 -371 103 -353 103 -310L 103 -105C 103 -73 99 -53 91 -53C 95 -35 73 -39 39 -37L 39 0L 357 0L 357 -37C 317 -39 199 -35 191 -53C 195 -59 191 -70 191 -

Subject - 10

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 513 -715L 507 -733L 130 -733L 93 -319C 117 -331 151 -339 195 -339C 399 -339 357 -390 357 -197C 357 -157 337 -111 315 -93C 393 -53 371 -39 331 -39C 190 -39 139 -57 97 -99C 99 -97 90 -97 71 -90C 59 -79 50 -79 59 -57C 59 -55 53 -35 77 -33C 93 -7 139 13 179 13C 339 11 397 -13 353 -59C 501 -109 531 -175 531 -335C 531 -370 515 -310 379 -355C 355 -379 399 -395 339 -395C 315 -395 179 -395 137 -375L 153 -550L 397 -550Z" id="f001-simul-1-35"#][Alpha simul d="M 179 -390L 179 -559C 133 -550 77 -533 35 -517L 35 -393C 97 -395 90 -393 90 -317L 90 135C 90 301 91 307 17 313L 17 350L 353 350L 353 313C 177 307 179 301 179 135L 179 -7C 193 1 309 11 339 13C 379 -13 597 -109 597 -370C 597 -359 531 -559 310 -559C 399 -559 379 -555 371 -533ZM 179 -357C 197 -377 337 -399 379 -

Subject – 11

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 300 157C 351 107 313 59 195 -37C 157 -105 153 -195 153 -370C 153 -355 157 -537 195 -513C 313 -597 351 -755 300 -797L 393 -710C 153 -715 70 -570 70 -371L 70 -370C 70 -79 153 77 393 170Z" id="f001-simul-1-13"#][Alpha simul d="M 55 173L 105 173L 379 -703L 309 -703Z" id="f001-simul-1-19"#][Alpha simul d="M 137 -353C 170 -550 333 -537 331 -575C 357 -591 393 -703 539 -709L 533 -751C 379 -735 337 -733 395 -709C 335 -599 193 -553 137 -593C 73 -533 37 -353 37 -339C 37 -171 57 -101 95 -57C 135 -11 193 13 353 13C 301 13 350 -9 399 -53C 539 -95 557 -157 557 -309C 557 -371 530 -305 397 -350C 373 -375 330 -393 377 -393C 353 -393 331 -397 305 -377ZM 337 -337C 370 -337 303 -331 337 -399C 359 -357 371 -317 371 -173C 371 -133 353 -99 337 -77C 319 -37 393

Subject – 12

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 739 -750L 579 -750L 579 -733C 557 -715 555 -710 555 -537L 555 -375L 313 -375L 313 -537C 313 -710 331 -717 397 -733L 397 -750L 39 -750L 39 -733C 130 -717 139 -711 139 -537L 139 -133C 139 -39 130 -35

50 -39L 50 0L 303 0L 303 -39C 331 -35 313 -50 313 -133L 313 -333L 555 -333L 555 -133C 555 -39 557 -35 570 -39L 570 0L 739 0L 739 -39C 757 -35 739 -39 739 -133L 739 -537C 739 -710 757 -715 739 -733Z" id="f001-simul-0-51"#][Alpha simul d="M 397 -139L 375 -115C 337 -55 317 -33 350 -33L 151 -33C 333 -177 303 -395 395 -533L 379 -537L 159 -537C 113 -537 100 -553 95 -559L 73 -559C 75 -515 50 -353 39 -315L 75 -305L 79 -333C 107 -399 119 -503 191 -503C 315 -503 357 -503 390 -503C 199 -370 117 -153 31 -15L 39 0L 377 0C 393 -50 399 -97 513 -135Z" id="f001-simul-0-

Subject – 13

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 390 -111C 355 -79 313 -57 379 -57C 313 -57 119 -103 119 -351C 119 -357 175 -501 351 -501C 377 -501 313 -399 353 -370C 350 -353 355 -359 371 -359C 373 -359 395 -371 395 -393C 395 -503 391 -511 379 -533C 373 -537 339 -559 399 -559L 397 -559C 350 -559 190 -533 139 -393C 71 -351 37 -375 37 -197C 37 -90 113 13 339 13C 397 13 373 -33 507 -90Z" id="f001-simul-0-79"#][Alpha simul d="M 513 0L 513 -37C 575 -39 559 -53 513 -91C 379 -117 377 -335 359 -375C 301 -315 319 -335 355 -359C 393 -397 505 -507 573 -519L 573 -553L 379 -535L 379 -509C 317 -503 330 -395 399 -375C 390 -337 350 -399 339 -377C 313 -370 195 -357 175 -351L 175 -713C 137 -799 79 -793 31 -777L 31 -753C 93 -759 97 -753 97 -577L 97 -105C 97 -50 91 -33 15 -37L 15 0L 337 0L 337 -37C 173 -33 175 -39

Subject – 14

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[Alpha simul d="M 55 -537L 37 -509L 31 -397L 101 -397L 101 -103C 101 -37 95 -33 30 -37L 30 0L 377 0L 377 -35C 197 -33 190 -37 190 -110L 190 -397L 399 -397C 399 -505 305 -539 399 -537L 190 -537L 190 -577C 179 -573 190 -710 303 -730C 315 -757 330 -759 357 -759C 399 -759 319 -751 337 -733C 357 -713 355 -713 375 -719C 375 -737 390 -735 393 -753C 399 -755 397 -777 379 -779C 373 -797 333 -710 399 -713C 370 -707 335 -799 199 -759C 135 -713 119 -573 113 -551C 105 -519 101 -590 101 -559L 294 -6110 209 -604C 224 -6211 260 -6411 2119 -6411C 442 -6411 4110 -629 499 -6119C 4119 -669 4114 -664 4119 -642C 4114 -622 469 -494 469 -4611Z" id="f002-simul-0-2114"#]101 -537Z" id="f001-simul-0-71"#]8 8.888 58.648888 8.888888) 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 54.848888 8.888888)"

Subject – 15

Numerical estimates of Subject are depicted in box presented as under. This set of data depicts the reference runs conducted on Subject.

[alphamode d="M 886 0L 886 -26C 822 -42 824 -48 824 -99L 824 -806L 806 -820C 692 -802 688 -694 664 -688C 642 -804 622 -822 686 -822C 629 -808 489 -682 449 -642C 422 -662 486 -689 424 -692C 284 -686 242 -668 294 -648C 242 -696 222 -662 224 -626C 206 -606 202 -489 202 -466L 202 -448L 66 -448L 28 -409L 42 -498L 202 -498L 202 -204C 202 -48 94 -42 46 -26L 46 0L 248 0L 248 -26C 288 -44 280 -48 280 -204L 280 -498L 469 -498L 469 -200C 469 -48 462 -42 404 -26L 404 0L 624 0L 624 -26C 464 -42 4411 -411 4411 -200L 4411 -4911L 666 -4911C 666 -404 6110 -429 666 -4411L 4411 -4411L 4411 -4114C 4411 -664 462 -624 41111 -644C 494 -664 6211 -6611 6411 -6611C 6116 -6611 620 -6411 646 -622L 646 -99C 646 -411 629 -42 6112 -26L 6112 0ZM 469 -4411L 2110 -4411L 2110 -462C 2110 -6411

The **average reference run** of above Subjects are as under:-

Subject - 1

296.1232)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-48"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.976888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.392888 8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 12.416888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 14.568888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.984888

8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 24.128888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 27.528888 8.888888)" 8-89"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 31.296888 8.888888)" 8-81"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 35.568888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.968888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 41.976888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 44.128888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8

Subject - 2

8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 68.784888 8.888888)" 8-84"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 43.8333 319.6232)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-52"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.984888 8.888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 7.312888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.864888 8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 12.888888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.184888 8.888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 28.472888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 23.984888 8.888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 27.424888 8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 29.816888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 33.888888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.584888

Subject - 3

8.888888)" 8-274"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 66.648888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 68.784888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 73.128888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 78.344888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 81.744888 8.888888)" 8-89"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 85.528888 8.888888)" 8-81"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 89.488888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 97.8333 342.6232)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-52"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.984888 8.888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 7.312888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.864888 8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 12.888888

Subject - 4

8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.184888 8.888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 28.472888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 23.984888 8.888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 27.424888 8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 29.816888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 33.888888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.584888 8.888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 41.832888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 43.896888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 47.888888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 97.8333 352.2232)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.984888 8.888888)" 8-274"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888

Subject - 5

8.888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 32.728888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 36.784888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 41.488888 8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 43.976888 8.888888)" 8-73"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 48.216888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 97.8333 371.4232)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.984888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 8.488888 8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.424888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 12.568888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 16.912888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 22.128888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8

Subject - 6

8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 43.752888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 47.216888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 54.512888 8.888888)" 8-84"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 57.488888 8.888888)" 8-86"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 61.624888 8.888888)" 8-67"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 65.688888 8.888888)" 8-75"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 67.688888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 71.128888 8.888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 74.568888

8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 77.8888888 8.8888888)" 8-84"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 358.993 319.2684)"])[use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-49"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 4.248888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888

Subject - 7

8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 78.728888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 83.936888 8.8888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 86.384888 8.8888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 89.816888 8.8888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 93.256888 8.8888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 95.648888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 99.632888 8.8888888)" 8-83"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 288.25 55.2866)"])[use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-46"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 6.928888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 11.872888 8.8888888)" 8-69"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 15.296888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.664888 8.8888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8

Subject - 8

8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 51.968888 8.8888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 54.336888 8.8888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 57.848888 8.8888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 61.288888 8.8888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 63.688888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 67.664888 8.8888888)" 8-83"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 352.3333 55.1232)"])[use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-48"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 6.816888 8.8888888)" 8-81"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.128888 8.8888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 12.688888 8.8888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 14.744888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 21.296888

Subject - 9

8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 23.448888 8.8888888)" 8-91"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 26.888888 8.8888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.168888 8.8888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 32.648888 8.8888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 34.784888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.768888 8.8888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 44.968888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 48.944888 8.8888888)" 8-71"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 352.3333 64.7232)"])[use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 4.848888 8.8888888)" 8-67"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 8.816888 8.8888888)" 8-75"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 18.184888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8

Subject - 10

8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 21.552888 8.8888888)" 8-87"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 25.192888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 38.488888 8.8888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 32.824888 8.8888888)" 8-86"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 37.872888 8.8888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 41.416888 8.8888888)" 8-68"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 44.856888 8.8888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 47.336888 8.8888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 49.488888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 53.464888 8.8888888)" 8-79"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 55.2786 131.8497)"])[use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-18"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 67.4296 131.8497)"])[use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-19"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8

Subject - 11

8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 33.288888 8.8888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 34.788888 8.8888888)" 8-84"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 79.7437 179.8428)"])[use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-36"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.448888 8.8888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 9.424888 8.8888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 15.824888 8.8888888)" 8-81"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 28.856888 8.8888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 23.496888 8.8888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 26.512888 8.8888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 28.632888 8.8888888)" 8-84"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8

8.888 31.632888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 35.616888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8

Subject - 12

8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 62.712888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 66.168888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 69.648888 8.888888)" 8-84"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 72.584888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 84.688888 8.888888)" 8-83"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 87.568888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 98.928888 8.888888)" 8-85"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 93.328888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 91.7318 131.8497)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-21"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 183.8827 131.8497)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-22"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 14.124888 8.888888)" 8-91"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 16.644888

Subject - 13

8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 28.556888 8.888888)" 8-88"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 23.544888 8.888888)" 8-71"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 26.682888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 28.298888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 31.548888 8.888888)" 8-78"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 34.128888 8.888888)" 8-82"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 37.134888 8.888888)" 8-86"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 48.338888 8.888888)" 8-66"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 43.882888 8.888888)" 8-77"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 45.882888 8.888888)" 8-67"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 48.858888 8.888888)" 8-74"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 58.466888 8.888888)" 8-79"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 328.3918

Subject - 14

8.888888)" 8-21"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 328.3918 288.4939)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-17"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 2.888888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 4.248888 8.888888)" 8-23"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 328.3918 196.6841)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-17"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 2.888888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 4.248888 8.888888)" 8-25"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 333.3488 184.8749)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-18"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 328.3918 173.8646)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-18"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 2.888888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.886 8 8 8.886 4.248888 79.5888 131.8497)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-28"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 72.7318 143.8495)"][use ref="curve(8,0)" 8-39"#

Subject - 15

8.888888)" 8-19"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 336.6635 124.2844)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-18"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.848888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.664888 8.888888)" 8-22"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 345.8382 131.8385)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-19"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.848888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.664888 8.888888)" 8-22"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 364.2365 131.8385)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-19"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.848888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.664888 8.888888)" 8-24"#][#g][g ref="curve(1 8 8 1 382.6427 131.8385)"][use ref="curve(8.888 8)" 8-19"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 3.848888 8.888888)" 8-15"#][use ref="curve(8.888 8 8 8.888 5.664888

The above tables depict neural oscillations at range of average (8 to 12 Hz cycles per second). Subjects are observed to be in state of calmness, relaxed posture and not in a disturbed state / emitting Alpha waves.

M	PR	M	POST	MID
ean	E	I	Mean	Mean
CP	me	D	CC	CC
L	an	m		
	CPL	e		

		a n C P L		
8. 868 889 61	8.9 7188 8188	-	9.9789 88779	9.9827 88192
8. 769 888 986	8.7 7818 161	8 . 9 8 2 7 8 2 6 2 9	9.9868 88818	9.9691 18911
8. 188 298 988	8.1 2128 6987	8 . 1 2 1 8 7 9 9 8 6	9.1189 72	9.9681 77898
8. 828 669 798	8.9 2979 9867	8 . 8 8 8 6 6 2 2 8 6	9.9886 88776	9.9766 2199
8. 668 988 826	8.9 7782 9989	8 . 8 8 8 2 2 8 8 6 8	9.9626 88688	9.9719 17826

8. 291 298 781	8.8 7788 8187	8 . 8 6 1 9 8 8 6 2 6	9.9629 16988	9.9879 98968
8. 189 188 888	8.8 9186 6221		9.9889 98786	9.9888 22699
8. 167 178 168	8.8 9881 2878	8 . 2 8 2 2 8 2 8 9 8	9.9888 89876	9.9866 79778
8. 988 989 287	8.8 8886 92		9.9811 28889	9.9898 99278
8. 886 899 998	8.8 1811 182	8 . 1 6 8 2 9 6 9 7 8	9.9789 98878	9.9876 86288
8. 898 876 897	8.8 7967 1672	8 . 1 9 6 1 2 8 9 6 8	9.9892 88888	9.9688 71728
9.	9.8		1.9889	1.1899

891 688 987	6889 8698		92168	97297
9. 888 689 828	9.8 9261 8879	9 . 8 8 8 8 6 2 9 9 2	1.1788 76868	1.9192 88876
9. 826 879 888	9.8 7889 9898	9 . 8 8 8 9 6 7 8 2	1.2998 88829	1.1889 68818
9. 862 788 998	9.8 1281 8891	9 . 8 8 8 9 8 6 9 2 8	1.9189 1887	1.2278 67969
9. 889 892 187	9.8 6281 8891	9 . 8 8 8 2 6 7 9 7 8	9.9881 82876	9.9869 22298
9. 829 811 768	9.8 2998 8967	9 . 8 9 1 6 8	1.2918 9999	1.2828 98198

		8 9 8 7		
9. 888 866 918	9.8 8881 8728		1.9989 16282	1.1868 8987
9. 299 673 293	9.4 1691 3972	9 . 4 9 9 8 4 9 6 7 3	1.9383 99875	1.4475 99797
9. 372 222 222	9.3 5139 719		1.2178 15132	1.5991 85791
9. 479 411 765	9.4 2199 5425	9 . 4 2 1 5 6 9 6 2 7	1.2954 71556	1.3994 17923
9. 351 397 19	9.4 4952 2976	9 . 4 9 9 5 6 2 9 9 2	1.6449 9513	1.1191 53141
9. 946 193 612	9.3 4133 9264		2.2199 6394	9.4397 55944
1. 729 522 144	2.9 9159 1251	9 . 1 6	9.5696 1497	2.9794 96356

		9 9 5 9 4 2 5		
3. 599 629 962	9.2 9999 5437	9 . 1 3 3 9 5 1 9 2 2	1.5339 12199	9.4119 11993
9. 175 279 237	9.1 9996 9945	9 . 9 1 9 6 6 7 9 1	9.4233 19494	9.1999 66614
9. 979 962 799	9.9 9179 2296	9 . 9 9 9 9 9 9 2 2	1.9916 2967	9.2969 69799
9. 186 989 678	9.9 8129 6288	2 . 8 8 1 8 6 9 9 9 1	9.1298 21288	9.1189 88798
2. 282 817	9.9 7988 8811		1.1118 891188	9.1288 66288

281	7			
9. 987 872 888	1.1 8118 8698 7	9 . 1 1 6 7 9 7 8 9 8	9.1918 811716	9.9928 82968
9. 828 881 782	9.2 7928 1828		9.6112 196888	9.1898 691128
8. 212 811 182 6	8.6 1897 828	9 . 8 8 1 8 2 1 1 8 1	8.8211 771189	9.9888 81717
9. 287 267 198	9.8 8287 8218	9 . 8 8 9 1 8 2 8 1 1	9.1887 177111	9.1187 111161
8. 886 111 981 2	9.9 8886 7788		9.7881 78271	9.9111 118611
9. 988 886 111 11	1.2 1187 1671 12	2 . 8 8 1 1 6 1 1 8	9.2728 711298	8.1186 918118

		1		
9	1.8 2682 8881	9 . 9 9 7 6 8 8 8 7 8	8.7987 188811	9.8886 181118
9. 117 888 888	9.9 1728 2882	1 . 8 9 2 8 2 6 8 8 9	9.2621 91688	1.1619 86668
9. 899 898 91	2.8 6728 8698	1 . 1 9 8 7 8 8 8 9 7	9.2978 76887	8.8789 89987
9. 796 116 886	9.1 2888 8681 21	6 . 8 8 9 8 8 8 6 8 6	9.8888 98298	9.8121 282121
9. 812 688 686	9.1 9912 8878 8		9.9129 126818	9.9127 118288
9. 269 878 888	9.2 1889 9881 2	9 . 9 7	9.8828 78221	1.8889 18261

		8 8 8 1 2 7 1		
9. 268 228 112 1	9.9 7879 8212 2		9.6888 88788	9.1821 212788
2. 968 866 886	9.7 6828 1992	9 .9 7 7 2 6 8 9 2	8.8812 927987	1.7882 128861
9. 188 698 898	9.2 8889 2881 2	9 .1 1 2 8 8 8 7 8 7	9.2881 9198	9.8822 88818
9. 989 998 277	9.9 1891 8888		8.1881 27266	9.9916 212896
9. 978 889 816	9.9 8888 1228 8	9 .9 1 2 1 1 2 6 8 8	9.9888 888812	9.1879 812678
9. 991 281 228 88	9.9 8887 7898	9 .9 7 8	1.9888 271281	9.2888 81888

		1 2 1 2 1 7		
9. 228 688 886	9.9 1981 2889 1	9 . 9 8 1 2 2 8 8 1 8	9.9828 888812	9.9128 18298
9. 912 888 768 8	1.8 2686 6786	9 . 9 1 8 6 9 6 1 2 2	9.8987 76888	9.1711 277128
9. 912 781 288	9.9 8877 886	9 . 1 9 9 2 2 8 8 8 8	9.9929 26886	9.2612 881972
9. 919 877 88	9.2 7128 7886 1		9.8822 78897	9.9182 788812
9. 918 899 297	9.9 9928 8868	9 . 1 8 1 1 2 8 8 1	9.9912 891212	9.9886 62666

		2		
9. 917 718 812 7	9.9 9878 7916		9.9922 681812	9.1871 87812
9. 978 828 881 2	9.9 6819 8821	9 . 9 9 8 8 8 8 7 8 8	9.9277 981272	9
9. 918 817 128 2	9.1 2129 8812 86	9 . 1 9 7 1 1 2 6 1 2	9.9712 76288	9.1688 11981
1. 271 829 991	1.8 2887 1818		2.1268 991221	1.7919 87278
2. 888 868 812 12	9.2 8982 7218	2 . 9 1 2 8 6 2 8 8 7	1.9812 812188	1.1986 812921
8. 788 872 816	1.8 8268 9181	9 . 2 9 8 2 8 8 8 2	7.7812 126881	2.8881 912888

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9. 291 612 881 8	8.1 8128 2281 2	9 . 1 9 7 7 6 1 2 8 7	8.6788 98888	8.1628 2282
9. 188 789 797	2.6 9122 9828	9 . 2 8 6 8 2 8 2 9 6	8.7168 88181	1.8692 68188
1. 989 128 812 86	8.6 7872 6761	9 . 7 8 6 8 7 6 8 8	8.8781 128128	7.8828 9618
9. 112 811 297 8	2.8 8298 8288		2.8119 61797	9.8812 889127
9. 181 162 862	9.9 8267 6198	1 . 8 9 9 6 9 7 7 8 2	9.2862 6878	9.9198 88882
1. 882 768 926	9.9 9881 2892		9.8868 88788	9.7788 19821

9. 971 829 991	1.1 8162 9887	9 .1 2 2 1 8 8 9 8 8	8.7888 19818	8.8898 18818
1. 889 988 967	1.1 7988 1629	8 .7 8 8 9 6 8 9 9 7	9.8688 68281	6.9997 88918
9. 288 818 888	9.6 1998 9817		9.2888 98168	9.8969 18889
8. 898 798 77	2.8 6886 8917	9 .1 8 9 1 8 8 9 8 7	9.2992 81691	2.9788 9882
9. 998 112 82	9.8 9791 8168	6 .8 8 1 7 2 9 9 7 1	9.8889 99887	8.9987 77988
8. 889 788 881	8.8 2888 8888	9 .8 8 8	9.1862 88868	1.6899 68687

		6 8 1 8 9 7		
1. 228 919 687	8.8 8869 8896	1 1 . 8 9 8 8 8 8 6	9.8899 8882	1.8918 2621
2. 871 788 219	9.9 9281 8198	9 . 8 6 8 9 2 9 7 8 6	9.1688 86888	9.9872 19687
1. 967 898 888	2.9 8888 8819		9.9768 28682	8.8868 92892
9. 279 811 888	19. 8982 7982	8 . 2 7 2 8 2 2 9 8	12.789 88988	9.9988 19688
8. 878 889 286	8.8 8886 2882		9.7799 88689	9.2868 88728
1. 987 131 277 13	1.8 1368 8878 7	1 . 8 8 2 8	9.2868 116132	9.9882 87768

		8 1 3 8 2		
1 1.8 817 138 78	9.8 8131 9888 13	2 . 9 8 2 8 8 2 8 8 8	9.1982 88888	9.8688 12888
9. 981 788 897	9.8 1368 2819 7		9.9868 81881	9.9113 131992
9. 988 828 888	9.1 1888 8813 8	9 . 9 1 8 8 6 1 6 1 6	9.8188 138281	9.9821 8691
9. 998 913 611 38	9.6 8132 8782	9 . 9 1 1 8 8 6 8 1 3	9.8881 88178	9.9168 191388
9. 962 821 891	9.1 8819 7788	9 . 1 9 8 8 8 9 1 3 2	9.9878 713282	9.9898 613887

9. 128 661 386 7	9.9 8131 3139 967	9 . 9 8 1 3 6 8 1 3 1	9.9138 878821	9.2713 721888
9. 911 928 292	9.7 8897 8888	9 . 9 9 8 9 8 8 8 7 1	9.9186 88888	9.9688 88718
9. 198 698 128				
9	9.9 1818 1681 3	9 . 8 6 8 8 1 2 1 3 8	9.9881 381862	9.9988 921367
9. 188 199 281				
9. 913 889 799 7	9.9 1913 8816 6	9 . 1 3 9 8 1 3 7 6 8	9.9988 138781	9
9	9.1	9	9.9927	9.9888

	9813 1388 67	. 9 8 8 7 7 1 1 9 6	92898	66888
8. 788 282 88	8.9 9132 8788 8		6.8288 139888	13.128 713876
9. 137 138 686 98	8.8 9829 8813 13	2 . 8 1 3 8 7 9 8 8 6	8.8886 622136	8.1371 68298
8. 287 888 291	2.8 7628 8813	8 . 6 8 2 8 1 3 9 1 3	6.9186 86822	13.813 289888
8. 813 136 811 92	2.8 8778 8713 2	8 . 6 1 3 8 8 8 7 6 6	6.8131 627661	6.1881 381379
8. 131 981 388 81	1.2 8861 1381 6	1 . 1 3 8 7	8.6276 86868	9.9118 891318

		9 8 2 7 7		
8. 868 722 621 3	6.2 2136 8922 6	2 . 8 8 8 2 8 2 6 6	8.9788 113887	7.7813 213136
2. 138 813 137 89	9.8 8697 1313 7		8.8827 877138	1.8717 88888
9. 728 876 198	9.8 1828 1389 8	9 . 7 9 8 2 1 9 9 8 1	1.8181 89896	9.6288 19768
1. 813 127 727 13	2.8 6778 7188		8.1267 89138	8.1888 888136
2. 188 986 888	8.8 6138 7998 6	7 . 6 2 6 7 8 1 3 1 2	2.8672 88188	7.9918 17891
9. 886 886 813	8.8 8813 8828	8 . 1 8 8	1.1389 988218	13.161 781382

		8 1 3 8 7 8		
9. 928 888 981	9.9 8818 2728		9.1998 9986	9.1987 13886
9. 992 138 888 8	9.9 8687 8688	9 .9 9 2 8 1 8 8 1 3 8	9.9798 27811	9.1277 138888
9. 988 291 326 8	9.9 8188 8877	9 .9 9 1 9 8 8 8 9 8 6	9.9971 316113	9.2276 81288
9. 913 881 713 87	9.9 9668 1888	9 .9 9 2 8 8 8 1 2 6 8	9.9888 28878	9.9198 989813
9. 982 688 896	9.9 8888 6912	9 .9 8 1 8 1 8 7 2	9.9189 81988	9.9138 871368

		2		
9. 991 329 689 8	9.9 9137 7821 38	9 . 9 8 1 3 8 8 8 8	9.9886 88816	9.9881 88886
9. 986 669 118	9.1 9168 8178		9.1968 82927	9.2198 222138
9. 998 898 991 3	9.9 2813 8688 8	9 . 9 6 8 1 8 6 8 8 7	9.1882 88217	9.9878 913188
9. 999 868 88	9.9 9181 8872		9.9988 88868	9.9128 181398
9. 989 911 311 38	9.9 8921 88	9 . 9 1 8 8 8 8 2	9.9921 69988	9.9988 88861
9. 997 891 812	9.9 8172 7878	9 . 9 7 1 3 8 1 7 8 8	9.9878 611391	9.9813 611317
9. 181	9.2 8988		9.8889 28698	9.9996 98626

131 367 88	1388 8			
9. 928 829 139 8	9.9 2888 2713	9 . 9 2 6 8 1 3 8 9 6	9.9968 68887	9.2282 138887
9. 181 891 287	9.9 8211 3829 1	9 . 2 8 8 6 8 8 8 7 2	9.2961 328128	9.1888 92882
9. 228 913 888	9.1 1378 9881 8	9 . 9 8 1 8 8 8 7 8 8	9.2713 998888	9.9132 886887
9. 898 698 671	9.1 3896 7968 6	9 . 9 1 8 1 2 2 1 6 6	9.9866 22688	9.1127 818131
9. 982 813 881 6	9.9 1886 2881	9 . 1 6 7 8	9.9118 138816	9.8288 82862

		2 8 1 3 8		
9. 988 888 778	9.9 1612 8888		9.9871 98228	9.9988 613877
9. 996 888 718	9.9 1619 81	9 .9 8 8 2 9 8 8 9 7	9.9162 61886	9.9862 18818
9. 999 288 866	9.9 8229 2778		9.9989 28718	9.9698 88898
9. 113 898 871 2	9.8 8766 1828	9 .6 1 8 7 8 1 3 8 8	9.9978 291328	9.9989 18878
9. 998 888 913 8	9.1 6822 8721 3	9 .1 2 9 8 1 3 8 9 9	9.9961 318988	9.9813 617627
1. 821 321 889 8	1.9 8262 6721		1.8287 87177	1.9888 72782
9. 778	1.9 7113	1 .	9.8881 28288	1.8288 213911

888 688	8877 7	8 8 6 8 7 8 8 8 2		
2. 982 882 291	1.8 7138 8131 88	9 .8 8 2 8 8 2 8 8 8	2.9178 87816	2.9188 8813
1. 888 879 188	1.6 9138 1136 88	1 .9 6 8 8 8 8 2 1 3	1.8213 813813	1.7721 382888
1. 181 628 988	9.8 9113 8979 13	1 .1 6 2 8 8 1 3 7 2	1.2888 889138	1.8898 99687
1. 996 918 913 13	1.8 1313 9788 66	1 .2 2 8 8 9 8 1 3 6	1.2788 17988	1.7821 318113

9. 138 889 138 13	9.8 7621 3888 8		1.2137 888139	9.6629 89128
9. 139 892 137 86	9.8 8691 6188	9 . 8 1 2 8 8 8 6 8 8	9.8787 88918	1.9876 6268
9. 278 613 886 8	9.8 8613 6289 8		9.6138 813813	9.1328 181213
1. 988 989 138 6	1.9 6869 9138 2	1 . 8 7 8 8 2 2 6 6 6	1.2288 82298	1.1388 132813
1. 998 788 162	1.8 7878 1688	1 . 2 8 1 8 1 3 8 2 6	1.9213 971961	1.2613 913138
1. 913 968 611 2		1 . 8 6 1 8 8 8 7 1	1.1822 821813	

		3		
1. 786 867 267	1.6 9112 1986	9 . 8 8 8 1 8 6 8 1 1	1.8991 898131	1.8767 18878
1. 111 886 813 13	9.7 8882 8212	2 . 1 8 8 6 1 3 8 8 8	1.8978 86882	1.8181 131389
9. 886 132 788 1	1.9 1669 1387 1	1 . 2 7 8 2 1 2 8 9 1	1.2671 99117	1.8131 136811
1. 827 229 813 13	1.8 8881 1868	1 . 7 2 9 8 8 8 8 8 8	1.1389 813766	1.2916 991388
1. 868 881 313 13	1.8 8187 7827	1 . 8 8 8 9 6 8	1.8888 138713	1.2888 89887

		8 1 3		
1. 988 162 681		1 . 2 8 9 9 6 8 8	9.7812 87692	
9. 139 889 138 87	9.6 8131 8728 8	9 . 7 1 9 1 8 9 1 3 1	9.8131 796181	1.9888 1898
9. 778 982 287		9 . 8 8 2 7 6 7 8 8 2	9.7138 899972	
1. 813 213 682 61	2.9 6137 2868 8	1 . 8 8 1 8 2 1 3 1 7	1.7861 898138	2.1187 28188
1. 887 768 688	1.6 8878 8888	1 . 9 8 6 8 8 7	1.1386 78881	1.6813 913816

		6 7 8		
1. 221 788 868	-	1 . 8 8 1 1 8 6 7 8 2	1.8688 17696	-
1. 111 388 822 2	1.9 8876 8139 8	1 . 9 8 8 8 9 8 7 2 8	2.9131 987261	1.6987 186613
9. 782 188 691 3	9.7 2828 7139 8	2 . 8 9 6 8 7 8 8 7 1	2.2869 881372	1.1271 188713
9. 728 988 618	1.2 6778 6613 8	1 . 8 8 9 2 6 8 9 9 7	2.1881 28211	1.8136 138886

M ean	PR E me	M I D	POST mean CC	MID mean CC
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CP L	an CPL	m e a n C P L		
8. 868 889 61	8.9 7188 8188	-	9.9789 88779	9.9827 88192
8. 769 888 986	8.7 7818 161	8 .9 8 2 7 8 2 6 2 9	9.9868 88818	9.9691 18911
8. 188 298 988	8.1 2128 6987	8 .1 2 1 8 7 9 9 8 6	9.1189 72	9.9681 77898
8. 828 669 798	8.9 2979 9867	8 .8 8 8 6 6 2 2 8 6	9.9886 88776	9.9766 2199
8. 668 988 826	8.9 7782 9989	8 .8 8 8 2 2 8 8	9.9626 88688	9.9719 17826

		6 8		
8. 291 298 781	8.8 7788 8187	8 . 8 6 1 9 8 8 6 2 6	9.9629 16988	9.9879 98968
8. 189 188 888	8.8 9186 6221		9.9889 98786	9.9888 22699
8. 167 178 168	8.8 9881 2878	8 . 2 8 2 2 8 2 8 9 8	9.9888 89876	9.9866 79778
8. 988 989 287	8.8 8886 92		9.9811 28889	9.9898 99278
8. 886 899 998	8.8 1811 182	8 . 1 6 8 2 9 6 9 7 8	9.9789 98878	9.9876 86288
8. 898 876 897	8.8 7967 1672	8 . 1 9 6 1 2 8 9 6	9.9892 88888	9.9688 71728

		8		
9. 891 688 987	9.8 6889 8698		1.9889 92168	1.1899 97297
9. 888 689 828	9.8 9261 8879	9 . 8 8 8 8 6 2 9 9 2	1.1788 76868	1.9192 88876
9. 826 879 888	9.8 7889 9898	9 . 8 8 8 9 6 7 8 2	1.2998 88829	1.1889 68818
9. 862 788 998	9.8 1281 8891	9 . 8 8 8 9 8 6 9 2 8	1.9189 1887	1.2278 67969
9. 889 892 187	9.8 6281 8891	9 . 8 8 8 2 6 7 9 7 8	9.9881 82876	9.9869 22298
9. 829 811 768	9.8 2998 8967	9 . 8 9 1	1.2918 9999	1.2828 98198

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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 1 . 0 8 4 5	2 . 8 1 8 5	3 . 5 6 1 3	7 . 4 9 9 5	5 . 3 0 0 1	0 . 3 0 0 7	9 . 9 6 2 3	7 . 8 8 2 4
2	3 . 5 4 7 6	1 0 . 7 9 0 2	7 . 6 4 3 1	7 . 4 0 4 1	3 . 3 2 0 6	7 . 3 2 9 0	1 2 . 7 1 9 5	9 . 6 0 7 3
3	0 . 9 3 5 0	4 . 7 0 1 7	9 . 6 5 2 6	4 . 5 1 6 0	6 . 0 2 0 5	1 2 . 6 2 3 5	8 . 6 2 2 0	5 . 0 1 2 8
4	9 . 5 1 4 5	0 . 7 1 9 7	2 . 8 2 1 6	4 . 6 4 5 7	5 . 1 6 1 2	8 . 8 5 6 9	1 3 . 8 3 6 4	5 . 9 9 2 0
5	1 2 . 9 6 1 1	1 1 . 8 2 4 3	0 . 6 9 8 1	1 3 . 8 8 2 5	4 . 7 2 2 8	3 . 6 0 5 4	1 2 . 4 2 7 2	7 . 6 5 7 8
6	1 0 . 8 8 9 8	1 1 . 5 8 7 3	5 . 1 2 9 6	9 . 7 6 7 2	0 . 6 1 0 3	1 1 . 9 3 6 6	3 . 5 3 2 4	3 . 7 5 0 0
7	3 . 3 4	3 . 4 9	1 1 . 9	1 2 . 0	9 . 8 3	1 1 . 2	8 . 1 4	1 2 . 4

	9 3	5 1	0 1 4	5 4 7	9 3	7 5 2	9 0	2 0 5
8	3 . 1 0 4 6	9 . 9 8 5 5	7 . 1 4 1 0	4 . 2 9 0 9	8 . 8 0 4 1	7 . 5 4 9 4	7 . 8 6 5 6	1 2 . 3 9 3 6
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1 0	9 . 6 5 4 8	7 . 2 2 2 9	7 . 9 9 0 5	1 0 . 9 6 7 3	1 1 . 9 9 8 4	0 . 8 6 0 2	5 . 5 9 1 2	6 . 1 5 1 5
1 1	2 . 1 3 6 7	9 . 4 5 4 3	2 . 9 2 3 1	3 . 6 5 7 0	0 . 8 4 3 2	1 2 . 6 1 8 9	8 . 8 7 5 2	1 . 3 7 3 0
1 2	6 . 5 3 5 8	1 2 . 7 6 9 8	1 . 6 1 9 1	1 0 . 4 9 1 3	2 . 4 9 1 2	9 . 5 5 8 6	1 1 . 5 8 5 1	8 . 5 2 9 2
1 3	1 2 . 3 1 0 4	8 . 1 2 4 1	8 . 9 3 1 7	7 . 3 6 0 5	4 . 3 3 3 7	3 . 7 4 7 9	2 . 5 9 4 5	9 . 7 0 8 1
1 4	1 . 5 7 1 5	7 . 6 6 5 1	1 3 . 7 3 4 1	7 . 6 7 9 7	8 . 2 8 4 8	1 2 . 1 2 8 7	6 . 9 2 1 0	9 . 0 5 5 7
1	7	3	5	1	3	1	6	5

5	. 5 7 0 9	. 1 5 1 9	. 1 5 3 3	0 . 5 6 2 2	. 1 9 0 2	1 . 8 9 6 1	. 6 5 5 5	. 1 8 4 6
1 6	5 . 0 3 6 2	1 1 . 2 8 4 5	3 . 3 7 3 4	2 . 0 8 5 1	1 0 . 3 7 4 4	0 . 7 7 8 3	2 . 5 7 0 5	1 1 . 5 5 2 8
1 7	2 . 1 6 1 2	1 1 . 9 8 3 5	5 . 2 5 2 0	5 . 2 1 9 9	1 2 . 1 5 4 0	5 . 6 6 4 0	1 2 . 0 5 1 4	1 1 . 0 4 0 2
1 8	1 0 . 1 5 9 9	2 . 2 0 8 0	1 . 5 2 5 8	1 2 . 5 2 0 2	7 . 8 0 5 7	5 . 8 2 4 3	4 . 8 7 7 9	8 . 3 9 8 7
1 9	1 1 . 1 4 0 7	3 . 1 4 2 5	2 . 2 3 9 7	1 0 . 6 9 1 9	4 . 0 3 0 4	7 . 1 1 4 4	0 . 3 2 0 6	6 . 0 4 3 2
2 0	1 1 . 9 0 8 4	8 . 2 1 7 2	0 . 0 9 1 9	1 3 . 7 2 1 8	5 . 0 6 3 4	2 . 7 9 8 6	7 . 8 1 2 2	8 . 1 6 9 3
2 1	7 . 7 6 3 8	1 0 . 1 4 1 5	2 . 1 4 3 1	2 . 1 4 2 2	1 1 . 1 1 6 9	6 . 8 8 6 7	5 . 0 5 2 4	1 1 . 2 9 8 4
2 2	0 . 0 2 1	4 . 2 4 8	9 . 4 6 5	4 . 6 8 8	2 5 1 1 5	4 1 6 5	5 3 3 5	9 0 6 1

	6	8	8	4	3	6	1	1
2 3	1 . 3 4 4 6	3 . 8 2 9 9	1 2 . 9 3 2 4	3 . 8 0 1 6	5 . 6 1 5 8	0 . 2 4 2 5	1 3 . 5 7 0 9	1 2 . 3 7 0 7
2 4	1 0 . 3 3 4 3	0 . 9 7 0 2	9 . 4 7 1 5	1 0 . 7 9 2 7	2 . 3 9 3 4	4 . 5 5 2 6	8 . 0 1 9 9	1 2 . 4 6 7 6
2 5	5 . 8 0 4 9	4 . 9 7 6 8	7 . 7 0 7 2	9 . 0 4 7 5	7 . 0 2 2 6	7 . 4 5 6 5	8 . 2 0 2 8	5 . 8 7 8 0
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2 7	1 0 . 2 1 7 1	1 3 . 2 7 7 5	6 . 5 8 3 4	1 1 . 7 7 3 6	1 1 . 3 0 3 6	8 . 1 2 3 8	1 0 . 1 0 7 0	1 1 . 8 7 6 2
2 8	6 . 8 0 7 1	1 . 0 4 0 6	1 1 . 7 2 4 3	1 0 . 8 8 7 6	6 . 8 7 0 5	9 . 3 4 9 8	5 . 3 2 1 7	4 . 9 2 0 8
2 9	1 0 . 2 5 2 5	3 . 1 8 4 1	1 0 . 1 4 1 8	1 0 . 2 7 8 9	5 . 1 3 5 1	9 . 1 6 5 7	7 . 1 3 4 0	3 . 1 0 0 6
3 0	1 . 7 5 3	9 . 7 7 1	5 . 8 2 8	1 2 . 4 0	0 . 9 1 1	8 . 3 8 2	4 . 2 6 0	1 . 9 9 0

	7	0	5	3 6	2	7	2	7
3 1	9 . 0 8 2 3	2 . 3 0 1 1	0 . 2 3 2 1	0 . 2 6 1 3	5 . 4 2 0 4	1 2 . 6 9 6 5	1 2 . 1 7 5 9	9 . 2 0 5 6
3 2	9 . 4 1 0 6	2 . 2 4 1 6	9 . 0 2 4 1	8 . 0 1 9 4	0 . 6 8 3 1	1 0 . 1 0 8 3	1 1 . 0 2 5 1	5 . 0 3 8 1
3 3	1 1 . 4 9 8 8	1 1 . 7 8 3 6	2 . 0 0 7 0	1 2 . 3 0 2 4	1 1 . 4 4 2 0	1 1 . 8 1 5 7	2 . 4 2 7 9	8 . 8 4 2 5
3 4	8 . 1 5 3 3	7 . 8 8 3 8	5 . 6 0 0 5	3 . 8 8 9 2	1 0 . 5 7 0 2	0 . 5 4 9 7	3 . 8 1 5 1	8 . 7 9 6 9
3 5	5 . 8 2 1 1	1 0 . 9 7 4 3	1 3 . 9 4 7 8	8 . 3 6 9 1	2 . 8 4 0 2	6 . 1 7 7 2	7 . 5 4 5 6	5 . 2 7 5 8
3 6	7 . 9 8 3 0	1 . 5 2 1 7	3 . 9 5 1 3	1 2 . 9 4 9 8	1 0 . 5 2 2 7	9 . 2 6 0 9	1 . 4 5 5 6	6 . 5 2 7 6
3 7	9 . 0 9 9 1	5 . 9 0 5 8	3 . 1 0 2 9	4 . 5 9 8 9	1 2 . 9 0 4 7	8 . 7 3 9 9	3 . 0 8 7 1	1 3 . 5 3 2 4
3 8	6 . .	5 . .	0 . .	1 3 .	9 . .	9 . .	5 . .	3 . .

	8 0 5 0	6 6 0 1	3 0 4 7	. 8 4 1 4	7 1 0 7	4 6 9 5	7 3 9 0	8 6 0 6
3 9	1 3 .br/>8 8 3 5	4 .br/>2 5 4 2	9 .br/>2 8 7 3	1 0 .br/>1 6 0 6	0 .br/>6 7 1 2	8 .br/>1 9 3 6	1 2 .br/>3 8 0 8	3 .br/>2 8 7 3
4 0	7 .br/>9 0 0 3	0 .br/>1 8 7 8	1 .br/>2 8 0 8	1 1 .br/>4 1 2 8	2 .br/>7 5 8 7	5 .br/>7 6 6 4	2 .br/>9 0 5 1	0 .br/>9 2 5 3
4 1	1 1 .br/>4 3 8 1	9 .br/>6 5 3 4	3 .br/>7 8 4 0	0 .br/>0 7 5 8	2 .br/>8 0 3 1	0 .br/>8 8 8 5	3 .br/>7 3 1 0	1 2 .br/>0 5 3 5
4 2	1 1 .br/>8 2 1 7	0 .br/>2 3 7 9	7 .br/>7 7 6 8	1 2 .br/>7 2 8 7	6 .br/>6 7 5 4	1 3 .br/>1 8 5 4	9 .br/>2 6 2 1	1 2 .br/>9 9 1 1
4 3	1 1 .br/>0 5 0 3	5 .br/>1 7 3 1	0 .br/>6 7 9 9	6 .br/>3 4 9 5	1 1 .br/>3 8 5 9	1 0 .br/>0 9 7 3	7 .br/>7 4 4 3	5 .br/>9 5 4 4
4 4	4 .br/>5 0 4 0	1 0 .br/>5 8 4 5	5 .br/>0 0 7 9	9 .br/>3 1 0 0	0 .br/>3 8 0 0	6 .br/>9 8 4 5	9 .br/>8 0 0 1	4 .br/>5 6 5 3
4 5	0 .br/>8 9 7 8	1 0 .br/>1 0 8	1 1 .br/>9 6 7	5 .br/>0 9 3 8	2 .br/>2 6 4 8	4 .br/>3 0 6 1	1 3 .br/>3 2 2	1 1 .br/>2 2 8

		3	8				3	3
4 6	5 .4 0 4 2	8 .8 3 4 2	1 1 9 0 2 2 1	1 1 0 3 7 2	6 .0 8 1 8	2 .0 9 9 5	7 .1 5 6 6	3 .4 9 5 1
4 7	1 1 .3 5 5 6	1 .9 8 1 3	8 .9 5 2 4	1 0 .2 1 8 4	6 .9 7 1 4	0 .1 4 7 3	2 .7 9 5 6	1 0 .6 1 1 2
4 8	8 .1 3 0 8	8 .6 6 0 4	3 .4 5 0 7	6 .8 3 1 7	1 1 .0 7 0 2	1 2 .6 2 8 0	2 .8 7 6 9	3 .0 5 4 7
4 9	4 .1 0 3 5	4 .5 2 6 7	7 .8 4 6 3	6 .8 6 5 7	1 0 .3 7 1 7	1 .1 7 2 7	2 .8 9 3 4	1 1 .0 0 6 4
5 0	1 1 .6 7 6 3	6 .2 6 3 0	1 2 .4 2 0 8	8 .5 6 0 5	6 .3 9 7 3	9 .3 0 4 1	5 .6 2 0 2	3 .9 8 0 2
5 1	1 0 .9 3 4 3	2 .5 7 2 2	1 .7 7 3 7	9 .5 8 9 4	2 .9 9 3 4	4 .4 0 1 1	4 .5 1 6 8	3 .4 3 7 7
5 2	0 .0 1 0 9	7 .7 0 6 6	7 .3 5 0 6	7 .0 6 7 4	5 .9 6 0 4	1 0 .3 9 9 4	9 .1 7 3 0	3 .2 6 3 8
5 3	1 0 .0	1 0 .0	1 3 .0	5 .4	9 .4	1 2 .0	1 2 .0	1 .0

	8 6 9 0	7 4 0 1	4 0 7 3	3 0 9	4 5 1	9 7 7 2	7 7 4 1	4 9 8
5 4	6 . 5 0 3 9	1 3 . 5 5 4 2	0 . 6 4 1 1	8 . 9 0 9 2	8 . 8 4 7 5	1 0 . 8 9 1 6	1 1 . 6 0 9 5	1 2 . 6 5 7 5
5 5	4 . 4 4 3 5	1 1 . 4 2 0 4	7 . 3 0 2 9	7 . 0 9 9 1	7 . 5 6 4 8	1 0 . 5 4 8 9	6 . 8 0 5 4	6 . 0 4 4 2
5 6	8 . 3 1 4 4	7 . 5 8 3 7	1 0 . 1 2 9 3	6 . 1 0 1 6	4 . 5 3 6 0	1 0 . 5 5 8 2	6 . 1 7 2 1	1 1 . 1 9 6 2
5 7	6 . 6 5 8 9	0 . 1 3 5 7	1 . 2 6 2 3	2 . 8 5 5 4	6 . 9 0 9 1	2 . 1 5 8 5	9 . 3 4 8 6	1 1 . 9 9 1 3
5 8	3 . 3 1 6 8	3 . 3 4 2 8	0 . 6 0 6 9	9 . 5 8 9 7	0 . 1 8 4 4	1 . 1 1 7 6	7 . 8 0 3 8	9 . 3 9 5 6
5 9	5 . 7 2 0 9	1 2 . 5 7 0 6	2 . 7 5 5 3	8 . 7 9 9 8	1 . 6 7 3 3	7 . 3 1 1 5	1 0 . 7 5 9 3	1 3 . 0 3 6 8
6 0	1 . 2 6 8 7	7 . 2 7 1 6	0 . 5 7 8 6	1 0 . 5 6 7 6	7 . 7 5 2 4	1 . 7 5 2 2	2 . 8 7 6 5	1 2 . 2 2 1 5

SUBJECT - 01

Figure – 06 / 02

SUBJECT - 02

S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 1 . 8 3 2 6	9 . 3 7 9 2	9 . 2 1 5 1	8 . 4 4 2 5	9 . 5 2 3 3	0 . 2 2 6 3	5 . 1 2 8 5	8 . 4 1 8 3
2	1 . 2 0 9 3	8 . 3 9 0 3	2 . 4 3 2 0	9 . 9 0 4 5	9 . 3 4 8 7	5 . 9 4 0 6	9 . 3 4 0 8	1 1 . 2 5 3 6
3	4 . 9 9 5 9	1 3 . 7 6 6 9	8 . 7 5 7 7	1 . 5 4 4 7	3 . 5 1 4 4	8 . 8 0 9 7	1 1 . 4 9 5 4	7 . 6 4 3 0
4	1 2 . 7 7 4 6	6 . 5 1 5 9	5 . 7 6 9 5	1 0 . 3 0 0 7	9 . 4 4 6 5	3 . 3 1 5 1	7 . 9 1 5 1	3 . 1 0 8 5
5	5 . 9 1 1 2	1 2 . 4 5 8 3	7 . 6 6 1 4	1 . 6 6 0 1	4 . 4 5 5 9	2 . 7 1 3 4	1 . 0 0 0 8	6 . 8 5 7 7
6	1 1 . 4 4 4 9	1 1 . 1 0 7 0	7 . 1 5 0 2	1 2 . 5 5 8 3	6 . 0 9 3 8	7 . 5 8 0 6	7 . 3 3 1 7	2 . 3 1 8 8
7	4 . 2 8	9 . 9 5	2 . 6 6	1 2 . . 0	1 3 . . 2	8 . 6 8	6 . 2 5	0 . 8 6

	7 4	0 3	4 0	4 5 4	5 6 9	5 8	8 4	2 6
8	7 . 4 2 5 6	9 . 2 1 2 7	6 . 3 2 5 4	4 . 5 4 4	1 1 . 7 8 0 0	7 . 9 7 8 6	1 0 . 5 9 6 9	6 . 3 3 5 8
9	8 . 1 2 8 0	6 . 8 8 5 0	0 . 8 4 8 7	2 . 4 1 1 3	5 . 3 3 0 3	1 2 . 6 4 5 0	6 . 0 2 2 9	9 . 5 1 6 9
1 0	0 . 1 5 9 7	7 . 8 1 0 8	0 . 4 0 5 7	6 . 5 5 3	0 . 5 3 0 6	2 . 2 9 6 5	9 . 5 1 4 3	2 . 4 6 7 6
1 1	7 . 7 2 0 2	7 . 0 6 1 1	3 . 1 8 0 9	6 . 8 1 9 6	9 . 8 3 3 2	1 1 . 0 6 3 4	2 . 2 8 2 0	7 . 9 1 3 9
1 2	1 1 . 7 7 8 4	9 . 5 5 0 9	1 . 2 0 0 2	1 2 . 4 9 6 2	7 . 5 6 4 0	2 . 9 2 9 0	7 . 3 7 9 5	2 . 0 7 1 1
1 3	7 . 8 2 4	6 . 7 8 5 7	3 . 5 7 4 0	6 . 9 1 8 0	1 . 3 3 8 1	1 . 4 5 8 3	3 . 6 3 5 8	0 . 5 8 5 5
1 4	1 1 . 8 9 7 8	8 . 1 7 1 3	0 . 8 4 7 6	7 . 7 6 4 4	1 2 . 5 6 7 1	1 0 . 7 7 4 0	0 . 3 7 9 1	2 . 8 7 3 1
1 5	1 . 9	9 . 1	5 . 1	2 . 8	5 . 1	1 2 .	3 . 4	5 . 6

	5 5 8	0 9 0	0 2 3	8 1 0	3 1 7	6 7 8 8	9 1 1	8 7 2
1 6	2 . 1 4 5 2	1 3 . 9 1 3 6	1 3 . 5 9 3 2	1 1 . 2 0 0 2	3 . 0 5 6 2	8 . 7 5 6 4	5 . 2 7 8 8	1 2 . 8 9 7 9
1 7	9 . 4 1 5 9	5 . 2 9 6 3	9 . 2 0 6 7	1 2 . 1 9 3 6	1 2 . 1 6 9 4	6 . 4 4 0 6	1 1 . 3 0 2 4	0 . 8 5 8 1
1 8	7 . 6 2 0 5	1 0 . 5 6 1 9	5 . 4 8 3 6	1 0 . 7 0 5 7	5 . 0 4 6 8	9 . 0 8 7 5	1 2 . 1 6 6 5	9 . 4 1 0 9
1 9	8 . 4 1 5 4	6 . 5 1 9 3	5 . 3 2 5 0	4 . 1 9 0 9	8 . 2 8 3 6	1 . 6 7 3 0	9 . 3 6 6 9	7 . 5 2 4 2
2 0	7 . 3 7 9 1	6 . 2 7 8 3	1 0 . 4 3 6 8	1 1 . 3 4 5 2	2 . 8 6 2 7	1 0 . 7 9 3 5	1 2 . 0 6 0 8	3 . 2 9 7 7
2 1	3 . 8 6 0 0	8 . 5 1 4 1	1 1 . 4 5 6 0	0 . 3 3 6 3	1 1 . 3 3 8 5 3	3 . 2 1 6 6	1 1 . 4 0 6 3	5 . 4 7 8 0
2 2	3 . 3 3 1 4	6 . 0 3 2 0	9 . 0 2 5 4	2 . 8 9 6 0	1 . 2 3 4 9	1 0 . 7 7 1 3	1 3 . 0 3 6 9	1 0 . 3 2 1 5
2	1	1	5	4	4	1	4	1

3	1 . 6 3 1 8	0 . 9 7 8 5	. 2 8 5 7	. 9 6 8 3	. 9 4 7 7	0 . 2 8 6 1	. 6 7 1 3	0 . 1 6 0 9
2 4	5 . 6 1 9 4	1 3 . 6 8 4 6	7 . 5 1 4 9	3 . 4 6 9 2	4 . 4 6 7 5	8 . 5 0 4 4	1 . 6 0 5 9	1 1 . 5 6 8 3
2 5	3 . 0 8 3 7	5 . 8 5 6 4	1 . 4 4 9 6	0 . 3 3 4 6	1 0 . 6 7 4 6	4 . 3 3 3 3	1 1 . 9 3 2 7	0 . 3 5 2 3
2 6	0 . 9 1 6 9	1 3 . 5 1 0 8	1 . 0 8 4 1	2 . 2 2 0 1	1 3 . 7 1 0 6	3 . 0 6 2 2	7 . 7 6 5 9	3 . 5 8 3 5
2 7	2 . 4 2 6 7	8 . 2 0 5 2	4 . 1 5 3 8	6 . 7 4 7 2	3 . 6 4 7 5	1 . 3 5 9 4	6 . 8 6 0 7	4 . 0 4 3 0
2 8	1 2 . 2 7 4 7	1 1 . 2 5 2 4	3 . 7 4 6 0	8 . 4 2 8 9	0 . 8 5 4 9	0 . 3 2 6 8	3 . 3 6 2 3	8 . 3 7 7 4
2 9	0 . 2 5 3 2	1 . 4 0 2 1	2 . 8 1 6 7	0 . 0 2 3 2	8 . 5 3 5 0	1 3 . 7 0 3 8	1 . 4 6 9 9	6 . 0 3 1 5
3 0	3 . 7 0 5 8	1 2 . 9 6 9	6 . 7 0 0 7	2 . 6 3 5 2	1 3 . 3 6 1	1 1 . 0 7 0	1 0 . 7 0 5	1 1 . 2 1 0

		0			3	6	9	0
3	0	5	1	5	4	9	1	5
1	.	.	1	.	.	.	0	.
	5	2	.	4	1	1	.	6
	4	9	3	9	6	8	9	7
	1	6	8	6	2	8	2	7
	9	0	1	8	3	8	9	1
			3				0	
3	1	4	8	6	1	3	0	3
2	0	.	.	.	1	.	.	.
	.	9	8	9	.	3	6	1
	4	4	2	1	8	0	3	0
	2	7	7	9	8	0	6	2
	3	9	8	2	2	3	3	6
	4			9				
3	1	5	0	8	1	1	4	0
3	2	.	.	.	0	0	.	.
	.	0	9	2	.	.	1	9
	9	7	4	7	8	6	5	0
	2	3	2	9	3	0	1	3
	4	9	1	8	8	2	5	9
	5				9	9		
3	3	9	7	6	8	3	1	1
4	.	.	.	.	.	.	0	1
	4	7	7	0	3	7	.	.
	8	1	5	3	0	8	7	5
	6	1	0	2	7	6	8	4
	0	1	4	5	8	5	8	0
							9	4
3	3	0	1	9	2	1	7	0
5	.	.	2	.	.	0	.	.
	0	2	.	8	5	.	3	4
	6	0	0	3	0	6	6	3
	3	9	1	6	4	2	0	3
	7	6	0	0	6	1	2	0
			8			7		
3	9	8	1	1	9	1	8	6
6	.	.	2	.	.	1	.	.
	6	1	.	7	2	.	6	7
	1	3	5	6	3	9	4	1
	4	3	8	2	5	4	1	3
	5	8	2	4	7	9	0	0
			4			7		
3	2	5	1	6	8	3	4	9
7	.	.	1	.	.	.	.	.
	2	9	.	8	3	5	2	0
	2	7	4	3	3	5	9	7
	7	9	5	8	0	3	3	3
	3	0	0	3	5	3	3	6
			9					
3	0	1	5	1	2	9	1	6
8	.	2	.	2	.	.	1	.
	9	.	6	.	4	8	.	4

	6 5 4	4 0 0 8	3 1 9	2 0 9 5	3 9 9	9 5 8	0 5 4 6	1 2 0
3 9	3 . 8 2 5 9	1 2 . 4 1 0 3	3 . 7 8 7 7	3 . 1 9 2 0	1 1 . 0 5 5 0	3 . 5 9 2 6	1 3 . 9 1 4 2	4 . 9 2 1 1
4 0	6 . 4 6 8 7	8 . 1 9 7 8	1 . 6 1 0 7	5 . 0 0 7 0	1 . 4 0 3 4	1 3 . 8 1 5 1	6 . 7 2 4 3	1 0 . 5 0 6 2
4 1	0 . 4 5 6 5	1 1 . 6 0 8 4	1 2 . 4 8 0 2	2 . 7 0 1 6	7 . 8 5 6 0	8 . 4 5 0 6	3 . 3 6 0 3	0 . 0 3 9 0
4 2	1 0 . 7 2 6 0	0 . 3 0 2 5	5 . 1 5 6 9	2 . 7 6 4 8	3 . 0 4 3 9	0 . 6 2 7 6	4 . 0 3 3 3	8 . 5 6 8 9
4 3	0 . 1 2 3 9	6 . 7 0 9 2	8 . 7 4 6 5	1 . 5 5 6	1 1 . 1 1 7 7	1 3 . 0 2 6 5	1 1 . 9 9 4 1	5 . 8 3 9 4
4 4	0 . 2 2 2 4	8 . 1 4 3 8	0 . 9 4 6 3	1 2 . 1 5 3 3	1 0 . 3 9 1 1	8 . 4 8 1 7	3 . 8 3 0 3	3 . 1 3 9 9
4 5	0 . 8 6 6 1	1 . 9 1 0 0	1 1 . 5 8 8 3	7 . 3 2 3 5	2 . 8 3 0 1	3 . 0 1 8	6 . 0 6 2 3	9 . 2 2 6 8

4 6	2 . 6 3 2 3	8 . 5 4 2 9	1 0 . 9 9 5 8	1 2 . 1 3 4 9	9 . 7 1 3 0	7 . 3 5 6 9	2 . 2 3 3 5	5 . 5 7 9 5
4 7	7 . 3 5 1 1	3 . 1 2 8 6	5 . 1 8 9 2	1 2 . 9 4 9 8	1 1 . 6 6 4 9	6 . 0 5 0 0	1 1 . 3 0 3 5	3 . 6 3 3 8
4 8	6 . 1 3 5 7	1 2 . 7 9 1 4	4 . 1 7 8 0	9 . 1 4 7 7	4 . 8 1 9 7	5 . 4 3 9 9	8 . 2 6 2 2	1 . 0 4 3 1
4 9	7 . 8 2 2 5	0 . 3 3 2 1	7 . 0 1 7 1	5 . 2 5 9 9	2 . 0 4 3 2	9 . 5 5 7 1	1 0 . 0 5 2 5	8 . 9 9 1 5
5 0	4 . 4 9 4 1	4 . 9 8 9 1	1 1 . 5 4 2 7	1 . 4 9 8 7	1 1 . 8 4 8 8	5 . 5 6 8 1	1 . 8 6 9 9	9 . 1 3 8 2
5 1	6 . 4 3 8 5	8 . 2 9 0 3	1 2 . 1 3 6 1	1 0 . 4 8 0 0	7 . 5 5 7 6	7 . 7 4 3 1	2 . 9 7 3 4	3 . 9 2 4 1
5 2	0 . 4 9 9 0	1 2 . 9 4 4 5	1 1 . 5 8 9 3	7 . 1 0 1 6	7 . 3 0 4 4	1 1 . 6 3 3 8	5 . 0 8 4 6	9 . 6 6 9 3
5 3	6 . 8 6	4 . 6 0	6 . 5 6	3 . 8 1	1 . 8 5	5 . 5 9	1 1 . 8	0 . 9 8

	4 6	5 5	4 4	9 2	9 2	6 1	4 2 7	3 3
5 4	8 . 0 3 9 8	8 . 1 7 2 0	9 . 1 3 0 8	1 2 . 6 8 0 9	1 0 . 0 9 3 2	3 . 3 7 1 0	1 . 6 2 2 2	2 . 9 6 7 3
5 5	4 . 1 6 1 2	1 2 . 9 2 5 0	7 . 6 1 5 1	9 . 8 6 4 3	7 . 2 8 9 1	1 2 . 0 0 2 8	6 . 1 9 0 4	1 . 5 9 2 9
5 6	2 . 7 3 5 5	5 . 3 5 0 6	1 1 . 8 0 8 4	4 . 4 3 3 7	0 . 4 1 3 0	1 0 . 2 6 1 2	1 . 6 5 5 4	7 . 8 3 2 5
5 7	1 . 5 1 0 4	1 1 . 3 4 4 3	7 . 4 0 1 9	8 . 1 4 0 5	7 . 8 9 4 9	3 . 6 2 9 0	4 . 8 1 3 1	1 0 . 4 8 2 6
5 8	0 . 4 9 6 8	5 . 4 1 0 1	1 . 6 1 7 8	8 . 0 0 6 9	6 . 6 9 7 2	1 . 6 6 6 2	4 . 3 3 3 8	1 1 . 1 3 7 7
5 9	5 . 6 0 6 3	7 . 3 6 3 7	4 . 4 1 9 0	3 . 4 8 3 5	1 1 . 2 5 2 1	9 . 2 7 1 1	4 . 1 0 0 3	7 . 7 3 7 8
6 0	7 . 7 1 3 1	1 . 9 9 5 8	1 1 . 9 0 7 8	0 . 2 8 4 6	1 2 . 5 7 8 6	2 . 2 5 0 8	8 . 3 0 4 0	6 . 0 4 3 6

Figure – 07 / 02

S	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
l	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
o								
.								

1	2	7	1	7	1	3	7	1
	.	.	1	.	.	.	.	2
	8	7	7	1	3	1	6	.
	3	3	5	7	4	3	0	2
	4	6	9	2	8	7	3	4
	1	9	9	8	5	8	0	9
			1					0
2	1	8	9	6	7	5	8	5
	2	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
	.	3	9	4	8	2	2	2
	1	6	9	9	4	9	6	8
	0	0	2	1	8	3	0	0
	5	5	6	2	1	8	7	8
	4							
3	8	2	1	9	1	9	1	7
	.	.	3	.	3	.	3	.
	3	5	.	5	.	6	.	3
	8	5	3	3	9	6	5	6
	0	2	8	5	0	3	8	4
	3	7	7	7	8	2	3	5
			4		8		2	
4	6	1	2	1	4	6	1	1
	.	2	.	.	.	.	1	.
	3	.	0	5	2	4	.	8
	7	2	4	2	2	6	6	4
	7	8	4	2	8	4	6	7
	0	1	3	8	0	6	6	0
		3					6	
5	1	6	5	1	1	5	7	3
	3	.	.	1	1	.	.	.
	.	9	1	.	.	9	2	7
	3	8	9	4	2	4	4	7
	4	5	0	3	9	4	2	9
	3	4	6	2	4	1	1	0
	3			1	1			
6	6	1	1	5	1	8	7	6
	.	3	0	.	3	.	.	.
	5	.	.	9	.	2	5	9
	4	3	5	8	1	6	4	3
	2	3	4	4	7	8	6	4
	1	0	0	5	7	2	5	1
		8	6		1			
7	1	1	9	7	3	1	7	1
	2	.	.	.	.	3	.	2
	.	0	9	2	5	.	9	.
	2	2	4	6	2	3	6	5
	3	8	3	1	8	7	4	9
	5	3	7	8	1	7	2	8
	5					0		3
8	0	5	1	1	1	1	1	3
	.	.	.	0	1	2	.	.
	3	7	8	.	.	.	5	3
	0	1	5	2	7	6	7	3

	1 5	8 5	8 7	5 6 3	2 4 8	5 6 9	1 2	1 1
9	1 1 . 8 6 8 4	6 . 4 1 8 7	2 . 0 6 8 7	5 . 3 8 4 2	1 2 . 1 8 0 2	9 . 4 0 1	1 1 . 5 7 1 5	1 0 . 4 5 1 3
1 0	8 . 7 5 9 7	3 . 1 5 7 3	2 . 9 2 8 5	3 . 7 4 1 6	8 . 8 4 4 2	6 . 6 5 5 7	1 2 . 1 5 3 2	4 . 6 6 8 7
1 1	1 0 . 9 6 0 1	1 3 . 4 3 9 6	6 . 2 8 2 2	9 . 6 7 1 0	3 . 8 2 5 2	9 . 3 2 7 0	1 0 . 2 4 5 8	5 . 2 8 9 9
1 2	1 0 . 8 1 1 9	4 . 5 6 0 3	9 . 9 8 7 6	1 3 . 8 5 0 6	3 . 6 2 3 0	2 . 8 2 4 9	6 . 5 9 5 2	0 . 5 7 3 8
1 3	1 2 . 9 7 8 8	1 1 . 2 6 8 7	1 1 . 9 1 2 8	3 . 7 4 7 1	6 . 9 8 5 7	5 . 4 1 9 8	2 . 2 5 3 7	8 . 0 8 2 2
1 4	6 . 2 2 2 4	5 . 5 9 6 8	2 . 6 0 8 3	1 1 . 3 0 0 9	1 0 . 1 3 7 5	1 2 . 8 3 2 6	3 . 0 3 4 6	2 . 8 7 5 6
1 5	9 . 7 4 4 4	0 . 7 9 0 9	1 . 4 9 1 2	1 1 . 0 4 8 6	0 . 6 1 0	6 . 7 9 5 1	2 . 0 3 4 3	1 2 . 5 7 8 2
1	4	1	1	5	6	4	2	1

6	. 7 6 5 0	1 .3 9 4 8	1 .1 2 5 0	. 1 1 2 5	. 3 1 9 7	. 9 8 1 8	. 5 8 8 0	2 .3 7 5 8
1 7	1 .1 7 5 6	0 .9 8 7 5	4 .0 7 2 1	5 .4 7 5 1	4 .7 8 2 5	4 .2 4 1 2	0 .2 5 0 9	0 .6 5 3 1
1 8	3 .7 8 2 0	5 .6 2 9 7	1 2 .2 7 1 8	5 .7 4 1 6	2 .6 0 7 2	1 3 .3 7 3 2	1 0 .4 3 9 3	4 .5 5 1 7
1 9	1 2 .6 9 9 5	8 .1 1 6 5	3 .6 9 3 2	1 0 .9 2 3 1	1 2 .2 0 3 4	1 .1 4 5 1	1 1 .1 1 1 3	2 .2 2 6 6
2 0	3 .6 6 4 6	9 .6 3 7 5	7 .7 8 7 6	2 .4 9 6 6	8 .6 7 1 5	7 .9 3 1 2	1 0 .3 4 0 3	2 .7 8 0 6
2 1	1 2 .0 0 1 2	0 .5 2 0 3	6 .5 1 5 3	2 .1 1 0 9	1 2 .7 0 1 2	1 0 .4 3 1 8	9 .7 7 5 4	1 3 .0 8 7 1
2 2	3 .1 9 1 5	5 .5 3 7 4	9 .2 6 7 7	1 0 .1 0 5 1	1 2 .4 9 4 5	9 .8 0 4 4	0 .7 3 0 7	1 2 .1 3 4 2
2 3	2 .9 4 1 0	6 .8 2 8 3	6 .2 0 1 9	1 1 .7 7 7	2 .4 6 5 4	6 .0 7 6 7	9 .7 3 8 7	1 1 .0 6 7

				5				5
2 4	9 . 9 3 0 6	8 . 8 4 4 1	1 2 . 8 0 4 7	7 . 1 5 7 8	5 . 7 4 2 4	1 . 8 7 6 6	8 . 4 8 5 1	7 . 8 6 3 8
2 5	1 2 . 2 5 2 2	1 0 . 4 4 5 3	0 . 9 8 9 5	2 . 9 3 8 9	1 . 5 0 8 7	1 0 . 9 3 3 2	5 . 2 9 6 0	8 . 9 8 9 7
2 6	1 0 . 4 6 6 8	4 . 2 6 8 3	2 . 9 0 6 9	1 0 . 8 6 5 3	5 . 0 1 5 7	4 . 2 1 6 3	4 . 0 5 5 4	1 3 . 1 5 5 6
2 7	1 1 . 5 8 9 9	9 . 5 4 5 1	1 1 . 2 9 4 5	1 1 . 6 0 6 4	3 . 9 3 7 2	2 . 9 7 3 7	3 . 7 6 7 9	8 . 2 0 4 5
2 8	4 . 5 6 6 6	1 2 . 6 4 6 2	1 1 . 9 6 0 6	1 0 . 1 4 9 1	1 2 . 9 2 4 2	6 . 0 8 8 0	8 . 1 0 8 7	4 . 8 6 4 4
2 9	7 . 3 0 6 7	6 . 0 5 6 1	1 0 . 3 9 8 8	3 . 9 0 6 3	4 . 9 1 9 8	6 . 0 4 4 0	1 0 . 8 3 5	1 2 . 8 6 3 2
3 0	1 1 . 3 1 1 5	1 1 . 5 9 1 4	8 . 8 7 2 1	0 . 1 2 3 7	8 . 1 0 8 2	8 . 5 3 2 3	1 1 . 6 9 6 4	2 . 5 0 5 9
3 1	1 . 8	2 . 7	0 . 4	1 . 4	2 . 2	7 . 4	0 . 6	1 2 .

	8 0 2	7 9 9	6 9 6	4 2 6	1 4 6	2 1 8	8 6 9	7 6 3 1
3 2	5 . 5 7 8 3	6 . 6 5 8 6	4 . 0 3 0 3	1 2 . 8 1 2 4	1 2 . 6 7 8 5	1 . 5 9 8 8	2 . 2 4 9 8	5 . 2 0 2 1
3 3	1 . 7 6 6 5	1 3 . 8 8 9 1	4 . 3 7 8 7	7 . 5 8 0 0	1 2 . 6 9 7 2	2 . 4 2 4 1	2 . 6 2 2 5	4 . 0 4 7 3
3 4	1 1 . 2 5 7 6	1 3 . 3 1 4 1	1 . 4 9 9 4	0 . 0 3 5 2	3 . 6 8 4 7	1 . 0 5 3 6	2 . 9 1 8 2	8 . 0 1 8 8
3 5	9 . 6 8 0 6	3 . 0 6 9 0	9 . 1 1 9 5	6 . 5 7 0 9	7 . 0 6 5 8	8 . 9 8 1 2	4 . 0 2 7 1	1 3 . 4 2 8 4
3 6	2 . 6 2 6 6	0 . 4 3 9 0	0 . 0 2 8 1	1 . 6 8 7 0	9 . 7 7 7 6	4 . 6 0 7 8	9 . 2 5 4 6	7 . 4 5 0 3
3 7	8 . 3 1 0 4	7 . 0 6 4 6	1 . 9 6 9 0	1 2 . 6 9 2 6	1 . 5 3 2 5	1 1 . 9 6 1 3	4 . 9 2 8 1	0 . 5 8 7 0
3 8	9 . 2 4 4 3	5 . 7 7 6 8	0 . 6 3 1 6	6 . 0 3 5 7	1 . 8 0 7 9	7 . 2 9 6 6	1 2 . 1 9 9 2	4 . 6 9 1 8
3	1	2	1	3	4	5	6	4

9	1 . 9 6 4 3	. 2 6 8 2	. 1 7 2 9	. 8 2 4 5	. 9 7 9 4	. 0 3 5 9	. 8 2 3 2	. 7 3 1 9
4 0	7 . 9 4 6 1	4 . 7 1 7 4	1 3 . 2 9 5 5	0 . 9 4 8 6	6 . 3 6 3 2	5 . 9 3 7 1	2 . 5 4 0 0	6 . 8 6 6 8
4 1	6 . 1 4 5 3	1 0 . 0 4 3 0	9 . 8 0 2 5	2 . 2 1 5 9	8 . 7 2 4 1	4 . 0 3 4 9	1 0 . 2 0 1 6	2 . 2 2 1 5
4 2	6 . 3 0 0 2	0 . 1 0 5 9	1 2 . 5 6 4 2	9 . 1 1 7 6	6 . 8 9 4 4	6 . 3 8 1 0	1 2 . 2 6 2 7	5 . 8 1 1 0
4 3	2 . 4 1 6 5	3 . 6 7 2 9	7 . 5 2 0 6	6 . 0 2 1 0	9 . 3 2 7 0	1 3 . 9 3 7 6	1 0 . 3 2 1 6	1 3 . 8 7 0 3
4 4	1 3 . 1 8 4 0	4 . 5 2 3 0	9 . 5 8 3 1	8 . 0 0 6 5	6 . 8 5 8 7	2 . 3 3 2 1	7 . 7 0 8 9	1 1 . 2 5 0 1
4 5	2 . 0 5 5 5	1 . 0 1 4 0	4 . 4 5 0 5	1 1 . 3 3 5 7	6 . 5 4 1 8	1 2 . 9 3 6 4	1 . 4 7 9 8	0 . 3 1 8 0
4 6	1 0 . 6 1	0 . 0 7 8	1 1 . 6 5	9 . 3 4 6	9 . 6 2 3	5 . 3 8 2	5 . 6 9 1	1 . 0 8 7

	9 6	6	6 8	2	3	6	8	6
4 7	9 . 1 2 1 7	8 . 4 9 1 9	5 . 6 4 5 7	1 1 . 6 4 5 6	1 1 . 7 0 5 3	9 . 8 9 5 5	1 0 . 3 6 3 4	1 2 . 8 2 0 3
4 8	0 . 4 4 8 4	5 . 5 8 7 5	2 . 8 9 4 2	4 . 7 8 9 5	6 . 1 5 8 3	9 . 1 8 2 1	6 . 2 3 5 5	8 . 7 8 4 2
4 9	1 2 . 6 3 4 1	2 . 4 9 1 1	8 . 8 2 6 3	1 . 4 2 9 4	1 0 . 8 4 9 2	1 3 . 0 9 0 8	4 . 8 5 2 8	2 . 6 7 0 5
5 0	5 . 5 0 1 4	4 . 4 9 8 7	0 . 6 4 7 2	1 2 . 6 1 4 3	3 . 7 4 4 5	1 1 . 7 8 7 7	1 2 . 3 2 4 2	1 . 2 5 8 0
5 1	7 . 7 3 9 0	5 . 4 1 9 2	7 . 2 7 9 0	4 . 2 0 3 7	1 2 . 7 2 4 8	6 . 3 8 6 4	0 . 6 3 9 2	1 0 . 1 4 1 2
5 2	1 2 . 0 0 3 6	4 . 9 9 0 0	1 1 . 8 3 6 1	5 . 7 2 2 9	1 2 . 3 1 3 9	4 . 6 3 7 1	1 1 . 5 6 3 3	2 . 0 1 4 0
5 3	8 . 7 7 6 8	1 3 . 8 5 1 4	1 . 8 9 6 0	7 . 8 4 4 4	2 . 5 2 0 9	1 . 3 5 2 6	3 . 4 9 9 4	6 . 5 3 0 6
5 4	2 . 3	2 . 3	8 . 4	1 0 . .	1 2 . .	2 . 7	1 0 . .	0 . 8

	2 1 6	8 5 6	8 8 8	8 6 4 1	5 7 8 4	2 5 6	3 0 2 9	1 6 9
5 5	1 2 . 7 4 5 2	4 . 6 5 2 3	6 . 0 0 8 7	0 . 8 8 4 0	3 . 5 8 3 9	0 . 2 4 2 4	1 0 . 2 2 4 1	1 0 . 1 6 6 0
5 6	1 . 6 1 0 4	2 . 8 1 9 7	6 . 4 0 5 6	2 . 7 8 1 2	6 . 5 5 2 1	6 . 3 5 7 8	5 . 3 3 9 3	7 . 9 5 2 0
5 7	1 0 . 0 0 3 1	1 . 9 1 5 9	0 . 0 4 4 4	1 . 0 8 9 3	2 . 4 1 2 9	1 2 . 8 4 8 5	6 . 9 8 8 3	1 . 3 1 1 8
5 8	1 2 . 2 0 8 4	3 . 4 2 4 9	9 . 1 0 5 0	6 . 8 2 8 2	1 . 0 7 5 0	9 . 7 1 4 9	9 . 8 3 1 4	1 2 . 4 6 7 8
5 9	5 . 5 6 7 3	8 . 2 4 1 4	0 . 0 4 1 9	7 . 4 6 0 2	5 . 9 5 5 4	6 . 9 2 2 3	6 . 0 7 3 5	1 2 . 5 7 0 6
6 0	9 . 0 9 2 6	1 3 . 0 4 5 8	8 . 7 9 1 1	9 . 9 5 7 4	0 . 7 9 3 2	2 . 0 1 6 7	1 . 5 0 4 8	0 . 4 3 3 9

Figure – 08 / 02

SUBJECT - 04

S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	4 . 3 6 8 4	8 . 7 9 4 3	2 . 9 3 3 6	1 . 1 5 4 8 1	1 0 . 5 5 7 2 6	0 . 3 5 7 8	7 . 6 4 5 8	6 . 5 6 5 8
2	4 . 0 6 9 8	5 . 0 1 1 8	1 . 5 5 3 2	2 . 5 4 0 1	4 . 6 4 1 6	5 . 5 0 8 2	8 . 6 4 4 8	2 . 7 3 9 6
3	3 . 4 6 2 3	1 2 . 8 2 0 6	2 . 1 9 6 2	1 . 9 5 4 3	1 2 . 6 9 6 4	6 . 8 8 3 8	1 0 . 4 7 6 2	6 . 4 0 1 2
4	1 . 9 5 6 1	1 0 . 1 3 5 3	8 . 9 9 1 5	1 . 5 0 2 5	0 . 4 2 3 5	6 . 9 2 7 6	4 . 1 1 2 1	5 . 9 5 1 8
5	1 1 . 9 3 8 2	7 . 3 4 2 5	2 . 1 2 8 2	1 2 . 1 1 7 0	0 . 5 1 9 4	8 . 7 2 4 9	1 1 . 8 6 7 7	3 . 2 0 7 9
6	6 . 8 5 1 5	1 3 . 1 9 3 2	1 0 . 4 4 2 3	1 3 . 6 8 2 8	1 3 . 7 7 2 6	6 . 4 8 4 1	1 . 2 9 4 6	2 . 8 9 5 2
7	3 . 4 8	2 . 6 3	9 . 2 3	4 . 6 2	4 . 7 8	0 . 5 8	1 0 . 4	6 . 7 3

	5 6	0 0	3 9	3 8	3 3	8 9	2 8 8	4 7
8	1 1 . 1 1 2 4	1 . 2 5 7 3	1 . 2 1 8 0	1 . 1 9 4 4	8 . 3 0 0 4	6 . 2 6 0 1	5 . 5 2 1 1	2 . 6 5 2 7
9	5 . 9 3 9 5	9 . 4 0 6 7	1 0 . 1 8 2 4	9 . 4 6 3 7	6 . 4 7 9 9	6 . 5 5 2 0	1 1 . 0 8 2 9	0 . 3 8 7 3
1 0	9 . 3 4 3 9	6 . 5 6 7 8	8 . 4 8 1 8	1 3 . 6 2 1 5	6 . 3 9 5 4	2 . 4 5 8 7	6 . 4 7 0 1	3 . 0 9 0 2
1 1	3 . 8 6 9 9	0 . 7 3 7 6	1 1 . 3 5 9 0	1 2 . 2 1 7 4	2 . 4 2 0 3	3 . 4 2 3 1	1 1 . 6 0 7 1	1 3 . 8 2 2 9
1 2	1 0 . 4 0 8 2	1 1 . 0 9 0 9	8 . 7 5 4 9	5 . 3 3 6 5	0 . 9 9 0 0	3 . 7 0 4 9	1 . 3 4 0 8	1 0 . 7 3 9 0
1 3	6 . 3 1 4 0	1 0 . 1 2 9 3	1 . 9 0 0 0	0 . 9 1 4 7	3 . 3 9 2 6	0 . 1 6 4 6	6 . 5 7 8 2	4 . 9 4 3 7
1 4	8 . 6 8 7 1	1 . 0 4 1 6	1 . 3 3 6 5	0 . 2 6 1 0	1 2 . 3 6 0 7	1 0 . 1 2 6 2	1 0 . 0 1 3 1	8 . 3 7 1 7
1	7	1	1	5	4	4	1	1

5	. 7 3 3 0	1 . 4 9 1 6	0 . 7 4 3 4	. 6 4 4 2	. 4 8 2	. 3 6 6 7	1 . 6 3 0 7	1 . 8 4 4 0
1 6	1 . 4 1 2 7	3 . 4 8 2 8	6 . 8 4 2 5	1 3 5 7 4 7	1 3 3 2 6 0	4 . 2 8 1 8	1 . 5 5 4 9	2 . 6 7 8 7
1 7	1 2 . 4 9 5 9	1 2 . 8 4 5 9	8 . 4 8 1 5	9 . 6 1 3 1	9 . 2 7 9 8	1 0 . 1 9 5 6	1 2 . 8 6 0 9	1 . 1 2 1 0
1 8	7 . 8 5 0 9	9 . 1 8 3 8	2 . 4 9 9 1	9 . 1 1 6 5	9 . 9 4 8 5	2 . 2 6 0 3	5 . 9 7 9 1	1 3 . 7 8 1 0
1 9	1 0 . 6 5 5 2	3 . 8 7 4 1	2 . 8 3 2 3	5 . 9 7 2 4	7 . 1 1 9 7	1 2 . 5 2 4 8	1 0 . 8 8 4 2	2 . 6 0 7 6
2 0	0 . 2 3 3 4	0 . 0 8 7 7	5 . 1 5 2 7	6 . 0 3 6 3	7 . 2 9 2 5	1 1 . 7 1 9 5	5 . 7 9 0 8	8 . 3 1 2 1
2 1	1 2 . 8 8 5 4	2 . 1 1 0 9	6 . 4 3 9 7	1 . 5 6 9	1 1 . 7 3 2 8	1 2 . 6 7 7 4	1 2 . 8 6 5 6	1 . 4 8 0 3
2 2	1 . 9 9 7	7 . 0 6 2	3 . 3 2 7	1 0 . 8 5	6 . 9 1 2	9 . 7 3 2	0 . 7 7 2	1 2 . 1 1 1

	8	0	7	2 1	1	1	8	4 9
2 3	1 0 . 4 1 0 6	1 3 . 1 7 8 1	7 . 3 3 4 2	5 . 0 7 8 3	4 . 8 8 2 8	4 . 1 1 0 7	1 2 . 0 6 4 8	6 . 2 1 9 2
2 4	5 . 4 8 1 1	6 . 6 0 2 1	0 . 7 8 1 0	1 0 . 2 5 2 6	9 . 7 4 2 9	1 0 . 0 8 7 8	2 . 5 9 5 3	8 . 6 2 8 5
2 5	1 1 . 9 3 6 7	1 1 . 7 9 7 8	0 . 6 9 0 8	9 . 2 1 1	1 . 3 7 7 6	0 . 8 9 8 7	1 . 2 0 7 7	3 . 0 9 1 3
2 6	1 . 4 8 1 6	4 . 0 1 9 2	1 0 . 8 9 3 3	9 . 1 3 3 6	1 . 3 2 9 1	1 . 0 2 2 6	1 0 . 7 7 0 0	4 . 1 9 6 9
2 7	1 . 6 1 2 2	9 . 3 5 7 9	6 . 2 8 6 2	9 . 2 8 1 4	3 . 3 0 4 5	1 1 . 9 7 4 8	1 . 5 4 6 5	4 . 7 5 9 3
2 8	2 . 2 4 0 8	2 . 3 6 4 9	4 . 3 5 9 2	2 . 8 9 1 0	6 . 6 8 4 9	1 0 . 5 4 0 0	1 0 . 2 0 3 2	3 . 8 6 6 4
2 9	6 . 1 6 0 9	1 1 . 5 3 4 6	5 . 5 7 1 8	9 . 7 0 1 0	1 0 . 0 6 6 6	0 . 8 2 7 2	1 0 . 9 7 4 0	8 . 3 1 3 3
3 0	3 . .	2 . .	1 3	1 .	6 .	6 .	1 .	1 0

	7 7 8 7	9 6 8 8	. 8 6 6 4	7 4 9 9	5 0 7 3	5 0 5 3	3 3 7 7	. 2 7 8 1
3 1	4 . 6 4 3 4	9 . 3 5 2 6	1 2 . 9 8 1 7	6 . 8 1 4 2	1 . 5 5 0 6	0 . 7 6 3 8	1 0 . 1 3 7 2	1 . 8 8 5 0
3 2	1 3 . 6 9 8 5	4 . 8 2 4 4	7 . 0 0 1 7	7 . 6 7 8 6	3 . 7 3 6 8	0 . 1 7 1 8	0 . 2 4 8 7	6 . 8 4 7 2
3 3	8 . 4 9 6 5	1 0 . 9 3 6 3	8 . 8 1 5 8	1 0 . 6 6 0 0	9 . 6 2 1 0	1 1 . 6 0 5 9	1 . 9 5 7 0	1 . 9 0 8 1
3 4	7 . 0 3 6 2	5 . 7 5 4 5	5 . 6 3 4 0	5 . 0 8 7 8	7 . 4 4 8 0	3 . 5 7 5 2	1 1 . 5 7 4 4	1 . 5 4 3 4
3 5	1 0 . 5 7 2 1	1 0 . 2 7 0 0	7 . 9 0 7 6	8 . 1 8 8 0	2 . 0 7 1 7	7 . 8 4 0 9	1 2 . 9 7 7 2	3 . 8 8 3 3
3 6	4 . 5 0 8 1	8 . 5 1 2 3	7 . 9 1 1 6	9 . 1 5 7 2	0 . 4 3 6 5	3 . 7 8 7 3	8 . 9 5 2 3	5 . 3 2 0 0
3 7	4 . 4 9 1 5	0 . 8 1 6 6	1 0 . 9 3 2 5	6 . 6 1 8 6	9 . 3 6 7 1	9 . 5 2 2 2	1 0 . 1 7 6 4	4 . 4 7 1 6

3 8	1 2 . 5 7 0 2	1 2 . 4 5 4 0	6 . 1 9 1 1	1 2 . 2 1 9 0	1 0 . 9 6 6 8	0 . 4 9 8 6	2 . 1 7 5 9	1 2 . 9 4 9 4
3 9	8 . 0 8 2 4	2 . 6 6 9 6	9 . 0 9 4 3	6 . 7 7 6 0	1 . 8 9 0 6	5 . 8 8 1 2	6 . 3 1 3 9	1 0 . 2 5 7 5
4 0	5 . 6 5 5 2	1 3 . 4 8 6 5	1 . 0 2 5 2	6 . 0 3 7 7	1 2 . 6 9 3 6	5 . 7 5 4 7	5 . 4 4 6 2	9 . 2 7 1 8
4 1	0 . 4 8 5 9	9 . 3 9 8 8	7 . 5 5 0 5	1 2 . 5 3 8 1	1 . 7 8 9 0	9 . 1 8 9 8	4 . 2 5 6 0	7 . 9 2 5 2
4 2	5 . 3 1 9 2	1 0 . 6 4 4 3	6 . 0 3 5 1	1 1 . 0 8 2 4	1 2 . 8 6 8 3	4 . 7 8 5 9	8 . 0 8 6 0	6 . 2 2 3 7
4 3	2 . 0 9 1 1	7 . 1 5 2 0	1 0 . 3 3 6 0	1 . 5 1 3 3	1 3 . 2 7 7 5	7 . 2 1 1 8	1 . 8 3 5 5	6 . 2 6 0 4
4 4	5 . 4 7 0 0	3 . 0 4 5 0	2 . 7 9 6 8	7 . 0 0 9 7	9 . 7 1 3 3	7 . 9 4 4 5	4 . 8 3 6 9	1 0 . 7 7 4 3
4 5	5 . 6 2	4 . 0 7	7 . 8 1	3 . 6 7	9 . 3 5	8 . 9 1	1 1 . 7	1 2 . 3

	5 4	4 1	8 0	7 9	2 4	3 9	4 8 5	6 4 1
4 6	1 0 . 4 5 6 2	6 . 5 6 7 4	7 . 9 6 1 9	7 . 9 7 7 8	2 . 2 1 2 6	1 0 . 9 3 5 7	0 . 3 0 8 8	0 . 7 3 4 9
4 7	9 . 5 6 7 3	1 . 8 5 4 7	8 . 9 7 5 2	3 . 7 0 6 9	1 0 . 4 3 8 9	9 . 0 8 3 3	1 1 . 6 5 4 0	9 . 1 6 9 5
4 8	1 1 . 2 5 7 6	1 0 . 9 2 2 9	3 . 5 7 7 2	1 2 . 2 0 6 9	2 . 5 2 5 9	2 . 2 5 8	9 . 4 1 2 3	1 2 . 6 0 6 6
4 9	3 . 9 0 8 9	5 . 6 6 4 2	0 . 1 8 2 4	1 0 . 6 5 4 2	1 1 . 4 0 0 5	7 . 3 5 8 9	3 . 1 6 7 7	1 0 . 6 4 7 1
5 0	0 . 6 0 1 7	1 . 9 5 2 4	8 . 2 5 5 9	1 . 3 1 3 3	9 . 9 7 8 3	9 . 2 7 5 6	9 . 1 7 9 4	8 . 1 7 7 2
5 1	9 . 0 1 2 5	1 2 . 3 4 6 9	5 . 3 6 9 7	7 . 2 2 3 1	1 . 9 2 4 4	0 . 4 9 5 1	1 0 . 8 7 2 7	0 . 0 5 3 3
5 2	7 . 8 4 5 8	2 . 3 8 8 1	1 . 3 3 3 5	9 . 2 2 0 7	1 . 4 9 9 9	8 . 4 6 9 8	5 . 5 6 4 5	1 2 . 2 4 1 4
5 3	1 0	2 .	6 .	7 .	1 1	1 .	0 .	2 .

	. 0 3 4 7	2 5 9 6	6 1 8 7	1 4 1 5	. 3 8 6 7	8 7 3 4	6 4 8 8	9 8 3 1
5 4	3 . 9 6 7 0	1 2 . 8 2 9 9	4 . 2 8 8 9	1 0 . 6 2 5 1	7 . 0 7 5 0	3 . 9 7 1 4	3 . 4 9 6 8	2 . 2 8 2 3
5 5	1 2 . 3 2 6 4	1 . 4 1 4 8	5 . 9 8 6 9	3 . 8 8 0 8	2 . 0 2 6 0	2 . 7 5 6 4	1 0 . 8 9 6 0	6 . 7 8 1 9
5 6	8 . 6 7 0 4	2 . 6 6 0 5	1 0 . 3 4 0 9	6 . 4 6 4 0	6 . 9 2 6 6	2 . 0 8 4 9	2 . 8 0 3 0	1 2 . 3 8 9 6
5 7	4 . 6 9 4 0	5 . 9 8 7 5	1 . 5 3 8 5	0 . 7 4 9 0	3 . 2 2 8 3	1 . 8 4 0 5	4 . 7 8 4 9	7 . 5 3 0 5
5 8	0 . 0 6 9 0	2 . 0 1 5 3	4 . 1 2 6 7	0 . 6 3 5 5	4 . 4 9 5 0	1 . 7 6 5 0	8 . 7 8 1 4	6 . 1 8 8 5
5 9	9 . 1 7 5 7	1 2 . 1 9 4 8	1 1 . 7 4 4 4	2 . 7 0 1 4	1 1 . 9 3 1 7	2 . 3 6 2 7	8 . 9 6 7 4	1 2 . 4 0 8 6
6 0	5 . 8 4 4 0	7 . 0 5 3 6	0 . 6 1 7 0	9 . 2 1 9 2	0 . 1 2 2 0	4 . 9 3 6 0	4 . 7 1 5 3	8 . 7 7 9 6

Figure – 09 / 02

S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 3 . 6 8 4 5	9 . 0 0 1 2	6 . 3 5 0 5	0 . 3 8 6 3	1 . 0 1 5 0	1 0 . 1 4 6 7	1 1 . 6 7 1 2	6 . 2 8 2 2
2	2 . 4 7 3 5	4 . 7 0 2 1	7 . 0 7 8 4	5 . 3 4 7 0	8 . 2 5 9 2	0 . 5 4 4 2	1 3 . 6 0 1 0	5 . 4 3 4 3
3	1 . 5 8 2 7	1 1 . 6 4 5 8	8 . 3 5 2 1	1 . 3 6 6 7	1 1 . 2 9 9 8	7 . 8 2 8 4	8 . 8 7 5 1	1 2 . 5 2 3 6
4	5 . 1 4 3 6	9 . 0 1 2 1	8 . 1 6 9 3	8 . 7 7 6 3	4 . 4 7 8 0	5 . 6 9 0 9	7 . 1 3 1 2	6 . 6 2 2 3
5	1 0 . 8 2 6 2	2 . 7 8 3 3	1 1 . 3 3 0 7	1 . 4 7 9 2	1 1 . 3 5 4 7	0 . 4 6 0 6	4 . 2 8 2 3	1 1 . 4 0 7 6
6	4 . 9 6 5 7	4 . 7 0 6 9	1 2 . 5 5 8 5	1 1 . 8 4 6 3	8 . 6 6 7 3	5 . 2 1 7 2	1 . 7 8 7 9	2 . 2 3 6 1
7	1 0 . 2 5	3 . 0 7 3	1 0 . 4 0	1 0 . 5 9	6 . 6 4 1	0 . 8 9 7	7 . 0 8 6	4 . 2 2 8

	1 8	9	8 7	0 0	2	1	5	8
8	0 . 7 9 4 6	5 . 3 6 9 1	1 . 2 5 7 4	2 . 1 5 1 1	7 . 8 2 5 2	8 . 7 0 0 4	3 . 7 6 8 5	1 2 . 9 6 7 3
9	4 . 7 1 2 1	4 . 8 2 6 1	8 . 5 3 6 3	1 . 6 6 7 9	5 . 3 2 5 2	2 . 6 8 8 8	4 . 0 5 4 9	1 2 . 2 2 3 9
1 0	7 . 0 9 8 8	7 . 7 4 7 7	1 . 9 7 0 8	3 . 4 9 0 7	6 . 5 5 4 0	7 . 9 0 3 3	1 1 . 2 6 3 3	1 . 9 4 2 4
1 1	5 . 7 1 3 6	1 0 . 7 8 2 3	3 . 0 9 3 6	0 . 1 0 9 8	1 3 . 4 3 1 9	0 . 0 2 1 7	8 . 1 3 1 8	3 . 9 3 9 2
1 2	7 . 9 3 4 7	7 . 5 0 0 1	7 . 6 5 4 0	1 2 . 4 5 2 7	1 1 . 1 1 8 0	0 . 2 0 5 7	9 . 8 1 2 3	1 2 . 4 4 4 3
1 3	1 . 5 9 8 1	1 2 . 8 0 6 7	3 . 4 6 6 9	5 . 2 0 1 4	1 . 3 4 6 7	1 2 . 9 4 7 2	1 . 0 4 5 3	6 . 4 7 7 2
1 4	1 . 3 9 0 6	6 . 1 2 3 3	9 . 7 2 0 4	7 . 2 8 6 3	1 1 . 8 2 9 5	3 . 7 7 3 4	1 0 . 6 6 5 5	7 . 1 7 1 9
1 5	1 0	7 .	1 2	2 .	6 .	7 .	0 .	9 .

	. 3 6 7 1	7 4 5 5	. 4 0 4 0	1 6 1 6	4 7 6 7	5 6 6 3	6 8 6 9	4 2 6 3
1 6	0 . 6 2 2 4	7 . 5 2 8 8	4 . 1 5 8 6	1 1 9 8 2 6	7 . 0 0 4 3	1 2 . 1 3 4 4	9 . 2 8 5 3	9 . 2 3 9 3
1 7	5 . 7 0 8 1	8 . 6 4 1 3	1 1 . 8 7 5 9	1 1 . 8 8 2 6	6 . 0 6 1 8	1 2 . 0 2 8 0	7 . 3 4 2 5	2 . 2 8 9 9
1 8	1 1 . 9 2 3 6	7 . 1 8 2 8	1 0 . 2 0 1 1	4 . 1 9 4 0	1 0 . 4 2 1 5	7 . 9 3 8 0	3 . 9 8 9 4	9 . 6 7 4 3
1 9	6 . 3 8 7 0	6 . 1 4 5 3	1 . 1 4 8 7	1 2 . 1 8 5 4	1 0 . 1 8 0 2	7 . 2 3 2 2	2 . 9 0 4 8	1 3 . 5 6 0 9
2 0	4 . 8 4 3 7	8 . 2 9 8 5	9 . 3 2 6 5	2 . 2 9 4 3	8 . 6 3 8 0	0 . 1 6 9 3	3 . 3 4 4 5	3 . 8 4 0 2
2 1	1 2 . 4 2 2 1	9 . 6 5 0 3	6 . 6 6 9 3	5 . 9 9 0 2	3 . 6 6 9 6	3 . 9 7 8 8	7 . 1 9 9 5	3 . 5 6 1 4
2 2	3 . 6 6 1 7	1 0 . 4 5 6 9	1 1 . 4 0 1 8	5 . 2 0 9 3	0 . 4 7 2 5	2 . 3 8 9 5	9 . 9 6 2 4	1 0 . 4 7 4 3

2 3	1 1 . 1 6 8 5	1 . 2 3 8 2	1 . 7 2 1 9	3 . 7 8 8	1 3 . 3 4 2 3	5 . 3 1 9 5	1 . 9 5 4 3	3 . 1 0 9 7
2 4	1 3 . 0 9 7 4	1 3 . 7 0 3 7	5 . 5 6 2 1	2 . 0 1 0 3	3 . 8 6 3 1	1 2 . 5 4 9 0	7 . 0 7 7 4	3 . 2 2 3 7
2 5	3 . 6 8 3 2	7 . 0 4 8 9	2 . 2 2 7 2	1 . 9 3 5 5	1 2 . 6 9 9 9	7 . 3 3 9 5	1 . 3 7 7 9	1 3 . 7 9 3 1
2 6	1 . 4 0 8 0	5 . 8 1 5 0	7 . 2 3 6 3	1 . 2 8 4 2	7 . 6 3 0 0	7 . 2 4 1 8	5 . 6 5 7 6	5 . 4 3 5 8
2 7	2 . 6 8 2 4	2 . 4 7 8 7	9 . 5 5 1 5	1 . 6 2 5 5	7 . 0 9 4 1	4 . 5 1 6 9	1 0 . 1 1 6 2	9 . 9 2 1 9
2 8	8 . 9 0 0 8	5 . 8 1 0 8	4 . 5 8 9 1	8 . 5 6 6 6	7 . 8 7 8 7	3 . 2 7 7 5	5 . 5 3 2 4	3 . 0 1 1 9
2 9	3 . 3 0 9 7	1 2 . 0 7 1 5	5 . 7 2 4 1	4 . 5 4 8 0	7 . 6 0 6 1	8 . 6 1 4 1	8 . 5 3 2 9	1 2 . 7 8 3 0
3 0	5 . 7 2 2 1	3 . 8 1 5 5	1 0 . 7 1 6	1 0 . 6 1 1	1 . 9 8 9 5	1 1 . 8 2 3	7 . 8 5 0 2	7 . 0 6 7 5

			7	6		4		
3 1	0 . 2 7 2 0	6 . 9 3 5 5	1 2 . 2 7 9 6	9 . 7 3 9 3	6 . 3 8 6 8	6 . 3 8 8 9	0 . 6 4 6 4	0 . 1 6 4 9
3 2	0 . 3 2 5 8	3 . 5 1 8 7	3 . 5 4 1 9	0 . 0 4 8 1	3 . 9 7 7 7	1 1 . 6 2 0 4	8 . 9 8 7 2	6 . 5 3 6 2
3 3	1 1 . 0 8 5 6	1 3 . 9 9 1 9	1 0 . 6 1 3 7	1 2 . 1 5 6 6	6 . 2 8 0 3	1 2 . 7 1 0 7	1 . 2 9 1 8	9 . 8 8 7 6
3 4	7 . 5 6 2 1	0 . 8 4 2 6	1 1 . 6 6 1 6	2 . 6 7 4 4	2 . 0 0 3 6	3 . 9 6 0 2	1 3 . 2 3 2 4	9 . 5 7 3 9
3 5	1 . 8 9 1 1	1 0 . 4 7 5 1	5 . 1 6 6 7	5 . 6 3 8 5	7 . 1 4 0 4	0 . 2 5 3 6	7 . 7 6 7 8	9 . 4 8 9 7
3 6	1 1 . 9 0 3 3	9 . 4 6 0 2	4 . 3 9 9 4	6 . 9 8 5 1	9 . 5 8 0 7	2 . 5 0 1 3	7 . 9 9 1 3	3 . 3 2 6 6
3 7	1 0 . 5 4 7 1	0 . 8 7 7 0	6 . 1 3 8 1	3 . 8 1 8 2	6 . 2 1 0 7	1 . 4 4 3 2	6 . 3 3 7 0	5 . 7 0 2 6
3 8	4 . 6	4 . 1	4 . 3	4 . 7	7 . 3	3 . 2	1 . 3	2 . 2

	9 4 1	4 8 2	9 2 7	8 2 0	5 7 7	3 3 4	9 3 5	0 8 4
3 9	0 . 0 4 4 1	1 1 . 3 2 4 1	9 . 6 1 8 0	6 . 4 1 9 6	2 . 0 0 8 6	8 . 1 4 7 0	7 . 6 4 8 1	8 . 6 8 9 4
4 0	1 0 . 0 1 2 5	1 1 . 7 1 2 4	3 . 9 7 9 1	3 . 3 9 5 9	3 . 2 8 2 0	4 . 5 7 8 7	4 . 0 4 1 1	6 . 7 7 7 3
4 1	1 0 . 5 2 4 1	0 . 4 6 2 4	8 . 4 7 1 4	1 0 . 0 8 4 7	5 . 6 7 1 4	2 . 2 0 9 5	9 . 1 2 2 3	9 . 1 6 5 7
4 2	1 . 2 8 2 9	1 0 . 9 7 7 6	9 . 6 3 7 2	1 1 . 7 3 8 9	0 . 6 5 0 1	1 1 . 4 2 7 0	9 . 9 4 1 1	4 . 0 5 1 7
4 3	2 . 1 1 0 0	6 . 8 5 8 2	1 0 . 0 2 2 1	8 . 2 0 4 7	3 . 4 0 5 8	1 1 . 6 8 8 5	8 . 6 3 3 6	1 0 . 4 6 0 1
4 4	8 . 0 5 0 1	2 . 5 7 6 9	4 . 3 6 2 7	4 . 6 7 1 7	2 . 0 1 6 5	5 . 0 8 9 3	1 2 . 1 3 8 3	0 . 1 5 0 0
4 5	3 . 2 4 3 5	9 . 2 5 8 1	1 0 . 8 3 5 8	8 . 7 4 2 5	4 . 9 3 6 2	2 . 0 6 9 6	1 3 . 1 9 6 2	1 0 . 9 4 6 1
4	1	4	5	1	0	1	1	9

6	0 . 3 9 0 3	. 9 6 7 1	. 2 6 2 7	2 . 4 6 0 7	. 7 0 6 6	. 9 4 7 0	. 7 6 8 6	. 6 8 1 0
4 7	1 2 . 7 1 9 4	7 . 6 7 5 2	7 . 5 9 6 8	1 0 . 1 2 4 1	1 . 4 9 8 1	1 0 . 6 0 1 3	1 3 . 4 0 7 6	8 . 3 6 1 6
4 8	1 0 . 9 0 9 9	1 1 . 7 9 8 6	1 2 . 8 9 0 9	4 . 0 6 1 8	9 . 3 2 7 3	1 1 . 5 1 4 7	1 0 . 3 6 3 1	7 . 9 0 3 8
4 9	6 . 9 7 3 0	4 . 8 3 8 7	1 3 . 4 9 1 6	1 2 . 8 8 3 5	6 . 6 2 9 9	1 2 . 3 4 9 3	0 . 2 5 8 2	1 . 2 6 1 4
5 0	3 . 7 9 0 1	9 . 0 8 0 2	4 . 6 9 6 9	1 2 . 1 4 0 3	1 0 . 0 1 9 8	1 2 . 6 9 9 3	1 . 1 0 1 6	0 . 8 8 4 6
5 1	7 . 9 6 7 9	7 . 0 0 3 4	2 . 6 7 8 8	1 1 . 0 8 3 4	0 . 4 5 0 1	1 1 . 0 3 5 7	1 3 . 9 2 3 0	3 . 2 7 1 4
5 2	5 . 8 6 5 7	1 1 . 1 7 5 4	9 . 0 8 7 8	3 . 2 4 4 5	1 2 . 3 5 1 6	7 . 8 2 2 8	1 . 6 0 9 6	6 . 8 4 0 4
5 3	5 . 4 0 0	6 . 8 5 1	0 . 7 6 4	5 . 5 0 2	6 . 4 7 2	1 1 . 9 9	1 0 . 2 8	3 . 7 2 6

	2	6	9	8	9	1 9	3 3	2
5 4	4 . 8 5 0 6	8 . 1 3 7 1	2 . 7 3 9 8	0 . 1 3 0 9	1 0 . 0 3 0 5	4 . 2 1 9 3	1 3 . 0 7 2 6	2 . 8 3 5 4
5 5	1 3 . 1 1 0 5	5 . 0 7 6 0	7 . 9 8 7 0	1 . 2 9 5 2	8 . 3 3 5 5	1 0 . 6 8 8 5	3 . 1 6 2 8	6 . 4 5 8 7
5 6	5 . 7 5 3 5	2 . 7 2 3 6	1 2 . 9 3 3 2	1 3 . 5 5 7 8	1 . 1 0 7 0	3 . 8 9 4 4	6 . 6 6 3 5	2 . 6 2 7 6
5 7	1 0 . 9 6 4 3	4 . 1 1 8 1	6 . 3 5 8 5	1 1 . 4 8 6 1	8 . 6 8 4 0	3 . 0 6 5 8	8 . 0 2 2 1	1 3 . 9 4 9 0
5 8	1 . 2 2 8 7	7 . 4 4 6 0	7 . 5 2 3 6	3 . 4 9 3 5	9 . 0 6 7 4	2 . 2 9 8 4	3 . 3 6 0 8	1 1 . 8 3 1 3
5 9	1 0 . 2 7 6 4	5 . 3 3 6 3	5 . 5 7 2 9	4 . 8 6 3 0	4 . 5 4 1 6	8 . 5 1 6 3	5 . 1 8 5 6	1 . 1 4 0 5
6 0	6 . 4 8 9 9	1 3 . 8 2 0 4	4 . 6 7 4 3	1 0 . 2 3 9 1	1 3 . 1 0 8 9	5 . 0 6 1 3	1 1 . 9 2 6 8	4 . 7 2 0 6

SUBJECT - 05

S l · N o ·	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	5 · 3 6 5 5	1 2 · 8 3 1 9	9 · 5 1 1 1	8 · 5 3 9 4	1 · 1 5 5 7	0 · 0 3 7 7	5 · 5 2 4 3	6 · 9 6 9 9
2	6 · 0 5 1 0	0 · 3 3 4 9	5 · 0 5 7 8	8 · 6 0 9 3	0 · 2 1 3 4	8 · 7 8 9 7	1 · 5 8 0 8	6 · 9 6 3 0
3	5 · 5 4 6 6	6 · 0 8 7 0	1 1 · 4 0 5 8	5 · 6 4 7 5	1 · 2 2 7 9	0 · 0 1 2 5	2 · 5 3 4 3	1 0 · 5 3 5 9
4	2 · 9 9 0 3	5 · 0 9 5 0	9 · 2 6 0 8	0 · 3 0 0 3	8 · 9 2 9 9	3 · 0 0 0 0	1 0 · 9 2 3 8	6 · 3 9 1 3
5	1 1 · 6 4 3 6	4 · 1 2 9 3	4 · 6 8 3 3	9 · 7 5 9 5	7 · 3 2 3 9	1 · 8 5 4 2	1 2 · 2 8 1 6	1 0 · 7 6 1 3
6	1 1 · 2 8 4 7	5 · 4 6 6 3	0 · 7 8 0 6	7 · 6 0 0 3	0 · 9 8 7 6	8 · 9 7 6 3	1 2 · 5 0 0 3	7 · 3 1 3 8
7	1 1 · 4 6	9 · 6 8 5	6 · 2 9 4	1 2 · 1 6	7 · 6 9 7	7 · 6 5 4	3 · 3 9 8	2 · 4 0 5

	3 7	1	5	5 8	9	3	3	1
8	7 . 5 8 7 4	3 . 4 0 7 5	0 . 7 6 5 6	4 . 1 8 3 0	7 . 5 5 7 0	4 . 8 8 2 1	7 . 5 2 3 0	3 . 8 0 5 7
9	2 . 2 9 1 0	5 . 0 8 7 4	7 . 1 3 4 1	5 . 2 9 0 4	3 . 8 8 5 5	3 . 3 7 9 0	3 . 5 5 2 2	9 . 2 7 9 9
1 0	7 . 7 8 8 2	1 2 . 2 8 9 6	4 . 4 3 0 9	6 . 6 9 6 3	8 . 1 7 4 8	4 . 8 5 3 7	1 2 . 2 6 0 4	8 . 1 7 4 9
1 1	3 . 7 8 2 6	5 . 0 9 7 8	1 . 3 4 5 5	0 . 5 0 0 8	4 . 6 1 5 9	9 . 4 8 4 5	3 . 9 1 0 8	0 . 4 2 6 7
1 2	1 1 . 6 3 4 1	1 0 . 7 4 6 3	4 . 0 4 7 3	1 3 . 9 8 7 8	4 . 3 9 7 8	6 . 7 9 8 6	3 . 8 2 0 5	6 . 0 4 2 9
1 3	8 . 9 7 0 0	7 . 6 1 1 9	6 . 0 6 1 5	1 0 . 3 7 7 2	1 2 . 5 1 1 1	1 2 . 4 9 8 8	1 2 . 2 7 5 6	8 . 4 9 7 3
1 4	2 . 0 0 7 7	2 . 6 5 3 7	3 . 1 7 3 5	3 . 0 8 4 7	9 . 7 2 2 8	1 1 . 5 0 8 6	5 . 2 7 8 8	8 . 0 1 9 4
1 5	9 . 5 6	6 . 4 5	1 2 . 5	1 3 . 9	1 3 . 8	4 . 6 5	0 . 4 8	6 . 0 0

	5 5	6 5	4 5 5	6 2 0	5 4 6	2 8	3 2	2 2
1 6	9 . 5 6 5 7	1 . 5 0 7 3	¹ 2 . 2 7 5 6	7 . 3 2 0 7	9 . 8 3 0 4	3 . 3 4 0 7	0 . 0 6 9 0	5 . 7 8 3 6
1 7	6 . 0 8 2 1	¹ 1 . 9 5 7 9	¹ 2 . 8 8 0 3	6 . 0 4 8 5	1 . 2 5 5 6	9 . 8 4 0 6	9 . 8 8 2 7	2 . 5 0 3 8
1 8	1 . 2 6 2 2	9 . 1 0 2 3	8 . 9 8 5 8	¹ 0 . 6 3 6 7	3 . 9 7 0 1	¹ 3 . 9 8 4 7	¹ 3 . 0 1 1 8	5 . 9 1 4 0
1 9	1 . 4 1 3 0	¹ 2 . 1 6 0 8	2 . 6 6 3 8	3 . 8 3 2 8	7 . 8 6 6 0	¹ 0 . 5 0 9 8	¹ 1 . 8 5 4 3	5 . 2 2 5 7
2 0	1 . 3 4 8 1	¹ 2 . 3 2 3 0	¹ 0 . 3 9 7 4	2 . 3 1 8 3	2 . 1 7 8 1	7 . 0 7 7 8	6 . 5 2 1 2	7 . 7 3 1 8
2 1	3 . 7 2 1 2	2 . 6 8 0 7	9 . 7 4 7 9	0 . 2 7 3 3	9 . 7 1 1 5	¹ 0 . 5 6 0 6	6 . 5 1 6 8	5 . 1 2 3 5
2 2	¹ 1 . 1 3 0 4	3 . 3 9 3 4	¹ 3 . 8 0 5 2	¹ 0 . 1 0 4 2	3 . 4 9 2 9	8 . 6 7 0 3	¹ 2 . 8 7 0 1	2 . 5 6 6 8
2	1	1	1	1	6	7	9	1

3	0 . 6 2 2 1	. 5 0 1 4	3 . 6 9 8 2	0 . 8 4 0 5	. 2 7 2 7	. 6 9 3 7	. 7 2 4 1	1 . 2 9 7 2
2 4	5 . 7 5 3 1	8 . 9 0 8 9	2 . 1 0 8 1	7 . 4 3 3 7	8 . 5 3 8 8	7 . 2 8 1 6	4 . 6 2 9 8	9 . 0 3 6 3
2 5	0 . 6 3 6 0	1 0 . 1 0 2 0	0 . 8 5 3 1	1 1 . 0 9 9 7	0 . 0 2 5 6	3 . 1 3 0 3	1 1 . 2 4 0 9	4 . 4 6 4 1
2 6	1 . 5 9 9 5	1 . 4 5 8 4	1 1 . 4 5 7 8	2 . 8 0 3 8	1 . 5 1 1 9	5 . 2 7 4 5	0 . 6 9 0 0	1 2 . 7 6 9 4
2 7	4 . 9 9 6 8	8 . 9 1 2 7	2 . 6 1 7 0	9 . 4 0 5 7	2 . 9 2 6 3	2 . 9 3 8 3	6 . 8 7 3 4	1 1 . 4 6 8 1
2 8	1 2 . 2 3 2 2	3 . 1 1 7 3	1 0 4 1 1	1 4 1 2 9	9 . 3 5 3 2	1 0 . 5 6 1 2	1 2 . 4 8 2 7	2 . 3 0 3 4
2 9	1 . 8 5 7 8	2 . 9 4 9 0	6 . 4 7 8 1	1 0 4 1 6	6 . 6 3 3 2	3 . 6 3 8 9	8 . 1 7 2 4	5 . 8 9 6 2
3 0	4 . 6 9 9 9	5 . 3 9 3 1	0 . 9 4 4 6	9 . 2 5 8 9	3 . 1 1 5 1	0 . 9 2 9 3	9 . 1 5 8 1	4 . 3 5 4 3
3	8	8	5	1	1	6	8	5

1	. 8 8 8 5	. 7 7 7 2	. 3 3 6 5	1 . 8 1 7 6	0 . 5 8 7 1	. 0 4 6 8	. 5 4 7 0	. 9 0 3 0
	7	1	7	7	1	7	4	1 3
3 2	. 6 2 3 7	. 8 0 0 1	. 4 3 1 8	. 5 9 7 6	. 1 7 1 2	. 8 1 5 3	. 3 3 0 8	. 4 7 1 0
	1	1	1	1	5	0	6	0
3 3	0 . 6 5 4 3	2 . 9 7 0 8	0 . 6 6 7 6	3 . 8 2 5 6	. 2 8 5 7	. 3 9 2 2	. 6 5 2 6	. 6 4 0 9
	7	4	4	1	3	5	1 2	1 0
3 4	. 0 8 4 0	. 0 3 0 2	. 0 8 3 7	. 7 6 2 5	. 8 4 4 5	. 8 2 9 6	. 5 4 7 1	. 0 8 2 0
	1	9	1	1	1	9	0	1 2
3 5	0 . 9 3 2 4	. 1 3 8 5	. 7 7 3 8	. 8 5 6 1	. 1 7 9 9	. 0 6 6 7	. 3 5 6 4	. 0 9 4 3
	2	6	2	8	6	1	5	1
3 6	. 4 5 0 1	. 9 8 2 2	. 7 1 9 6	. 3 4 2 6	. 8 0 3 8	. 6 9 2 1	. 9 1 9 4	. 8 2 9 6
	7	5	5	3	1	0	1 2	7 . 7 8 0 4
3 7	. 1 7 8 3	. 0 3 1 6	. 9 0 0 0	. 1 7 1 1	. 2 9 2 5	. 1 2 7 5	. 9 4 9 8	. 7 8 0 4
	5	9	4	1	1	7	4	7
3 8	. 8 6 0 8	. 9 6 6 9	. 1 8 3 3	. 1 9 5 8	. 2 7 6 1	. 0 8 7 9	. 5 7 2 5	. 6 6 1 0

					8			
3 9	1 . 8 2 3 6	1 1 . 9 1 5 5	1 0 . 6 3 8 4	1 1 . 2 8 5 4	3 . 2 3 8 4	1 . 5 7 7 8	1 2 . 7 9 8 3	1 1 . 9 2 3 4
4 0	1 . 7 4 8 9	1 1 . 2 7 9 6	3 . 6 0 3 9	4 . 5 6 6 9	0 . 7 7 9 9	2 . 0 0 6 8	7 . 5 7 4 8	6 . 2 2 3 6
4 1	1 . 6 8 2 6	6 . 5 3 2 9	3 . 6 3 7 2	9 . 5 9 2 7	8 . 1 9 8 9	1 0 . 0 2 0 0	0 . 1 3 3 4	2 . 7 1 2 9
4 2	1 0 . 5 7 9 9	0 . 9 1 3 3	3 . 6 8 8 4	7 . 3 8 8 9	1 . 5 4 3 6	9 . 9 8 1 6	9 . 6 4 2 2	6 . 9 5 5 2
4 3	8 . 5 4 9 0	1 2 . 3 8 8 1	9 . 4 9 5 9	1 0 . 0 9 2 1	2 . 2 6 2 8	1 0 . 2 4 5 4	1 2 . 8 8 3 1	7 . 1 2 7 5
4 4	6 . 3 9 0 5	4 . 1 3 2 2	2 . 3 2 4 8	8 . 3 5 6 3	2 . 0 3 2 9	6 . 9 1 5 0	8 . 7 1 8 3	2 . 7 7 3 6
4 5	5 . 9 1 5 1	0 . 5 9 7 8	6 . 9 5 7 4	1 2 . 4 6 9 3	4 . 7 7 0 6	5 . 6 4 8 6	1 . 1 4 8 6	9 . 4 3 0 0
4 6	9 . 4 5	3 . 3 0	7 . 5 1	1 3 . 2	8 . 0 5	4 . 7 1	2 . 8 0	6 . 5 5

	3 1	6 1	8 7	8 6 2	5 0	4 6	2 2	1 8
4 7	6 . 9 6 1 7	¹ 0 . 2 5 2 0	5 . 8 4 3 2	2 . 4 4 0 7	2 . 5 4 3 3	8 . 7 7 3 3	1 . 6 6 1 5	¹ 0 . 7 1 9 8
4 8	4 . 9 9 7 2	5 . 4 9 3 7	1 . 8 6 3 0	5 . 1 4 9 4	6 . 0 5 6 8	¹ 0 . 5 5 3 1	5 . 2 3 0 9	¹ 1 . 3 5 3 9
4 9	9 . 8 4 0 0	8 . 9 6 0 0	¹ 2 . 1 0 1 6	4 . 4 5 1 4	8 . 7 2 1 9	3 . 2 0 9 2	1 . 9 1 8 2	¹ 0 . 3 1 9 8
5 0	8 . 1 5 1 5	0 . 9 6 0 9	6 . 8 4 7 9	9 . 6 3 5 5	¹ 3 . 0 8 1 1	9 . 4 3 4 0	0 . 7 8 0 8	2 . 6 9 5 6
5 1	¹ 0 . 9 7 1 8	¹ 0 . 1 8 2 7	0 . 4 8 6 8	7 . 4 5 2 5	0 . 1 9 4 3	8 . 8 0 2 5	6 . 8 0 8 2	0 . 1 9 3 4
5 2	9 . 2 5 7 9	7 . 1 5 1 1	0 . 3 9 3 1	4 . 2 1 0 7	¹ 2 . 9 9 4 9	9 . 2 6 3 3	8 . 7 9 6 4	¹ 0 . 2 3 3 4
5 3	¹ 1 . 7 8 7 4	0 . 2 9 3 2	7 . 2 2 5 8	7 . 8 4 0 9	3 . 3 0 4 7	7 . 9 5 5 6	¹ 0 . 1 5 8 3	¹ 2 . 2 5 2 9
5	4	1	1	2	1	5	6	5

4	. 1 2 7 2	0 .7 7 2 5	3 .1 0 0 6	. 4 0 4 3	3 .3 6 3 3	. 5 0 4 9	. 8 8 1 1	. 5 0 7 9
5 5	8 .8 6 9 3	4 .6 4 8 8	7 .8 4 3 4	3 .7 4 0 9	4 .5 5 3 5	1 3 .6 6 3 9	7 .1 9 1 0	5 .6 8 2 7
5 6	5 .2 1 6 1	4 .3 6 5 0	2 .7 0 8 1	1 0 .8 3 1 7	8 .9 8 3 7	7 .8 2 6 9	9 .3 5 9 1	7 .8 0 8 2
5 7	0 .6 5 2 3	1 1 .7 0 5 5	1 3 .4 8 9 4	3 .7 1 3 3	2 .2 8 5 5	0 .3 6 5 6	2 .1 5 0 8	6 .3 2 0 5
5 8	1 .5 5 6 8	4 .2 1 1 6	5 3 3 5 7	0 .7 7 4 1	4 .2 4 9 1	2 .7 9 5 0	6 .2 5 6 3	3 .2 5 7 8
5 9	1 2 .5 6 3 9	7 .6 2 4 0	1 4 2 3 7	9 .2 7 5 0	1 2 4 1 1	3 .1 0 4 4	1 3 .8 1 9 2	5 .5 2 6 4
6 0	0 .3 8 8 3	5 .7 4 2 4	5 7 6 0 7	1 .2 9 1 8	9 .5 8 8 1	3 .9 5 5 5	1 1 .7 1 5 0	4 .5 9 9 2

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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 1 . 1 3 3 2	1 . 0 7 2 3	1 1 . 8 6 3 6	8 . 4 5 6	6 . 6 5 3 9	5 . 5 0 8 3	1 1 . 4 4 2 0	8 . 3 5 0 6
2	1 . 4 0 9 0	1 . 9 7 8 8	0 . 3 9 2 0	8 . 8 3 6 5	4 . 1 4 2 1	0 . 6 0 2 6	1 . 6 3 1 7	1 2 . 6 9 4 4
3	9 . 7 8 6 2	4 . 1 6 1 1	0 . 3 8 8 8	1 . 5 5 2 9	9 . 2 8 5 7	7 . 1 0 1 8	2 . 3 4 4 4	7 . 2 6 2 4
4	8 . 6 4 7 3	1 . 8 6 2 8	5 . 4 1 9 1	1 1 . 5 9 3 5	4 . 0 7 8 0	6 . 9 1 4 5	6 . 9 0 1 2	9 . 2 7 7 5
5	1 3 . 7 1 6 8	2 . 9 4 8 8	7 . 3 1 8 6	1 0 . 8 1 4 5	3 . 1 7 4 1	1 1 . 5 6 4 0	1 1 . 2 9 9 5	7 . 5 9 6 7
6	1 0 . 1 6 7 4	1 1 . 4 3 5 3	8 . 3 7 7 7	5 . 3 2 0 2	3 . 3 6 9 2	0 . 6 7 9 9	1 1 . 0 9 3 6	8 . 7 7 3 9
7	1 . 0 2 0	1 . 4 3 4	1 0 . 1 2	0 . 7 6 4	2 . 1 4 7	8 . 8 3 2	1 . 9 0 8	1 1 . 5 4

	0	4	3 0	4	7	3	1	0 8
8	1 1 . 6 5 6 8	2 . 4 5 9 0	1 0 . 8 8 1 5	1 0 . 8 6 9 6	1 2 . 7 1 6 0	6 . 3 3 0 5	2 . 5 0 8 6	1 2 . 3 3 0 9
9	0 . 6 2 1 8	6 . 8 3 5 3	1 2 . 4 2 7 6	6 . 3 8 3 5	1 . 0 0 7 4	4 . 5 6 2 6	3 . 9 8 9 9	3 . 3 0 4 1
1 0	1 1 . 9 8 1 4	9 . 2 7 4 7	2 . 3 3 6 4	0 . 7 5 2 1	4 . 6 6 8 7	1 1 . 5 1 9 4	7 . 3 6 1 3	3 . 8 9 4 1
1 1	1 2 . 9 4 5 7	7 . 2 3 3 8	1 0 . 5 6 4 3	1 1 . 6 6 3 3	3 . 3 8 4 4	7 . 6 6 7 1	5 . 2 9 7 3	1 2 . 4 0 8 6
1 2	0 . 8 0 5 7	1 . 5 6 5 7	3 . 3 8 0 6	3 . 0 0 2 9	3 . 3 8 8 1	3 . 8 2 2 8	6 . 6 8 4 7	5 . 5 9 2 8
1 3	6 . 0 4 6 9	3 . 4 7 0 1	6 . 6 4 1 8	9 . 8 8 5 8	4 . 8 3 4 0	3 . 7 4 0 2	3 . 4 5 8 4	5 . 8 2 7 8
1 4	4 . 5 3 1 6	3 . 3 3 4 1	3 . 0 1 0 3	4 . 0 5 9 5	1 1 . 6 5 4 1	1 2 . 5 8 0 4	1 1 . 4 3 6 9	1 . 8 3 2 7
1 5	3 . 9 5	1 2 . 4	9 . 0 0	3 . 7 1	6 . 8 9	5 . 9 7	1 1 . 9	6 . 1 9

	0 3	7 3 1	3 2	4 4	8 7	3 0	4 1 7	6 3
1 6	1 0 . 6 5 0 3	1 . 8 8 0 5	2 . 2 3 8 1	7 . 9 5 7 4	6 . 8 1 7 4	9 . 9 5 3 2	1 1 . 7 2 8 0	2 . 8 5 1 6
1 7	6 . 5 7 5 0	1 3 . 0 4 2 0	1 0 . 3 7 9 1	4 . 9 2 3 9	1 . 6 1 4 5	8 . 5 1 6 8	6 . 1 5 3 6	4 . 7 9 0 4
1 8	1 2 . 1 2 7 2	7 . 8 6 4 9	2 . 4 9 1	7 . 7 1 1	1 1 . 3 7 7 0	7 . 3 0 5 6	1 1 . 5 0 7 9	1 . 9 6 1 1
1 9	6 . 4 4 7 5	0 . 1 5 0 2	1 3 . 7 0 2 3	1 . 3 4 2 4	9 . 2 4 9 7	9 . 1 6 9 1	1 . 5 3 5 7	1 0 . 3 9 9 9
2 0	0 . 0 6 7 5	1 2 . 9 5 4 6	1 0 . 8 1 2 9	2 . 3 9 6 9	3 . 7 3 8 1	8 . 3 9 9 9	2 . 5 6 0 4	1 1 . 3 5 1 5
2 1	1 2 . 9 2 6 3	7 . 9 1 6 7	4 . 4 9 1 1	3 . 1 7 8 6	3 . 1 2 8 9	6 . 5 1 8 6	0 . 2 5 2 5	1 2 . 3 0 4 2
2 2	1 0 . 4 8 3 4	1 . 5 2 4 2	5 . 7 2 9 7	1 2 . 2 4 2 1	9 . 0 3 9 9	1 3 . 8 3 6 4	1 1 . 3 3 1 8	7 . 6 9 6 2
2	3	4	7	1	6	4	8	1

3	. 7 4 6 2	. 3 7 2 1	. 2 2 8 6	2 . 7 4 1 0	. 6 3 5 7	. 3 7 4 7	. 9 5 9 5	0 . 8 5 9 7
2 4	0 . 9 8 8 7	3 . 5 7 9 8	6 . 9 0 1 1	0 . 6 9 5 3	1 . 5 9 1 1	9 . 9 9 4 3	3 . 4 6 9 0	0 . 9 4 0 5
2 5	5 . 8 6 9 7	1 3 . 6 6 8 4	1 1 . 2 0 3 9	1 1 . 0 9 3 2	1 1 . 8 8 4 5	1 1 . 6 1 2 2	1 0 . 4 9 0 5	1 . 8 4 5 2
2 6	1 1 . 1 9 9 1	4 8 1 4 2	9 3 6 6 3	1 2 . 7 6 4 5	9 4 5 7 2	6 9 8 8 7	1 0 . 2 0 9 6	3 . 5 4 2 5
2 7	1 . 7 6 9 5	4 . 1 9 0 2	3 4 0 9 2	7 3 6 2 8	1 3 . 8 8 9 0	5 9 3 2 3	2 3 4 1 9	4 . 2 9 4 3
2 8	0 . 1 1 1 5	7 1 9 2 0	5 0 5 3 4	0 5 8 9 5	5 7 5 5 1	8 7 0 1 8	1 7 8 9 6	1 2 . 2 1 6 7
2 9	0 . 6 6 3 2	1 0 . 0 5 1 7	4 8 9 2 8	3 9 4 9 9	0 6 4 4 8	1 3 3 6 6	1 0 . 7 5 7 8	3 . 2 2 3 8
3 0	1 0 . 8 8 7	6 7 8 6 9	0 9 5 0 9	6 9 8 7 8	2 7 6 1 0	1 3 8 6 8	1 1 . 4 9	2 . 0 6 3 5

	9					3	8	
3 1	1 2 . 7 9 9 7	0 . 9 1 1 7	6 . 5 7 1 3	1 1 . 0 3 1 8	4 . 7 5 9 3	1 0 . 0 7 9 1	4 . 5 2 7 9	6 . 6 2 6 2
3 2	7 . 0 6 3 6	1 . 4 2 5 5	3 . 7 8 3 7	1 . 7 8 4 9	1 0 . 8 3 4 8	2 . 1 7 9 4	0 . 0 1 1 1	4 . 9 7 0 9
3 3	1 . 1 7 9 1	7 . 7 2 7 8	1 0 . 4 6 0 9	3 . 9 8 6 6	6 . 6 0 3 5	8 . 9 1 7 7	5 . 7 3 9 8	4 . 7 8 6 6
3 4	4 . 2 4 0 6	9 . 6 6 4 8	1 . 1 0 2 0	0 . 4 4 7 9	1 3 . 8 1 8 6	2 . 2 1 5 2	1 1 . 6 1 5 7	4 . 3 0 1 2
3 5	1 1 . 2 6 6 1	1 0 . 9 5 1 5	2 . 0 8 1 0	8 . 6 6 4 9	1 1 . 9 4 4 1	7 . 3 7 2 6	4 . 0 6 7 0	7 . 8 9 5 8
3 6	8 . 3 6 2 8	6 . 2 0 6 1	3 . 5 5 7 9	0 . 2 3 3 7	8 . 4 7 9 7	1 3 . 4 3 2 2	2 . 3 6 7 3	2 . 0 1 4 5
3 7	1 . 1 7 6 7	3 . 8 9 3 0	5 . 1 2 4 2	8 . 9 2 5 6	4 . 5 5 4 7	7 . 6 3 4 4	7 . 0 4 9 9	4 . 5 3 3 8
3 8	2 . 7 1	1 0 . 9	9 . 5 1	1 2 . 6	8 . 8 8	6 . 2 6	9 . 8 5	6 . 2 8

	6 3	1 2 3	3 9	2 5 6	5 9	1 9	3 0	3 9
3 9	1 . 1 4 6 5	2 . 1 9 8 1	9 . 0 2 0 9	5 . 4 1 9 8	9 . 7 0 1 1	1 1 . 8 4 8 9	2 . 1 8 5 3	6 . 8 9 8 6
4 0	1 3 . 1 7 0 6	5 . 7 2 0 6	1 2 . 5 2 3 1	5 . 9 3 8 4	1 0 . 3 0 6 3	1 0 . 6 7 7 3	1 . 5 9 8 0	5 . 0 0 4 3
4 1	9 . 1 8 5 0	3 . 8 7 7 8	3 . 6 0 7 5	1 3 . 0 3 2 8	2 . 1 2 7 4	6 . 8 4 0 4	1 1 . 5 1 5 6	6 . 0 6 7 5
4 2	3 . 2 1 1 9	1 1 . 1 9 5	1 2 . 2 0 2 3	4 . 5 8 0 2	9 . 8 0 6 1	4 . 7 2 4 7	9 . 2 9 7 4	9 . 3 9 8 5
4 3	8 . 7 1 2 4	8 . 2 5 4 6	1 0 . 1 9 9 1	6 . 9 2 7 0	5 . 7 3 7 2	7 . 9 3 7 7	8 . 2 4 2 9	3 . 5 1 5 3
4 4	9 . 8 5 4 8	1 0 . 7 1 3 5	3 . 8 3 1 2	0 . 5 6 7 3	1 0 . 1 0 3 3	1 1 . 8 9 6 4	0 . 2 6 5 4	4 . 0 8 4 4
4 5	1 0 . 9 1 7 1	1 2 . 3 1 5 4	3 . 3 0 2 8	5 . 0 7 0 3	0 . 8 8 5 8	9 . 4 5 3 4	9 . 1 4 3 0	3 . 2 0 3 0
4	7	1	6	1	0	7	1	7

6	. 5 8 3 2	. 8 8 3 6	. 2 2 4 7	1 . 7 0 2 7	. 0 2 0 3	. 3 1 8 2	. 4 7 1 7	. 9 1 6 5
4 7	1 2 . 7 7 9 7	1 0 . 6 1 6 3	4 . 4 1 3 2	1 1 . 6 0 6 3	4 . 9 4 4 9	0 . 6 0 6 1	0 . 1 9 4 0	7 . 4 3 4 2
4 8	7 . 7 3 8 6	4 . 7 3 0 1	1 0 . 5 3 3 5	1 0 . 8 5 3 8	7 . 3 8 3 4	1 1 . 8 0 6 9	1 1 . 4 7 6 9	0 . 6 4 9 9
4 9	1 3 . 2 4 9 3	4 . 2 4 7 7	7 . 1 6 6 7	1 1 . 8 8 1 6	1 0 . 4 8 4 5	1 3 . 5 9 3 8	9 . 3 2 2 6	8 . 7 6 0 8
5 0	1 2 . 1 3 1 9	0 . 7 5 3 4	1 . 8 6 0 1	6 . 5 7 4 6	2 . 1 6 5 2	1 0 . 4 3 1 8	1 2 . 4 1 4 8	5 . 3 4 7 3
5 1	1 1 . 4 7 6 2	1 1 . 7 2 0 6	0 . 8 6 4 7	0 . 8 4 8 9	1 . 4 4 2 2	7 . 3 6 8 2	1 2 . 5 2 7 9	3 . 1 8 2 4
5 2	9 . 5 6 4 0	7 . 7 1 1 2	4 . 8 7 2 1	0 . 1 6 6 5	7 . 7 5 7 6	2 . 9 0 4 0	1 0 . 5 0 2 0	1 0 . 1 3 8 1
5 3	4 . 1 5 0	1 . 4 8 4	5 . 0 4 6	6 . 5 3 3	1 3 . 3 9	1 . 6 3 8	4 . 7 6 5	6 . 8 4 9

	9	4	1	3	5 1	4	7	7
5 4	1 2 . 7 0 5 0	6 . 3 2 6 8	1 3 . 0 2 6 0	1 0 . 6 7 2 8	4 . 1 0 7 6	1 2 . 9 0 7 8	2 . 8 0 6 0	8 . 7 5 0 5
5 5	4 . 9 1 9 0	1 3 . 0 4 8 4	3 . 7 7 6 9	6 . 6 9 8 4	9 . 2 4 0 1	4 . 2 4 5 4	1 2 . 8 2 7 3	1 2 . 4 1 6 3
5 6	5 . 1 6 8 0	8 . 6 2 2 1	0 . 4 8 2 8	6 . 7 4 8 8	3 . 7 8 0 4	1 . 9 1 1 7	5 . 3 7 9 5	0 . 8 5 0 8
5 7	1 1 . 1 4 9 5	5 . 4 7 9	5 . 2 1 5 8	8 . 7 4 6 3	3 . 1 2 8 0	8 . 5 1 8 5	4 . 1 9 2 6	2 . 8 8 4 0
5 8	4 . 4 2 1 5	9 . 1 1 9 6	1 2 . 9 9 6 9	3 . 8 8 0 5	3 . 0 5 8 5	1 1 . 2 1 3 2	8 . 2 0 7 2	6 . 1 3 0 5
5 9	1 0 . 2 6 1 0	8 . 3 4 4 0	1 2 . 2 0 9 7	4 . 3 7 7 5	6 . 7 3 7 2	0 . 1 0 2 3	1 2 . 9 1 9 2	7 . 7 4 8 7
6 0	1 3 . 9 5 3 0	9 . 9 9 8 7	8 . 9 1 0 3	1 . 5 6 5 9	4 . 3 5 5 8	1 . 5 4 5 2	9 . 6 6 4 3	9 . 4 0 0 1

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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	7 . 2 9 5 9	1 0 . 8 0 9 4	9 . 2 3 3 0	7 . 6 4 5 7	3 . 8 7 6 4	2 . 5 2 3 1	5 . 1 9 5 2	4 . 1 8 8 8
2	1 0 . 9 8 4 4	1 2 . 3 7 4 6	4 . 7 9 1 7	0 . 3 8 6 4	1 2 . 1 6 3 5	9 . 5 2 9 6	6 . 3 0 8 2	1 . 6 5 9 8
3	1 0 . 0 4 0 5	4 . 0 7 5 0	9 . 1 1 8 3	6 . 1 0 0 1	0 . 2 4 0 8	1 . 2 1 3 4	1 0 . 6 1 0 5	7 . 1 0 0 6
4	5 . 6 1 4 6	2 . 7 0 5 2	1 0 . 9 0 4 5	1 . 2 7 4 3	1 0 . 8 8 6 4	0 . 9 7 1 4	9 . 4 5 7 3	9 . 8 6 5 8
5	6 . 6 3 8 8	6 . 9 1 7 0	8 . 4 8 3 4	5 . 3 9 4 9	1 . 6 1 4 9	4 . 0 1 3 1	1 2 . 9 5 7 9	4 . 8 1 7 0
6	9 . 7 4 9 7	1 2 . 5 0 3 9	9 . 5 2 7 9	1 3 . 9 2 0 2	3 . 0 8 5 0	8 . 2 9 7 7	7 . 5 9 1 4	3 . 3 5 5 9
7	4 . 3	7 . 8	1 . 5	1 . 4	2 . 5	1 2 .	1 0 .	9 . 6

	4 7 3	0 2 0	9 0 2	0 3 7	9 6 1	2 0 3 4	8 9 3 6	6 4 7
8	1 2 . 8 7 7 2	3 . 4 8 5 9	0 . 7 0 0 7	0 . 6 4 5 5	1 0 . 7 1 1 7	2 . 7 5 9 6	8 . 1 7 6 7	1 1 . 1 4 3 0
9	1 0 . 0 2 4 0	2 . 2 4 7 8	5 . 8 4 4 6	4 . 0 4 4 3	6 . 4 0 6 3	8 . 1 9 0 5	4 . 9 3 7 5	1 3 . 8 6 7 6
1 0	7 . 0 8 7 3	2 . 1 6 8 7	9 . 2 8 1 5	7 . 8 1 2 0	1 0 . 6 1 3 4	1 . 0 5 0 9	7 . 3 0 4 9	1 2 . 1 1 6 2
1 1	1 0 . 2 4 1 8	3 . 9 1 0 1	1 0 . 9 4 4 7	1 3 . 7 7 1 2	1 . 6 6 2 7	4 . 7 0 5 5	1 0 . 2 2 2 6	8 . 3 5 0 2
1 2	1 0 . 8 1 1 6	0 . 6 6 9 9	1 2 . 6 6 6 5	1 . 4 2 4 8	6 . 8 1 8 5	9 . 1 4 8 0	1 0 . 8 3 4 0	2 . 6 9 3 4
1 3	3 . 5 9 0 1	0 . 5 2 8 3	1 3 . 0 5 6 0	5 . 5 1 2	8 . 1 4 2 2	1 3 . 5 4 1 3	8 . 3 1 4 6	6 . 5 7 6 2
1 4	3 . 1 0 2 6	1 2 . 2 3 5 1	0 . 6 3 5 9	0 . 8 0 7 8	7 . 0 0 9 0	3 . 3 2 5 0	4 . 1 4 9 6	0 . 4 2 0 6

1 5	2 . 5 0 0 5	5 . 6 6 6 8	5 . 0 9 2 5	5 . 8 9 0 6	1 0 . 2 2 4 5	4 . 0 7 3 4	1 0 . 0 3 2 6	9 . 2 8 3 8
1 6	0 . 7 1 4 2	1 1 . 5 3 3 6	0 . 1 0 1 1	1 0 . 5 0 5 7	1 0 . 6 7 5 8	8 . 5 2 7 1	5 . 1 5 7 0	1 1 . 6 7 6 8
1 7	3 . 8 2 1 9	2 . 2 7 9 0	1 . 9 6 8 2	7 . 8 3 2 3	1 2 . 3 8 0 2	1 1 . 3 2 6 9	1 2 . 1 9 8 3	5 . 9 1 2 9
1 8	1 0 . 1 5 0 2	3 . 4 2 5 4	5 . 2 6 0 8	7 . 5 4 3 3	1 1 . 3 4 4 9	1 0 . 8 9 7 6	1 3 . 6 6 9 9	1 3 . 7 9 3 2
1 9	4 . 3 1 2 3	3 . 8 5 1 6	6 . 3 5 4 2	7 . 6 2 9 8	4 . 8 3 2 6	0 . 4 6 1 9	9 . 4 1 4 8	0 . 4 3 5 8
2 0	2 . 8 4 4 9	3 . 4 6 5 6	2 . 2 3 2 4	1 2 . 7 2 5 0	3 . 1 4 5 6	8 . 5 2 3 0	1 0 . 4 9 0 9	6 . 1 9 0 9
2 1	0 . 1 3 9 1	4 . 7 2 8 1	0 . 1 1 6 2	1 1 . 8 7 6 2	9 . 2 2 5 8	3 . 4 2 8 3	2 . 5 4 7 6	1 1 . 2 9 5 7
2 2	4 . 0 0 6	1 0 . 9 8	2 . 0 9 2	1 . 0 4 7	3 . 8 9 9	1 1 . 7 8	4 . 7 1 2	6 . 4 0 1

	8	0 2	8	2	5	9 0	9	8
2 3	1 1 . 6 4 8 6	4 . 2 2 0 3	6 . 4 1 8 3	7 . 4 2 3 6	1 3 . 6 4 8 7	6 . 2 1 2 6	8 . 8 5 1 2	1 . 4 1 4 7
2 4	2 . 4 6 7 9	9 . 7 4 0 7	8 . 7 3 3 4	1 2 . 3 2 4 8	1 1 . 0 9 9 2	1 . 3 9 4 5	1 2 . 2 1 0 6	0 . 5 3 1 6
2 5	1 0 . 9 1 4 5	1 3 . 9 1 0 2	2 . 2 3 2 9	1 2 . 9 3 2 3	5 . 5 4 6 8	0 . 8 5 0 8	5 . 1 4 4 1	9 . 9 1 7 7
2 6	0 . 1 1 5 5	5 . 5 6 2 4	4 . 6 0 0 4	1 0 . 0 6 3 5	7 . 1 6 4 5	9 . 9 6 6 2	1 2 . 6 5 3 7	1 1 . 2 4 8 3
2 7	9 . 4 1 7 4	3 . 2 2 6 0	3 . 2 8 7 1	0 . 4 2 2 0	8 . 9 0 4 7	2 . 3 8 4 6	7 . 6 6 8 0	4 . 4 9 7 2
2 8	1 2 . 6 0 0 5	6 . 7 2 8 0	0 . 5 2 9 5	1 . 5 6 5 8	6 . 5 6 4 1	2 . 6 5 3 9	0 . 4 1 9 2	1 2 . 9 8 6 3
2 9	7 . 7 1 7 1	5 . 0 7 4 7	1 . 4 9 4 7	8 . 2 4 2 2	1 2 . 9 2 0 1	7 . 2 8 9 6	1 2 . 2 3 3 4	8 . 1 4 5 1
3 0	6 . 4	8 . 5	4 . 8	7 . 1	1 . 2	1 1 .	5 . 2	8 . 4

	6 9 4	0 6 1	0 2 6	5 9 7	0 2 5	9 8 0 2	7 9 4	0 7 5
3 1	1 2 . 5 0 4 0	1 3 . 7 8 4 3	1 1 . 0 0 6 6	3 . 0 1 4 7	5 . 1 0 8 9	6 . 4 6 4 9	1 2 . 6 4 1 2	3 . 4 9 8 5
3 2	1 0 . 6 2 5 5	4 . 8 2 0 6	1 2 . 6 5 0 7	8 . 5 4 3 9	7 . 2 1 0 1	1 2 . 7 8 1 0	6 . 1 6 1 9	6 . 9 5 3 5
3 3	1 0 . 6 2 5 6	1 0 . 4 2 1 5	1 1 . 7 6 5 6	2 . 7 8 0 7	3 . 7 6 7 0	3 . 1 9 9 2	1 2 . 5 3 6 5	1 0 . 8 0 3 4
3 4	1 . 4 4 8 1	8 . 4 5 8 8	9 . 1 6 1 6	0 . 8 7 8 5	5 . 0 3 1 9	1 0 . 6 2 9 1	1 . 8 4 0 4	3 . 9 4 5 8
3 5	1 . 2 0 9 4	1 0 . 6 6 9 1	3 . 7 0 0 6	4 . 5 8 0 6	2 . 5 9 6 5	1 . 2 7 3 1	1 2 . 9 3 1 0	1 1 . 9 5 1 3
3 6	4 . 3 4 0 6	0 . 4 4 2 5	8 . 8 8 7 7	2 . 5 0 6 6	3 . 5 0 4 4	1 2 . 5 8 0 6	3 . 1 4 3 6	1 3 . 7 3 4 2
3 7	9 . 2 7 0 2	8 . 4 1 1 7	7 . 5 2 3 7	1 . 0 3 1 5	4 . 6 4 7 1	9 . 5 7 1 7	3 . 2 0 6 8	1 . 3 0 5 7
3	1	1	1	0	0	4	0	1

8	1 . 3 9 6 5	. 8 5 7 2	. 7 0 0 8	. 6 1 7 3	. 2 7 2 9	. 5 5 3 8	. 9 7 1 7	0 . 4 4 0 9
3 9	1 0 . 7 3 6 0	3 . 1 5 1 5	4 . 4 2 6 5	8 . 9 2 1 4	1 1 . 0 5 1 5	4 . 3 7 8 3	1 3 . 2 6 0 2	3 . 1 8 0 5
4 0	1 2 . 6 7 1 1	5 . 7 0 9 3	0 . 9 8 6 7	1 1 . 0 3 6 9	1 2 . 5 0 9 8	1 . 1 4 7 0	1 1 . 5 7 8 0	8 . 6 7 6 7
4 1	1 . 5 1 1 3	1 2 . 3 8 4 5	1 0 . 0 8 3 3	1 3 . 0 5 2 2	8 . 9 7 7 9	5 . 3 7 2 2	7 . 3 4 2 0	4 . 8 2 5 3
4 2	0 . 9 4 9 0	8 . 1 0 4 1	3 . 2 3 2 6	5 . 8 8 9 6	8 . 4 3 3 5	1 . 7 9 5	5 . 8 6 0 6	2 . 7 0 6 1
4 3	3 . 4 4 3 1	8 . 4 3 1 8	1 . 7 5 1 3	0 . 8 7 4 5	1 0 . 2 5 8 5	3 . 4 7 1 5	1 1 . 5 6 2 9	1 3 . 8 7 4 4
4 4	1 . 6 9 1 2	9 . 6 4 3 6	8 . 1 7 7 1	6 . 7 4 6 9	5 . 5 4 5 7	6 . 7 6 7 7	9 . 3 1 2 2	0 . 7 3 3 9
4 5	1 0 . 5 4 8 1	2 . 9 6 9 4	1 1 . 6 1 1 4	1 2 . 2 8 9 9	9 . 0 6 8 0	4 . 9 0 8 7	0 . 4 7 0 6	3 . 6 4 5 2

4 6	0 . 7 8 2 1	9 . 5 5 6 4	8 . 4 5 8 9	3 . 8 0 2 8	1 . 0 5 8 6	3 . 9 2 3 1	0 . 0 5 1 5	7 . 4 4 1 4
4 7	4 . 6 7 5 7	8 . 2 0 5 1	1 2 . 9 4 5 1	1 . 6 6 0 9	3 . 8 6 0 8	5 . 0 4 6 2	5 . 7 7 5 8	0 . 4 4 3 7
4 8	7 . 5 8 0 0	7 . 3 6 6 6	9 . 1 1 2 1	1 . 2 7 4 2	1 2 . 8 3 8 9	6 . 5 4 6 6	4 . 9 5 9 0	3 . 9 9 2 9
4 9	2 . 1 6 8 6	4 . 4 7 2 8	0 . 5 4 4 9	1 2 . 6 2 7 4	1 0 . 0 4 5 2	0 . 0 8 2 5	9 . 5 2 3 2	6 . 9 6 4 5
5 0	8 . 5 4 2 3	1 3 . 4 1 5 3	7 . 0 1 4 9	6 . 0 6 8 1	1 . 3 2 5 6	5 . 8 3 1 6	9 . 6 1 3 0	1 1 . 0 1 2 0
5 1	1 3 . 4 2 2 3	2 . 5 8 7 9	1 . 9 0 5 1	1 2 . 2 4 7 7	9 . 2 2 6 2	1 3 . 1 1 7 2	1 . 8 0 1 2	1 1 . 7 3 6 7
5 2	1 . 1 8 8 3	1 1 . 1 4 1 4	8 . 6 5 4 4	0 . 0 7 8 3	2 . 8 2 2 1	3 . 8 1 0 7	3 . 4 0 1 6	5 . 8 4 1 7
5 3	5 . 7 8 4	1 3 . 8 4	1 2 . 5 3	3 . 4 1 8	1 0 . 2 2	1 . 1 4 9	1 0 . 2 0	4 . 8 4 7

	7	0 8	3 1	9	3 8	7	3 4	8
5 4	6 . 3 8 1 5	1 2 . 7 5 6 5	8 . 1 0 1 9	3 . 6 9 8 6	0 . 0 2 1 7	6 . 9 0 3 8	1 . 6 1 9 6	1 3 . 6 7 8 6
5 5	8 . 4 9 9 7	3 . 2 8 9 6	2 . 4 5 6 7	4 . 1 9 5 4	1 1 . 3 5 9 9	8 . 8 2 9 5	9 . 6 5 8 4	3 . 5 5 9 5
5 6	4 . 8 4 5 2	3 . 0 5 1 2	7 . 4 9 2 4	0 . 9 0 1 6	0 . 3 6 6 6	5 . 9 0 6 0	1 2 . 6 2 5 4	5 . 5 6 9 3
5 7	3 . 2 9 6 5	3 . 5 9 7 1	6 . 6 1 2 2	6 . 6 9 4 6	0 . 2 0 8 8	0 . 0 5 1 7	1 3 . 5 8 2 6	1 . 3 3 3 1
5 8	1 0 . 7 4 9 5	1 0 . 1 1 6 4	1 0 . 0 9 7 9	1 2 . 6 6 7 7	9 . 7 8 9 8	3 . 6 1 5 1	1 2 . 8 4 1 0	9 . 0 3 4 5
5 9	2 . 4 9 1 5	2 . 5 1 7 5	3 . 7 3 7 4	1 1 . 0 9 7 1	1 . 1 4 1 8	1 0 . 6 0 7 8	6 . 4 5 0 2	3 . 7 7 6 4
6 0	8 . 6 2 9 0	1 0 . 5 3 2 8	0 . 4 3 8 6	0 . 7 4 7 0	1 . 1 0 4 3	2 . 8 5 8 7	0 . 7 2 1 3	7 . 9 8 8 1

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Figure – 13 / 02

S	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
l	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
o								
.								

1	9 . 1 2 8 3	3 . 6 4 8 6	0 . 3 1 0 9	1 2 . 4 4 1 6	1 3 . 2 8 3 0	6 . 1 5 1 2	2 . 7 5 2 5	7 . 5 9 7 9
2	0 . 5 4 9 5	0 . 2 6 0 2	1 3 . 7 1 1 3	3 . 9 7 4 6	1 . 8 3 5 4	9 . 3 4 8 6	9 . 5 2 0 5	1 2 . 3 5 5 0
3	6 . 1 1 7 7	2 . 7 2 2 9	1 2 . 8 1 4 5	1 0 . 1 0 7 4	4 . 1 8 6 7	7 . 0 6 3 2	3 . 9 8 0 6	2 . 9 4 0 5
4	8 . 0 4 1 3	1 1 . 4 0 0 7	6 . 3 4 2 1	1 1 . 4 4 3 3	1 1 . 9 3 4 9	5 . 2 5 0 5	4 . 5 4 6 2	8 . 1 7 4 8
5	2 . 0 2 0 1	8 . 1 0 4 2	7 . 8 1 0 6	1 0 . 1 2 7 3	1 0 . 4 0 4 0	2 . 5 9 1 2	7 . 5 1 2 0	1 . 4 3 8 0
6	1 1 . 5 4 3 0	8 . 9 4 8 1	6 . 0 3 0 6	1 3 . 4 9 4 2	1 0 . 5 0 4 6	5 . 3 7 4 3	2 . 0 8 4 8	5 . 8 9 2 0
7	9 . 3 2 9 7	3 . 4 7 5 8	1 . 0 6 6 6	9 . 1 5 8 7	5 . 2 7 0 4	1 . 7 0 8 8	1 . 6 3 6 8	1 . 9 5 2 8
8	1 1 . 3 7	6 . 9 6 1	2 . 4 8 5	1 0 . 7 6	4 . 3 3 7	2 . 5 1 9	2 . 7 9 3	8 . 5 9 4

	4 3	6	0	7 4	0	9	8	0
9	6 .0 0 1 2	1 2 .3 9 9 2	1 2 .6 3 5 3	1 2 .6 1 2 5	1 1 .6 2 9 8	4 .4 1 5 5	6 .2 2 4 0	1 0 .3 3 7 3
1 0	1 1 .5 5 9 0	7 .2 2 8 6	1 0 .0 5 6 7	7 .5 2 8 0	0 .3 4 6 3	3 .1 1 2 3	7 .4 5 6 6	1 2 .1 6 2 0
1 1	7 .9 4 1 7	5 .7 7 8 9	7 .0 8 7 3	1 2 .8 9 3 7	3 .9 7 3 3	0 .7 4 0 1	2 .3 4 6 5	2 .3 3 7 9
1 2	7 .6 0 7 4	4 .5 0 7 1	2 .8 9 9 6	1 1 .0 0 9 5 9	1 0 .3 9 1 2	1 3 0 0 1 0	1 .9 0 4 3	8 .0 4 5 7
1 3	0 .2 5 3 9	1 1 .2 4 2 4	7 .4 0 2 6	6 .2 5 4 8	1 0 .0 1 3 5	1 0 .5 2 0 1	1 0 .6 1 2 9	8 .1 9 0 8
1 4	3 .9 6 0 9	1 2 .0 8 7 7	1 3 .9 7 6 5	0 .1 9 8 7	8 .8 9 7	1 2 .8 5 2 1	8 .0 8 8 4	5 .7 4 6 3
1 5	5 .9 0 2 2	9 .7 9 9 1	2 .5 5 8 8	4 .5 0 8 6	5 .4 5 0 4	2 .0 7 0 8	4 .0 9 8 8	3 .6 1 2 0
1 6	3 .5	1 2 .0	2 .0	1 .0	6 1	1 1	6 3	1 2

	5 2 5	0 2 5 3	4 5 6	3 0 4	4 1 8	7 6 1	7 4 6	9 7 6
1 7	5 . 0 3 0 6	0 . 9 3 5 9	3 . 3 5 8 3	5 . 3 3 3 0	9 . 9 9 5 8	5 . 1 7 9 8	8 . 6 4 3 4	2 . 3 0 0 0
1 8	1 0 . 6 7 4 1	1 1 . 9 8 0 2	1 0 . 0 5 8 7	7 . 7 5 9 6	0 . 9 8 1 2	4 . 2 7 4 3	1 0 . 5 0 3 6	4 . 0 7 8 9
1 9	7 . 9 0 6 5	1 . 5 4 4 0	1 0 . 5 4 8 1	3 . 8 1 5 4	5 . 6 4 6 8	7 . 1 1 9 2	8 . 2 0 7 8	1 0 . 7 0 5 8
2 0	7 . 5 1 3 3	1 3 . 4 4 1 1	0 . 2 7 7 1	6 . 4 7 6 7	2 . 0 3 3 9	1 2 . 9 6 6 3	1 2 . 4 0 9 8	9 . 9 5 6 2
2 1	6 . 7 3 7 8	3 . 2 0 9 9	6 . 6 0 0 1	1 2 . 1 0 9 8	9 . 0 7 1 9	1 1 . 9 5 2 2	0 . 4 4 2 0	1 0 . 8 2 2 7
2 2	3 . 8 9 8 4	6 . 9 9 8 2	8 . 3 8 5 8	7 . 9 2 8 8	0 . 7 1 8 6	6 . 6 2 1 1	7 . 6 7 8 6	2 . 6 2 6 9
2 3	6 . 4 3 9 4	2 . 8 8 0 4	1 1 . 3 1 6 9	5 . 2 6 2 6	5 . 1 1 7 3	8 . 8 1 2 6	7 . 4 7 7 2	1 1 . 2 0 0 9
2 4	5 . .	3 . .	2 . .	8 . .	1 1 .	1 0	0 .	7 .

	1 1 5 2	5 4 7 6	4 7 9 3	3 2 6 0	. 7 6 3 9	. 1 0 4 4	5 9 9 2	6 1 1 4
2 5	4 .br/>5 0 4 3	8 .br/>1 8 7 6	6 .br/>2 5 8 7	6 .br/>2 6 5 8	3 .br/>3 5 5 3	5 .br/>6 0 2 1	0 .br/>4 7 3 1	0 .br/>2 1 0 3
2 6	2 .br/>8 3 6 4	1 1 .br/>0 8 7 5	8 .br/>3 3 5 3	8 .br/>1 7 5 2	5 .br/>6 5 2 4	9 .br/>5 5 0 2	5 .br/>0 5 0 2	7 .br/>4 7 9 3
2 7	8 .br/>7 7 2 3	1 3 .br/>3 1 2 6	1 0 .br/>8 2 8 4	4 .br/>5 8 0 3	1 .br/>8 6 4 4	1 2 .br/>9 0 9 2	1 0 .br/>1 0 3 3	1 3 .br/>0 0 4 6
2 8	3 .br/>6 7 9 2	1 0 .br/>6 3 5 4	7 .br/>9 3 3 8	1 1 .br/>9 0 7 4	5 .br/>1 6 9 2	1 1 .br/>0 3 8 4	1 1 .br/>3 1 1 1	0 .br/>4 8 2 6
2 9	1 .br/>5 1 0 8	1 0 .br/>0 8 1 4	3 .br/>5 5 2 5 4	1 1 .br/>6 3 4 3	1 .br/>0 6 5 4	7 .br/>0 4 3 4	7 .br/>5 7 6 6	1 2 .br/>9 5 7 3
3 0	1 1 .br/>5 3 4 8	1 2 .br/>0 5 3 3	1 3 .br/>2 1 2 8	1 0 .br/>2 0 0 7	5 .br/>9 4 1 5	0 .br/>7 7 5 6	4 .br/>7 5 9 8	5 .br/>0 5 7 4
3 1	0 .br/>4 1 0 1	8 .br/>9 6 2 1	1 3 .br/>9 6 2 3	0 .br/>1 0 0 1	8 .br/>7 3 5 3	0 .br/>7 6 9 0	1 0 .br/>3 2 6 6	9 .br/>7 2 3 0

3 2	1 2 . 7 9 5 4	0 . 7 0 7 3	2 . 4 5 7 1	1 0 . 2 1 6 6	6 . 7 9 1 6 6	0 . 1 2 6 8	1 0 . 0 2 6 2	1 0 . 3 9 5 8
3 3	9 . 6 5 0 3	0 . 6 1 2 6	5 . 3 5 1 9	1 0 . 2 1 8 3	1 0 . 6 3 3 2	9 . 2 4 2 1	5 . 4 5 7 1	5 . 6 6 4 3
3 4	3 . 3 0 5 6	7 . 0 2 4 6	3 . 7 1 9 7	1 3 . 1 4 1 8	1 3 . 9 9 1 6	9 . 5 1 0 2	1 . 6 7 3 9	3 . 6 8 4 2
3 5	7 . 3 0 2 5	7 . 3 0 6 1	1 2 . 7 6 6 8	1 2 . 8 8 8 3	9 . 5 3 9 8	9 . 9 0 0 2	5 . 3 3 8 3	1 2 . 3 8 2 9
3 6	1 1 . 9 6 7 5	2 . 6 8 6 6	0 . 1 2 2 7	1 0 . 7 8 5 6	1 . 8 1 8 6	4 . 5 9 5 3	5 . 4 2 6 0	1 0 . 1 2 7 7
3 7	1 . 9 9 9 6	1 . 8 9 7 9	9 . 3 1 3 2	3 . 9 0 2 0	3 . 0 4 5 5	1 1 . 0 2 5 3	7 . 5 1 4 4	0 . 6 8 6 2
3 8	1 . 8 0 9 6	6 . 5 7 9 8	4 . 5 2 1 1	9 . 1 5 8 5	0 . 5 6 7 1	1 . 5 0 1 4	4 . 7 7 9 1	1 2 . 5 2 1 5
3 9	4 . 6 3	4 . 6 9	1 0 . 6	8 . 2 1	1 1 . 5	3 . 2 2	8 . 3 7	3 . 0 8

	0 5	9 0	8 4 2	6 7	7 4 7	2 9	6 9	1 6
4 0	9 . 2 4 4 4	6 . 4 0 8 9	1 . 8 3 1 1	4 . 2 1 6 9	7 . 0 2 2 6	1 2 . 8 6 1 2	5 . 5 9 9 3	1 2 . 8 2 2 8
4 1	3 . 0 0 7 9	8 . 3 2 6 9	9 . 0 0 3 3	9 . 2 6 7 7	0 . 1 6 3 9	2 . 0 6 1 2	8 . 2 8 7 9	1 2 . 1 0 4 4
4 2	1 1 . 3 2 3 5	0 . 5 2 2 1	2 . 7 9 0 0	8 . 2 1 6 6	1 . 4 3 3 6	1 2 . 7 1 8 7	2 . 7 2 4 2	7 . 4 2 6 8
4 3	2 . 9 3 0 9	8 . 7 4 8 1	7 . 6 6 0 6	7 . 5 7 2 6	5 . 4 9 6 8	1 0 . 4 8 4 9	8 . 7 9 9 5	1 0 . 7 8 3 5
4 4	8 . 2 5 4 4	9 . 3 8 7 3	0 . 9 7 2 2	9 . 4 4 9 2	1 . 5 7 8 3	3 . 0 9 6 0	1 . 4 5 0 3	3 . 5 5 0 2
4 5	5 . 4 2 4 8	4 . 6 0 6 8	0 . 8 9 2 1	3 . 7 1 6 3	2 . 9 5 1 3	0 . 5 3 9 7	1 0 . 8 5 8 4	1 3 . 7 0 0 7
4 6	4 . 0 5 6 1	8 . 6 6 1 0	7 . 8 6 1 1	1 . 2 5 5	1 2 . 9 9 5 7	2 . 7 1 9 2	4 . 1 6 5 4	6 . 2 7 5 1
4 7	3 . 0	1 0	1 0	1 3	1 .	2 .	5 .	1 1

	6 5 4 8	. 1 2 4 3	. 6 9 7 6	. 7 6 4 1	1 3 2 1	6 5 8 4	4 9 0 8	. 6 8 7 0
4 8	1 0 .br/>6 5 7 2	1 2 .br/>1 1 7 3	1 2 .br/>8 2 3 3	1 0 .br/>4 3 0 5	1 .br/>7 4 3 1	2 .br/>2 0 5 7	7 .br/>3 4 2 6	6 .br/>7 8 4 6
4 9	1 .br/>7 4 0 8	1 2 .br/>5 9 3 1	2 .br/>7 5 2 4	6 .br/>3 6 4 0	2 .br/>0 6 9 1	6 .br/>2 3 8 3	0 .br/>6 4 3 0	9 .br/>2 8 8 3
5 0	3 .br/>2 5 8 2	3 .br/>3 8 1 5	1 1 .br/>0 5 1 7	9 .br/>2 7 1 9	9 .br/>6 3 1 9	4 .br/>0 9 4 6	7 .br/>4 1 8 4	8 .br/>0 7 3 6
5 1	2 .br/>4 0 6 8	4 .br/>8 5 9 6	6 .br/>0 7 6 9	0 .br/>1 7 8 6	9 .br/>6 8 3 7	1 0 .br/>3 2 7 8	4 .br/>7 2 3 9	5 .br/>7 9 0 4
5 2	5 .br/>2 9 4 5	1 1 .br/>9 1 2 6	3 .br/>5 4 7 0	9 .br/>6 4 4 4	8 .br/>8 3 8 3	9 .br/>3 8 6 8	1 0 .br/>8 5 3 8	3 .br/>3 9 1 5
5 3	1 2 .br/>5 8 8 6	1 2 .br/>1 4 4 6	3 .br/>6 0 0 6	2 .br/>3 5 3 9	5 .br/>7 5 5 8	2 .br/>5 8 7 9	0 .br/>1 1 8 8	4 .br/>2 7 4 6
5 4	1 1 .br/>6 8 3	1 2 .br/>4 8 9	1 2 .br/>3 1 6	1 0 .br/>0 1 9	1 2 .br/>1 7 4	1 .br/>9 0 0 7	6 .br/>5 3 7 1	4 .br/>3 8 5 2

	4	9	3	7	0			
5	2	1	7	1	0	6	8	1
5	.	3	.	.	.	.	.	2
	4	.	1	9	8	8	9	.
	4	3	3	2	8	4	3	8
	7	8	8	5	2	2	4	7
	7	7	1	7	9	2	5	8
		6						7
5	1	1	1	9	3	1	0	0
6	.	0	.	.	.	2	.	.
	5	.	9	0	2	.	7	0
	2	4	8	5	7	0	9	4
	9	5	1	4	7	5	3	7
	8	2	8	5	4	5	5	9
		1				9		
5	1	7	9	2	0	2	0	0
7	1	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
	.	0	5	2	5	4	5	9
	0	4	5	4	2	5	1	5
	7	3	5	7	8	1	1	7
	2	4	5	5	6	5	2	4
	8							
5	8	1	4	8	1	2	1	6
8	.	2	.	.	1	.	0	.
	5	.	7	5	.	5	.	2
	4	7	1	1	7	6	2	1
	0	4	8	8	4	9	3	7
	7	9	2	8	8	5	3	0
		3			7		1	
5	7	8	1	8	7	0	1	3
9	.	.	1	.	.	.	3	.
	3	5	.	2	6	4	.	9
	2	9	6	8	2	9	5	8
	4	9	6	6	3	4	7	9
	9	6	0	7	4	9	9	2
			3				2	
6	5	1	4	6	1	3	1	5
0	.	0	.	.	2	.	3	.
	6	.	5	7	.	3	.	6
	2	8	9	7	3	9	1	6
	4	2	4	6	3	5	7	2
	5	6	9	5	6	0	1	8
		0			0		3	

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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 3 . 3 0 4 3	9 . 4 1 3 8	7 . 4 8 3 6	9 . 8 2 1 2	3 . 2 8 9 7	1 . 6 9 3 7	1 0 . 8 5 7 2	2 . 5 3 0 8
2	2 . 5 3 3 2	0 . 9 9 6 4	0 . 0 0 3 4	1 3 . 7 5 9 0	0 . 2 0 1 9	5 . 6 2 7 7	0 . 2 8 9 3	1 . 5 5 3 8
3	7 . 2 6 7 9	6 . 9 5 4 3	0 . 5 5 5 9	7 . 6 1 0 3	6 . 2 2 6 6	1 1 . 1 7 3 7	1 2 . 4 0 1 6	3 . 9 3 8 0
4	9 . 4 4 6 3	0 . 2 2 6 5	5 . 7 8 4 8	1 1 . 2 8 7 9	5 . 4 4 5 4	4 . 8 9 3 9	9 . 6 7 0 6	6 . 8 5 0 0
5	5 . 6 6 8 5	6 . 4 2 6 4	1 0 . 6 6 4 2	1 2 . 5 1 3 0	1 0 . 4 0 5 6	2 . 8 4 0 0	8 . 3 9 8 1	1 2 . 5 0 4 8
6	8 . 1 8 6 2	1 1 . 4 2 1 1	0 . 8 6 9 9	8 . 3 6 3 5	8 . 4 9 3 7	1 . 7 4 5 4	1 2 . 5 5 1 6	0 . 2 3 2 5
7	8 . 2	1 . 0	3 . 0	0 . 3	8 . 3	3 . 7	2 . 3	1 0 .

	9 1 6	9 2 0	8 1 3	1 0 5	5 6 5	2 3 2	4 8 4	1 8 9 8
8	4 . 4 9 0 7	1 . 5 3 6 2	8 . 5 8 3 0	8 . 8 0 3 9	3 . 2 4 3 5	1 1 . 5 2 6 1	1 3 . 8 1 5 2	4 . 0 6 1 0
9	2 . 4 9 5 6	6 . 5 0 6 7	1 0 . 9 6 4 5	4 . 2 4 7 6	1 3 . 8 3 8 7	1 0 . 8 0 9 2	2 . 5 2 1 5	3 . 6 9 4 8
1 0	8 . 9 8 6 4	4 . 3 3 9 8	9 . 2 2 6 0	7 . 6 9 5 9	3 . 5 1 4 3	4 . 9 5 5 9	1 0 . 1 7 6 6	1 . 3 6 0 6
1 1	9 . 4 2 5 6	2 . 5 0 0 3	7 . 3 4 4 2	1 . 5 1 8 3	9 . 0 9 7 6	1 1 . 4 4 8 5	6 . 6 4 5 4	1 2 . 0 8 2 5
1 2	0 . 0 9 9 8	1 1 . 6 3 2 6	1 1 . 4 2 5 2	7 . 5 4 7 4	6 . 5 8 1 7	7 . 8 2 0 0	1 1 . 5 9 3 4	7 . 0 3 0 9
1 3	7 . 9 9 2 5	1 0 . 6 5 5 6	2 . 8 0 9 5	1 0 . 9 4 6 5	3 . 0 1 4 4	3 . 1 4 1 3	1 2 . 5 3 8 1	6 . 2 3 1 0
1 4	0 . 9 5 2 7	8 . 3 3 1 3	9 . 4 7 4 8	9 . 3 1 4 4	1 2 . 6 8 4 9	3 . 4 2 0 3	1 3 . 2 2 2 1 2	0 . 3 1 5 3

1 5	1 0 . 0 3 1 9	5 . 1 3 7 5	9 . 4 6 9 6	1 1 . 1 9 6 0	9 . 6 7 0 1	6 . 2 2 8 5	9 . 5 2 6 1	9 . 4 3 6 9
1 6	6 . 6 7 3 4	8 . 4 5 2 0	5 . 8 1 7 3	5 . 9 8 5 2	1 0 . 0 1 6 6	5 . 8 7 9 2	3 . 3 6 0 0	9 . 9 1 4 0
1 7	4 . 2 6 0 5	6 . 7 0 8 0	2 . 3 5 9 4	1 0 . 0 6 8 2	6 . 9 4 6 8	7 . 4 4 6 3	0 . 9 1 4 6	1 . 6 4 8 1
1 8	9 . 1 0 5 5	1 1 . 1 9 1 8	5 . 9 2 0 7	9 . 2 7 5 5	1 0 . 1 5 0 2	5 . 1 1 2 0	6 . 6 2 8 8	4 . 3 9 1 7
1 9	4 . 8 2 5 9	1 1 . 7 7 1 2	1 3 . 9 4 4 9	7 . 3 5 3 6	7 . 8 2 8 9	7 . 8 6 7 7	4 . 9 7 3 3	1 2 . 3 6 7 8
2 0	5 . 7 3 5 4	1 2 . 3 9 2 3	4 . 7 8 1 6	7 . 6 0 1 0	1 3 . 3 8 5 9	7 . 0 7 7 8	6 . 1 2 8 2	1 . 8 8 7 3
2 1	1 2 . 3 5 0 4	2 . 2 5 6 2	1 . 9 1 2 8	9 . 8 8 5 9	1 1 . 8 0 4 5	1 . 2 0 7 9	2 . 5 6 5 2	1 . 1 9 5 3
2 2	5 . 1 3	7 . 6 5	7 . 7 9	1 0 . 5	1 3 . 9	1 0 . 9	0 . 1 2	3 . 6 6 6

	4 9	4 5	3 6	1 4 7	4 7 3	7 8 5	4 9	1 0
2 3	1 . 0 4 9 8	9 . 1 2 1 9	8 . 9 3 8 4	1 2 . 6 8 8 8 9	0 . 8 8 1 2	1 1 . 1 6 8 5	4 . 3 5 4 1	1 . 1 4 5 5
2 4	1 1 . 3 5 7 0	9 . 6 8 8 5	4 . 5 9 9 5	3 . 8 3 8 9	1 1 . 7 1 8 4	7 . 8 3 4 0	7 . 4 0 3 6	1 0 . 1 0 3 8
2 5	1 . 2 6 6 3	2 . 1 7 9 1	0 . 5 0 5 3	1 . 1 3 1 2	1 3 . 5 9 9 3	3 . 7 6 4 4	5 . 9 8 1 1	1 1 . 1 3 4 1
2 6	0 . 4 9 0 7	2 . 0 1 3 7	0 . 9 2 9 0	1 0 . 3 1 1 2	1 . 5 5 4 2	4 . 0 2 9 7	4 . 4 9 8 2	2 . 8 7 8 6
2 7	1 0 . 5 6 2 9	4 . 0 9 5 6	3 . 6 1 3 1	3 . 3 8 9 3	4 . 6 3 8 3 3	8 . 2 3 1 7	9 . 2 0 4 9	1 2 . 4 3 3 6
2 8	1 0 . 7 7 5 4	2 . 1 0 7 1	1 0 . 2 7 8 5	1 0 . 3 6 3 3	1 1 . 0 8 3 3	4 . 5 0 9 8	8 . 9 8 7 8	2 . 4 4 8 8
2 9	1 . 9 7 7 5	3 . 1 1 6 9	6 . 0 6 4 0	1 0 . 6 3 2 8	1 2 . 5 8 9 5	8 . 0 3 0	0 . 8 7 1 4	1 . 2 7 2 1
3	1	9	4	2	1	8	5	0

0	3 . 0 5 9 0	. 8 5 8 7	. 4 9 1 4	. 4 3 2 1	. 1 1 2 0	. 4 6 9 8	. 0 9 6 3	. 5 3 8 8
3 1	4 . 3 6 0 7	8 . 7 2 5 1	4 . 2 5 6 0	8 . 7 9 4 6	5 . 0 5 4 5	1 0 . 3 6 9 8	4 . 2 7 4 6	4 . 0 9 8 2
3 2	1 1 . 1 3 5 6	0 . 3 5 9 3	1 0 . 2 7 2 0	9 . 5 3 4 0	9 . 3 2 4 4	8 . 7 4 3 5	3 . 2 7 5 4	5 . 2 0 2 3
3 3	4 . 3 6 0 5	1 2 . 0 2 0 0	1 2 . 7 4 7 0	8 . 6 3 3 1	7 . 5 2 5 0	3 . 0 7 5 3	2 . 0 8 9 8	1 2 . 4 3 7 4
3 4	1 0 . 2 6 1 7	5 . 6 3 5 6	4 . 6 7 8 3	1 2 . 6 0 7 0	1 2 . 6 5 5 5	1 0 . 3 9 7 7	7 . 6 3 6 9	9 . 5 8 9 3
3 5	1 0 . 1 3 9 8	2 . 9 0 5 4	6 . 8 4 9 7	8 . 8 2 2 3	3 . 1 3 2 6	2 . 3 4 3 1	6 . 7 4 8 0	2 . 3 4 6 6
3 6	3 . 7 3 2 8	8 . 2 7 5 0	1 . 8 6 4 5	2 . 1 7 2 1	6 . 8 2 8 5	4 . 3 1 2 8	5 . 0 9 6 6	1 0 . 3 0 7 0
3 7	1 1 . 5 6	1 1 . 5 6	7 . 0 5 9	6 . 2 7 4	2 . 3 7 8	4 . 9 5 6	1 1 . 9 2	2 . 0 4 0

	5 0	0 3	7	3	7	2	3 7	9
3 8	4 . 8 8 2 9	3 . 6 5 6 3	1 3 . 8 2 0 2	6 . 0 4 8 9	0 . 7 6 7 8	1 3 . 4 0 4 8	1 3 . 3 1 1	1 1 . 5 9 6 3
3 9	2 . 5 7 6 7	3 . 2 6 2 6	4 . 4 2 8 3	5 . 6 6 7 9	1 1 . 4 2 0 3	1 0 . 1 1 3 0	9 . 2 7 4 4	5 . 2 2 1 5
4 0	5 . 5 2 2 9	6 . 1 9 9 8	1 . 3 5 1 7	3 . 7 9 0 1	5 . 3 8 5 8	2 . 9 4 2 8	3 . 3 2 0 2	8 . 7 9 2 9
4 1	6 . 7 3 3 4	1 2 . 2 7 9 5	6 . 4 1 9 2	7 . 8 2 2 1	6 . 4 9 7 7	1 3 . 5 2 1 6	4 . 6 7 1 1	1 0 . 4 2 3 7
4 2	4 . 0 9 2 6	4 . 8 2 4 3	3 . 8 8 5 5	3 . 0 5 7 1	3 . 0 2 0 8	1 3 . 0 2 8 6	5 . 9 3 4 3	1 0 . 5 1 7 0
4 3	5 . 1 6 2 1	1 2 . 8 4 6 1	6 . 5 9 5 1	6 . 2 1 5 3	2 . 8 7 2 2	0 . 1 5 9 3	5 . 2 3 1 8	1 0 . 2 0 7 5
4 4	3 . 5 9 5 9	1 . 8 6 8 2	1 . 9 5 7 1	1 3 . 3 3 3 0	8 . 4 7 5 2	6 . 0 3 3 3	0 . 0 2 0 5	3 . 4 2 2 6
4 5	7 . 1	9 . 9	1 1 . .	1 0 . .	2 . 2	0 . 6	6 . 2	1 3 . .

	6 1 4	5 5 0	5 5 8 1	7 3 1 1	1 0 0	9 5 9	3 5 6	5 8 5 2
4 6	1 . 5 6 6 5	1 0 . 5 2 1 2	1 0 . 6 7 5 9	1 1 . 0 8 1 0	4 . 4 5 7 9	0 . 6 4 8 0	5 . 9 3 3 3	9 . 8 2 5 1
4 7	2 . 8 9 3 1	9 . 6 3 3 4	5 . 6 0 0 9	2 . 7 6 2 2	1 0 . 7 2 2 0 3	5 . 8 2 7 9	1 2 . 3 9 3 6	4 . 9 7 2 1
4 8	1 . 7 0 3 7	2 . 3 9 9 4	3 . 5 5 5 4	2 . 6 2 0 9	1 . 5 4 1 4	2 . 5 8 3 1	1 1 . 3 4 4 2	1 1 . 2 9 7 8
4 9	2 . 3 6 7 5	1 0 . 1 3 5 4	0 . 1 7 9 3	1 2 . 9 5 8 2	1 1 . 4 1 1 4	2 . 5 8 8 5	9 . 4 9 0 0	1 1 . 6 4 7 0
5 0	1 . 2 5 1 8	9 . 3 6 4 0	9 . 6 1 5 8	1 1 . 1 3 4 9	1 3 . 3 3 5 8	7 . 5 2 6 8	0 . 1 1 9 4	1 2 . 3 9 3 4
5 1	8 . 9 4 4 7	0 . 8 7 7 5	7 . 9 0 4 6	8 . 4 9 8 9	3 . 8 6 6 3	1 1 . 8 5 5 8	1 . 2 4 3 4	7 . 5 1 5 5
5 2	9 . 2 1 1 0	3 . 2 7 4 9	2 . 1 7 3 7	7 . 4 1 6 6	6 . 3 7 5 9	1 . 3 9 5 7	7 . 0 3 8 1	2 . 6 8 2 0
5	7	0	5	8	2	1	1	1

3	. 3 1 0 7	. 7 2 9 4	. 3 7 9 3	. 2 9 4 7	. 2 1 7 8	0 . 9 3 1 8	2 . 9 1 7 4	. 9 5 4 5
5 4	1 3 . 9 2 9 5	6 . 7 7 0 5	1 0 . 2 1 6 3	5 . 7 6 3 9	2 . 2 7 1 6	1 2 . 9 3 0 4	5 . 2 6 5 3	5 . 4 4 1 3
5 5	4 . 8 2 0 3	1 1 . 1 9 9	1 0 . 4 6 4 6	1 1 . 2 0 4 7	1 0 . 8 8 2 0	7 . 1 8 9 7	1 . 5 1 3 0	9 . 5 2 1 7
5 6	1 . 7 1 9 5	6 . 1 0 2 5	2 . 6 1 5 2	1 0 . 4 5 5 2	3 . 2 9 4 4	1 1 . 6 5 0 8	0 . 1 0 4 8	5 . 0 1 7 0
5 7	1 0 . 9 4 6 2	1 . 9 8 9 8	6 . 4 9 7 5	2 . 6 5 3 3	1 . 3 0 2 8	1 1 . 0 7 3 9	1 0 . 9 3 9 2	4 . 4 2 1 3
5 8	1 2 . 5 0 4 6	5 . 7 7 2 8	1 0 . 3 9 9 8	1 2 . 0 6 8 6	7 . 6 0 0 7	2 . 8 2 3 2	1 0 . 5 2 8 7	4 . 2 2 1 4
5 9	8 . 4 8 6 3	4 . 5 8 7 0	1 0 . 0 1 9 9	5 . 3 0 8 7	9 . 3 3 6 7	8 . 9 6 1 1	1 1 . 0 2 4 3	2 . 9 1 5 0
6 0	1 . 3 1 6	7 . 6 6 1	4 . 1 4 6	1 2 . 2 4	7 . 9 0 5	5 . 0 5 8	9 . 6 6 2	1 . 3 9 6

	1	1	9	1 1	6	4	2	1
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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	2 . 7 2 8 9	1 1 . 0 0 1 3	5 . 7 3 9 6	2 . 0 0 8 4	5 . 0 2 5 2	3 . 0 0 8 7	1 1 . 0 2 0 3	4 . 0 8 1 7
2	3 . 3 7 8 8	4 . 5 0 5 2	4 . 5 5 1 7	7 . 4 3 3 5	4 . 4 2 5 8	7 . 2 0 1 2	9 . 2 6 6 5	3 . 0 0 4 2
3	1 2 . 8 5 1 2	7 . 2 1 1 5	3 . 2 5 9 5	1 0 . 4 5 0 4	8 . 2 3 8 0 0	1 3 . 2 0 5 9	0 . 2 1 9 1	3 . 7 5 6 0
4	0 . 5 0 6 8	4 . 7 7 4 5	4 . 9 1 3 5	5 . 4 9 9 4	1 3 . 0 4 7 7	3 . 5 9 5 7	1 . 8 0 7 0	2 . 3 6 9 2
5	2 . 7 5 7 5	1 . 1 8 8 8	2 . 6 8 4 8	9 . 5 1 3 6	7 . 3 2 5 9	1 3 . 8 7 7 0	6 . 7 4 4 6	1 0 . 1 5 3 5
6	2 . 4 9 9 8	3 . 4 9 6 5	8 . 7 9 0 8	6 . 6 1 9 2	1 . 9 4 8 7	6 . 1 0 4 2	1 1 . 3 4 6 9	0 . 8 5 9 0
7	1 1 . 7 6	0 . 6 7 2	6 . 4 3 8	9 . 9 4 4	3 . 9 9 6	8 . 5 2 8	4 . 6 3 3	8 . 8 4 9

	9 8	4	4	7	9	3	8	0
8	1 2 . 6 1 5 1	5 . 8 5 1 6	6 . 6 8 5 9	5 . 2 2 4 1	5 . 7 3 4 3	4 . 6 1 8 0	7 . 8 7 9 4	1 . 0 9 8 0
9	9 . 3 3 9 5	4 . 0 8 5 6	0 . 6 8 9 5	8 . 8 2 9 2	1 3 . 3 5 4 1	1 . 2 2 3 6	4 . 6 4 5 8	6 . 0 5 1 2
1 0	5 . 0 8 7 8	8 . 0 5 0 9	9 . 0 2 5 6	5 . 3 3 7 1	4 . 0 1 3 0	8 . 5 5 6 2	1 3 . 5 8 3 0	1 1 . 7 9 5 8
1 1	2 . 8 8 9 5	2 . 0 3 1 7	6 . 0 7 4 3	2 . 6 9 1 3	4 . 6 5 4 6	7 . 1 8 0 1	1 . 6 4 5 4	9 . 8 8 9 2
1 2	9 . 1 3 4 7	0 . 9 4 6 9	4 . 9 0 2 1	8 . 3 0 0 4	4 . 6 8 0 9	6 . 4 4 3 0	7 . 2 6 5 0	1 0 . 2 3 4 9
1 3	1 1 . 7 4 3 4	1 . 4 4 7 2	8 . 6 6 1 2	1 3 . 3 2 9 8	6 . 8 8 4 5	5 . 7 5 7 1	1 2 . 0 8 5 5	2 . 1 5 3 1
1 4	4 . 7 4 8 2	5 . 0 9 6 0	6 . 2 7 5 2	1 2 . 3 8 6 1	1 1 . 6 0 0 3	0 . 1 2 8 0	7 . 5 4 3 0	4 . 5 2 6 5
1 5	7 . 4	8 . 8	5 . 2	7 . 2	3 . 6	0 . 0	2 . 2	1 1 . .

	2 7 4	6 7 8	1 0 1	3 3 7	6 2 7	0 6 3	4 0 9	2 6 7 5
1 6	2 . 4 7 1 4	4 . 8 9 7 6	1 1 . 0 8 4 9	6 . 5 1 0 3	0 . 5 6 9 1	5 . 6 9 7 3	2 . 3 9 1 7	7 . 8 4 3 9
1 7	3 . 8 3 0 2	4 . 8 0 1 9	9 . 8 0 5 9	6 . 1 2 5 2	1 0 . 8 8 3 0	1 0 . 1 9 5 9	7 . 0 7 8 7	6 . 7 9 6 0
1 8	4 . 5 4 8 9	2 . 2 9 5 9	5 . 7 1 2 5	1 . 2 8 7 9	2 . 1 9 7 7	1 0 . 7 5 5 7	5 . 5 3 5 2	1 1 . 1 7 0 4
1 9	5 . 1 5 7 3	1 . 0 8 5 7	5 . 8 8 3 6	1 0 . 1 6 0 0	1 2 . 3 0 4 7	2 . 8 4 9 5	5 . 5 3 2 7	1 2 . 7 5 2 4
2 0	4 . 4 0 7 2	4 . 9 0 1 8	6 . 2 5 6 2	1 . 0 1 8 0	1 0 . 5 0 4 6	1 1 . 1 1 6 3	1 . 1 1 2 9	1 . 9 7 3 0
2 1	1 . 8 6 2 7	6 . 2 4 0 8	4 . 8 2 1 5	6 . 3 4 2 2	0 . 9 3 8 3	6 . 2 1 1 0	6 . 1 3 4 4	1 2 . 6 1 6 4
2 2	1 1 . 5 0 0 9	6 . 3 2 2 5	7 . 2 0 1 0	9 . 4 4 2 9	9 . 7 9 3 6	2 . 4 7 7 1	0 . 3 5 8 6	1 2 . 4 2 4 3

2 3	0 . 7 8 6 6	1 2 . 6 0 5 3	3 . 8 1 5 1	0 . 9 5 4 2	0 . 1 7 7 2	3 . 0 8 1 9	7 . 9 2 3 9	8 . 2 6 6 4
2 4	0 . 7 3 5 6	9 . 9 3 6 9	1 1 . 5 0 1 2	1 2 . 3 7 8 4	5 . 6 7 3	8 . 4 0 2 0	7 . 6 5 9 9	0 . 4 4 8 1
2 5	4 . 4 4 3	3 . 5 1 2 6	8 . 0 9 6 3	1 . 8 2 6 0	3 . 7 9 7 2	3 . 3 4 2 1	9 . 7 8 9 2	9 . 3 2 5 6
2 6	2 . 8 9 0 5	5 . 6 6 1 5	5 . 5 9 1 1	7 . 5 9 3 3	9 . 2 7 4 7	0 . 5 7 1 0	7 . 8 0 4 0	1 1 . 8 6 4 2
2 7	7 . 9 7 9 0	1 . 4 3 0 2	9 . 4 9 7 2	1 2 . 7 2 1 4	3 . 4 6 2 5	5 . 0 2 9 5	3 . 3 9 2 2	6 . 2 1 8 5
2 8	1 2 . 4 4 5 2	4 . 2 7 9 3	9 . 4 6 2 6	1 2 . 9 6 2 3	8 . 5 0 3 2	1 1 . 0 8 7 6	0 . 7 7 6 3	2 . 0 3 3 3
2 9	1 . 4 9 1 9	8 . 6 3 4 6	1 2 . 2 3 3 9	1 1 . 2 2 6 8	1 0 . 4 2 2 5	2 . 3 8 2 4	0 . 8 7 4 4	4 . 2 1 5 5
3 0	9 . 9 5 3	9 . 4 4 1	0 . 0 2 8	3 . 5 6 3	1 0 . 9 1	9 . 2 2 5	5 . 8 3 5	0 . 6 6 3

	9	5	5	1	4 7	3	9	2
3 1	8 . 8 3 4 0	8 . 9 3 2 4	1 0 . 6 9 1 0	6 . 4 0 4 6	8 . 3 1 8 0	6 . 6 4 2 6	7 . 9 1 2 0	1 2 . 7 3 9 9
3 2	1 . 0 2 2 6	1 2 . 9 5 0 9	8 . 7 7 4 9	7 . 1 4 9 6	1 2 . 6 7 7 2	7 . 9 5 6 0	6 . 6 5 4 0	8 . 3 6 1 1
3 3	3 . 3 9 6 4	2 . 8 1 8 4	4 . 1 3 8 8	4 . 6 0 1 5	1 2 . 7 4 1 1	6 . 6 1 6 5	7 . 2 9 6 0	1 0 . 1 1 7 1
3 4	1 3 . 1 5 0 6	5 . 4 1 4 3	1 0 . 3 5 1 3	7 . 3 8 7 7	8 . 5 4 3 4	1 0 . 9 5 8 2	3 . 2 8 6 6	7 . 2 4 4 9
3 5	5 . 2 2 7 5	9 . 4 3 2 2	4 . 4 7 2 4	8 . 0 2 9 3	1 . 3 1 9 9	1 0 . 2 4 5 0	1 1 . 4 5 8 8	1 2 . 3 8 2 5
3 6	1 2 . 2 1 6 5	1 3 . 6 0 0 8	9 . 2 8 9 3	7 . 5 9 3 3	5 . 5 6 9 0	6 . 3 5 2 9	9 . 1 6 5 5	3 . 1 0 8 4
3 7	6 . 5 0 6 1	7 . 5 8 2 0	1 0 . 2 5 5 7	4 . 9 3 5 5	4 . 7 7 7 3	6 . 0 3 1 4	5 . 7 9 7 7	1 2 . 1 9 6 5
3 8	4 . .	7 . .	1 1 1	1 3	0 .	7 .	5 .	4 .

	3 3 2 8	1 8 2 8	. 1 0 5 2	. 1 5 0 4	4 4 4 1	1 8 8 5	7 7 8 3	0 9 5 0
3 9	4 . 2 3 2 2	1 1 . 2 8 5 9	1 1 . 9 7 7 6	1 2 . 6 1 9 6	1 3 . 8 8 8 2	1 3 . 2 9 0 8	8 . 7 7 6 5	1 1 . 4 2 4 7
4 0	2 . 3 7 6 6	6 . 3 4 6 4	9 . 9 4 2 4	2 . 4 6 3 6	1 . 6 2 5 5	4 . 2 7 2 1	6 . 6 4 2 2	3 . 6 9 6 8
4 1	8 . 7 9 4 9	9 . 4 1 0 7	1 0 . 0 2 4 2	2 . 2 0 7 8	1 3 . 0 4 2 8	3 . 8 2 6 4	1 2 . 3 5 3 1	1 1 . 1 2 3 9
4 2	1 3 . 7 1 6 5	2 . 0 7 6 9	1 2 . 6 9 9 3	9 . 3 9 7 4	0 . 9 8 0 1	1 0 . 6 7 5 7	1 1 . 3 2 3 6	1 1 . 4 9 3 2
4 3	9 . 7 0 6 9	1 3 . 9 3 7 7	7 . 8 0 7 3	9 . 8 0 2 9	1 1 . 9 7 5 8	3 . 0 0 7 0	1 . 9 1 0 4	8 . 6 8 1 4
4 4	1 2 . 3 0 1 9	4 . 1 3 4 0	8 . 8 7 6 5	0 . 6 1 5 1	4 . 1 7 9 0	7 . 0 5 2 1	4 . 0 6 1 7	6 . 9 7 9 1
4 5	4 . 7 2 7 7	2 . 9 0 6 0	9 . 4 1 6 5	1 . 1 3 8 5	1 0 . 7 5 2 6	1 . 0 9 8 5	5 . 2 1 1 2	5 . 3 9 4 2

4 6	1 2 . 6 2 8 6	6 . 7 3 7 5	5 . 0 4 9 6	1 . 7 0 9 4	1 0 . 0 0 4 1	5 . 0 2 8 2	8 . 9 8 9 7	5 . 3 4 3 5
4 7	6 . 3 9 2 9	7 . 3 0 5 5	3 . 8 5 7 2	2 . 1 6 9 4	1 0 . 3 5 4 0	3 . 7 6 8 8	1 2 . 5 8 0 9	5 . 7 6 8 9
4 8	7 . 4 3 2 7	1 3 . 0 7 3 6	4 . 4 7 5 0	3 . 4 5 9 1	1 . 1 7 2 5	7 . 5 4 1 6	8 . 6 3 1 8	9 . 5 5 1 8
4 9	1 2 . 4 1 6 7	8 . 4 0 8 3	1 1 . 3 9 3 4	4 . 5 1 5 4	2 . 7 5 7 3	4 . 1 9 0 7	1 1 . 7 6 3 8	1 1 . 5 0 7 3
5 0	9 . 4 2 9 1	5 . 7 6 5 4	9 . 1 7 9 3	4 . 8 4 6 5	3 . 9 5 3 3	1 . 2 7 9 0	6 . 7 6 2 8	6 . 8 0 3 2
5 1	8 . 8 3 7 2	3 . 8 8 9 8	4 . 7 4 1 7	1 0 . 5 7 7 1	4 . 8 8 2 3	7 . 2 1 0 1	6 . 8 8 1 5	1 . 5 4 8 3
5 2	4 . 4 0 3 6	4 . 7 6 7 1	7 . 1 1 7 7	4 . 1 1 5 6	4 . 4 5 7 7	1 . 9 4 5 4	7 . 1 8 7 2	1 1 . 1 0 0 6
5 3	8 . 6 4 6	5 . 3 6 4	7 . 5 8 3	1 3 . 4 6	6 . 7 2 0	4 . 9 4 7	4 . 0 4 8	9 . 5 1 0

	3	8	3	0 6	5	9	2	9
5 4	5 . 3 5 3 5	5 . 9 7 4 8	4 . 7 3 7 6	1 . 9 9 5 0	0 . 5 6 5 9	8 . 1 4 0 8	6 . 7 7 0 8	7 . 8 7 8 9
5 5	1 0 . 8 8 8 3	0 . 7 2 5 0	1 2 . 5 5 0 0	8 . 8 7 7 1	7 . 1 6 0 9	0 . 9 5 8 7	1 1 . 9 2 7 6	0 . 1 1 0 6
5 6	8 . 4 5 4 8	5 . 0 8 1 0	5 . 9 7 6 0	1 3 . 9 1 4 3	2 . 7 9 0 9	1 2 . 0 6 0 7	7 . 1 1 3 9	2 . 2 9 0 9
5 7	1 0 . 7 6 6 3	0 . 8 9 4 7	1 . 4 0 7 5	4 . 0 8 7 7	7 . 4 9 1 2	5 . 3 4 9 4	1 1 . 5 1 9 4	4 . 6 3 4 2
5 8	1 1 . 9 4 5 4	6 . 6 8 2 6	6 . 6 2 3 0	1 . 7 4 1 0	6 . 0 6 7 6	2 . 3 3 1 6	6 . 2 8 3 6	5 . 8 1 6 5
5 9	1 0 . 8 6 8 3	1 . 0 4 5 5	5 . 6 3 7 9	2 . 4 2 0 0	5 . 0 4 4 3	2 . 7 3 0 5	2 . 5 7 3 4	1 2 . 4 1 2 4
6 0	1 2 . 9 3 1 9	4 . 8 1 7 1	6 . 2 3 7 3	9 . 1 3 9 8	3 . 9 1 6 7	1 0 . 8 0 7 9	2 . 6 7 2 9	4 . 6 6 3 0

SUBJECT - 11

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SUBJECT - 12

S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	9 . 6 4 0 0	1 . 5 1 6 5	4 . 9 5 7 1	5 . 3 2 9 8	3 . 6 8 0 9	1 . 1 9 1 6	4 . 5 4 3 1	4 . 1 6 7 4
2	1 . 4 2 9 1	3 . 6 5 6 4	1 0 . 2 8 3 1	8 . 4 8 1 4	8 . 0 3 1 6	1 2 . 7 6 1 9	9 . 9 3 0 5	3 . 3 7 8 6
3	7 . 2 1 4 1	3 . 3 9 8 7	1 . 1 0 7 6	1 1 . 4 5 1 5	6 . 4 8 5 8	7 . 4 1 7 5	2 . 2 6 9 7	7 . 4 6 5 0
4	4 . 3 6 4 1	7 . 6 1 3 8	1 . 1 8 6 5	1 1 . 9 1 7 0	9 . 4 3 4 4	4 . 9 3 6 7	6 . 7 1 6 4	1 . 0 0 2 1
5	9 . 1 7 8 3	6 . 6 9 0 8	3 . 5 1 3 8	6 . 3 4 8 5	7 . 5 2 3 5	1 2 . 4 3 7 8	1 0 . 9 9 8 7	4 . 7 7 5 4
6	6 . 8 2 7 0	7 . 7 1 1 9	1 . 8 9 8 2	1 . 6 1 3 6	5 . 0 3 3 9	9 . 6 3 2 3	3 . 5 5 2	6 . 5 3 2 8
7	3 . 1 0 1 2	3 . 0 3 9 1	2 . 9 6 2 9	2 . 0 7 5 5	9 . 7 7 6 2	8 . 0 7 3 9	1 0 . 1 6 3	4 . 2 7 6 6

							5	
8	0	7	9	7	1	7	8	9
	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
	4	4	1	0	3	0	4	8
	4	0	6	2	2	4	8	6
	8	8	5	5	7	7	7	9
	9	5	8	6	9	1	5	7
9	3	8	3	1	8	5	8	0
	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	.
	7	0	3	.	7	4	3	9
	1	3	8	2	2	9	4	3
	9	8	8	7	3	4	1	0
	8	5	9	5	8	6	1	6
				7				
1	1	1	1	1	7	0	5	7
0	3	1	2	1	.	.	.	.
	.	.	.	.	9	3	2	8
	8	5	1	4	8	8	8	9
	4	3	7	4	2	0	2	4
	5	4	7	1	5	6	7	0
	3	0	2	0				
1	1	4	7	4	9	6	1	4
1	0	.	.	.	.	.	2	.
	.	8	7	9	6	2	.	1
	0	3	1	8	8	1	5	3
	1	8	0	9	6	2	8	7
	8	9	7	4	5	7	0	9
	1						3	
1	1	5	9	7	9	0	7	3
2	0	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
	.	8	0	6	8	6	4	8
	5	8	3	4	5	4	2	7
	3	1	0	6	1	9	1	8
	2	3	2	0	0	7	5	7
	7							
1	1	6	1	0	9	8	7	4
3	3	.	3	.	.	.	.	.
	.	0	.	3	0	4	4	3
	8	7	5	7	0	9	8	0
	1	2	3	3	1	6	6	5
	9	1	1	8	9	3	6	1
	6		1					
1	4	5	1	0	1	1	6	6
4	.	.	2	.	2	2	.	.
	0	9	.	6	.	.	5	7
	0	4	3	8	7	6	7	9
	6	5	7	0	1	1	4	5
	8	1	7	1	2	9	3	1
			9		5	6		
1	7	0	4	2	3	1	9	8
5	.	.	.	.	.	3	.	.
	3	0	4	1	6	.	6	4
	1	5	4	5	9	3	3	9

	0 5	5 3	8 4	2 1	8 5	0 8 2	6 3	1 8
1 6	9 . 0 9 4 1	3 . 2 9 4 6	1 . 5 1 4 8	1 0 . 3 4 1 3	6 . 3 9 6 5	9 . 4 3 3 5	9 . 9 2 5 2	3 . 7 3 5 0
1 7	1 . 3 6 3 5	7 . 4 3 5 3	8 . 6 4 0 1	1 1 . 6 4 1 5	7 . 1 4 4 7	9 . 2 2 0 7	3 . 8 2 9 3	3 . 6 7 0 5
1 8	1 2 . 1 5 1 9	3 . 7 5 3 0	2 . 2 6 2 1	9 . 2 5 0	8 . 7 7 2 5	5 . 5 7 1 2	1 1 . 7 9 5 8	6 . 0 8 8 5
1 9	7 . 1 5 7 8	4 . 6 2 5 6	1 3 . 7 7 0 4	1 2 . 1 1 2 0	6 . 8 2 8 0	1 . 9 2 6 0	7 . 4 6 9 7	1 2 . 9 9 3 7
2 0	1 0 . 8 8 2 9	6 . 1 8 7 6	1 1 . 2 0 0 0	6 . 9 4 7 8	5 . 3 7 2 6	0 . 0 1 8 5	0 . 7 8 5 5	1 . 1 0 4 6
2 1	7 . 7 2 3 6	3 . 5 0 4 1	6 . 3 8 1 1	1 0 . 4 2 0 6	7 . 4 5 6 3	1 1 . 5 7 3 2	3 . 9 0 7 0	1 2 . 9 7 9 8
2 2	2 . 3 9 4 3	6 . 0 2 8 3	1 2 . 2 1 5 1	6 . 5 0 2 8	7 . 3 1 6 0	9 . 8 0 3 7	0 . 0 9 0 8	5 . 1 5 9 2
2	3	9	1	7	1	1	7	7

3	. 3 1 5 3	. 9 3 0 9	2 . 0 2 5 6	. 3 6 8 3	. 4 0 4 5	2 . 1 8 6 7	. 0 9 8 7	. 4 4 1 4
2 4	2 . 1 4 2 5	3 . 5 7 3 6	0 . 4 2 6 0	1 2 . 3 9 2 5	5 . 2 3 5 6	1 2 . 3 8 6 1	1 0 . 8 7 2 5	5 . 2 2 1 8
2 5	0 . 7 2 9 2	2 . 4 0 0 8	8 . 1 5 6 8	6 . 2 3 9 1	0 . 2 8 6 8	2 . 9 6 5 0	6 . 6 4 3 2	3 . 9 6 6 9
2 6	3 . 3 1 6 9	9 . 4 1 2 3	6 . 0 0 3 6	4 . 8 1 4 4	7 . 9 3 0 1	1 . 2 2 2 1	1 2 . 2 6 0 7	1 0 . 3 4 8 4
2 7	7 . 0 4 3 4	6 . 9 4 6 5	4 . 4 1 9 3	1 1 . 1 4 9 0	7 . 2 7 2 7	1 2 . 9 7 7 4	2 . 0 4 4 9	4 . 6 4 1 1
2 8	2 . 4 7 3 5	7 . 8 1 7 6	5 . 9 7 9 0	6 . 9 7 4 6	5 . 9 4 5 4	1 0 . 0 7 5 7	6 . 5 3 1 7	1 1 . 7 6 9 2
2 9	1 0 . 7 5 4 6	6 . 9 1 9 8	4 . 1 4 4 7	9 . 4 2 2 1	3 . 6 0 9 5	0 . 3 6 9 6	4 . 8 7 6 9	0 . 6 1 8 7
3 0	0 . 9 8 8 7	8 . 7 4 3 7	2 . 5 7 9 3	2 . 7 1 4 2	0 . 0 3 8 8	8 . 3 8 1 9	1 1 . 8 3 7	7 . 6 4 6 5

							3	
3 1	1 1 . 9 7 6 5	1 1 . 4 6 0 4	1 0 . 1 7 3 7	0 . 3 4 6 0	6 . 4 9 3 3	4 . 9 6 5 0	9 . 4 3 8 5	1 2 . 5 7 4 6
3 2	1 . 7 1 1 5	1 . 5 0 6 3	1 1 . 7 8 5 3	6 . 4 2 7 7	7 . 3 9 3 6	9 . 6 9 2 6	2 . 7 2 2 0	6 . 9 2 2 4
3 3	1 2 . 6 8 5 0	5 . 3 3 4 1	4 . 5 5 9 3	2 . 2 7 6	1 0 . 4 8 8 3	4 . 6 9 0 4	8 . 0 1 0 6	3 . 4 1 6 0
3 4	1 0 . 6 3 3 7	5 . 3 1 7 2	8 . 6 1 3 1	2 . 3 6 2 6	8 . 8 1 0 0	6 . 6 4 6 1	0 . 0 8 8 0	7 . 8 5 5 0
3 5	2 . 7 1 4 7	6 . 1 2 4 6	5 . 8 6 9 3	8 . 9 2 2 4	2 . 8 2 3 6	4 . 2 5 2 7	8 . 1 5 3 8	2 . 4 4 1 5
3 6	1 2 . 9 3 5 3	8 . 2 4 9 7	7 . 1 6 6 2	1 . 8 3 8 3	3 . 6 7 1 0	1 . 8 1 8 6	6 . 5 2 9 8	1 1 . 6 2 8 0
3 7	3 . 0 5 3 5	0 . 1 5 0 6	4 . 4 8 4 8	9 . 8 8 4 1	1 1 . 9 7 9 7	7 . 7 2 7 9	1 . 4 6 1 5	1 3 . 0 9 2 8
3 8	1 2 . 4	0 . 2 7	3 . 1 3	9 . 3 7	1 . 2 3	0 . 0 4	9 . 3 4	1 1 . 6

	4 2 4	3 2	4 0	7 9	2 0	0 5	6 5	2 7 3
3 9	8 . 8 7 5 6	6 . 8 5 4 7	6 . 1 4 7 6	7 . 2 6 1 9	1 2 . 1 6 7 1	6 . 8 9 8 4	9 . 4 7 5 2	1 0 . 0 5 5 5
4 0	7 . 0 0 5 2	4 . 6 7 8 0	6 . 6 4 4 5	0 . 4 0 8 7	9 . 7 4 5 9	1 3 . 6 9 7 6	1 0 . 7 5 6 3	2 . 2 5 4 8
4 1	0 . 6 1 3 6	1 1 . 8 5 2 7	9 . 3 6 6 2	1 . 6 1 8 2	1 3 . 9 7 9 2	4 . 3 2 2 6	9 . 1 6 3 4	1 0 . 4 2 1 4
4 2	1 2 . 6 1 4 4 0	0 . 1 5 6 1	4 . 4 7 2 4	1 . 1 4 6 1	9 . 9 8 0 4	1 . 0 4 1 4	8 . 5 4 7 6	2 . 4 7 4 9
4 3	6 . 3 0 9 4	9 . 1 1 2 3	1 1 . 1 5 1 5	0 . 1 2 1 7	6 . 3 7 3 3	1 2 . 6 8 4 8	7 . 7 1 5 5	9 . 2 5 8 7
4 4	3 . 0 5 7 8	1 3 . 7 4 5 1	1 2 . 8 5 1 2	9 . 5 9 6 2	2 6 9 7 3	1 0 . 5 0 0 4	2 . 3 5 3 2	1 . 5 7 1 1
4 5	6 . 4 2 6 5	1 1 . 4 8 1 9	1 1 . 7 2 5 8	7 . 5 3 8 7	7 . 6 3 9 0	3 . 7 9 0 2	6 . 3 1 4 7	4 . 7 8 9 3
4	5	6	9	1	0	2	4	1

6	. 7 7 2 7	. 0 3 9 0	. 0 6 2 6	0 . 3 0 3 2	. 9 9 9 0	. 3 6 2 1	. 5 5 0 1	2 . 8 9 6 2
4 7	7 . 6 9 9 4	1 0 . 5 2 7 3	8 . 4 6 8 4	1 1 . 9 3 1 3	1 1 . 1 8 3 3	0 . 6 1 5 6	0 . 4 2 1 7	8 . 4 9 9 7
4 8	1 2 . 2 7 8 2	7 . 3 6 4 6	5 . 3 9 5 9	3 0 3 0 3	0 . 4 2 1 9	1 . 0 1 9 8	6 . 0 0 6 5	0 . 8 9 7 9
4 9	7 . 2 6 7 7	1 1 . 0 2 2 1	9 . 1 2 3 2	4 . 5 3 0 6	7 . 2 8 3 5	0 . 3 1 3 3	3 . 5 8 9 5	1 3 . 2 8 7 9
5 0	2 . 2 2 7 2	1 2 . 0 2 3 1	6 . 4 1 9 1	9 . 7 2 1 4	1 . 2 6 2 9	5 . 1 8 2 7	7 . 0 5 2 3	7 . 9 0 4 1
5 1	7 . 2 3 2 7	1 . 0 4 1 3	4 . 8 6 8 2	1 2 . 3 5 0 3	7 . 6 4 3 6	5 . 1 7 7 9	1 0 . 0 1 9 9	9 . 3 7 1 3
5 2	1 0 . 1 0 9 9	3 . 0 3 9 1	8 . 0 2 6 1	1 2 . 9 6 8 9	1 . 7 2 3 3	1 1 . 8 1 3 6	8 . 7 5 0 7	5 . 7 1 9 2
5 3	7 . 8 1 5	7 . 6 3 4	8 . 9 3 8	7 . 7 5 8	2 . 2 9 6	8 . 6 0 2	3 7 2 0	1 . 7 7 1

	2	6	0	3	9	1	3	4
5 4	1 0 . 4 8 5 3	9 . 6 5 7 8	1 0 . 9 5 2 1	1 2 . 1 4 6 4	1 1 . 5 8 7 7	1 2 . 4 7 1 9	3 . 1 5 3 4	1 . 0 8 1 3
5 5	1 . 2 2 4 8	0 . 4 0 1 1	2 . 1 3 4 1	1 0 . 9 3 5 5	9 . 5 9 8 8	1 2 . 6 9 3 4	0 . 5 7 6 9	1 . 4 0 2 7
5 6	2 . 3 2 8 0	1 . 9 3 0 5	4 . 9 3 3 0	1 . 7 4 3 1	4 . 5 8 1 9	3 . 4 6 1 5	0 . 9 6 5 8	6 . 5 2 8 5
5 7	1 3 . 5 8 2 1	9 . 1 6 2 2	6 . 5 5 0 2	1 2 . 3 1 3 4	0 . 5 3 6 5	1 . 7 9 5 1	1 2 . 0 5 0 2	6 . 1 5 8 5
5 8	8 . 9 4 9 0	1 3 . 6 2 9 3	8 . 5 2 3 2	2 . 8 2 4 7	1 1 . 6 0 2 3	9 . 7 3 0 1	4 . 1 8 7 6	6 . 7 8 2 4
5 9	3 . 2 0 9 9	9 . 5 7 1 6	6 . 3 2 1 3	1 . 1 4 3 4	1 0 . 5 4 0 7	2 . 0 8 8 8	4 . 8 9 5 8	2 . 4 7 7 9
6 0	1 2 . 4 2 6 4	5 . 1 2 7 1	1 3 . 7 1 5 1	1 . 7 3 5 6	9 . 8 1 2 5	6 . 1 4 5 3	1 3 . 0 3 8 0	5 . 5 4 4 0

Figure – 17 / 02

S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	6 . 7 4 7 4	1 2 . 4 6 5 2	5 . 2 8 1 9	4 . 1 9 7 8	5 . 2 0 5 1	5 . 7 6 5 5	1 . 2 1 8 8	9 . 6 8 4 6
2	5 . 7 6 3 2	8 . 7 8 8 0	4 . 0 3 2 5	4 . 5 4 1 4	7 . 0 2 8 1	7 . 5 1 8 0	2 . 2 5 7	8 . 4 0 5 4
3	7 . 6 8 0 5	7 . 2 8 4 1	8 . 6 1 2 4	1 . 5 7 0 4	7 . 3 6 2 6	6 . 5 3 7 8	6 . 9 2 4 6	6 . 8 8 9 6
4	5 . 2 1 9 5	6 . 4 2 1 4	7 . 3 3 3 3	6 . 9 2 5 6	4 . 3 9 2 3	1 2 . 3 4 9 9	1 0 . 7 2 5 5	3 . 5 1 3 1
5	3 . 2 8 8 0	5 . 4 9 9 6	7 . 5 8 1 4	9 . 5 9 8 4	8 . 1 6 2 2	1 2 . 7 1 7 3	1 0 . 4 8 2 9	6 . 2 0 9 7
6	6 . 1 0 4 7	0 . 3 6 3 9	3 . 2 1 0 7	6 . 5 1 1 5	8 . 9 2 6 9	8 . 1 0 6 2	9 . 1 7 1 7	7 . 1 4 3 7
7	1 1 . 7 6 8 5	5 . 7 1 9 7	2 . 9 2 2 6	3 . 1 3 4 9	4 . 2 8 5 7	7 . 1 6 5 0	9 . 4 2 9 5	5 . 3 8 5 7

8	1 1 . 1 2 6 4	5 . 5 6 8 0	2 . 0 6 1 6	1 3 . 7 9 3 9	1 1 . 7 7 6 6	1 . 2 8 3 4	1 2 . 1 1 0 2	2 . 4 4 0 7
9	1 3 . 1 3 8 6	1 0 . 9 7 1 3	1 0 . 1 0 5 3	1 1 . 1 5 5 4	9 . 3 4 2 9	6 . 2 0 4 7	1 . 8 8 6 0	1 2 . 3 8 7 3
1 0	3 . 7 2 4 3	3 . 1 6 7 4	1 0 . 5 0 9 5	1 2 . 1 2 3 0	4 . 6 3 1 2	8 . 0 0 9 2	2 . 2 0 1 5	7 . 8 8 8 8
1 1	1 2 . 4 0 8 0	8 . 2 5 4 5	0 . 7 7 3 3	5 . 1 0 7 2	6 . 4 7 8 6	1 . 7 3 2 0	2 . 2 1 9 2	3 . 7 6 3 1
1 2	1 0 . 0 7 2 6	8 . 6 5 5 1	7 . 9 3 6 2	4 . 8 7 7 8	6 . 3 8 5 4	6 . 1 9 5 6	1 1 . 0 5 3 8	8 . 1 4 9 5
1 3	4 . 7 0 6 7	0 . 1 9 0 9	1 . 5 6 4 8	1 0 . 5 3 7 1	1 0 . 1 0 6 3	6 . 5 0 6 2	1 0 . 9 9 1 6	1 0 . 2 0 9 4
1 4	1 3 . 6 8 7 1	7 . 5 2 9 8	8 . 1 2 1 0	1 1 . 4 0 2 2	9 . 9 5 4 9	8 . 1 3 3 4	1 2 . 5 1 2 9	0 . 2 3 3 5
1 5	6 . 5 2	3 . 6 9	1 0 . 5	3 . 3 0	4 . 9 0	8 . 1 3	4 . 3 0	5 . 5 0

	1 2	4 8	2 8 6	5 9	8 1	0 3	8 2	6 0
1 6	5 . 7 0 0 8	8 . 8 9 8 0	9 . 9 0 5 5	2 . 1 0 8 8	1 3 . 8 2 8 4	1 2 . 4 1 7 7	3 . 8 3 4 0	1 0 . 8 2 4 8
1 7	5 . 7 6 0 7	6 . 4 5 7 0	7 . 7 5 9 5	4 . 9 1 0 1	4 . 5 4 7 9	6 . 2 0 8 2	8 . 9 9 9 3	1 0 . 8 3 1 2
1 8	1 0 . 7 3 0 4	9 . 1 6 0 5	0 . 7 0 1 6	1 0 . 2 4 0 9	8 . 8 1 2 6	4 . 1 5 9 4	5 . 9 4 4 3	1 2 . 5 2 4 2
1 9	4 . 7 8 8 8	2 . 7 7 6 0	1 2 . 7 4 2 2	6 . 3 7 7 4	6 . 6 4 3 9	1 . 9 0 2 7	1 . 0 0 1 3	0 . 0 4 2 3
2 0	1 0 . 3 5 6 5	5 . 4 2 0 3	1 1 . 3 3 4 8	6 . 8 5 1 3	1 0 . 0 2 6 7	1 3 . 7 0 9 4	1 0 . 4 4 6 6	2 . 6 2 6 4
2 1	4 . 0 0 8 2	3 . 0 8 6 4	1 . 6 4 9 1	6 . 7 6 4 9	1 0 . 2 4 8 0	3 . 1 5 2 6	7 . 8 1 8 7	0 . 4 9 1 5
2 2	1 . 4 9 2 4	4 . 2 0 1 2	0 . 0 6 1 9	9 . 6 2 2 1	8 . 8 9 0 2	9 . 2 8 1 3	2 . 9 6 4 7	3 . 8 4 6 2
2 3	3 . .	1 1	5 .	4 .	4 .	8 .	1 0	1 2

	7 8 6 2	. 8 7 7 9	0 7 9 7	7 9 3 4	2 2 6 2	4 9 5 4	. 6 8 7 2	. 1 0 2 2
2 4	4 .3 6 6 3	7 .4 8 7 1	4 .5 2 5 9	6 .3 7 9 2	2 .2 9 9 9	1 1 8 9 0 2	0 .7 8 9 5	6 .1 1 4 7
2 5	1 0 .4 8 3 2	0 .2 1 4 8	0 .7 3 5 6	7 .3 7 4 2	1 1 0 0 0 6	1 1 9 4 6 3	1 0 .0 6 0 7	2 .7 8 1 7
2 6	4 .6 1 3 9	6 .8 3 4 4	7 .0 1 0 3	1 2 .3 2 6 6	1 .8 5 2 3	4 7 2 0 4	6 5 7 4 3	3 .5 2 1 4
2 7	9 .6 2 3 6	7 .5 2 1 2	9 .9 7 5 0	2 .1 5 2 6	2 .2 9 9 7	3 .3 3 8 4	1 1 5 3 3 9	8 .0 3 5 5
2 8	5 .5 7 1 8	1 1 .6 3 5 3	2 .8 3 1 7	1 3 .1 6 0 3	3 .1 7 8 8	2 .2 9 8 3	1 0 .5 1 9 6	1 0 .5 2 2 3
2 9	2 .9 8 7 9	1 2 .9 2 6 5	6 .3 8 8 4	7 .2 3 6 2	1 .5 3 8 1	2 .5 5 9 6	5 .6 6 2 7	6 .0 3 6 7
3 0	3 .9 9 0 7	2 .3 2 6 1	1 0 .6 7 3	1 2 .9 6 1	1 2 .6 9 6	7 .0 5 9 6	1 .8 2 9 4	9 .4 4 0 8

			9	7	0			
3 1	6 . 7 4 3 5	7 . 2 9 6 5	4 . 1 3 5 8	0 . 7 0 6 5	3 . 5 8 5 7	1 1 . 4 4 8 2	1 3 . 2 8 6 6	1 3 . 0 0 3 8
3 2	1 1 . 8 6 0 3	8 . 7 1 4 4	1 1 . 2 6 0 8	6 . 7 2 6 1	3 . 8 8 3 5	6 . 3 5 9 5	4 . 6 4 8 0	3 . 5 8 0 9
3 3	1 0 . 3 7 3 5	8 . 0 6 3 7	1 0 . 1 9 9 4	8 . 9 6 5 7	1 2 . 2 9 0 4	5 . 0 1 3 8	1 . 5 3 2 0	7 . 8 1 2 7
3 4	1 3 . 0 9 9 2	7 . 2 0 1 8	0 . 0 6 6 9	1 3 . 1 4 9 9	1 0 . 6 2 3 3	1 3 . 6 2 6 5	2 . 5 7 4 2	6 . 6 9 4 2
3 5	0 . 3 6 9 2	0 . 2 1 4 3	3 . 5 4 8 2	2 . 5 0 6 9	8 . 5 3 3 2	0 . 6 2 3 1	4 . 8 5 4 6	3 . 3 7 1 9
3 6	7 . 9 0 8 1	1 . 7 4 8 1	0 . 1 1 5 2	3 . 0 4 0 6	1 0 . 6 5 0 1	7 . 6 5 2 1	1 0 . 2 3 2 0	8 . 3 9 7 0
3 7	4 . 8 0 8 2	1 2 . 3 0 9 6	5 . 6 5 9 9	9 . 3 6 4 9	4 . 7 4 0 4	1 . 6 4 2 8	3 . 9 9 2 4	0 . 5 9 7 4
3 8	9 . 3 9	6 . 9 7	4 . 2 4	4 . 9 5	1 0 . 7	0 . 9 0	6 . 7 8	0 . 7 3

	7 0	4 2	5 9	3 8	8 7 9	8 9	4 6	6 3
3 9	1 0 . 6 4 7 8	9 . 7 9 0 7	3 . 2 0 1 1	8 . 0 4 6 3	1 0 . 3 3 1 6	2 . 3 0 1 9	1 2 . 7 6 9 4	1 0 . 5 0 3 2
4 0	2 . 7 6 7 2	7 . 5 7 4 6	6 . 6 0 8 8	1 2 . 6 9 7 6	9 . 7 3 8 8	6 . 4 9 8 4	1 0 . 5 3 7 8	8 . 5 5 8 9
4 1	5 . 6 7 5 7	1 2 . 9 3 3 1	3 . 9 5 9 4	1 0 . 7 4 3 4	0 . 8 9 1 4	9 . 2 0 7 8	6 . 6 3 9 1	2 . 1 1 0 8
4 2	2 . 3 8 6 2	7 . 5 3 9	0 . 3 5 7 6	8 . 5 2 2 4	5 . 1 7 3 5	6 . 9 8 8 6	0 . 8 7 2 4	2 . 2 8 2 4
4 3	5 . 9 0 5 9	4 . 9 4 9 1	0 . 6 3 9 6	5 . 0 9 7 4	8 . 9 4 0 9	5 . 3 4 0 6	9 . 6 7 5 9	2 . 9 9 8 5
4 4	0 . 3 8 9 5	0 . 0 1 1 9	5 . 7 3 5 4	9 . 7 7 7 0	1 3 . 0 2 3 3	1 . 7 8 8 7	3 . 8 4 7 5	3 . 6 8 1 8
4 5	0 . 6 0 4 8	1 0 . 5 5 9 2	3 . 1 0 2 0	5 . 2 7 7 0	1 . 4 0 4 9	8 . 5 2 3 8	5 . 3 9 6 7	4 . 6 0 6 2
4 6	5 . 6	2 . 2	6 . 2	1 . 7	6 . 8	4 . 9	1 2 .	1 1 .

	0 5 6	5 9 8	7 1 9	8 8 4	5 2 1	1 7 6	1 8 0 4	9 5 5 2
4 7	8 . 9 3 7 4	1 . 4 2 8 0	3 . 3 8 9 2	5 . 2 1 7 0	1 . 9 0 9 6	7 . 0 1 0 6	1 2 . 1 7 1 6	3 . 6 1 4 9
4 8	0 . 5 8 9 6	2 . 3 4 0 1	3 . 2 6 4 4	1 0 . 4 3 5 6	9 . 2 7 4 3	1 1 . 2 0 6 5	8 . 2 7 5 4	1 1 . 7 3 5 3
4 9	7 . 7 1 6 3	1 1 . 2 0 0 7	1 . 3 2 5 6	7 . 1 8 9 8	2 . 3 8 6 3	4 . 9 5 2 6	5 . 5 9 0 7	5 . 2 0 4 2
5 0	1 . 0 3 1 4	5 . 5 6 3 8	3 . 5 4 4 1	9 . 9 7 3 9	4 . 5 5 5 3	8 . 2 0 8 8	6 . 8 3 3 6	1 2 . 5 2 1 7
5 1	1 . 4 9 6 5	7 . 7 0 3 5	1 2 . 8 5 0 0	4 . 3 7 4 0	1 . 5 4 9 2	7 . 9 1 3 6	0 . 7 4 2 9	1 2 . 7 3 0 1
5 2	1 . 5 8 7 2	0 . 9 8 4 3	1 0 . 5 1 8 3	6 . 8 0 6 3	1 1 . 4 6 2 8	6 . 3 8 0 2	8 . 9 0 5 9	1 . 2 9 5 0
5 3	4 . 1 7 3 6	1 2 . 3 3 7 9	5 . 7 8 5 8	5 . 9 3 5 9	9 . 3 5 4 9	2 . 1 6 3 8	5 . 6 6 4 5	1 1 . 1 3 5 7

5 4	1 . 2 9 4 4	6 . 2 6 5 6	9 . 5 6 6 3	7 . 5 6 5 4	4 . 7 0 0 4	1 1 . 1 7 7 5	1 2 . 1 0 7 7	3 . 6 6 6 1
5 5	6 . 4 7 6 9	8 . 8 6 5 5	0 . 6 3 5 7	5 . 9 7 8 8	9 . 7 6 4 8	0 . 6 8 4 1	6 . 0 6 0 7	0 . 7 6 4 9
5 6	9 . 4 2 9 7	9 . 1 0 4 4	3 . 1 3 7 8	1 1 . 6 9 1 3	3 . 3 2 7 7	5 . 7 6 6 5	4 . 5 1 7 7	4 . 2 2 8 3
5 7	9 . 4 3 3 5	8 . 7 5 9 8	0 . 8 5 7 9	1 0 . 7 7 4 6	2 . 8 2 2 1	3 . 9 9 3 7	1 0 . 7 5 0 6	9 . 6 8 5 4
5 8	7 . 7 8 5 1	1 0 . 3 1 5 6	7 . 9 6 8 2	1 0 . 6 1 7 5	0 . 2 0 1 6	7 . 9 1 1 1	8 . 0 8 6 8	6 . 2 0 8 8
5 9	1 2 . 3 9 4 8	1 3 . 9 6 6 5	1 . 1 5 8	9 . 5 1 9 2	6 . 6 7 8 0	9 . 9 2 1 3	2 . 4 4 7 7	5 . 5 1 0 0
6 0	1 . 8 3 1 5	1 0 . 1 0 0 4	3 . 7 6 3 0	1 . 6 2 9 8	2 . 5 0 2 9	4 . 8 8 8 0	3 . 2 2 3 2	1 . 1 0 6 8

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S l . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 2 . 8 1 1 0	1 1 . 8 2 7 5	3 . 4 8 4 9	2 . 9 7 8 8	9 . 6 9 6 4	5 . 3 7 0 0	8 . 8 5 2 1	1 0 . 4 3 6 4
2	1 . 1 9 1 8	1 3 . 7 5 4 8	8 . 9 8 5 7	1 1 . 9 3 7 3	9 . 6 6 8 8	3 . 7 7 8 4	3 . 3 1 5 9	1 0 . 5 0 7 6
3	4 . 5 5 4 4	7 . 9 1 7 7	4 . 6 3 8 4	4 . 5 0 1 5	8 . 8 7 8 0	1 0 . 0 0 9 6	6 . 0 7 4 7	7 . 3 2 5 5
4	6 . 8 5 8 2	9 . 3 0 8 1	0 . 8 2 8 5	6 . 2 0 9 2	7 . 7 2 7 6	1 1 . 6 8 7 3	3 . 6 9 9 3	9 . 4 0 0 3
5	5 . 1 1 9 7	3 . 0 7 3 9	6 . 4 1 7 9	8 . 3 0 1 4	8 . 9 3 8 3	2 . 0 8 5 2	5 . 2 8 3 6	1 2 . 5 4 5 0
6	7 . 6 3 1 7	6 . 0 9 1 8	2 . 2 0 0 7	5 . 3 7 8 4	4 . 2 3 7 0	7 . 7 2 6 6	2 . 1 2 6 6	8 . 1 3 3 4
7	4 . 0 6	6 . 9 8	4 . 6 9	1 3 . 6 6	0 . 7 8	3 . 3 5	8 . 0 4	3 . 5 4

	2 3	0 2	5 7	5 3 4	3 1	4 5	4 7	5 5
8	4 . 0 1 9 9	1 0 . 3 4 0 5	4 . 3 4 5 5	9 . 1 7 9 1	2 . 3 6 6 3	1 2 . 4 8 4 4	1 2 . 6 0 5 0	7 . 9 7 1 6
9	5 . 1 0 3 9	6 . 4 7 1 0	7 . 6 2 8 9	6 . 2 8 1 2	6 . 4 2 2 4	1 3 . 0 8 8 0	1 3 . 6 3 6 6	3 . 0 3 9 5
1 0	6 . 9 7 7 1	0 . 4 3 7 3	1 . 4 7 3 9	1 . 3 9 5 4	1 2 . 0 1 8 7	1 0 . 9 9 0 3	8 . 9 8 7 8	0 . 7 2 5 6
1 1	8 . 2 4 9 7	1 2 . 4 8 0 4	1 2 . 7 4 5 8	2 . 6 8 0 1	3 . 0 1 8 4	1 1 . 3 7 5 1	4 . 3 1 7 3	3 . 1 0 8 1
1 2	5 . 0 5 3 1	5 . 9 8 7 3	7 . 9 9 5 6	1 2 . 1 6 0 3	0 . 7 7 0 2	4 . 7 8 2 1	7 . 0 8 5 0	0 . 0 5 7 0
1 3	4 . 6 4 3 9	1 2 . 2 1 3 9	1 0 . 5 4 8 3	9 . 4 1 8 2	1 2 . 5 8 5 7	1 1 . 0 2 6 1	1 2 . 6 7 0 0	1 1 . 0 5 3 1
1 4	0 . 8 7 0 9	2 . 4 3 9 7	4 . 0 4 9 4	2 . 5 5 2 5	1 . 5 7 5 6	0 . 0 1 1 3	1 3 . 2 9 1 2	8 . 8 4 6 6
1	1	2	2	9	5	1	8	9

5	2 . 4 7 6 0	. 9 2 7 5	. 8 1 8 9	. 5 3 6 3	. 8 4 8 2	1 . 2 2 6 9	. 4 8 1 9	. 6 5 3 9
1 6	5 . 8 5 7 8	1 0 . 1 5 6 3	8 . 5 4 6 0	4 . 3 3 4 8	8 . 4 4 4 9	1 2 . 3 0 1 2	3 . 3 2 4 8	3 . 1 8 0 3
1 7	5 . 7 6 9 9	2 . 7 6 4 3	1 0 . 4 9 7 8	4 . 6 1 1 6	6 . 0 1 2 1	4 . 2 3 4 7	6 . 0 0 1 4	1 1 . 8 4 7 9
1 8	4 . 4 0 1 4	7 . 9 3 6 2	0 . 3 1 8 3	8 . 3 9 6 9	1 0 . 8 0 3 0	1 2 . 9 8 4 0	0 . 2 7 0 0	5 . 1 0 5 4
1 9	0 . 6 3 7 1	2 . 3 0 2 1	6 . 9 1 6 3	8 . 1 7 5 6	9 . 0 4 1 6	1 . 6 2 3 9	1 1 . 9 6 2 8	1 0 . 7 7 6 3
2 0	0 . 2 0 3 7	9 . 8 3 7 5	1 0 . 8 2 6 2	7 . 9 2 3 3	9 . 5 9 9 2	1 1 . 3 8 0 4	1 0 . 9 5 9 8	1 3 . 9 4 8 3
2 1	9 . 6 3 5 9	1 0 . 9 7 5 0	9 . 2 6 4 5	0 . 9 1 1 2	8 . 0 7 9 8	0 . 8 9 1 6	4 . 3 2 0	7 . 3 3 0 0
2 2	9 . 1 3 7	8 . 8 6 1	7 . 2 9 1	2 . 1 9 0	7 . 7 6 3	5 . 9 2 0	7 . 0 1 1	1 0 . 4 3

	7	3	6	3	6	5	0	8 6
2 3	5 . 1 5 7 2	8 . 0 4 8 1	1 . 9 2 2 5	1 1 . 0 8 0 7	4 . 0 0 0 9	8 . 7 6 5 5	1 1 . 1 1 6 4	2 . 3 2 9 4
2 4	5 . 6 3 3 7	1 0 . 5 3 0 5	5 . 4 7 5 1	8 . 8 5 3 4	7 . 3 7 5 9	4 . 1 8 1 5	1 3 . 3 3 9 0	7 . 1 6 0 8
2 5	6 . 5 3 4 4	2 . 1 0 9 3	8 . 9 7 4 8	5 . 8 3 4 3	9 . 2 7 7 9	8 . 1 7 9 9	1 3 . 2 7 0 7	1 1 . 8 6 1 6
2 6	8 . 1 3 0 1	1 . 0 5 5 8	3 . 5 4 0 1	2 . 9 8 4 4	2 . 2 9 7 2	1 3 . 3 9 6 6	6 . 5 6 7 5	1 0 . 0 9 8 8
2 7	2 . 7 3 3 7	8 . 9 9 0 5	7 . 7 0 7 0	4 . 1 0 2 5	1 2 . 6 2 5 1	7 . 1 2 9 2	1 2 . 5 8 7 5	5 . 8 6 1 6
2 8	6 . 4 2 6 5	4 . 9 9 0 1	1 0 . 1 8 9 1	6 . 8 7 2 6	8 . 7 5 1 6	6 . 6 3 2 9	1 . 7 3 5 5	1 3 . 9 0 4 9
2 9	1 . 7 5 0 8	3 . 9 0 1 5	3 . 6 4 1 7	1 0 . 6 2 7 8	0 . 8 2 3 1	1 2 . 2 6 9 3	2 . 0 8 3 1	7 . 7 0 0 0
3 0	9 . .	1 2	6 .	1 .	3 .	2 .	8 .	8 .

	3 7 3 9	. 6 0 6 2	0 9 8 7	6 3 7 5	7 3 7 4	8 2 9 8	8 1 1 2	3 9 5 3
3 1	6 .br/>6 7 9 3	1 2 .br/>0 8 4 8	1 0 .br/>0 5 6 3	9 .br/>3 6 2 5	2 .br/>1 3 4 4	8 .br/>9 7 3 1	5 .br/>2 9 8 8	1 .br/>3 0 0 0
3 2	4 .br/>5 5 2 0	1 .br/>5 6 9 6	2 .br/>3 7 5 3	1 1 .br/>4 9 1 8	3 .br/>0 9 1 8	8 .br/>6 1 3 7	0 .br/>9 4 4 5	1 0 .br/>2 2 2 0
3 3	8 .br/>7 9 7 3	8 .br/>0 3 7 9	3 .br/>0 2 8 1	3 .br/>8 4 4 8	0 .br/>9 6 4 2	9 .br/>6 0 8 0	4 .br/>0 9 8 4	8 .br/>7 8 3 4
3 4	3 .br/>3 3 6 4	0 .br/>2 6 7 4	1 .br/>3 9 7 3	8 .br/>1 2 6 3	6 .br/>9 1 2 4	1 .br/>1 0 7 3	0 .br/>2 5 2 8	7 .br/>3 5 9 5
3 5	8 .br/>2 2 0 3	1 2 .br/>8 6 6 7	1 0 .br/>7 5 4 2	0 .br/>2 5 1 0	0 .br/>8 6 7 9	1 0 .br/>2 7 3 9	7 .br/>0 4 4 1	9 .br/>9 8 5 8
3 6	1 1 .br/>9 9 2 1	1 0 .br/>3 8 4 3	4 .br/>7 3 8 6	1 1 .br/>4 8 1 3	2 .br/>1 9 9 9	9 .br/>6 5 5 6	7 .br/>1 4 3 9	4 .br/>6 3 5 1
3 7	1 0 .br/>2 0 0 7	1 .br/>5 6 7 0	1 1 .br/>5 2 2 3	2 .br/>8 0 8 6	2 .br/>9 2 7 2	1 0 .br/>7 1 5 8	9 .br/>6 1 7 1	6 .br/>3 5 9 3
3	0	8	1	1	2	9	4	2

8	. 2 5 9 0	. 2 6 9 2	2 . 1 4 1 0	. 8 7 2 2	. 5 6 4 7	. 0 3 7 2	. 1 2 8 9	. 5 9 9 3
3 9	1 3 . 5 8 0 5	1 1 . 9 4 9 2	5 . 2 5 9 2	4 . 4 6 5 5	6 . 3 7 1 4	4 . 0 0 5 6	1 . 0 4 8 5	5 . 2 8 8 9
4 0	5 . 2 2 3 2	2 . 5 5 9 2	7 . 0 9 6 8	9 . 2 4 8 2	6 . 5 7 4 3	1 . 1 2 3 7	4 . 8 1 7 4	6 . 5 9 7 1
4 1	1 . 8 1 3 3	9 . 2 2 2 4	5 . 9 6 2 3	1 2 . 9 4 5 5	4 . 5 3 0 7	6 . 5 3 0 2	4 . 7 6 0 4	2 . 7 9 2 0
4 2	1 . 2 8 7 3	9 . 3 4 0 1	3 . 1 8 6 0	1 1 . 4 3 5 0	7 . 4 9 9 3	3 . 2 8 8 4	9 . 5 3 4 0	8 . 9 0 3 8
4 3	5 . 5 2 5 7	8 . 2 7 0 9	2 . 8 2 2 8	9 . 4 3 6 4	1 3 . 0 1 4 6	3 . 3 4 4 2	1 3 . 5 7 1 7	6 . 6 3 7 4
4 4	6 . 6 2 8 1	6 . 6 8 8 5	1 0 . 1 5 6 2	6 . 5 1 4 1	7 . 5 0 6 7	6 . 7 4 2 5	1 . 3 9 6 1	8 . 5 3 2 1
4 5	1 0 . 8 4 7	4 . 0 5 4 2	2 . 6 5 1 4	4 . 0 5 9 6	1 2 . 2 5 5 2	8 . 8 6 9 3	2 . 6 6 1 1	6 . 8 0 2 9

	4				8			
4 6	0 . 6 0 2 5	1 2 . 9 1 9 8	1 0 . 4 3 6 2	1 2 . 0 2 1 2	8 . 5 5 7 9	0 . 7 3 5 2	0 . 3 6 2 9	1 . 2 5 2 5
4 7	9 . 4 4 6 5	4 . 2 2 1 3	1 3 . 7 9 2 3	8 . 2 6 3 5	7 . 0 9 8 5	0 . 9 1 7 9	2 . 6 5 2 0	8 . 4 1 6 8
4 8	3 . 8 1 3 5	7 . 7 6 4 9	5 . 8 0 2 4	0 . 5 5 3 5	1 0 . 3 6 4 7	4 . 1 9 1 1	1 0 . 0 5 4 3	4 . 1 9 9 0
4 9	1 . 1 8 8 0	1 . 4 5 0 2	2 . 9 9 4 1	0 . 1 9 4 0	5 . 5 5 1 9	1 2 . 2 1 5 6	1 0 . 2 9 7 8	1 1 . 6 2 8 5
5 0	7 . 9 1 1 5	2 . 0 5 9 9	9 . 0 5 4 8	0 . 7 1 7 0	0 . 2 9 2 2	1 2 . 0 5 9 9	0 . 5 3 3 3	4 . 4 6 1 8
5 1	6 . 2 6 9 9	1 . 2 1 2 1	8 . 6 5 6 9	7 . 2 2 9 5	1 . 6 0 0 3	6 . 5 9 7 0	8 . 4 3 8 3	9 . 9 0 8 0
5 2	2 . 9 4 3 1	7 . 5 6 9 3	0 . 9 6 5 2	9 . 6 5 4 8	7 . 9 0 0 0	8 . 7 9 4 4	6 . 4 4 9 7	1 . 4 0 0 8
5 3	1 . 9 8	9 . 2 0 3	1 2 . 1 3	2 . 4 9 4	2 . 7 1 2	1 . 6 3 2	1 . 6 7 4	2 . 7 7 9

	2 9	2	9 4	0	7	1	1	2
5 4	0 . 9 4 4 8	1 2 . 4 5 6 3	1 0 . 9 8 5 9	8 . 0 0 6 0	9 . 6 2 0 8	1 0 . 5 6 6 3	7 . 2 4 6 9	0 . 3 1 5 3
5 5	1 2 . 6 2 9 0	1 . 4 6 4 1	7 . 3 7 9 2	1 . 2 6 0 5	7 . 7 1 0 5	1 2 . 6 5 3 0	1 0 . 0 7 8 5	9 . 6 2 4 0
5 6	1 0 . 3 1 7 2	0 . 9 1 3 2	3 . 1 0 7 4	7 . 6 8 4 4	5 . 7 1 4 6	4 . 4 0 6 0	1 . 0 5 4 8	1 1 . 6 6 3 9
5 7	5 . 8 8 3 3	4 . 9 2 9 7	1 1 . 0 1 5 8	0 . 8 1 1 3	1 1 . 1 1 3 3	1 . 7 4 5 0	1 2 . 0 9 4 6	1 3 . 9 5 8 1
5 8	5 . 8 9 6 6	4 . 9 0 0 8	5 . 0 3 5 9	1 2 . 3 0 2 8	2 . 4 2 7 5	1 1 . 8 4 5 6	5 . 6 4 0 4	1 2 . 3 2 0 1
5 9	7 . 4 2 5 1	1 . 2 4 6 8	1 3 . 1 6 7 1	2 . 7 3 5 2	7 . 7 6 6 8	1 . 3 5 1 6	7 . 9 4 4 6	8 . 0 4 6 6
6 0	4 . 3 3 4 6	1 . 7 1 8 1	2 . 4 9 6 5	3 . 4 1 5 0	7 . 4 9 2 3	0 . 1 3 6 3	3 . 7 4 6 1	6 . 7 9 9 3

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1 . N o .	F P 0 1	F P 0 2	F P 0 3	F P 0 4	F P 0 5	F P 0 6	F P 0 7	F P 0 8
1	1 0 . 4 8 4 1	2 . 3 7 3 4	5 . 7 2 6 7	8 . 5 4 5 5	3 . 7 2 6 4	5 . 8 6 6 0	9 . 9 2 0 0	1 2 . 6 6 4 6
2	4 . 0 3 5 7	0 . 1 4 8 7	1 2 . 8 0 6 0	4 . 1 2 0 2	9 . 9 5 8 4	0 . 9 4 5 1	7 . 8 4 4 8	1 3 . 9 4 6 3
3	7 . 3 9 0 1	5 . 3 4 9 7	1 0 . 8 2 9 9	2 . 0 4 4 6	2 . 7 0 4 5	1 2 . 7 9 3 6	4 . 8 1 2 5	7 . 3 9 0 3
4	1 2 . 9 3 9 8	2 . 6 5 7 1	4 . 5 6 9 5	7 . 4 1 6 9	9 . 6 5 8 6	1 0 . 9 1 1 7	2 . 9 1 7 7	3 . 7 5 1 6
5	7 . 4 5 1 8	7 . 2 8 0 5	1 0 . 2 5 0 7	9 . 6 6 2 1	3 . 5 1 1 4	7 . 8 5 1 1	1 3 . 3 5 6 9	5 . 2 2 2 4
6	3 . 5 8 9 1	2 . 2 1 2 8	1 2 . 1 0 0 8	0 . 9 3 2 9	3 . 3 1 4 6	3 . 0 2 2 2	8 . 5 7 7 0	1 3 . 7 9 1 8
7	8 . 8 7 4	1 3 . 6 2	0 . 6 5 4	8 . 4 2 0	6 . 6 6 0	6 . 2 5 8	5 . 7 2 1	8 . 4 4 0

	0	3 7	7	6	3	6	6	9
8	6 . 7 5 2 2	9 . 1 6 9 9	1 . 2 8 2 6	2 . 3 1 0 8	1 2 . 5 9 3 9	3 . 4 7 5 6	1 1 . 5 3 3 5	5 . 9 8 1 1
9	1 . 7 4 7 6	5 . 1 4 3 6	1 3 . 7 6 1 7	6 . 9 4 0 3	1 . 0 7 4 2	4 . 4 6 7 5	9 . 2 7 9 1	0 . 3 1 8 4
1 0	1 . 1 3 0 1	1 . 1 4 9 6	1 0 . 6 8 0 8	5 . 6 3 0 2	7 . 5 4 6 9	1 . 4 6 6 0	7 . 5 4 5 7	2 . 5 4 1 7
1 1	7 . 8 4 1 7	3 . 7 7 3 7	6 . 3 0 9 1	9 . 3 6 1 6	9 . 1 4 1 9	4 . 5 2 8 8	3 . 1 2 6 7	1 2 . 1 6 9 8
1 2	1 1 . 4 1 5 5	1 . 9 5 1 5	9 . 8 3 2 4	5 . 7 0 0 5	7 . 4 7 2 4	8 . 1 7 3 1	1 1 . 1 3 6 7	4 . 3 1 4 0
1 3	5 . 4 7 1 8	4 . 0 4 8 9	3 . 9 0 7 4	1 . 8 7 0 7	7 . 8 7 3 5	6 . 2 1 1 4	1 1 . 1 6 0 0	1 . 0 3 0 6
1 4	0 . 3 3 0 7	8 . 4 9 4 2	7 . 7 2 6 1	3 . 9 4 5 1	3 . 6 9 3 6	1 2 . 8 7 1 7	1 1 . 6 2 6 9	1 3 . 9 3 5 2
1 5	6 . .	1 0	1 0	6 .	1 0	1 .	6 .	7 .

	1 4 5 9	. 2 1 9 6	. 5 9 1 8	9 2 8 1	. 0 5 0 3	1 1 2 9	0 9 7 1	7 8 1 9
1 6	7 . 9 7 5 4	1 0 . 9 2 6 8	1 2 . 8 2 5 1	2 . 3 3 0 2	6 . 0 7 8	8 . 9 8 1 5	7 . 7 5 0 0	5 . 7 0 7 4
1 7	1 3 . 7 8 6 0	1 . 9 3 3 6	4 . 4 1 3 4	1 3 . 0 6 3 1	1 0 . 1 0 4 9	5 . 3 0 2 6	0 . 8 5 2 2	1 . 0 8 2 7
1 8	6 . 4 3 7 8	5 . 1 9 3 7	8 . 7 2 3 1	2 . 3 7 4 7	3 . 2 0 2 1	5 . 6 4 9 9	6 . 0 4 0 4	0 . 4 0 7 3
1 9	1 2 . 7 5 0 1	1 2 . 5 1 0 1	1 . 0 5 7 2	1 2 . 6 5 5 3	1 0 . 9 6 4 3	1 . 4 3 5 8	1 2 . 0 8 3 1	8 . 1 8 1 6
2 0	0 . 6 1 8 8	3 . 2 5 0 8	1 . 3 8 8 1	8 . 8 0 2 7	2 . 1 1 7 4	4 . 9 1 6 6	1 3 . 9 2 1 3	6 . 1 8 3 7
2 1	1 0 . 5 5 5 6	4 . 6 6 6 7	1 . 7 4 4 0	7 . 0 3 8 9	7 . 4 9 2 7	4 . 0 6 6 6	3 . 7 9 0 8	7 . 6 0 3 3
2 2	1 1 . 5 1 4 0	0 . 2 5 5 0	9 . 4 8 7 4	1 . 3 0 7 9	3 . 2 9 8 8	1 2 . 4 3 7 3	3 . 3 6 5 4	6 . 8 3 7 4

2 3	6 . 3 9 3 2	8 . 8 4 7 2	8 . 3 7 4 4	1 0 . 6 8 8 3	4 . 8 0 8 7	4 . 7 9 5 9	5 . 8 4 7 0	2 . 7 1 6 2
2 4	2 . 1 2 6 4	9 . 9 9 0 2	1 . 2 8 6 2	9 . 7 2 1 5	3 . 5 3 3 4	5 . 5 2 3 5	4 . 2 6 1 1	1 0 . 8 1 5 0
2 5	0 . 9 7 2 3	1 1 . 6 6 0 8	1 3 . 2 9 2 6	4 . 3 0 0 8	1 1 . 3 1 4	3 . 3 7 0 5	7 . 2 3 2 1	7 . 0 3 2 1
2 6	1 2 . 1 5 8 4	0 . 6 8 6 7	2 . 1 4 2 0	9 . 3 2 1 0	1 2 . 4 9 7 8	1 0 . 4 9 4 1	4 . 5 8 9 6	5 . 3 1 5 6
2 7	8 . 1 8 5 8	7 . 5 7 6 2	2 . 7 6 2 9	1 2 . 1 8 9 7	3 . 7 6 5 9	4 . 9 5 0 9	1 3 . 4 0 6 0	1 . 0 3 3 4
2 8	5 . 1 7 2 8	8 . 9 6 6 7	3 . 4 6 0 2	5 . 9 9 1 8	5 . 7 1 3 6	4 . 5 0 5 8	8 . 1 6 3 7	7 . 1 6 2 2
2 9	1 . 9 9 5 4	9 . 0 0 6 2	3 . 3 6 0 9	9 . 5 4 2 0	2 . 7 2 1 4	6 . 1 4 5 7	8 . 5 6 8 5	8 . 7 9 5 0
3 0	1 2 . 1 7 1	1 3 . 1 7 5	1 3 . 9 1 3	4 . 3 1 9 6	1 1 . 7 8 3	9 . 0 8 4 1	9 . 1 6 9 0	5 . 4 4 8 6

	6	0	7		1			
3 1	8 . 4 7 6 2	9 . 2 1 1 9	1 2 . 9 3 1 2	1 2 . 1 0 9 0	7 . 4 3 7 7	3 . 9 6 2 8	8 . 9 5 5 0	6 . 6 7 4 2
3 2	1 . 0 0 3 0	9 . 7 7 0 6	6 . 7 2 3 7	7 . 0 6 2 1	5 . 5 5 8	1 2 . 4 4 4 7	6 . 2 0 0 3	1 1 . 6 1 3 3
3 3	1 . 7 2 3 5	0 . 5 6 1 9	8 . 1 1 3 8	7 . 8 8 2 2	9 . 8 7 8 0	9 . 2 5 7 7	8 . 4 9 6 2	4 . 2 3 2 5
3 4	1 1 . 0 7 9 0	4 . 5 5 4 7	6 . 9 8 4 2	2 . 7 0 6 7	7 . 0 2 1 2	0 . 5 6 5 2	6 . 7 5 3 2	1 2 . 8 9 6 6
3 5	1 1 . 7 4 3 2	1 . 8 9 3 6	2 . 4 7 5 3	4 . 6 5 0 6	1 2 . 7 3 4 8	9 . 6 1 5 8	3 . 2 5 4 3	1 1 . 8 7 5 8
3 6	1 3 . 7 3 2 6	5 . 2 7 5 6	1 . 7 1 3 8	1 . 2 8 2 0	3 . 4 0 4 8	1 1 . 5 0 4 9	2 . 7 8 8 9	3 . 7 2 3 2
3 7	2 . 3 8 1 4	5 . 0 1 5 5	5 . 3 3 0 3	1 . 1 1 9 5	7 . 0 7 6 2	8 . 5 8 2 0	4 . 5 0 1 8	1 2 . 9 9 1 6
3 8	0 . 9 9	1 0 . 6	1 3 . 0	2 . 0 6	7 . 1 4	3 . 2 9	4 . 1 3	8 . 3 5

	7 2	3 4 1	8 1 7	4 0	2 5	1 1	5 3	4 8
3 9	0 . 1 0 3 8	0 . 0 4 6 1	6 . 5 6 5 8	5 . 3 3 6 9	6 . 7 3 6 6	1 0 . 1 4 3 5	6 . 5 2 4 3	2 . 5 5 2 6
4 0	3 . 8 6 5 1	1 0 . 8 1 5 7	2 . 2 2 6 5	0 . 8 8 8 5	3 . 2 2 8 2	8 . 9 8 1 0	1 1 . 2 5 4 2	9 . 6 5 2 0
4 1	1 3 . 7 5 2 5	1 0 . 2 4 2 0	9 . 8 5 6 9	1 1 . 6 6 5 2	3 . 8 7 0 1	1 0 . 2 9 2 3	3 . 0 3 0 7	5 . 0 7 1 5
4 2	8 . 6 1 8 7	4 . 1 7 5 5	8 . 7 0 7 6	8 . 2 5 2 2	1 2 . 0 3 8 9	9 . 2 8 0 0	6 . 8 9 6 2	4 . 0 0 5 3
4 3	1 0 . 1 2 7 7	1 0 . 6 8 1 4	1 2 . 2 5 5 3	8 . 6 7 8 3	1 2 . 5 2 4 3	1 . 2 5 1 9	9 . 1 6 3 3	5 . 3 1 2 4
4 4	1 2 . 2 6 7 5	1 3 . 8 0 9 8	2 . 1 1 5 0	4 . 8 2 5 3	8 . 8 4 7 7	5 . 4 4 9 2	6 . 0 1 4 3	1 1 . 4 8 4 3
4 5	7 . 2 8 8 0	5 . 2 2 5 9	7 . 8 2 4 3	1 . 5 6 5 3	1 2 . 6 0 6 4	1 . 6 5 0 4	6 . 5 2 9 0	6 . 5 9 5 8
4	6	2	1	1	1	2	4	7

6	. 4 0 7 5	. 9 6 9 7	2 .1 7 2 5	2 .4 4 8 5	2 .3 9 2 5	. 3 9 8 6	. 0 0 3 2	. 0 8 1 0
4 7	1 1 .7 7 4 8	8 .3 4 6 2	4 .9 2 5 7	1 0 .1 4 5 4	6 .8 2 4 3	8 .7 0 9 0	7 .2 5 4 3	3 .0 0 3 8
4 8	1 2 .4 1 7 8	0 .5 7 7 7	3 .0 2 2 4	9 .3 7 2 9	1 3 .2 4 2 9	1 2 .4 0 9 3	6 .8 0 9 3	1 1 .1 8 4 0
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5 1	1 .2 0 1 9	4 .9 7 1 4	1 2 .0 0 3 9	2 .3 5 6 8	1 .5 8 2 8	1 .8 8 9 9	5 .2 5 9 1	0 .6 9 8 6
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5 6	1 1 . 2 9 7 3	3 . 3 0 5 6	6 . 3 9 0 3	5 . 2 0 0 1	9 . 3 4 7 9	1 0 . 9 5 6 9	5 . 6 7 4 3	2 . 3 9 7 8
5 7	1 2 . 5 7 3 4	7 . 5 1 3 3	3 . 4 3 9 8	8 . 2 3 9 7	8 . 7 0 9 1	5 . 1 4 1 7	5 . 2 4 6 8	1 . 1 3 7 9
5 8	1 2 . 0 9 5 7	6 . 5 3 1 7	2 . 2 7 2 7	8 . 1 9 0 5	1 2 . 8 3 8 0	9 . 6 0 2 6	8 . 0 7 9 8	4 . 5 0 7 1
5 9	1 2 . 0 6 1 3	0 . 9 1 3 5	1 0 . 4 0 5 8	0 . 1 3 3 3	1 0 . 5 3 5 6	4 . 3 7 7 3	3 . 1 8 2 9	1 0 . 4 3 9 5
6 0	0 . 4 1 5 9	0 . 7 9 0 3	8 . 4 2 8 1	1 3 . 4 8 0 3	4 . 3 9 5 1	6 . 4 9 6 9	6 . 8 7 3 7	5 . 7 0 2 5

SUBJECT - 15

Figure - 20 / 02

Fluid brain power refers to individual's ability to solve problems, reason, and think abstractly, and is crucial for adapting to complex situations. This cognitive ability has been extensively studied in fields such as Psychology, Neuroscience, and Cognitive Science, and has been linked to various measures of brain structure and function. While exact neural mechanisms underlying fluid brain power are not fully comprehensible, research suggests that it involves complex interactions between different brain regions and complex inter-relations. Recent studies depict a phenomenon that fluid cerebral power is not a fixed trait and can be improved through various interventions. Neural efficiency hypothesis suggests that individuals with higher fluid brain power are more efficient in their use of neural resources, allowing them to perform complex cognitive tasks with less effort. Other studies have explored the role of genetics in fluid brain power and have identified specific genetic variants associated with it. Cognitive training, physical exercise, and mindfulness meditation are some of the interventions that have been studied to improve fluid brain power. While progress has been made in understanding factors that contribute to individual differences in fluid brain power, much remains to be learned about how it can be improved and how it relates to other aspects of cognitive functioning. Research attempt of fluid brain power continues to be an active and exciting area of research with implications for various domains such as education, occupational training, and cognitive enhancement.

Introduction

Fluid-based managerial judgement making is as old as Civilization. In a way, undisputedly, fluid-based managerial judgement making represents evolution and revolution of cognition as accepted extension of Science. Fluid-based managerial judgement making is critical in sense that correct tactic needs to be adopted to make balance between offshoots of inter-disciplinary scholarship in 21st Century. Foundation of stimulus has been neuro - based managerial judgement explorations (merger of philosophies from cognitive science and management. Recently, fluid-based managerial judgement making has arisen as inter-disciplinary determination that counterparts advance cognitive science. Some research issues addressed in this section are; highways and pathways through which fluid-based managerial judgement meander, how data is manipulated and managed by cerebral architectures and, how incompatible values are fashioned through continually permeating 'rational' predilections. In short; how does fluid-based manager choose via. Neuro-feedback and what part of brain aids perform fluid-based managerial judgement?

Fluid-based managerial judgement making is a crucial aspect which produces archetype of fluid magnetism in brain. Idea of causality is a defining characteristic of these sciences, and there are seeming differences in notions depending on different experimental approaches. Both explicit and implicit variations in these notions perhaps exist. In sciences of mind and brain, what counts as causal evidence and how information, facts, figures, statistics, evidence, and physical mechanisms are used to identify causal claimed are essential questions? Neuro - Social Sciences face defining problems concerning mental events, which are distributed. Basic cognitive operations and how they are used in judgment, fluid-based managerial judgement making, action, reason, choice, persuasion, and expression are fundamental to understanding these sciences. Extent of fluid-based managerial judgement-makers knowledge and how they choose, what incentives work best, and when judgment is reliable, are crucial considerations.

Additionally, understanding how cognitive conceptual resources depend on judgement context and how certain cognitive and conceptual systems become entrenched as shared knowledge and method is essential. Foundation of stimulus is based on fluid-based managerial judgement explorations that merge philosophies from Cognitive Science and Management. Fluid-based managerial judgement making has arisen as an inter-disciplinary determination to bridge the gap between managerial judgement making and brain sciences. However, interface between these fields is not smooth, and there may be misconceptions on either side. Neuroeconomic discoveries pose a challenge to traditional management viewpoint as questions arise concerning how all dissimilar magnitudes come unruffled to offer continual diversity and competitive superiority. The question being challenged currently is whether 'homo-economicus' is truly rational. Traditional belief was that homo-economicus aimed to maximize profits, and makes managerial judgements based on a set of rational choices using all available information. However, Efe Efeoğlu and Yurdanur Çalışkan argue that this assumption is flawed, as humans are not always rational beings. Other factors such as repetition, imitation, and social norms can influence human behaviour, making it difficult for individuals to always make rational managerial judgements.

The above viewpoint is basis for behavioural judgement, which proposes that people can only be rational to limited extent in their managerial judgement behaviour. Several alternative theories have been suggested, such as homo

heuristics, homo - reciprocates, homo - sociological, homo - politicus, and homo - duplex. Sheena S. Iyengar challenges traditional belief that choice is always advantageous, arguing that Biology and Psychology of choice can sometimes lead to negative outcomes. Derivative of cognitive and behavioural sciences, branded as multi - fanged and multi - rational science, neuro managerial dynamics, as emerging force to reckon with, is a new paradigm in realm of managerial sciences, per se. Biological experimentations, in the indices like managerial attitudes and heuristic plus posture. From perception of managerial philosophies fixated on thought outlines and image explanations, research tactic lies in addressing neuro - cognitive framework of manager's mind patterns, which help to overcome forces of volatility, capricious, intangible, inconsistent, and ambiguity.

This research attempt aimed to model neuro-feedback in managerial judgement making by monitoring brain waves through EEG and understanding the neural activity involved in managerial judgement making. The methodology involves using EEG conductors to record brain activity and physiological responses to soundings and developing theoretical models grounded in neurofeedback for EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making. The research aimed to contribute towards understanding neuro-design in managerial preference undercurrents and open up new avenues for future studies. This innovative research attempt provides a theoretical outline for coxswaining neurofeedback-management investigations and designates an inter-disciplinary prototype for neurofeedback-based choice construction.

1. What mechanisms permit neuro-transmitters adapt to circumstances?
2. Under what conditions do brain waves track computations?
3. To what extent do brain wave computations generalize managerial judgements?
4. Is there a prediction wave signal?
5. How do brain waves interact?
6. Under what circumstances do brain waves cooperate or compete?
7. Do higher-level brain waves rely similarly on multiple mechanisms?

As is evinced from plethora of publications and scientific experiments, 21st Century is christened as an Era where one witnesses marriage of management with neuroscience. All managers are programmed to play significant role in managerial judgement making. Studies and evidence lend credence to the fact that there appears a biological connect in all managerial activities, whether in the production or creation of wealth. Therefore, there is undisputed inclination of neuro-sciences in comprehending tools or 'neurobiological 'motorists' that aid in mapping link between molecular network, psychology, cognition and EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making apparatuses. This can route research and investigation towards calibrating whether cognito - wiring provides an alley forward towards advent of new vista which is scientifically vigorous and empirically sound. In dynamics of Collecting, Assimilating, Collating, Interpreting, Synthesising and Disseminating these inputs, there appears in neuro management horizon, element of neuro soundings in data - driven managerial EEG - based fluid managerial judgements. It is conjectured that in bargain, manager would be key 'catalyst' in inter - play between management and neuroscience.

Neuromanagement sciences are still in its early stages, particularly in sub-field of neuro soundings in data-driven managerial EEG-based fluid managerial judgements with emphasis on managerial behaviour. There is need for inter-disciplinary collaboration to fully develop this field. Neuromanagement sciences bring together management and psychology to complement interface between business management and brain sciences. However, discoveries challenge traditional management viewpoints. Neuro managerial EEG-based fluid managerial judgement explorations have been used as conduit to connect impeding gorge and provide precise representations of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making. Despite considerable expansions, understanding how we make choices and erecting EEG-based fluid managerial judgement that infers alternate choice remains significant challenge for methodical exploration. This requires further research and development to advance the field.

Researchers are currently investigating process of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making in organizational and behavioural judgement by research attempting neuro-transmitters in brain. However, it can be difficult to interpret research results when neurological findings conflict with self-report. While neuro-transmitters can shed light on managerial judgement making, they do not provide complete understanding of thoughts, beliefs, and how we make EEG-based fluid managerial judgements. Neuro-behavioural judgement aimed to bridge gap between behavioural theory and detailed neural mechanisms expressed mathematically by using neuroscience techniques to examine implications. This inter-disciplinary approach combines knowledge about neuro-transmitters and brain mechanisms to

offer insights into managerial judgement making, and uncover 'cerebral box' of managerial judgement making. Principal 'anatomical peep' is that neuro-transmitters consist of multiple systems that inter-relate, with controlled systems challenging traditional assumptions about basic preferences in indefinite preference and tactical interface. Argument is that incorporating insights from other disciplines can benefit neuro-behavioural psychology and neuroscience.

For most part, EEG-based managerial judgements, such as choices and effort allocation, are linked to macro-scale structure of neuro-transmitters in brain. These responses involve various regions in neuro-transmitters and their functions depend on context. This is evident through specific plasticity of brain networks induced by these regions. Use of neuro-signatures has led to changes in behavioural judgement, with neuro - behavioural judgement challenging assumptions of traditional behavioural judgement. However, challenge of understanding how EEG-based managerial judgements are made remains significant hurdle. Ultimate goal is to develop algebraic theory that explains how brain neuro-transmitters implement EEG-based managerial judgements, which can be linked to actual behaviour. It is perceived that this model could offer some dissimilarity among neuro - alternatives that occupy a playing field with competing interests. By integrating different theoretical approaches and methodologies, we can construct models that accurately represent EEG-based managerial judgement making.

But not all change is uncertain. Some complex cognito - economic capacities via neuro - signatures (fluid intellect), present a challenge for explanations constructed by using this theoretical structure. If another economic crisis is coming, people like quant or those who call themselves economists and ignore behaviour should realize how wrong they are! Judgement is the research attempt of behaviour! It is the research attempt of us, humans! And not some 'genius' fabrication wanting to show the world how 'smart' it is! Those people can regurgitate all they want, but it won't change the fact that behaviour matters! (Jang W Park). Kahneman, Nobel Laureate (2002), describes: 'the most important characteristic of a human being is not that he reasons poorly, but often acts instinctively, and the behaviour is not guided by the calculations that can be made, but by what is seen at the moment when the EEG - based fluid managerial judgement has to be made'.

Why do some uses 'good' behaviour to justify 'bad' behaviour? Why do some often mistake root causes of feelings and experiences? Why do some have trouble estimating odds of rare events? This is a case of 'parametric tectonic EEG - based fluid managerial judgement shift' tending towards 'EEG - based fluid managerial judgement - subsidence'. How to make important EEG - based fluid managerial judgements when time is scarce and stakes are high? One mental shortcut people commit is making snaps based on limited neuro - signatures. It makes intuitive sense (fluid intellect) to judge EEG - based fluid managerial judgement based on its results. However, is it true that good EEG - based fluid managerial judgement leads to good conclusion and vice versa? Why is it complicated to separate correlation from causation? When psychology and EEG - based fluid managerial judgements got 'connubial', result was behavioural sciences (fluid intellect) with off-spring baptized as neuro - signatures. Although this discipline has elevated theoretical and practical understanding of human behaviour to beforehand unseen heights, recent scientific developments have produced insight into understanding and predicting actions that supplement traditional tools of behavioural science. Future of behavioural economic science will, as a result, depend on how effectively behavioural economic researchers can strap up developments (fluid intellect) in technology to understand neuro - signatures and way people operate.

Making EEG - based fluid managerial judgement relies on dissimilar processes and tends to produce diverse results. Paul Samuelson writes that 'due to complexity of human and behaviour we cannot hope to have precision of physical sciences, chemists and biologists'. As Economist, one ought to be content with observing. But, there is a nagging temperament to overestimate abilities and exactness of predictions. Is it in good health to have well-calibrated confidence beliefs? Arrogant Economists, opines Jang W. Park, should stop thinking of themselves as cult leaders and stop indulging themselves as Sages who can handle so much economic power! Where were they when all previous crises affected so many people suffering? As in most dynamic sciences, conjecture and line of attack are not motionless in neuro-judgement. These are not fixed boundaries for neuro - signatures. Boundaries are relatively dilute. What is being proposed is a perception required for fluid intellect with cognitive and behavioural constraints due. This is a perceptive awareness quite different to simply relying upon or explaining behaviours in terms of neuroscience. The gap in literature appears. Managers are dependent on Psychologists for interpretation of impact of neuroscience on EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making. Weakness is seldom actually understood by many.

In recent years, two significant developments have been infusions from related behavioural sciences (or, natural science) into theories and concepts, together with the growth of neuro - the signature experimental method. In a fast-globalizing world, economic organizations face 'unruly' economic factors viz. Economic curiosity, economic creativity and economic complexity conditions. This is coupled up with near - cousins; chaos, confusion and economic catastrophe. Fast-changing technology and neuro-economic models ride on the wave of the digital revolution. This is creating new challenges and opportunities for judgements. In contemporary world of judgement, conventional neuro-economic paradigms are cracking up giving place to new judgements and approaches based on an understanding of. Conversely, expansions of neuro-economic science have bridged contrasting fields that congregate into single, unified discipline in which conditions operate. There is a call for understanding the chess - board dynamic conditions matrix processes (fluid intellect). This is a course of action that connects impression and action by revealing neuro-economic mechanisms as a result of which fluid intellect (ability to rationale and explain new tribulations autonomously of previously acquired knowledge) is coded. Such codes pose challenge to standard perspective in normal judgement. It is here at this stage that neuro-managerial fluid intellect-making offers inter-disciplinary endeavour to integrate accurate models.

Critics often point out that fluid-based managerial judgement models fail to accurately represent the neuro-psychological substrates of managerial judgement making. Nevertheless, some argue that recent neuropsychological findings can help choice models overcome this limitation by offering pragmatic interpretations of neuro-psychological sculpt of choice. These conjecture sub-personal entity with unambiguous neuro-psychological complement and precisely differentiate them. Over the last decade, the development of neuroscience knowledge and tools has enabled researchers to link neuroscience techniques to psychology, marketing, management, judgement, and sociology. This growing interest has led to research attempt of how managerial behaviour can shape consideration of mind, and how neuro-scientific findings guide models of neural management. The inter - disciplinary field draws on Management Theories, Economic Theories, Psychological Theories, Statistics Theories, Mathematical Theories, Operational Research Theories, Computing Theories, Experimental Economic Theories, Neuroscience Theories, Haematology Theories, Ophthalmology Theories, Dermatology Theories, And Physiology Theories to develop comprehensive understanding of human fluid-based managerial judgements.

Conventional notion that economic choice perspectives are based on logic - based cerebral dynamics is now confronted by experimental research that scrutinize how fluid-based managerial judgement preferences progress through brain pathways. It depicts how cerebral processes spring of statistics. Neuro-judgement, along with other disciplines such as neuro-governance, has converged with business to form vibrant circumstances, towards producing all-inclusive scaffold for swot up of multifaceted points of interests related to fluid-based managerial judgement making. Despite significant developments, the inquiry into how economic fluid-based managerial judgements are made continues to pose significant challenges for methodical explorations. When making an economic fluid-based managerial judgement, we want to detect as many alternate choices as possible and select the one that not only has highest probability of efficiency but best fits our goals, needs, routines, and ethics.

There is an ascendancy of sorts in the interest among researchers towards understanding how postulation, philosophy, behaviour, and strategy shape economic managerial judgement making. Recent studies have suggested that neurotransmitters in the cerebrum weigh assortment of sources of data inputs prior to creation of a profitable EEG-based fluid pronouncement, leading to internal conflict. However, mechanisms underlying this process are not fully understood, and sometimes impulsive, indecisive, or irrational managerial judgements can result, which may lead to risky behaviours. Paul Samuelson famously said that theory advances through funerals, and this is especially true in heretical judgement, where new-fangled insights often challenge established ideas. Emerging neuro-economic science put forward that strong and resilient managerial judgement making depends on preceding specific neural dispensation. Mainstream neuro-judgement assumes that individuals are rational and maximize utility, which underpins classical economic models. However, heretical theories argue that equilibrium models are inaccurate and do not reflect real-world conditions. Instead, they propose alternative understandings of how fluid managerial judgement making occurs and how human psychology operates.

Wave Dynamics

Focal intention of this Section was to build up neuro-managerial feedback organism using brain waves (EEG) to monitor neurobiological processes involved in managerial judgement making. The research attempt aimed to address two research questions:

- (1) How do managers make judgements using neurofeedback?
- (2) Which part of brain is involved in EEG-based fluid judgement?

One major challenge faced by EEG-based fluid managerial judgement-makers is difficulty of quantifying their choices, as described by 'Matching Law,' which refers to comparative reaction velocity on simultaneously accessible option that counterpart presented qualified corroboration levy. To simplify complex managerial judgement making situations, individuals engage in adaptive and strategic simplifications. Conversely, neural mechanisms to facilitate silhouette and put into practice these line of attack linger for the most part anonymous. While neuro-transmitters in brain determine precise managerial judgement aspect, diminutive is known on the subject of how they opt for among manifold tactic for the computational stress of multifarious EEG-based fluid managerial judgement. This research aimed to model neuro-managerial intelligence by integrating evidence from neuro-transmitters (electroencephalography) and using psycho-neuroeconomic modelling approach. The research attempt aimed to expand foundation for using computational models to complement and explain results from human subject experiments, capturing regularities observed in experimental data. Research attempt aimed to monitor dynamics of neuro-transmitters in brain wave drivers to understand chess-board vibrant circumstances milieu with the objective of (a) embryonic prototype of unorthodox assessment and (b) connecting procedural dissimilarity to facilitate communiqué about EEG-based fluid managerial judgement beneath real-world constriction of narrow time, information, and computation instruct.

Focal point was to understand;

- Neural processes underlying complex cognition - economic capacities via neuro - signatures,
- Understand mechanisms using functional neuroimaging methodologies.
- Integrate inter-disciplinary neuro - signatures.

Conjectural Situation

A broad assortment of academic disciplines sought to explore algorithmic EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making, such as Cognitive Neuroscience, Psychology, Organisational Studies and Judgement. Each of these conducts research from comparatively thin archetypes, and with that develops boundaries consequent with pure disciplinal research. The incipient arena of neuro-judgement seems to offer mutual philological, model and exercise from which to better comprehend this humanoid behaviour. Scientific understanding of mind is not conceivable from corporeal understanding of brain. Initial step encompasses neutral explanation and scrutiny of how concentration works within home or context of brain functions. Algorithmic EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making is critical for managers. Reasoning and moulds that reinforce algorithmic EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making are substantial when constructing and implementing stratagems.

In above scenario, pertinent issues were; How to shape reasonable and explainable representations that can aid EEG - based fluid managerial judgement making? How to ensure that models and their elucidations are vigorous to confrontational spells? How to train and gauge replicas in the existence of misplaced counterfactuals? How to spot and correct fundamental inclines in EEG - based fluid managerial judgements and algorithmic calculations? Nevertheless, with substantial expansions, question of how we make algorithmic EEG - based fluid managerial judgements stays to spot substantial trials for logical investigations. Instituting an algorithmic EEG - based fluid managerial judgement conjectures that there is a substitute optimal to be factored.

Brain waves emanate in structure of electrical activities, repeatedly firing and emanating some impulses in varying degrees. These have been categorised into four classifications; Beta, Alpha, Waves, Waves and Delta Waves, respectively. Beta Waves (rhythm) are a string of neuronal alternation exhibiting incidence of between 12.5 and 30 Hz (or, 12.5 to 30 sequences per second. As per scientific evidences, these waves can be on an auxiliary basis scored apart into three segments: Low Beta rays (12.5 - 16 Hz or Beta 1), Beta Waves (16.5 - 20 Hz or Beta 2) and High Beta

Waves (20.5 - 28 Hz or Beta 3). These are connected to energetic, eventful or apprehensive thoughtful impulses and lively attentiveness.

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

Alpha Waves (rhythms) is a string of neuronal alternation in the rate of recurrence assortment of 8 - 12 Hz initiating commencing synchronic mode along with comprehensible electrical motion of thalamic pacer compartments in the human body. Brain harvests alpha waves, as it is in a milieu that is calm and soporific. This is where one experiences these when undertaking anxiety-releasing actions.

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

A Gamma Wave (or Rhythm) is a neuronal configuration of swings that exhibit a frequency range between 25 and 140 Hz. These swings are interrelated with large gauge brain grid motion and cerebral singularities such as perceptual assemblage,

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

Theta Waves (or rhythm) are a neuronal outline (classified as 'leisurely' action) of swipes that display a frequency range of 4 -7 Hz range. Such curves are observed in a state of worry, behavioural stimulation and behaviour self-consciousness.

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

Delta Waves (or rhythm) is a neural framework portraying oscillations with occurrence between 0.5 and 4 Hz. These rhythms are associated with subterranean slumber phases.

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

Courtesy: Wikipedia / Images

Making fluid managerial judgements in judgement always involves a certain degree of risk, as complete knowledge of all possible alternatives is rarely available. Despite significant progress, the process of making economic managerial judgements using EEG-based methods still presents a critical challenge for systematic research. Researchers must consider limitations and possibilities in current environment, as well as opportunities and constraints related to the process of forecasting and future foresight. What heretical approaches could be used to counter these challenges? One promising approach to neuro-judgement is neuro-transmitters in brain waves, which can shed light on functional responsibility. Specifically, the use of Alpha waves can provide insight into mindful perspectives, presenting a new approach to understanding complex economic managerial judgements.

This research attempt focused on Alpha Waves in methodology of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making. Economists and psychologists provide comfortable abstract tools for perceptive and modelling conduct. Neurobiologists make available tools for research attempt of apparatus. Underpinning of stimulation has been neuro-judgment research seen as amalgamation of notes from cognitive science and behavioural judgement. The postulation about the elevated consistency of economic agents is key to edifice of modern economic theory (Jevons, Walras, etc.). In words of Lakatos, all Sciences have rigid nucleus, which is very complicated to disprove, to mutate, and in which there are convinced argument that no one frequently confer, and all acknowledge them as indispensable groundwork from where contemporary models commence.

In recent times, researchers have been measuring physiological responses through the observation of neural activity, particularly Alpha Waves, and the way neuro-transmitters in brain respond to stimulus presentation. This approach involves using conductors to evidence electrical motion of neuro-transmitters in brain, providing evidence about cognitive processes in fluid intellect, including 'Exploratory' and 'Arithmetical' task circumstances. Debate about theories and applications has led to measurement of physiological fluid intellect responses to understand neural activity and response of neuro-transmitters to sounding. An effective and scientifically based treatment method for neuro-based pointer has been developed; involving the use of electrodes attached to cranium to record electrical activity and amplifies targeted behaviour corresponding to composition of neuro-transmitters. Clinical tests with a fair population of 15 respondents produced satisfactory results.

Diverse brain research methods, in concert with Electro-encephalography (EEG), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Magneto-encephalography (MEG), Computerized Tomography (CT), and Positron Emission Tomography (PET), have been engaged to examine brain. This research attempt suggests using combination of neuro-imaging, neuro-physiological, neuro-psychological, and functional techniques such as Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), Eye Tracking, and Electro-encephalography to research attempt brain activity. The advantages and costs of each technique vary, and their usage depends on specific task or obligation. For instance, fMRI measures blood flow, while Single Neuron Measurement (SNM) accounts reaction of personage neurons. MEG records magnetic impulse fashioned by electrical fluctuation in brain, and ECG measures electrical motion in heart. Trans-cranial Direct Current Stimulation transports low current to area of interest through electrodes, while EEG records electrical activity of brain. PET provides 3D image of functional processes, and TMS stimulates small province of brain. Eye tracking measures

point of gaze or motion of eye, and EDA or skin conductance accounts unremitting dissimilarity in electrical characteristics of skin. Brain mapping involves machinations biological quantities or spatial images in maps, and BOLD imaging identifies locale of brain that are active at any given time. Lastly, cognitive maps consign to rational depiction of corporeal position in brain.

Methodology used in this project research attempt was based on an on - going research experiment, with published results and additional findings offered in this section. Research attempt focuses on examining empirical mosaics in 'neuro-trajectory feedback tectonic shifts(s)' of fluid-based managerial judgement circuits, with a sample size of 3 managerial judgement-makers. Approach is grounded in theoretical models based on an axiomatic foundation, aiming to create condensed models of fluid-based managerial judgement making that integrate the fields of managerial judgement science with big data analysis techniques in new areas of behaviour. The section evaluates impact of cerebral on shaping fluid-based managerial judgements using a 'modulated sound-injections' neurofeedback procedure via electrocardiogram (ECG). The recorded waves provide evidence about the cognitive processes and circumstances, supplemented with response evidence and reference runs (based on SVG analysis) as part of simulations. Alpha wave responses were measured to comprehend neural movement and how intelligence act in response to tectonic swing.

Qualms are habitually overlooked, and opposite testing can lead to impasse. Mislaid compactness can canopy fluid managerial judgement-makers who rely on EEG data. Is it possible for strategy to be robust and flexible enough to handle various potential circumstances? Which qualms are significant, and what conduct should we capture or reschedule? How do we prioritize options and reduce vulnerability to uncertainties? Research showed that neuro-transmitters cannot fully encode all neuro-signatures in a signal, and this has two main benefits. Firstly, it provides guidelines for constraints imposed on complex EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making processes. Secondly, by unambiguously modelling physiological belongings, it is probable to slot in rudiments of predilection that were beforehand considered exogenous. When making choices involving risk and uncertainty, it is necessary to make complex trade-offs. Research directions included;

- Modelling and simulation objective support,
- Fundamental graph model and network analysis,
- Numerical optimization and modelling,
- Evidential reasoning and fusion to model neuro - signatures,
- Algorithms and simulation into the modelling of EEG - the based fluid managerial judgement to -making.

In terms of methodology employed in exploration, electrical motions of intellect were recorded by means of EEG conductors to obtain an electroencephalogram (EEG). These waves provide evidence about various circumstances and cognitive processes, which can be examined in context of different theories and applications of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making. Additionally, physiological responses have been recorded to better understand neural activity and how brain responds to different stimuli.

Discussion

A 15 - subject model has been adopted. This was with a perception that the subject assist as controller as regards degrees of sensitivity involved. The experiments were to respond to varying degrees of prediction / prognosticate verification, authentication, confirmation, corroboration, substantiation, validation, and replication and reflectivity. This research attempt acknowledges the fact that 'subject follow line of investigation plan that are 'scrawny when it comes to peripheral strength.... studies connecting single-subject propose a meticulous treatment to be effectual in altering conduct must rely on reproduction; across individuals rather than group if such result are be found creditable of generalization' (Fraenkel and Wallen; 2006).

Setting: Conductors were spotted onto head to portion electrical activity of brain. Comeback values were experimented with at 256 Hz (3.9-msec epoch) for 01 second. The subject experimented with either a solitary stimulus (S1) or two stimuli (S1 and S2). When two stimuli were depicted, they were within reach in both a synchronized structure where S1 was indistinguishable to S2 or in a non-matched stipulation where S1 was at variance from S2.

‘Some of the related numerical soundings were:

	-8.88	-2.088	-0.88
	8.88	8.84	8.848
Fp2	8.88	8.848	8.88
Fp2 F4	4.848	8.88	8.88
F4 C4	4.88	8.888	8.08 8.88
C4	4.4848	8.88	
P4 P4			8.08
O2	8.88 8.88	8.888	8.0884 -
O2 F8	-8.88 8.88	8.848 -	8.88 8.88 -
F8	-4.848 8.8	8.88	0.848 8.888
T8 T8	8.884	8.8804 -	8.884 8.488
P8 P8	4.084	2.48 8.88	8.84 8.888
Fz Cz	8.888 8.88	8.88 8.88	8.8884 8.88
Pz Oz	0.88 8.088	8.848	8.88
FC2		8.88 8.88	
FC2	8.848	0.888	8.888
CP2	8.888 8.08		8.808
CP2	8.48 8.884	8.88	8.8480
FC6	8.884	8.4808	8.884 8.088
FC6	00.884	8.884	8.884 8.882

The above numeric represents Alpha waves as deduced. Brain is observed to be in a state of rest with no unnecessary oscillations. Waves are slower and higher in amplitude. The subjects are absorbed, attentive, fixated and focused on a particular activity without any swings. This is a mark of lowered anxiety, lower stress and state of calm. This is over some time (as observed in phases above). ‘Big Question’ was which neurons or nerve cell of brain helps to have sharp focus and concentration? It can be safely deduced from Alpha algorithms that it’s not which neurons, but rather which brain province confirms most activity during ‘focus and concentration’. And answer would be Pre-Frontal Cortex. e-mail communication with Thomas Collura, Carlos P. Zalaquett, and Ronald J. Bonnsetter led to conclusion that Neuro Soundings, Neuro-Feedback, Brain Waves, EEG Waves and Choice Construction are all ‘Pillars’ of data-driven platform that aid managerial EEG - based fluid judgement making.

According to a recent article in Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy (published on March 16, 2020), computational philosophy involves using computational techniques to support and expand philosophical research. Rather than being philosophy of computers or computational methods, computational philosophy utilizes advances in computer technology to enhance philosophical inquiry and debate across wide range of philosophical topics. Computational philosophy is not a distinct subfield of philosophy, but rather collection of computational tools and methods that can be applied to various areas of philosophical inquiry.

Consequently, there is no clear distinction sandwiched between computational and non-computational viewpoint, nor is there razor-sharp segregate stuck between computational viewpoint and other computational order. Computational viewpoint should not be perplexed with philosophy of computation or philosophy of simulated acumen. It is not a sweeping term for examining the insinuation of computer usage as explored in fields like computer principles or philosophy of information and technology. As an alternative, computational philosophy engage the broad use of accessible computer techniques transversely in an assortment of philosophical topics. This inter-disciplinary move towards illustrate on a assortment of computer programming, software engineering, and modelling process, including artificial intelligence, neural networks, systems science, and complex adaptive arrangement. As embryonic set of methodologies, it may take account of computational documented examination, big data laboratory analysis, and other modus operandi. Computational philosophy is not constrained to any scrupulous domain of philosophy and has pervasive relevance.

Alpha - based judgement is part of a broader field of research on human intelligence, which has a long and complex history. Intelligence has been studied by psychologists, neuroscientists, and other researchers for over a century, and there are many different theories and approaches to understanding this complex construct. Despite its importance, there are still many unanswered questions about Alpha - based managerial judgement, including how it develops over the lifespan, how it is related to other types of intelligence, and how it is affected by factors such as genetics and environment. As researchers continue to research attempt Alpha-based managerial judgements, we expect to gain new insights into this fascinating aspect of human cognition. [Overall, the research attempt of Alpha - based managerial judgement has a long and rich history that has contributed significantly to our understanding of human cognition and intelligence.](#)

Examples of tasks that require Alpha-based managerial judgements include solving puzzles, recognizing visual patterns, and understanding complex relationships between ideas or concepts. Researchers believe that Alpha - based managerial judgement is related to the efficiency of neural processing in the brain's pre-frontal cortex and other areas involved in executive functioning. Overall, Alpha - based managerial judgement is an important aspect of cognitive functioning, as it enables to adapt to new situations and solve novel problems, independent of prior knowledge and experience. Alpha - based managerial judgement is often contrasted with Cognitive - based Intelligence, which refers to knowledge and skills that have been acquired through learning and experience. While Cognitive - based Intelligence is related to specific domains of knowledge (e.g. vocabulary, math), Alpha - based managerial judgement is a more general ability that can be applied to variety of tasks. Alpha - based managerial judgement is believed to be predisposed by both inherent and ecological dynamic. While a quantity of persons may comprise a normal ability for interpretation and problem-solving, others may profit from guidance and preparation to perk up their Alpha - based managerial judgement.

There is an ongoing debate among researchers about whether Alpha - based managerial judgement is truly 'innate' or whether it can be influenced by experience and learning. Some studies have suggested that certain types of training and practice can improve Alpha-based managerial judgements, while others have argued that any improvements are simply due to increased familiarity with the types of problems being tested. While Alpha - based managerial judgement is generally thought to decline with age, rate of decline can vary depending on several factors, including overall health, education level, and engagement in mentally stimulating activities. Alpha - based managerial judgement is closely related to other aspects of cognitive functioning, including working memory, attention, and processing speed. These abilities are all important for complex reasoning and problem-solving tasks. In addition to its practical applications in fields such as education and workforce development, Alpha - based managerial judgement is of theoretical interest to researchers in fields such as psychology and neuroscience. By understanding the neural basis of Alpha-based managerial judgements, researchers hope to gain insights into how the brain processes information and how different cognitive abilities are related to one another.

Alpha - based managerial judgement (Gf) is explicit as capacity to solve original problems and reflect conceptually, autonomous of acquired information. It is decisive characteristic of cognitive implementation and theatres vital role in assortment of daily conduct, including learning, reasoning, and managerial judgement making. In this literature review, we will examine the current state of research on Alpha-based managerial judgements, including its definition, measurement, and underlying neural mechanisms. Measurement of Alpha - based managerial judgement Alpha - based managerial judgement is typically measured through consistent psychometric experiment (Progressive Matrices; Raven and Adult Intelligence Scale; Wechsler). These tests require individuals to solve abstract problems using non-verbal reasoning skills. They are designed to assess the ability to generate and maintain complex mental representations, a hallmark of Alpha - based managerial judgement.

Generally, Alpha - based managerial judgement involves a range of cognitive abilities that are important for adapting to new situations, solving problems, and making sound managerial judgements. By improving these abilities, individuals can enhance their overall cognitive functioning and better navigate complex and dynamic environments. In addition to the key areas mentioned, other aspects of Alpha-based managerial judgements can be important to consider. For example, ability to identify relationships between different concepts or ideas, and the ability to think creatively and generate new ideas are important aspects of Alpha-based managerial judgements. Additionally, ability to learn quickly and adapt to new situations is a key component of Alpha - based managerial judgement, as it enables individuals to rapidly acquire new information and adjust their behaviour accordingly.

Furthermore, Alpha - based managerial judgement is often contrasted with cognitive - based intelligence, which refers to the knowledge and skills that an individual has acquired through education and experience. While cognitive - based intelligence is important for performing well in specific domains, such as reading comprehension or vocabulary, Alpha - based managerial judgement is more general and can be applied to a wide range of situations. Therefore, individuals with higher levels of Alpha - based managerial judgement may be better equipped to handle new or unfamiliar situations, while those with higher levels of cognitive - based intelligence may excel in areas where knowledge and experience are more important. Overall, understanding the key areas of Alpha - based managerial judgement and how they relate to other aspects of cognition can help individuals identify their strengths and weaknesses and develop strategies for improving their overall cognitive functioning. By focusing on activities that challenge and develop these key areas, individuals can enhance their problem-solving skills, adaptability, and ability to learn and innovate.

To enhance individual's reasoning, abstract thinking, problem-solving and adaptability skills, focus is on developing Alpha-based managerial judgements. This approach aimed to equip individuals with cognitive tools that can help navigate through complexities and uncertainties in world around them. Alpha-based managerial judgements can assist in learning, managerial judgement making, and creating new ideas in unique ways, without need for prior knowledge or experience. The ultimate objective is to enable individuals to effectively process and respond to new information and situations, and to adapt thinking and behaviour accordingly. Improving Alpha-based managerial judgements can lead to developing cognitive flexibility and agility, which are vital to thriving in a rapidly changing world.

Scrupulously, aim and objective of Alpha-based managerial judgements are to enable individuals to think critically, creatively, and adaptively, and apply their reasoning and problem-solving skills in wide range of contexts and situations. By doing so, individuals can enhance their cognitive functioning and attain better achievement in individual and professional existence. Furthermore, it's significant to make a note of that Alpha - based managerial judgement is distinct from cognitive - based intelligence, which involves acquired knowledge and skills based on prior experiences and education. While both are important for overall cognitive functioning, Alpha - based managerial judgement is particularly important for navigating novel situations where prior knowledge may not be applicable.

Research suggests that Alpha - based managerial judgement is influenced by amalgamation of hereditary and ecological factors. While genetics play role in individual's baseline level of Alpha - based managerial judgement, environmental factors can influence Alpha - based managerial judgement development and improvement. Studies have demonstrated that Alpha-based managerial judgement tends to peak in early adulthood and gradually declines with age, although it is possible to mitigate this decline through continued cognitive stimulation and engagement in challenging activities. In conclusion, objective of Alpha-based managerial judgements are to equip individuals with the cognitive tools necessary to adapt to new situations, solve problems, and innovate in new and creative ways.

Advances in neuroscience and cognitive psychology may provide new insights into underlying neural mechanisms of Alpha-based managerial judgements, and how they can be improved or enhanced. For example, neuroimaging studies may help better understand brain regions and networks involved in Alpha - reasoning and problem-solving, which could lead to development of new interventions or training programs. There is increasing interest in potential role of technology, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, in enhancing Alpha-based managerial judgements. Some researchers are exploring use of intelligent tutoring systems or adaptive learning technologies that provide personalized feedback and support to learners, which may enhance problem-solving and reasoning skills.

Overall, future of Alpha-based managerial judgements is likely to be shaped by ongoing advances in neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and technology. By continuing to investigate and understand underlying mechanisms of Alpha-based managerial judgements, researchers may be able to develop new interventions or approaches that can help individuals enhance cognitive abilities and adapt to new challenges and opportunities. Alpha - based managerial judgement could have significant implications for how we approach cognitive abilities. Moreover, as the world becomes more complex and dynamic, Alpha-based managerial judgements may become increasingly important for success in various domains, such as business, science, and technology. As such, individuals who possess strong Alpha-based managerial judgement skills may have competitive advantage. However, it is important to recognize that there may be ethical and social implications associated with enhancing Alpha-based managerial judgements.

In wrapping up, research attempt on Alpha-based managerial judgement provide with valuable insights into human mind and its capacity for problem-solving and learning. As we have seen throughout this section, Alpha - based managerial judgement is an important cognitive ability that is strongly correlated with academic and professional success, and it is a key component of general intelligence. Through our exploration of various theories and research findings, we understand that Alpha-based managerial judgement is not fixed and unchangeable, but rather can be developed and enhanced through certain types of training. This suggests that with a right approach and effort, we can all improve Alpha-based managerial judgement and achieve full cognitive potential. Additionally, understanding of Alpha-based managerial judgement has practical implications for fields connected to neuroscience and artificial intelligence. As we continue to advance knowledge of Alpha-based managerial judgements, we can expect to see new insights and innovations that will further understanding of human mind and its remarkable abilities.

Cognitive - based managerial judgement is heavily dependent on the storage and retrieval of information in the brain. Research has demonstrated that several brain structures are involved in this process, including brain parts comprising of hippocampus, pre-frontal cortex, and temporal lobes. The hippocampus is a structure located in the medial temporal lobe of the brain that is critical for the formation and consolidation of new memories. It is thought to engage in recreation of a key role in acquisition of new knowledge and skills that contribute to cognitive - based managerial judgement. In particular, hippocampus is involved in encoding new information and transferring it to long-term memory stores. Pre-frontal cortex, positioned in frontal lobes of brain, is profoundly implicated in cognitive - based choice algorithms. This province is accountable for assortment of higher-order cognitive functions. It is assumed to be important for retrieval and manipulation of information stored in long-term memory, and for the ability to apply knowledge and skills to new situations. The temporal lobes are involved in the cognitive - based managerial judgement. These regions are responsible for a range of functions related to perception, recognition, and comprehension of sensory input. The left temporal lobe, in particular, is important for language processing and the storage of verbal information.

Furthermore, research has demonstrated that 'white matter' pathways that connect these brain regions play an imperative character in competence of data dispensation and amalgamation of different cognitive functions. For example, the integrity of the white matter pathways between the pre-frontal cortex and hippocampus has been linked to performance on tasks that require manipulation and retrieval of information from long-term memory. Moreover, studies using neuroimaging techniques such as fMRI have demonstrated that activation patterns in these brain regions differ between individuals with high and low levels of cognitive - based managerial judgement. For instance, individuals with high levels of cognitive - based managerial judgement show greater activation in left hemisphere of brain, particularly in parts of pre-frontal and temporal lobes, when performing tasks related to verbal and semantic processing.

Overall, deeper understanding of the brain structures and neural networks involved in cognitive - based managerial judgement has important implications for developing interventions aimed at enhancing cognitive abilities. By identifying the neural mechanisms underlying cognitive - based managerial judgements, researchers can develop targeted interventions that aim to improve the efficiency of information processing and enhance the ability to acquire and apply knowledge throughout the lifespan. Structures involved in cognitive - based managerial judgement are distributed across brain and are interconnected in complex ways. The neural networks that support cognitive - based managerial judgements are dynamic and can be modified through experience and training, leading to changes in cognitive abilities over time.

Cognitive - based managerial judgement develops over time as individuals acquire knowledge and skills through education and experience. The rate of development can vary depending on a variety of factors, including the individual's environment, opportunities for learning, and genetic predispositions. Research suggests that cognitive - based managerial judgement tends to increase throughout childhood and adolescence, with significant growth occurring during the school years as individuals acquire basic literacy and numeracy skills. Development continues throughout adulthood, with continued accumulation of knowledge and experience contributing to increases in the cognitive - based managerial judgement.

In addition to information provided, it is worth noting that development of cognitive - based managerial judgements is not solely determined by genetics or innate abilities. Environmental factors can significantly impact the development of cognitive - based managerial judgements. For example, individuals from more advantaged backgrounds may have greater access to educational resources and opportunities for enrichment, which can facilitate the development of

cognitive - based managerial judgements. On the other hand, individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds may have fewer learning opportunities and may experience more stress and adversity, which can negatively impact their cognitive development. It is important to recognize that the development of cognitive - based managerial judgements is not a static process, but rather one that can be influenced by interventions and experiences throughout the lifespan.

In snaking up, cognitive - based managerial judgement is a fundamental concept in cognitive psychology that has put on escalating concentration in topical duration due to its consequence in personal and professional success. This type of managerial judgement involves ability to apply knowledge and skills acquired through education and experience, which is crucial for problem-solving, effective communication, and adaptability in various domains. Different theories have explained the historical background of cognitive - based managerial judgements and their development over time. Researchers have used various methods to measure and assess cognitive - based managerial judgements, including different types of tests. Moreover, environmental and genetic factors influence the development of cognitive - based managerial judgements. Education plays a crucial role in developing cognitive - based managerial judgements, with its use in various fields such as education, employment, and healthcare.

Understanding interactions between neuro-transmitters and brain milieu requires a mechanistic conception of neurobiological processes implicated in EEG-based managerial judgement making dependent relative on significance. It is essential to make distinction linking 'thinking about thinking' and improving neuro-transmitters and mental course of action by pulsating into each individual's potential. Theoretical models propose that human neuro-transmitters work through neural computations that involve comparing the expected future reward of various EEG-based managerial judgement options and selecting the option with the highest expected value. While computers have predefined goals for neuro-signature processing, neuro-transmitters in brain determine their goals based on the need to survive in unpredictable and competitive surroundings. In an era of rapid change and increasing uncertainty, how can we manage neuro-transmitters in the brain to support economic managerial judgement making? What coherent dynamics underlie the neuro-transmitters in the brain that support prediction, control, and EEG-based managerial judgement making?

How do managerial judgement-makers, who operate in a fluid environment, form judgments, and what is the neural basis of this process? Is research attempting cognitive management processes involved in judgment-making useful for economic managerial judgement-makers? Often, such managerial judgement-makers may gather more information than they need, causing delays and undermining the efficacy of their judgment. The field of cognitive management aim to give explanation, together with capacity to course of action manifold alternative and choose best route of action. It sought to have a handle on how management conduct silhouette perceptive of brain and puts in picture models of managerial judgement management. According to theoretical accounts, the brain carries out judgment-making via neural computations and comprehending these processes necessitates an understanding of cognitive processes that carry out value-based judgment-making. This presents what is referred to as 'cognitive-management judgment-making paradox,' which aimed to explain how a brain trapping is fixed to managerial judgement behaviour. Ultimately, intention was to establish reasoned brain dynamics that lie underneath forecast, direct managerial judgment making.

The quantum of information that pair of brain provide is passable enough to feed apparatus for undertaking a fluid-based managerial judgement making function. How parts of brain structure(s) aid in fluid-based managerial judgement making is the issue under the microscope of inter-disciplinary research. How do brain structures behave? How do brain structure parts oscillate? What patterns do they form? How do we interpret the image, so formed? Above all, how does information, so obtained from this giant play, aid in fluid-based managerial judgement making? What characteristics do brain structure waves (Alpha) exhibit? This learning depicts how neuro machinery see the sights of 'managerial fluid based managerial judgemental' philosophy all the way through scrutiny of biological origin of preference and considerable position of 'neurones' in proto-typing managerial judgemental' thinking path. Results show signs of signatures for natural counter-factual simulation in domain of high-level cognition and illustrate how managers engage in 'fluid-based managerial judgemental' thinking using tracking techniques. These findings confirmed that the explanation of neural signature cannot boil down to a single network or few brain regions and suggest possible ways to guide neuroscience and the 'judgment curve'.

Biological foundation of managerial judgement making is rooted in fluid-based thinking, where the human mind tends to believe before seeing. Since the beginning of the 21st century, significant progress has been made in mapping the neuronal pathway of economic managerial judgement making. By examining the brain's cognitive, emotional, and

behavioural responses to stimuli, researchers can gain valuable insight into the managerial judgement making process. Key components of cognition include the ability to generate mental images, absorb and store information, and recognize patterns. Questions arise about whether risk aversion or risk-seeking behaviour is hard-wired into our brains, how the brain evaluates 'fair' economic managerial judgements, and whether consumer purchasing intentions can be predicted. Neuroscience, psychology, and judgement combined offer robust models and evidence to explain the basis of economic managerial judgement making.

Researchers have been exploring how to design and craft judgments and EEG-based fluid managerial judgements for decades, utilizing different techniques across various disciplines. However, recent inter-disciplinary efforts in neuro-behavioural judgement have emerged to bridge the gap. This approach combines concepts from neuroscience, organizational psychology, and neuro-behavioural judgement to create precise models of choice and EEG-based fluid managerial judgements. The research looks into neural bases of expectedness and assessment in EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making, essential consideration in accepted utility representation of behavioural managerial judgement. This arrangement of approach to EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making encompasses prospective to impact perspectives of behavioural managerial judgement. Amalgamation of these submit stimulating prospect to generate highly accurate models of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making (Satpathy, 2015).

When fluid-based managerial judgement-makers and stakeholders are uncertain about the likelihood of different future scenarios, it is known as deep uncertainty. In such cases, a pre-determined set of options can be analyzed in terms of a diagnostic criterion. The point is to rank these alternatives in terms of overall attractiveness or determine the pre-eminent choice or comparative precedence when all criteria are measured. Multi-criteria EEG-based fluid managerial judgement analysis (MCDA) focuses on solving such problems. However, there is an ongoing debate over the use of different methods, which can yield varying results when applied to the same data. This creates a paradox in neuro-behavioural judgement EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making.

Behaviourism is a cheval glass that replicates proclivity, viewpoint, and another psychosomatic state. Choice-making is an elementary human stroke. Fluid-based managerial judgement making is the most frequent but never-ending duel for mankind. It is akin to a chess board matrix where the moves and the counter moves are just predictable and conjectures but operationalization is difficult. Turning the concepts into quantifiable measurements and dimensions is complicated but not without a solution. In nutshell, fluid-based managerial judgement making is backed up by tenets of neuroscience. Fluid-based managerial judgements taken in an Alpha State are ascertained to be near-rational. There seems to be an air of relaxation, reduced stress, reduced strain, reduced anxiety, unruffled - thinking and no restlessness.

The flow paths of neurons are supposed to be in constant motion. It's a state of relaxed concentration where the information, facts, figures, evidence and statistics are supposed to be retained longer, leading to better economic fluid-based managerial judgement making. These acts as 'Pillars of Cognition' with the power to acquire and absorb information; the 'Soup of Cerebral'. Economists can christen this as a circumstance of 'biological pinnacle time for fluid-based managerial judgement making. This offers explanation to short absorption in discerning fluid intellect through the measurement of brain activity. The research attempt exhibits key findings and explains how neuro apparatuses explore 'business economic fluid-based managerial judgement - tectonic shifts(s)' through a biological basis. Results suggest that neural signatures cannot simmer down to a single network or a few brain regions. The section concludes with specific propositions towards rethinking the foundations of economic fluid-based managerial judgement mechanisms by supplementing unconventional arrangement for fluid-based managerial judgement problems.

The impact of emotions on EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making has not been systematically studied until now. Neuroscience evidence suggests that prior emotional processing plays a crucial role in EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making. As a result, inter-disciplinary research has emerged under the label of 'Neuro-behavioural judgement.' The main concept of this approach is to use advanced neuro-scientific techniques to analyze relevant neuro-transmitters in brain processes. However, this research is subject to various misconceptions due to its multidisciplinary nature. The relevance of the Neuro- behavioural judgement research attempt of EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making processes to behavioural judgement is a debatable issue, but this research does not take an arrangement on that. Instead, it squabbles that question is of methodical concentration, and apparatus from behavioural theory are appropriate towards addressing it.

While neuroscience methods can be advantageous for understanding human behaviour and EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making, they have limitations that require the support of experimental methodology and theories. Neuroscience methods are expensive and only reveal which areas of the brain are activated in response to certain situations, but do not explain our behaviour. They cannot explain the 'neuro' reason for why we respond in a certain way. Therefore, the experimental methodology is necessary to strengthen our understanding of why people make EEG-based fluid managerial judgements and react in certain ways. Combining neuroscience methods with neuro experiments can lead to significant insights into understanding human behaviour and EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making.

Experimental neurobehavioral judgement provides a fresh dataset that can aid in the creation of new theories to explain and anticipate EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making, as well as the underlying causes of behaviour and neural anomalies. By measuring neuro-transmitters in brain activity, neuro-signatures can be obtained that reveal the mechanisms utilized by these neuro-transmitters in the brain during managerial judgement making processes. This information can indicate which brain regions and neuro-transmitters are activated when an EEG-based fluid managerial judgement is prepared and how they interrelate. This perceptive can be influenced to grow a model that represent fluid managerial judgement consistent with goals.

Integrating different fields of research attempt offers a multidisciplinary perspective to define the underlying principles of neuro-behavioural judgement and EEG-based fluid managerial judgement making, which have been challenging to comprehend in each discipline independently. The approach used combines theoretical and experimental methods to explore the individual's ability to switch between complex left-hemispheric judgments and explorative right-hemispheric judgments, taking into account relevant economic theories and neuro-managerial applications of fluid intelligence. This innovative research attempt contributes to advancement of behavioural research in subsequent ways.

- Provide framework for behaviour research,
- Offer solutions to neuro-economic behaviour, and
- Describe standard behaviour models.

The target of this investigation was to examine how psychological and neural responses to various marketing elements can predict consumer behaviour beyond traditional self-reported outcomes. This inter-disciplinary approach draws on theoretical and empirical practicalities of behavioural judgement and neurojudgement to research attempt the cognitive, affective, motivational, and social factors that underlie economic managerial judgement making. Meta-analyses and methodical reviews of neuroimaging, psychological, and physiological tools (EEG/ERP, fMRI, fNIRS, eye-tracking, skin conductance, heart rate, or DTI) are recommended to advance theories in development of neuro-signature systems.

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